

IVET

Institut für
Verfahrens- und
Energietechnik

**MINISYMPOSIUM
VERFAHRENSTECHNIK**

2023

Proceedings

17th Minisymposium Verfahrenstechnik

and

8th Partikelforum

April 13th, 2023

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU)

Department for Material Science and Process Engineering

Institute for Chemical and Energy Engineering

Proceedings of the 17th Minisymposium Verfahrenstechnik

Tagungsband des 17. Minisymposiums Verfahrenstechnik

1st edition, April 2023

Publisher: University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Department of Material Sciences and Process Engineering, Institute for Chemical and Energy Engineering, Muthgasse 107, A-1190 Wien

www.boku.ac.at/map/ivet

ISBN: 978-3-900397-08-1

Editors: Bernhard Kling, Thomas Keller

Reviewer Team: Rafat Al Afif

Jitka Hrbek

Jan Kotik

Christoph Pfeifer

Tobias Pröll

Magdalena Wolf

David Wöß

Konferenzprogramm | Conference Program

13. April 2023

09:00 – 09:30 Uhr:	Registrierung & Kaffee Registration & Coffee (EH 05)
09:30 – 09:45 Uhr:	Eröffnung & Begrüßung Welcome session (EH 04)
09:45 – 11:10 Uhr:	Vorträge Lectures: Session 1a – Simulation (EH 04)
09:45 – 11:10 Uhr:	Vorträge Lectures: Session 1b – Activated Carbon (EH 03)
11:10 – 11:30 Uhr:	Kaffeepause Coffee break (EH 05)
11:30 – 12:15 Uhr:	Poster Session 01 (EH 04)
12:15 – 13:45 Uhr:	Mittagspause Lunch (Mensa)
13:45 – 15:10 Uhr:	Vorträge Lectures: Session 2a – Biogas & Waste (EH 04)
13:45 – 15:10 Uhr:	Vorträge Lectures: Session 2b – Fluid Mechanics (EH 03)
15:10 – 15:30 Uhr:	Kaffeepause Coffee break (EH 05)
15:30 – 16:15 Uhr:	Poster Session 02 (EH 04)
16:15 – 17:00 Uhr:	Partikelforum Particle Forum (EH 04)
17:00 – 17:30 Uhr:	Übergabe Marini & Closing Session (EH 04)
18:30 Uhr:	Social Event Wiener Prater

Session 1a – Simulation, 09:45-11:10 Uhr, EH 04

Chair: Magdalena Wolf

Autor	Universität	Titel
Schlager	Uni Leoben	Experimental and modeling study of packed marine exhaust gas scrubbing
Markowitsch	Uni Leoben	Evaluation and Comparison of the Conventional and Renewable-based Polyolefin Production based on Greenhouse Gas Reduction
Weiß B.	TU Wien	Multistep SO ₂ absorption – Making process design choices based on process simulation
Steiner	MCI	Study on Ammonia Preparation in the Exhaust Path of Stationary Gas Engines

Session 1b – Activated Carbon, 09:45-11:10 Uhr, EH 03

Chair: Christoph Pfeifer

Autor	Universität	Titel
Gurtner	MCI	Lab-scale production of activated carbon from gasification residues via thermochemical CO ₂ activation
Bosch	MCI	A promising material stream? Activated carbon from municipal residues for micropollutant adsorption
Marx	MCI	Comparison of Mixed-Matrix Membranes with Embedded Boron Nitride and Powdered Activated Carbon for Micropollutant Removal
Schinnerl	Uni Leoben	Direct ex-situ carbonation of minerals and secondary materials without the use of additives

Poster Session 01, 11:30-12:15 Uhr, EH 04

Chair: Bernhard Kling

Autor	Universität	Titel
Steiner	TU Wien	Production of sustainable bio-based platform chemicals via syngas fermentation from dual fluidized bed steam gasification
Fleiß	TU Wien	Utilization of Chemical Looping Combustion CO ₂ by exhaust gas methanation – CLCH ₄ – Experimental demonstration of a full process chain
Klapal	JKU	Power to gas in air driven bioreactors
Weiss H.	Uni Leoben	Simulation of methane pyrolysis in a molten metal bubble column reactor: Validation approaches
Kling	BOKU	Improving energy efficiency in modern buildings with forecast based control systems
Keller	BOKU	Sani60ies - Facade-integrated component activation for buildings
Keller	BOKU	Implementation of thermodynamic properties of working fluids in IPSEpro - a workaround for freeze-drying simulations

Session 2a – Biogas & Waste, 13:45-15:10 Uhr, EH 04

Chair: Jitka Hrbek

Autor	Universität	Titel
Salbrechter	Uni Leoben	A field test – Actively cooled double jacket, tubular reactor for catalytic methanation of biogas
Kresta	MCI	Characterisation and gasification of waste wood fractions in a staged process
Flatscher	JKU	Fractional crystallization of wastewater of a fly ash plant with membrane distillation crystallization

Session 2b – Fluid Mechanics, 13:45-15:10 Uhr, EH 03

Chair: Jan Kotik

Autor	Universität	Titel
Berger	MCI	Fluid mechanical and economic analysis of a spherical hot water storage tank
Raffeiner	MCI	Comparison of CFD and PIV of a NACA 0012 airfoil and first approaches to using artificial intelligence with Deep CFD for prediction of 2D flow fields
Ramonet	TU Wien	Modelling of Multi-Stage Internal Loop Air Lift Bioreactor Utilizing Computational Fluid Dynamics

Poster Session 02, 15:30-16:15 Uhr, EH 04

Chair: Thomas Keller

Autor	Universität	Titel
Berger	MCI	CFD simulation of corona virus propagation at the MCI classroom 4A-024
Imran	TU Wien	Investigation of Dope Characteristics and Take-Up Speed on the Spinning of Asymmetric Hollow Fiber Membranes
Holzer (Senfter)	MCI	Influence of selected design parameters on the operation of coanda effect screens for hydropower plants
Niederkofler	MCI	Design and evaluation of a thermogravimetric analysis-based setup for thermochemical energy storage material testing
Hofer	TU Wien	Alterung und Nasssiebung als Strategien zur Verbesserung der Produktqualität einer industriell hergestellten Gesteinskörnung aus Müllverbrennungs-Bettaschen als Zuschlagstoff für Beton
Cabeza	TU Wien	Combining Ultrafiltration with Activated Carbon Adsorption: Synergy for Industrial Decolourisation of Starch Hydrolysates
Cabrera-González	TU Wien	Isolation and downstream processing of high-value products from preserved brown seaweed – A Literature Review.

Partikelforum, 16:15-17:00 Uhr, EH 04

Autor	Universität	Titel
Esgandari	JKU	A comparative study of TFM and CFD-DEM approaches in a spout fluidized bed
Tausendschön	TU Graz	Neural network-based closure development for modeling of cohesive gas-particle flows

Experimental and modeling study of packed marine exhaust gas scrubbing

Marcus Schlager^{1,*}, Georg Haushofer¹, Verena Wolf-Zöllner¹, Markus Lehner¹

1: Process Technology and Environmental Protection, Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria

* Corresponding author: marcus.schlager@unileoben.ac.at

Keywords: Mass transfer model, absorption, column packing, emission control, sulfur dioxide removal

Research field: Gas scrubbing

Introduction

Sulfur oxide emissions from marine vessels are a major contributor to air pollution: Sulfur oxides are known to have negative impact on human health (stroke, asthma, cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases) and the environment. Going into effect on January 1, 2020, several regulations were set by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) to limit sulfur emissions of all ships operating in international waters independent of flag state.

To comply with the new IMO regulations, ship operators may choose to install/retrofit their vessels with exhaust gas scrubbers to remove sulfur from the exhaust gas stream before being released into the atmosphere (along with the continued use of sulfur-rich fuel oils). Retrofit with exhaust gas scrubbers is assumed the most economical solution in many cases [1]. For vessels currently undergoing construction the proportion of ships equipped with scrubbers is between 5 and 30%, depending on ship type [2].

A growing body of research exists on the use of gas-liquid countercurrent packed bed absorption columns for cleaning marine exhaust gases. Studies have explored the effectiveness of using seawater to remove sulfur dioxide in packed columns, with factors such as liquid flow rate, gas temperature and flow rate, seawater pH, and sulfur dioxide input concentration being examined [3]. Research has also compared the efficiency of different types of packings, with some studies indicating that fourth generation random packings are particularly effective for sulfur dioxide removal. It has been highlighted that the choice of column packing has a significant impact on sulfur dioxide removal efficiency. More research is needed to develop a mass transfer model starting from mass transfer properties of the specific column packings used [4,5].

The goal of this work is to develop a concise modeling approach for the absorption of sulfur dioxide in packed seawater scrubbers. Sulfur dioxide equilibrium molality is calculated from a simplified reaction scheme. Next, standardized measurement techniques are used to experimentally determine gas and liquid side volumetric mass transfer coefficients of multiple column packings. With this, a mass transfer model for the absorption of sulfur dioxide in seawater is derived and validated by experimentally determining sulfur dioxide removal efficiency for different column packings.

Reaction scheme and equilibrium calculations

The process of scrubbing involves physical absorption of sulfur dioxide along with subsequent dissociation reactions, which lead to an acidification of the scrubbing liquid. However, naturally occurring alkaline species within seawater counteract this acidification by reacting with protons emerging from dissociation reactions.

Various approaches have been proposed for equilibrium molality calculation using simplified reaction schemes [4,5,6,7,8]. These typically consist of a number of sulfur and carbon species, but additional species are included on occasion. The selected simplified reaction scheme for this work includes: the physical absorption of sulfur dioxide and its dissociation reactions, the dissociation reaction of carbon dioxide to model seawater alkalinity as hydrogen carbonate, and the dissociation reaction of hydrogensulfate. The autodissociation reaction of water is omitted, as it is not expected to influence pH due to the high molality of other species. A total of 8 species dissolved in the liquid phase are considered in the reaction scheme:

Temperature-dependent equilibrium constants and Henry's law coefficient of the corresponding laws of mass action are evaluated from literature correlations. [9,10,11,12]

Equations by Bromley [13] are chosen for the calculation of ionic species activity coefficients γ , where X and Y denote generic anions and cations respectively: .

$$\log \gamma_X = -\frac{A_Y z_X^2 \sqrt{I}}{1 + \rho_B \sqrt{I}} + B_X \sum_Y b_Y + \sum_Y B_Y b_Y$$

$$\log \gamma_Y = -\frac{A_Y z_Y^2 \sqrt{I}}{1 + \rho_B \sqrt{I}} + B_Y \sum_X b_X + \sum_X B_X b_X$$

Here, B_X and B_Y are ion-specific model parameters that are documented in [13] for ρ_B set to 1 (kg/mol)^{0.5}. A_Y is the Debye-Hückel constant and b denotes species molality. I is ionic strength and z denotes ion charge.

Activity coefficients γ_G of the physically dissolved gases $\text{SO}_2 (\text{aq})$ and $\text{CO}_2 (\text{aq})$ are calculated from a correlation by Schumpe [14]:

$$\log \gamma_G = \sum_i (h_{i,G} + h_G) c_i$$

$h_{i,G}$ is an ion-specific and h_G is a gas-specific parameter while c denotes ion concentration in the scrubbing liquid.

Figure 1: Scheme of the 150 mm absorption/desorption column experimental plant. 1) Saturator column, 2) Absorption/desorption measurement column, 3) Carbonation unit for $k_L a$ measurements (not shown in this work), 4) Seawater preparation unit for production and storage of synthetic seawater.

Two additional balancing equations are introduced for carbon and sulfur-VI species:

$$[\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})]^* = [\text{HCO}_3^-]^0 - [\text{HCO}_3^-]^*$$

$$[\text{HSO}_4^-]^* = [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^0 - [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^*$$

Superscripts are used to denote equilibrium (*) and initial state (0) and square brackets denote molality. The latter equation suggests that there is no oxidation from sulfur-IV to sulfur-VI species taking place inside the packed column. This is a common assumption in pertinent literature [4,5,6,7] since only an insufficient supply of oxygen is dissolved within the scrubbing liquid.

With the above considerations the only remaining variable is proton molality. A proton balance between initial and equilibrium states is used to calculate proton molality of the equilibrium state. From that, the molality of all other species can be calculated using the equilibrium reactions from the simplified reaction scheme.

Mass transfer modeling

To model mass transfer in the counter current absorption column, the apparatus with cross-section A is divided into segments of equal height Δz . Molar flux \dot{N}_j in a generic segment j is assumed proportional to the liquid phase concentration differential ($x_j^* - x_j$):

$$\dot{N}_j = (k_{OL}a)_j (x_j^* - x_j) A \Delta z$$

$(k_{OL}a)_j$ is determined from packing specific single phase volumetric mass transfer coefficients $k_G a$ and $k_L a$:

$$\frac{1}{k_{OL}a} = \frac{1}{k_G a} \frac{RT}{\tilde{H}} + \frac{1}{k_L a}$$

where R is the universal gas constant, T is thermodynamic temperature. \tilde{H} is a pseudo-Henry coefficient to consider the fact that absorbed SO_2 exists in three species:

$$\tilde{H} = \frac{[\text{SO}_2(\text{aq})] + [\text{HSO}_3^-] + [\text{SO}_3^{2-}]}{p_{\text{SO}_2}}$$

\tilde{H} is calculated from the equilibrium considerations and the simplified reaction scheme presented in the preceding chapter of this work.

Experimental

The experimental apparatus includes a saturator column and a measurement column made from polypropylene. Both columns have an inner diameter of 150 mm. A packing height of up to 1.1 m can be characterized in the measurement column. A scheme of the experimental setup is given in Figure 1.

During operation ambient air first flows into the saturator column where it is saturated with water vapor to maintain consistent experimental conditions through the prevention of evaporation in the measurement column. The gas flow then enters the actual measurement column, where it is contacted with the liquid phase flowing down through the column packing currently under investigation. A more detailed description of the experimental plant is given in [15].

Absorption experiments are conducted to determine removal efficiency of sulfur dioxide in seawater. For this, synthetic seawater is produced from commercially available sea salt ("Instant Ocean", Aquarium Systems). Alkalinity of the resulting seawater is determined with titrimetric analysis. During measurements,

Figure 2: Comparison of mass transfer model predictions (calc.) and experimental results (exp.) for sulfur dioxide removal efficiency and effluent scrubbing liquid pH.

saturated air containing sulfur dioxide is contacted with the synthetic seawater in the measuring column. The washing liquid is discarded after a single pass through the apparatus. Sulfur dioxide inlet and outlet concentrations c_{SO_2} are continuously monitored in the gas phase and used to calculate sulfur dioxide removal efficiency η_{SO_2} :

$$\eta_{SO_2} = 1 - \frac{c_{SO_2,out}}{c_{SO_2,in}}$$

Experiments are conducted for five structured packings: RSP 250Y, RMP N 250X and RMP N 250Y, RMP SP 250, and Hiflow PLUS 2. The packings are manufactured by Raschig (RSP 250Y packing) and RVT Process Equipment (all other packings). All packings except for the Hiflow PLUS 2 are made of stainless steel and have a specific geometric surface area of 250 m²/m³. The Hiflow PLUS 2 packing is made of plastic and has a specific surface area of 100 m²/m³.

Results and Discussion

Sulfur dioxide removal efficiency was experimentally evaluated using a constant gas flow of approximately 0.95 m/s while varying liquid flow between 10 and 60 m/h. Input sulfur dioxide concentration was set to 1000 ppm. The average salinity, alkalinity, and temperature of the washing water were 32.7 g/kg, 156 mg/L, and 20.7°C respectively. The measurements were then recalculated using the mass transfer modeling approach. η_{SO_2} and effluent washing liquid pH were calculated using measured values for gas and liquid flow rates, temperature, seawater alkalinity, seawater salinity, and sulfur dioxide input concentration.

Model predictions of η_{SO_2} (left side of Figure 2) can be seen to fit very well with experimental results for the entire investigated operating range and all examined column packings. Average deviation is -0.92% and maximum deviation of a single data point is 12.04%. Model prediction accuracy improves with increasing liquid load.

Overall model predictions of effluent scrubbing liquid pH (right side of Figure 2) fit good with an average deviation of 2.67% to experimental data. However, while most data points are in the range of $\pm 15\%$ to measurement results, there appears to exist a lack of correlation for pH between approx. 3.5 and 5. In this region, significantly larger deviations of up to 50% exist between model predictions and experimental results. The reason for this apparent

lack of correlation is that small model errors in predicted proton molality calculation have much more pronounced effects on pH in the unbuffered region between pH 3.5 and 5.

Figure 3 shows scrubbing liquid pH and speciation of the CO₂(aq)/HCO₃⁻ and SO₂(aq)/HSO₃⁻/SO₃²⁻ systems for each calculated segment along the packing height.

The upper area of the packed section sees alkalinity of the scrubbing liquid consumed through reaction of HCO₃⁻ with H⁺ formed in dissociation of SO₂. Here, pH changes only slightly due to this buffering effect. As soon as alkalinity is completely consumed, the pH changes more strongly. Depending on the operating point, this is the case approximately in the lower third of the apparatus. At higher liquid load, effluent scrubbing liquid contains residual alkalinity (pH above 4.5).

Regarding speciation of the SO₂(aq)/HSO₃⁻/SO₃²⁻ system, absorbed SO₂ is mainly present as HSO₃⁻. In addition, a significant amount of SO₃²⁻ is formed in the upper part of the column (pH > 5). However, this effect is only temporary as this equilibrium shifts towards HSO₃⁻ as pH decreases. At low liquid load, physically dissolved SO₂(aq) is formed in the lower part of the column due to acidification of scrubbing liquid having well advanced in this region (pH < 3.5).

Conclusions

Increased demand for marine scrubbers due to stricter sulfur dioxide emissions limits for ships has led to an interest in seawater scrubbers equipped with column packings. The development of suitable modeling approaches is important for accurate column dimensioning.

This study aims to contribute to more efficient scrubber design by providing a better understanding of sulfur dioxide absorption in seawater. A simple mass transfer modeling approach is derived through combining calculation methods for equilibrium molality with experimentally determined column packing mass transfer

Figure 3: Modeling results of washing liquid pH and speciation as function of packing height for varied liquid load (RMP N 250Y packing, $u_G = 0.95$ m/h; mean composition of scrubbing liquid: Salinity 33.7 g/kg, Alkalinity 161 mg/m³, Temperature 20.3 °C). Left: Scrubbing liquid pH. Middle: Speciation of the CO₂(aq)/HCO₃⁻ system. Right: Speciation of the SO₂(aq)/HSO₃⁻/SO₃²⁻ system.

properties. The resulting model accurately predicts sulfur dioxide removal efficiency and effluent scrubbing liquid pH. Model predictions are verified for five different structured column packings for different operating conditions.

References

- [1] Zhang, X., Bao, Z., Ge, Y.E., “Investigating the determinants of shipowners’ emission abatement solutions for newbuilding vessels”, *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, vol. 99, 2021. doi:10.1016/j.trd.2021.102989
- [2] Li, K., Wu, M., Gu, X., Yuen, K.F., Xiao, Y., “Determinants of ship operators’ options for compliance with IMO 2020”, *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, vol. 86, 102459, 2020. doi:10.1016/j.trd.2020.102459.
- [3] Darake, S., Rahimi, A., Hatamipour, M.S., Hamzeloui, P., “SO₂ Removal by Seawater in a Packed-Bed Tower: Experimental Study and Mathematical Modeling”, *Separation Science and Technology*, vol. 49, pp. 988–998, 2014. doi:10.1080/01496395.2013.872660
- [4] Iliuta, I., Larachi, F., “Modeling and Simulations of NO_x and SO₂ Seawater Scrubbing in Packed-Bed Columns for Marine Applications”, *Catalysts*, vol. 9, 2019. doi:10.3390/catal9060489
- [5] Flagiello, D., Erto, A., Lancia, A., Di Natale, F., “Experimental and modelling analysis of seawater scrubbers for sulphur dioxide removal from flue-gas”, *Fuel*, vol. 214, pp. 254–263, 2018. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2017.10.098
- [6] Rodríguez-Sevilla, J., Álvarez, M., Díaz, M.C., Marrero, M.C., “Absorption Equilibria of Dilute SO₂ in Seawater”, *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, vol. 49, pp. 1710–1716, 2004. doi:10.1021/je0498331
- [7] Andreasen, A., Mayer, S., “Use of Seawater Scrubbing for SO₂ Removal from Marine Engine Exhaust Gas”, *Energy & Fuels*, vol. 21, pp. 3274–3279, 2007. doi:10.1021/ef700359w
- [8] Cox, C., Pasel, C., Luckas, M., Bathen, D., “Absorption of SO₂ in different electrolyte solutions, seawater and brine”, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, vol. 402, pp. 89–101, 2015. doi:10.1016/j.fluid.2015.05.041
- [9] Harned, H.S., Bonner, F.T., “The First Ionization of Carbonic Acid in Aqueous Solutions of Sodium Chloride”, *Journal of the*

American Chemical Society, vol. 67, pp. 1026–1031, 1945. doi:10.1021/ja01222a037

[10] Pitzer, K.S., Roy, R.N., Silvester, L.F., “Thermodynamics of electrolytes. 7. Sulfuric acid”, Journal of the American Chemical Society, vol. 99, pp. 4930–4936, 1977. doi:10.1021/ja00457a008

[11] Goldberg, R.N., Parker, V.B., “Thermodynamics of Solution of SO₂(g) in Water and of Aqueous Sulfur Dioxide Solutions”, Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards, vol. 90, 1985.

[12] Sander, R., “Compilation of Henry’s law constants (version 4.0) for water as solvent”, Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics, vol. 15, pp. 4399–4981, 2015. doi:10.5194/acp-15-4399-2015

[13] Bromley, L., “Approximate individual values of B in extended Debye-Hückel theory for uni-univalent aqueous solutions at 298.15 K”, J. Chem. Thermodynamics, vol. 4, pp. 669–673, 1972. doi:10.1016/0021-9614(72)90038-9

[14] Schumpe, A., “The estimation of gas solubilities in salt solutions”, Chemical Engineering Science, vol. 48, pp. 153–158, 1993. doi:10.1016/0009-2509(93)80291-W

[15] Schlager, M., Haushofer, G., Triebel, A., Wolf-Zöllner, V., Lehner, M., „Determination of volumetric mass transfer coefficients of structured packings at two different column diameters”, Chemical Engineering Research and Design, vol. 186, pp. 462–472, 2022. doi:10.1016/j.cherd.2022.08.002

Evaluation and Comparison of the Conventional and Renewable-based Polyolefin Production based on Greenhouse Gas Reduction

C. Markowitsch^{1,*}, M. Lehner¹, J. Kitzweger², W. Haider³, S. Ivanovici⁴, M. Unfried⁵, M. Maly⁴

1: Chair of Process Technology and Environmental Protection, Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria

2: Lafarge Permooser GmbH, Austria

3: Borealis Polyolefin GmbH, Schwechat

4: OMV Downstream GmbH, Wien

5: VERBUND Energy4Business GmbH

* Corresponding author: christoph.markowitsch@unileoben.ac.at

Keywords: Power-to-X Processes, GHG Reduction, Renewable Polyolefins

Research field: Chemical Engineering

Introduction

The Paris Agreement has the ambition to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to achieve a maximum global temperature increase of 2 °C above pre-industrial levels [1]. To render this goal possible, the greenhouse gas emissions of the different sectors need to be greatly reduced. In Austria, the main contributors can be divided into energy and industry (37.0 % ETS (European Trading System), 7.4 % non-ETS) and transport sector (27.8 %), which accounted for about three quarters of the total Austrian greenhouse gas emissions in 2021. The remainder consists of other sectors such as buildings (11.7 %), agriculture (10.6 %), waste management (3.0 %) and fluorinated gases (2.4 wt.-%) [3]. As the electrification of transport vehicles (cars, trucks) is only one way to decarbonize the transport sector, research on renewable fuels, so-called e-fuels, is booming in Europe. Nevertheless, proposals for the other sectors, especially for the energy and industry sector, need to be identified and evaluated for decarbonization [4].

In this work, the focus is therefore on the reduction of greenhouse gases in the chemical industry, especially for the production of polyolefins. In 2020, Borealis AG produced around 1 million tons of polyolefins at its Schwechat site in Austria [5]. The production of polyolefins is based on the polymerization of olefins. There are several methods to produce the feedstock olefin. On the one hand, this is possible with fossil feedstocks such as naphtha, which is a product of fossil crude oil distillation [6]. Another approach is the use of biomass or power-to-X (PtX) processes for climate-neutral production of olefins. In this work, the assumption is made that the industry and transport sectors cannot be completely decarbonized from biogenic feedstock, as the amount of biomass required would be far greater than the amount that can be produced. The production of 1 million ton polyolefins per year requires 12.1 million tons of biomass, which accounts for about 60 wt.-% of Austria's forest biomass potential [7,8].

Therefore, Power-to-X (PtX) technologies are considered in this work. In a first step, in order to come closer to climate neutrality, carbon sources, suitable for further processing to polyolefins must be found and defined. The capture effort from gas streams decreases with increasing CO₂ concentration. Direct air capture (DAC) would therefore be 2.9 times more energy-intensive (in combination with high electricity prices economical infeasible) than concentrated sources (e.g. exhaust gas streams). Therefore, DAC is not considered in this work [9]. Point sources, especially from process-related CO₂ emissions, represent a favorable application area for such PtX plants.

In Austria, the cement industry emitted 9.0 % of ETS certificates and 3.3 % of the total national greenhouse gases in 2019. In the cement production process, two thirds of CO₂ is emitted due to the calcination of the limestone in the pre-heater and rotary kiln and is accounted as process related CO₂. The remaining third is emitted by the heat supply for calcination, especially the firing of conventional

fuels (e.g., coke) and substitute fuels (e.g., waste oil, residual waste, such as plastics, which are not mechanically or chemically able to be recycled) [10].

Carbon Capture and Utilization or Storage "CCU/S" is an indispensable option to decarbonize the cement industry sector. The "Association of Austria's Cement Industry" stated in their report [11], that CO₂ reduction can be achieved by various factors such as clinker reduction, savings in transportation and the use of green electricity. But the remaining 44 % of the CO₂ emissions must be reduced by CCU/S [11]. In Austria, the "C2PAT – Carbon to Product Austria" project is a flagship project, where CO₂ should be utilized for the production of renewable based polyolefins. A consortium of four industrial partners, Lafarge Zementwerke GmbH, Verbund AG, OMV AG and Borealis AG are working together with the scientific partners Montanuniversität Leoben and Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien to gain experience in the implementation of such a Carbon Capture and Utilization unit, which should be realized in the cement plant in Mannersdorf am Leithagebirge. In order to analyze the impact of a large-scale plant on the reduction of fossil raw materials and savings of CO₂, the 700,000 tons of CO₂ emitted annually by the cement plant is considered.

At present, fossil raw materials are required for the production of polyolefins. Additionally, CO₂ emissions are also generated during the production of polyolefins. On the other hand, in the cement industry, process related CO₂ emissions arise, as long as cement is produced. By combining these two industry sectors, the emitted CO₂ from the cement plant could be used for the production of renewable plastics. This would have two effects: 1. the reduction of the amount of fossil crude oil used for naphtha and in the broadest sense a reduction of fossil olefin production and CO₂ emission in its production chain, and 2. the use of "anyway" emitted CO₂ from the cement industry, i.e. the reuse of CO₂ and, if necessary, storage in longer-lasting plastic products. It should be mentioned that the use in plastic production, e.g. for high-voltage cable sheathing, would have a further advantage of long-term CO₂ storage (~50-100 years).

Consequently, this work aims to provide an overview of the production of polyolefins from conventional fossil raw materials and the use of process-related CO₂ from the cement industry. The PtX pathway from CO₂ and hydrogen via the intermediate Fischer-Tropsch syn crude to polyolefins (mainly polypropylene – PP, or polyethylene – PE) is described in this work. A post-processing unit such as a steam cracker will also be considered in the process comparison. A mass balance of these process routes is established in order to calculate the GHG reduction potential in kgCO₂/t_{polyolefin}. Furthermore, conclusions on the used feedstock are made and discussed.

Methodology

The work is based on a calculation of the mass balance of the conventional fossil production of polyolefins using literature data. For comparison, a simulation of a PtX plant producing polyolefins based on 700,000 tons of CO₂ from the cement plant off-gas will be created [12]. The yearly operation time of the cement plant amounts about 7,880 h. As a first step, the ASPEN Plus based simulation will be performed, and the mass flows will be analyzed. The contained product amount of polyolefins will then be used as a basis for back-calculation to fossil naphtha and crude oil to determine the fossil feedstock reduction potential.

Figure 4 defines the two process routes for polyolefins production. Process route 1 describes the conventional production process with the feedstock fossil crude oil. In a first step, the crude oil is separated into different fractions, with naphtha being the feedstock for the refinery's olefins production. Depending on the composition of the crude oil, a yield of 2 – 14 vol.-% is obtained from crude oil for light naphtha (5 – 90 °C) and 8 – 26 vol.-% for heavy naphtha (distillation range 90 – 180°C) [13]. Naphtha is converted into the main products ethylene and propylene and several by-products in the steam cracker. For 1 ton of ethylene and 0.53 tons of propylene, 3.25 tons of naphtha are needed [14]. The by-products are not considered further here. The conversion of the olefins into polyolefins is done almost completely in Borealis' own Borstar plant. Today, the distillation and steam cracker are still operated with fossil fuels, which means that CO₂ emissions are already released during the production of naphtha. It is assumed that around 1.91 kgCO₂/kg of product is emitted for polypropylene and 1.98 kgCO₂/kg of product for polyethylene [6,15].

In the PtX routes defined in process route 2, CO₂ is captured from the cement plant off-gas. Hydrogen is produced via an electrolysis and converted with CO₂ in a reverse water-gas-shift (rWGS) reactor to synthesis gas, which is the feed for the downstream Fischer Tropsch synthesis (FTS). The FTS product, also called syncrude, is separated in flash units to obtain the product fractions naphtha, middle distillate and waxes. These products are further converted in the steam cracker to olefins and in the polymerization unit to polyolefins. The simulation includes the carbon capture unit, electrolysis, rWGS and FT reactor including the product separation unit of the PtX route. The simulation is carried out in ASPEN Plus and described below. A detailed flow sheet is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 4: Process Route description (1 - fossil path; 2 - renewable path via rWGS and FTS)

Carbon capture unit

The carbon capture unit is realized with an amine scrubber, since this process has a generally high technology readiness level (TRL). Other sustainable capture technologies such as PSA and cryogenic capture will also be considered in the further project design phase. In order to get the exhaust gas free of particles and pollutants (e.g., sulfur) and at operating temperature for the absorber, it is subjected to a pre-cleaning unit [2]. The pre-cleaned gas is fed to the absorber tower in counterflow to the monoethanolamin (MEA) solution in the lower section. CO₂ dissolves in the solution at ambient pressure, while the other gases leave the absorber at the top and are released into the environment. The loaded amine mixture is heated and fed to the

desorber tower. Reboiler heat of about 3.8 MJ/kgCO₂ is supplied, releasing the CO₂ from the solution, which is stripped from the head of the stripper with water vapor, cooled, and separated in a flash to achieve concentrated CO₂ and water. The CO₂ stream has a purity of about 95 wt.-% (wet), or 99.8 wt.-% (dry) [2].

Hydrogen production

Hydrogen must be provided for the catalytic conversion of CO₂ to hydrocarbons via the Fischer Tropsch synthesis. Using water electrolysis technologies, this can be produced by splitting water with the supply of electricity according to endothermic reaction 1.

It is important to note that decarbonization only makes sense if the electricity used comes 100 % from renewable sources. Otherwise, if electricity is produced by fossil power plants, e.g. coal or natural gas, CO₂ would already be emitted by the electricity supply for hydrogen production. Although not at the production site, this emission must also be included in the overall system analysis [2]. High-temperature electrolysis is used in the simulation because excess heat from the FTS can be used to evaporate feed water from the electrolysis, which improves the overall efficiency. It is assumed that the electrolysis is operated at temperatures between 700 and 900 °C and ambient pressure with a specific system efficiency of 3.6 kWh/Nm³H₂ [16]. The oxygen flow is directly linked to the cement plant, if the electrolysis is located there. For an electrolysis comparison, the electricity demand for a low-temperature PEM electrolysis (5 kWh/Nm³H₂) is also considered [16].

Reverse water gas shift reaction

The rWGS reaction is the conversion of CO₂ and hydrogen to syngas. According to the thermodynamic equilibrium (Figure 5), high temperatures (950 °C) and low pressures (10 barg) favor the endothermic reaction (reaction 2) and conversion.

Furthermore, these operating conditions reduce the production of by-products, e.g. methane and solid carbon. Moreover, it is necessary to adjust the hydrogen flow to guarantee a H₂:CO ratio at the inlet of the FT reactor (2.08:1). In addition to the high operating temperature, the over stoichiometric operation suppresses the formation of carbon [2]. It is important to mention that short-chain hydrocarbons (C₁ – C₄) are recycled back to the rWGS reactor through the recycling stream from the FTS, which is explained in the FTS section. Steam and dry reforming take place, whereby methane in particular is converted with H₂O to synthesis gas.

Figure 5: Thermodynamic equilibrium of the rWGS reaction for an operation temperature range from 300 to 1,100 °C and pressures of 1, 5, 10 and 30 barg

Figure 6: Flow sheet of the simulated PtX process including carbon capture, electrolysis, rWGS and FT reactor with product separation unit [2]

Fischer Tropsch synthesis

It can be differentiated between low and high temperature FTS, whereas the main distinction is the product formation. The product of the low temperature FTS consists mainly of normal paraffinic hydrocarbons, compared to low chain olefins in the high temperature FTS [17]. Therefore, low temperature FTS (220 °C and 25 barg) with a cobalt catalyst is used, which has the advantage that the product is similar to fossil crude oil. In the simulation a stoichiometric reactor is implemented, whereas reaction 3 describes the conversion of CO₂ and hydrogen to hydrocarbons, with a single conversion rate of 40 % [2].

The production of the hydrocarbons is described by the Anderson-Schulz-Flory (ASF) distribution, which assumes a chain growth probability of 0.92 [18]. Accordingly, the required input ratio of H₂:CO is calculated to be 2.08:1 [19]. It must be added here that the distribution has been modified because in reality there is a higher methane content in the product than the ASF distribution specifies [20]. Accordingly, in addition to the main reaction (reaction 3), the methanation (reaction 4) with a methane selectivity in the FT product of 16 % is also considered in the simulation [2].

Both reactions are strongly exothermic, which requires an appropriate cooling system for the FT reactor to avoid "runaway". This dissipated heat is taken into account in the heat integration to obtain a holistically high efficiency of the entire process setup.

The wax produced (>C₂₂) is liquid and is drawn off directly from the reactor. The gas phase is separated in a two-stage flash separation into the fractions middle distillate (C₁₁ – C₂₂) and naphtha

(C₅ – C₁₀), and the by-product water. These fractions are then transported to the Schwechat refinery for further use. The remaining gaseous stream, consisting of predominantly C₁ – C₄ hydrocarbons, is recycled upstream the rWGS reactor to achieve the highest possible conversion rate to liquid products. In order to avoid accumulation of inert gases (e.g. nitrogen), 2 vol.-% of the recycle gas is purged.

Steam cracker and polymerization unit

In contrast to the fossil operation of a steam cracker, studies have been conducted for FTS syncrude from CO₂ and H₂, with the result that the complete syncrude (naphtha, middle distillate and wax) can be processed. The conversion parameters for the different fractions are taken from Karaba et al. [21]. The downstream polymerization efficiency is assumed with 99 %. The prerequisite for a green process would be again, that the energy required in the steam cracker and polymerization unit must be provided from renewable sources (i.e. green electricity).

Results

Using the previously defined process routes, the mass balance of the fossil and renewable pathways can be established. Table 1 shows the mass balance based on the 700,000 tons of CO₂ emitted annually by the cement plant. It is clearly evident that approx. 90 wt.-% of the CO₂ fed from the cement plant is separated in the amine wash and converted into syncrude in the synthesis process. It is important to mention that CO₂ is contained in the clean gas of the amine scrubbing, which is released to the environment. This CO₂ is emitted, but possible improvements and developments of the separation technology could further increase the reduction of CO₂ released to atmosphere.

Considering the water consumption of the electrolysis, which is a result of the simulation, this plant requires about 11.4 t/h or

Table 1: Mass balance of the simulated PtX process route

Mass balance	Inlet			Outlet							
	Flue gas	Makeup amine	Water electrolysis	Prewasher	Clean gas	Water treatment plant	Unconverted water	Oxygen	rWGS water	Purgegas	Syncrude
Total [t/h]	427.1	50.1	222.8	15.5	378.6	111.4	11.1	89.0	24.0	3.1	24.5
CO [t/h]			0.0							2.0	
H ₂ [t/h]			0.0							0.3	
H ₂ O [t/h]	32.2	50.1	222.8	15.5	64.2	111.4	11.1	0.0	24.0		0.1
CO ₂ [t/h]	88.8		0.0		8.3					0.4	
N ₂ [t/h]	258.7		0.0		258.6					0.1	
O ₂ [t/h]	47.4		222.8		47.4			89.0			
MEA [t/h]		0.002									
C ₁₊ [t/h]										0.4	24.4

127,440 Nm³/h of hydrogen, which corresponds to an electrolysis power of about 460 MW (SOEC, 3.6 kWh/Nm³H₂) or 637 MW (PEM, 5 kWh/Nm³H₂). The implementation of this plant size at the cement plant site in Mannersdorf am Leithagebirge is currently impossible due to the lack of grid capacities.

Table 2 shows the mass balance of the steam cracker and the polymerization unit. Thus, from the 700,000 tons of CO₂ per year, 120,560 tons of polyolefins (sum of polyethylene and polypropylene) can be produced annually. By-products (e.g., Butene, Butadiene, ...) generated in the steam cracker and in the polymerization unit are listed as "rest" [21].

Initially, it can be stated that in the PtX process (process route 2) CO₂ is only released in the amine wash. The energies required for electrolysis, synthesis, steam cracker and polymerization unit are provided with green electricity, which means that no CO₂ is produced by electricity supply. [22].

Table 3: Mass balance of the steam cracker and the polymerization unit

Inlet – Syncrude			Outlet – Olefins			Polymerization		
Total	[t/h]	24.3	Total	[t/h]	24.3	Total	[t/h]	15.3
C ₂ -C ₁₁	[t/h]	3.5	Ethylene	[t/h]	10.8	PE	[t/h]	10.7
C ₁₂ -C ₂₄	[t/h]	9.9	Propylene	[t/h]	4.5	PP	[t/h]	4.5
>C ₂₄	[t/h]	10.9	Rest	[t/h]	9.0	Rest	[t/h]	0.2

With the obtained amount of polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) from the PtX process, the mass balances of the fossil route is recalculated and given in Table 3. Here it is clearly evident that a higher amount of naphtha is required for the same amount of polyolefins, i.e. about one third more. The steam cracker for fossil naphtha has correspondingly different conversion yields. The distribution between ethylene and propylene is the same as for the PtX process route. Furthermore, naphtha is provided by the distillation of crude oil. For the production of 15.1 t/h polyolefins, about 114 t/h (898,320 t/year) crude oil are required, assuming that light and heavy naphtha can be converted in the steam cracker. It should also be taken into account that only naphtha is included in olefin production and the rest is used for other applications.

Table 4: Calculation of the naphtha and crude oil demand in regard to the overall polyolefin production

Polymerization			Steam Cracker			Distillation – Crude Oil		
Total Olefins	[t/h]	15.3	Total Naphtha	[t/h]	32.6	Total Crude	[t/h]	113.8
PE	[t/h]	9.9	Ethylene	[t/h]	10.0	Naphtha	[t/h]	32.5
PP	[t/h]	5.2	Propylene	[t/h]	5.3	Rest	[t/h]	81.3
Rest	[t/h]	0.2	Rest	[t/h]	17.3			

Finally, Table 4 compares the CO₂ emissions generated by the conventional (fossil) and PtX process routes. In any case, the emissions from the fossil process route are significantly higher compared to the PtX process route. This is mainly due to the fact that the CO₂ in PtX process route 2 is provided as a resource for polyolefin production. In a broader sense, this means that 1.96 kgCO₂/kg_{polyolefin} is emitted during production in process route 1, while process route 2 is a CO₂ sink with 3.37 kgCO₂/kg_{polyolefin}. If the difference is considered, the so-called CO₂ saving potential, around 110 t of CO₂ can be saved per hour by switching to the PtX process route. This corresponds to 866,800 tons of CO₂ per year. It should be noted that the entire electrical supply must be provided by green electricity.

Table 2: Comparison of the emitted CO₂ amount for the conventional, fossil and PtX process route

CO ₂ emissions reduction				
Process route 1 Crude oil	PP	PE	Total	Saving potential
	[t/h]	[t/h]	[t/h]	[t/h]
	10.0	19.6	29.6	-110.1
Specific CO ₂ [kgCO ₂ /kg _{polyolefin}]				
1.96				
Process route 2 PtX	Exhaust gas	Clean gas	Total	
	[t/h]	[t/h]	[t/h]	
	-88.8	8.3	-80.5	
	Specific CO ₂ [kgCO ₂ /kg _{polyolefin}]			
-3.37				

Conclusion

In this paper, the comparison of two process routes for the production of polyolefins is considered and critically analyzed. The consideration of the mass balances of both process routes gives a clear statement that the use of CO₂ from the cement plant off-gas results in a reduction of the fossil naphtha and its production from crude oil. A PtX plant with an annual capacity of 700,000 tons of CO₂ per year would save 256,100 tons of fossil naphtha, which has to be produced from 890,440 tons of crude oil by energy-intensive distillation per year. With these 700,000 tons of CO₂ emitted annually, about 120,000 tons of polyolefins can be produced. This covers the demand of about one tenth of Austrians Borealis' production demand for polyolefins. Other point sources, e.g. from other cement plants, CO₂-rich waste gases from the steel industry or refinery, can be used as feedstock for the upscaling of such a plant.

Corresponding logistic considerations regarding decentralized separation plants in the factories on site and transport of CO₂ to a central intake and turnover location (e.g. transport of concentrated CO₂ from Mannersdorf via pipeline to the Schwechat refinery), as well as the production or import of green hydrogen have to be analyzed in detail and evaluated in the industrial consortium.

Under the circumstances that the PtX process route is fully powered by green energy, it is evident that the production of polyolefins has a clear advantage in CO₂ reduction. In contrast to production with fossil raw materials, which emits 1.96 kgCO₂ per kg of product, production with renewable energies saves CO₂ emissions of 3.37 kgCO₂ per kg of product. As a prerequisite, it must be mentioned here that the lifetime of the products does not play a role in this consideration, since the area of application is undefined for both process routes. If CO₂ emissions were taken into account, as in the lifecycle analysis, this would have a negative impact on the calculated CO₂ emissions for both process routes. In conclusion, it can be said that the conversion of polyethylene and polypropylene produced via a PtX plant into long-life products is desirable, since the carbon remains bound in the product in the long term. Carbon sequestration in a product over many years (e.g., more than 50) should also be considered carbon capture and storage in the most general sense.

Acknowledgement

This research was developed as a part of the “C2PAT – Carbon to product Austria” project. The financial support by Holcim Technology Ltd., Verbund Energy4Business GmbH, OMV AG and Borealis Polyolefine GmbH is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] Climate Action. Übereinkommen von Paris. [February 02, 2022]; Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/international-action-climate-change/climate-negotiations/paris-agreement_de.
- [2] Markowitsch C, Lehner M, Maly M. Evaluation of Process Structures and Reactor Technologies of an Integrated Power-to-Liquid Plant at a Cement Factory. SSRN Journal 2022. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4297380>.
- [3] Umweltbundesamt Environment Agency Austria. Treibhausgase. [January 25, 2023]; Available from: <https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/klima/treibhausgase>.
- [4] Herz G, Rix C, Jacobasch E, Müller N, Reichelt E, Jahn M et al. Economic assessment of Power-to-Liquid processes – Influence of electrolysis technology and operating conditions. *Applied Energy* 2021;292:116655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116655>.
- [5] Kunststoffe: Zahlen und Fakten zur Kunststoffindustrie in Österreich - Blog. [January 25, 2023]; Available from: <https://blog.donau-chemie-group.com/blog-posts/Donauchem/Kunststoffe-Daten-und-Fakten-zur-Kunststoffindust?lang=DE>.
- [6] Davarnejad R, Azizi J, Bahari S. A Look at the Industrial Production of Olefins Based on Naphtha Feed: A Process Study of a Petrochemical Unit. In: Davarnejad R, editor. *Alkenes: Recent Advances, New Perspectives and Applications*. Erscheinungsort nicht ermittelbar: IntechOpen; 2021.
- [7] Michael Englisch, Thomas Gschwantner, Thomas Ledermann, Klaus Katzensteiner. An Integrated Approach to Assess Sustainable Forest Biomass Potentials at Country Level. In: *Biochar: A Regional Supply Chain Approach in View of Climate Change Mitigation*. Cambridge University Press; 2016, p. 123–138.
- [8] Albrecht FG, König DH, Baucks N, Dietrich R-U. A standardized methodology for the techno-economic evaluation of alternative fuels – A case study. *Fuel* 2017;194:511–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2016.12.003>.
- [9] Unde RB. Kinetics and Reaction Engineering Aspects of Syngas Production by the Heterogeneously Catalysed Reverse Water Gas Shift Reaction [Dissertation]. Bayreuth: Universität Bayreuth; 2012.
- [10] Mauschitz G. Emissionen aus Anlagen der österreichischen Zementindustrie - Berichtsjahr 2020. Wien; 2021.
- [11] Spaun S, Bauer C, Dankl C, Friedle R, Papsch F. Roadmap zur CO₂-Neutralität der österreichischen Zementindustrie bis 2050. Wien; 2022.
- [12] International Cement Review. The Global Cement Report 14th Edition. [January 25, 2022]; Available from: <https://www.cemnet.com/Publications/Item/187049/the-global-cement-report-14th-edition.html>.
- [13] Engineering Toolbox. Yield structure of crude oils with increasing density of crude. [January 26, 2023]; Available from: https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/crude-oil-petroleum-specific-gravity-density-yield-structure-gasoil-VGO-diesel-naphtha-residue-d_1970.html.
- [14] Boulamanti A, Moya JA. Production costs of the chemical industry in the EU and other countries: Ammonia, methanol and light olefins. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2017;68:1205–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.02.021>.
- [15] Vanderreydt I, Rommens T, Tenhunen A, Mortensen L, Tange I. Greenhouse gas emissions and natural capital implications of plastics (including biobased plastics): Eionet Report – ETC/WMGE 2021/3; 2021.
- [16] Tratner A, Höglinger M, Macherhammer M-G, Sartory M. Renewable Hydrogen: Modular Concepts from Production over Storage to the Consumer. *Chemie Ingenieur Technik* 2021;93(4):706–16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cite.202000197>.
- [17] Klerk A de. *Fischer-Tropsch Refining*. 1st ed. Hoboken, NJ, Weinheim: Wiley; 2011.
- [18] Vervloet D, Kapteijn F, Nijenhuis J, van Ommen JR. Fischer–Tropsch reaction–diffusion in a cobalt catalyst particle: aspects of activity and selectivity for a variable chain growth probability. *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 2012;2(6):1221. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C2CY20060K>.
- [19] Ostadi M, Rytter E, Hillestad M. Evaluation of kinetic models for Fischer–Tropsch cobalt catalysts in a plug flow reactor. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design* 2016;114:236–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2016.08.026>.
- [20] Förtsch D, Pabst K, Groß-Hardt E. The product distribution in Fischer–Tropsch synthesis: An extension of the ASF model to describe common deviations. *Chemical Engineering Science* 2015;138:333–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2015.07.005>.
- [21] Karaba A, Rozhon J, Patera J, Hájek J, Zámostný P. Fischer-Tropsch Wax from Renewable Resources as an Excellent Feedstock for the Steam-Cracking Process. *Chemical Engineering & Technology* 2021;44(2):329–38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.202000400>.
- [22] Bundesministerium für Klimaschutz, Umwelt, Energie, Mobilität, Innovation und Technologie. Österreichisches Umweltzeichen - Grüner Strom: Richtlinie UZ 46. Wien; 2022.

Multistep SO₂ absorption – Making process design choices based on process simulation

B.D.Weiß^{1, 2,*}, B. Haddadi², M.Harasek²

1: Competence Center CHASE GmbH, Ghegastraße 3, 1030 Vienna, Austria

2: Thermal Process Engineering - Computational Fluid Dynamics, Institute of Chemical, Environmental & Bioscience Engineering, TU Wien, Getreidemarkt 9, 1060 Vienna, Austria

*Corresponding author: barbara.weiss@tuwien.ac.at

Keywords: Flue gas treatment, Process optimization, Precipitation, Process design, Pulp industry, Chemical Recovery, Mg(OH)₂

Research field: Process simulation

Abstract

This study proposes two different process designs of a multistep SO₂ absorption process using an Mg(OH)₂ slurry. The first design aims to absorb as much SO₂ as possible in as few steps as necessary until a target SO₂ content in the exhaust gas is reached. The second design focuses on reaching the target SO₂ content in the exhaust gas and minimizing the chemical loss due to precipitation in the system. The process designs were designed and calculated using the process simulation environment of Aspen Plus® V10. The results show that the target SO₂ limit is reached after four absorption steps for the first process design. However, the precipitation loss makes up almost 20 wt% based on the product output. The second design requires eight absorption steps to reach the target SO₂ limit in the exhaust gas. However, the precipitation loss can be reduced to 5 wt% based on the product output. The results suggest that minimizing precipitation in the system can improve material process performance.

Introduction

The absorption of SO₂ with a magnesium-based absorptive slurry is a commonly used technology to reduce SO₂ emissions from SO₂-containing exhaust gas [1]. In magnesium bisulfite (Mg(HSO₃)₂) based pulp processes, the chemisorption of SO₂ leads to the recovery of the cooking liquor Mg(HSO₃)₂ following Equation (1) and (2):

Figure 7 shows the simplified process loop of the chemical recovery in a magnesium bisulfite-based pulping process.

Figure 7: Simplified process loop of the chemical recovery of a magnesium bisulfite pulping process

The absorption of SO₂ with Mg(OH)₂ is a crucial step in recovering the cooking liquor. The chemical reaction system during absorption is complex and consists of equilibrium, dissociation, and precipitation reactions. Previous studies identified CaSO₃ hemihydrate, Ca(OH)₂, Mg(OH)₂, MgSO₃ tri-, and hexahydrate as potential salts precipitating in the system under usual absorption conditions [2], [3]. While reactions leading to the formation of Mg(HSO₃)₂ (see Equation (1) and (2)) are wanted, precipitation reactions are highly unwanted. Precipitation in the system leads to deposits on the process equipment, blockage of pipes, and subsequently to chemical loss as the salts have to be washed out in a regular cleaning step and are not recycled in the recovery process [4]. This challenges the efficiency of the process and increases its ecological footprint. Therefore, this study suggests that it is crucial to not only focus on SO₂ removal efficiency but also to include the issue of precipitation in process simulations to design an optimized process for absorption.

Figure 8 summarizes the input and output streams of the process.

Figure 8: Input and output streams of the absorption process

Solids, which translate into chemical loss, are considered as separated outlet stream. To use the liquid product as cooking liquor, a pH value of around 4.5 is required for the magnesium bisulfate pulping process [5]. To meet this pH value, additional SO₂ has to be added to the liquid product depending on the pH value after absorption. Figure 8 includes this required SO₂ as an input stream.

The following investigates two different process design approaches and proposes an optimized process design based on process simulations.

Methods

The process was modeled as steady-state process in Aspen Plus® V10 using the Elec-NRTL property method. The chemical system includes all relevant equilibrium, dissociation, and precipitation reactions. The model covers the precipitation of CaSO₃ hemihydrate, Ca(OH)₂, Mg(OH)₂, MgSO₃ tri- and hexahydrate.

Figure 9 shows the flowsheet of the process as it was implemented in AspenPlus.

Figure 9: Process flowsheet of multi-step SO₂ absorption (exemplary six steps)

The figure shows exemplary a 6-step absorption process.

Input streams

The flue gas has typical properties for a flue gas coming from a combustion unit in the pulp industry. It enters the absorption process saturated with water and at 68 °C and a pressure of 1.077 bar. Table 5 summarizes the flue gas composition.

Table 5: Flue gas composition in mass-% (wet basis)

H ₂ O	N ₂	CO ₂	O ₂	SO ₂	NO
17.49	58.36	15.81	5.04	1.94	1.36

The total flue gas flow was set to be 100 000 kg/h. The slurry consists of 91.35 wt% H₂O, 8.5 wt% MgO, and 0.15 wt% CaO.

Besides flue gas and slurry, there is also extra SO₂ entering the process. The liquid product, after absorption, needs to have a pH value of 4.5 to be used as cooking liquor in the bisulfite pulping process [5]. Depending on the pH value of the liquid output of the absorption process, extra SO₂ needs to be added to reach a pH value of 4.5. The flow of the extra SO₂ was adjusted to reach this pH value by a design specification.

Output streams

The SO₂ content in the exhaust must not exceed a specific SO₂ limit. In this study, a target content of 450 mg/Nm³ SO₂ was set following the suggestions given by the Austrian Federal Environmental Agency [6]. It needs to be considered that this limit is referred to dry exhaust gas with an oxygen content of 5 %. Equation (3) describes the conversion from the actual O₂ content in the exhaust gas to the reference O₂ content of 5 %:

$$SO_2 \left(\frac{mg}{Nm^3}, 5\% O_2 \right) = \frac{21\% - 5\%}{21\% - O_2(\%)} * SO_2 \left(\frac{mg}{Nm^3} \right) \quad (3)$$

The liquid product stream is set to have a pH value of 4.5. At each absorption unit, a solid stream exits the process representing the loss due to precipitation.

Process units

Stoichiometric reactors cover the hydration of MgO and CaO in the slurry input. The implemented reactors consider complete hydration

of MgO and CaO to Mg(OH)₂ and Ca(OH)₂.

The absorption units are implemented as flash units, which calculate the phase and chemical equilibrium between all entering streams. An industrial absorption unit does not reach equilibrium, with the physical solubility of SO₂ being the limiting process in the system (Marocco 2010). The absorption efficiency in each absorption unit was set to 70 % using a bypass stream for the flue gas. It is assumed that 30 wt% of the flue gas is not reacting with the entering liquid streams but passing through to the next unit without interacting with the entering liquid stream.

After each absorption unit, a stoichiometric reactor covers the oxidation of SO₃⁻ to SO₄⁻ with O₂ in the liquid outlet. The fractional conversion of O₂ was set to 1 due to the fast kinetics of the oxidation reaction [7].

A subsequent split unit separates the precipitates from the liquid stream. All salts present after each absorption stream are removed from the liquid stream and discharged from the process. These solids make up the chemical loss, which occurs during an absorption process due to precipitation in the system.

The described flowsheet was used to design two different process approaches. Sensitivity analyses varying the slurry input of each absorption unit allowed to find optimized process conditions.

Process design maximized absorption

The first design aims to minimize the SO₂ in the exhaust gas with as few absorption units as possible. Sensitivity analyses varying the slurry input streams allowed finding the highest absorption rate of each unit without adding excess slurry. The flowsheet was systematically extended with absorption units until the target SO₂ content in the exhaust gas was reached.

Process design minimized precipitation

The second design aims to minimize precipitation in the system while reducing the SO₂ content in the exhaust until the target SO₂ content. To find the optimized slurry input, sensitivity analyses were performed by varying the slurry input. The optimized slurry input was defined as the highest slurry input possible, where the SO₂ drop in the gas phase was still high and the solid increase low. This point can be identified by plotting the ratio (y) of SO₂ drop in the gas phase

and solid increase over the slurry input following Equation (4):

$$y = \frac{|\Delta SO_2 \text{ in gas phase}|}{\Delta \text{slurry input}} * \frac{\Delta \text{slurry input}}{\Delta \text{solids}} \quad (4)$$

The flowsheet was systematically extended with absorption units until the target SO₂ content in the exhaust gas was reached.

Evaluation and comparison of both process designs

Finally, the process designs were compared and evaluated using the following parameters:

- Number of required absorption units to reach a target SO₂ content in the exhaust gas
- Material loss due to precipitation (kg)
- The ratio of the amount of material loss due to precipitations and final liquid product (%)
- Amount of extra SO₂ required to reach a pH value in the liquid product stream of 4.5
- The ratio between the amount of liquid product and overall slurry input (kg/kg)

Results and Discussion

Figure 10 shows the result of the sensitivity analysis varying the slurry input for the first absorption step (V0). The following describes the choice of operating point for the first absorption step exemplary.

Figure 10: Solid precipitations and SO₂ content in the exhaust gas over slurry input for the first absorption step (V0)

The figure shows the chosen operating points for the first absorption step for each process design. The SO₂ decrease in the exhaust gas flattens significantly at a slurry input of 5100 kg/h. Higher slurry input does not improve the absorption of SO₂ anymore. Therefore, the operating point for the process design maximized absorption is set at a slurry input of 5100 kg/h. The optimized operating point for a process design that aims for minimized precipitations is at a slurry input of 3400 kg/h. At a lower slurry input, almost no precipitation occurs. Only around 9 kg/h precipitates form. Looking closer at the composition of the solid stream shows that the solid stream at a lower slurry input consists mainly of CaSO₃ Hemihydrate. At higher slurry input, MgSO₃ Trihydrate starts precipitating, indicating that the solubility limit of MgSO₃ is exceeded. This point can be clearly identified in Figure 11. Figure 11 shows the ratio between SO₂ decrease and solid increase (y) following Equation (4) over the slurry input.

Figure 11: Ratio y (following Equation (4)) over slurry input for the first absorption step (V0)

The ratio drops significantly at a slurry input of 3400 kg/h. A higher slurry input would drastically increase the system's precipitation, making this operating point the optimized point for the process design minimized precipitation.

The slurry input for the subsequent absorption steps is chosen following the same approach until the target SO₂ content in the exhaust gas is reached. Figure 12 summarizes the resulting slurry input for each absorption step for both designs. Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. shows the SO₂ content in the exhaust gas after each absorption step.

Figure 12: Slurry input for each absorption step and total slurry input for both process designs

Figure 13: SO₂ content in the exhaust gas after each absorption step for both process designs

Figure 13 shows that the process design maximized absorption requires four absorption steps to reach the target SO₂ content. The process design minimized precipitation requires eight absorption steps. Both designs reach an SO₂ content in the exhaust gas of around

80 ppm on a wet basis. This corresponds to an SO₂ content of around 350 mg/Nm³, referred to dry exhaust gas with an oxygen content of 5%. Although the process design minimized precipitations requires more absorption steps, it requires less overall slurry input to reach the target SO₂ level (Figure 12). While the process design maximized absorption requires a total slurry input of 9700 kg/h, the process design minimized precipitation requires only a total slurry input of 7700 kg/h. Minimizing precipitations can therefore lower the slurry demand by 20%. The lower chemical loss due to precipitation explains the lower slurry demand. Figure 14 shows the solid precipitation after each absorption step and the total solid precipitation for both process designs.

Figure 14: Solid removal after each absorption step and the total solid removal for both process designs

1620 kg/h solids precipitate in the process design maximized absorption. In the process design minimized precipitation only 390 kg/h solids precipitate. Precipitation is therefore minimized by around 75%.

Considering the material input and product output, minimization of precipitation results in an overall better process performance as it reduces chemical loss. This can be illustrated by giving the ratio of final product, which serves as cooking liquor, and slurry input. The amount of chemical loss due to precipitation compared to the product output is given by the ratio of solids and the final product (Figure 15).

Figure 15: left: Ratio between product and slurry demand; right: Ratio between solids and product expressed in percentage

When designing the process following the minimized precipitation design, the product output is higher than the slurry input, leading to

a ratio of 1.04. When designing the process following the maximized absorption design, the product output is lower than the slurry input, leading to a ratio of 0.88. The ratio between solids and final product output shows that without considering the minimization of precipitations, the amount of chemical loss in the system due to precipitations makes up almost 20% of the amount of the final product.

But slurry input is not the only material input required. Depending on the pH value of the liquid outlet of the absorption process, SO₂ needs to be added to reach the target pH value of the cooking liquor of 4.5. Figure 16 shows the pH value of the liquid after the absorption and the SO₂ needed to reach the target pH value of 4.5 for both process designs.

Figure 16: left: pH value of liquid after absorption before SO₂ addition; right: SO₂ demand to reach target pH of 4.5

The minimized precipitation design leads to around five times lower SO₂ demand to reach the target pH value of 4.5. The SO₂ demand is 6.3 kg/h, while the process design maximized absorption requires the addition of 32.8 kg/h SO₂.

Conclusion

The results show that heavy precipitation occurs in the first three absorption steps when designing the process to reach maximized absorption. By lowering the absorption in each step, precipitation can be significantly reduced. However, more absorption steps are necessary to reach the target SO₂ content in the exhaust gas. The process design minimized precipitation results in a five times lower SO₂ demand and a 20% lower slurry demand. This study only compares the two process designs regarding slurry input, SO₂ input, and chemical loss due to precipitation. It does not include the chemicals required to wash out the solid deposits during maintenance intervals. High precipitations also lead to a high washing liquid demand.

The study suggests that a process that aims to minimize precipitations performs more material efficiently due to an overall lower chemical demand and lower chemical loss in the process. The performed analyses show that including unwanted precipitations in process simulation experiments is crucial to find optimized absorption conditions. To make a final judgment about the economic and ecologic advantages of installing extra absorption units to reduce precipitation, a comprehensive case study is necessary, which takes a cradle to grave or cradle to cradle approach for the process, the

process equipment, process chemicals and the energy demand into account.

Acknowledgment

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support by the project partner Sappi Papier Holding GmbH.

References

- [1] X. Liu *et al.*, "Research progress in the environmental application of magnesium hydroxide nanomaterials," *Surfaces and Interfaces*, vol. 21, p. 100701, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.surfin.2020.100701.
- [2] B. D. Weiß and M. Harasek, "Solubility Data of Potential Salts in the MgO-CaO-SO₂-H₂O-O₂ System for Process Modeling," *Processes*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 50, 2021, doi: 10.3390/pr9010050.
- [3] B. D. Weiß, W. Fuchs, and M. Harasek, "Finding Optimized Process Conditions to Minimize Precipitations in an SO₂ Absorption Process Using Thermodynamic Process Simulation," *Chem Eng Trans*, vol. 88, pp. 535–540, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.3303/CET2188089.
- [4] M. Steindl, T. Röder, R. Simharl, M. Harasek, A. Friedl, and H. Sixta, "Online Raman monitoring of the phase transition of magnesium sulphite hydrate," *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 471–475, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.cep.2004.06.011.
- [5] P. Bajpai, "Pulping Fundamentals," *Biermann's Handbook of Pulp and Paper*, pp. 295–351, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-814240-0.00012-4.
- [6] J. Stubenvoll, E. Holzerbauer, S. Böhmer, T. Krutzler, and T. Janhsen, "TECHNISCHE MASSNAHMEN ZUR MINDERUNG DER STAUB-UND NO X-EMISSIONEN BEI WIRBELSCHICHT-UND LAUGENVERBRENNUNGSKESSELN," 2007, Accessed: Feb. 13, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://www.umweltbundesamt.at/>
- [7] J. L. Hudson, J. Erwin, and N. M. Catipovic, "Kinetics of Sulfur Dioxide Oxidation in Aqueous Solution," *Interagency Energy-Environment Research and Development series*, vol. EPA-600/7-79-030, no. EPA-600/7-79-030, 1979.

Study on Ammonia Preparation in the Exhaust Path of Stationary Gas Engines

T. Steiner^{1*}, D. Deniff¹, M. Pillei¹, V. Schallhart¹, L. Möltner^{1,2}

1: Dept. of Life Science and Technology, MCI, Austria

2: Institute of Powertrains and Automotive Technology, Vienna University of Technology

* Corresponding author: thomas.steiner@mci.edu

Keywords: Exhaust Gas Treatment, Nitrogen Oxides, Selective Catalytic Reduction, Spray Characterization

Research field: Emission control

Abstract

This study investigates SCR injection systems for large-scale gas engines; it includes three consecutive steps from a component test run to a simulation tool. Different injection systems and nozzles have been analyzed with laser diffraction measurement. One system was chosen for a trial run under real conditions. On the hand of these two tests, a simulation was built up with MATLAB to compare different parameters for SCR systems. The simulation helps figure out the specificities of these systems for stationary gas engines compared to mobile diesel engines. The different scales of both, exhaust gas mass flow and dimensions of the exhaust pipe, change the conditions and requirements. The focus is on the urea preparation in front of the catalytic converter and not on the catalytic processes itself. With the created simulation is it possible to design different SCR systems in aspect to the geometric parameters of the exhaust pipe and the desired injection system and position.

Introduction

Nitrogen oxides (NO_x) occur during combustion processes; especially at conditions above 1573 K, the formation increases rapidly. It is harmful to human health and an air pollution with consequences like smog formation and acid rain. Selective catalytic reduction (SCR) is a commonly used technology for the reduction of NO_x emissions from combustion processes such as those of combustion plants and internal combustion engines (ICE). SCR systems are highly effective at reducing NO_x emissions and are widely used in stationary and mobile applications [1]. Modern natural gas engines, like in combined heat and power units (CHP), can achieve NO_x emission limits below 500 mg/Nm³ (related to 5% oxygen in the exhaust gas) due to engine internal measures. Depending on the applicable regulations, even stricter limits have to be observed. For lean combustion, an SCR system is the most effective approach.

The effectiveness of the system depends on several parameters. Success-critical steps are the injection and preparation of the reducing fluid, before interacting with the catalytic converter. The reducing agent is mostly ammonia, which is, due to safety reasons, used as 32.5 m.-% urea-water solution (UWS) partly known as AdBlue® or for stationary applications even in higher gravimetric shares, e.g. with 40 m.-% called Aqueous Urea Solution (AUS 40). Upstream the converter, urea is converted to ammonia, which is needed for the intended reduction of NO_x. When UWS is injected into the exhaust stream, it vaporizes and decomposes into ammonia and carbon dioxide. Consequently, ammonia reacts with NO_x over a catalytic substrate, which can be modified zeolites or vanadium, tungsten or titanium oxide-based (anatas) catalyst. The catalyst promotes the chemical reaction of reducing NO_x to nitrogen (N₂) and gaseous water (H₂O) and can lower emissions up to 90%. Urea decomposition is starting at a temperature of 353 K; higher temperatures are leading to faster decomposition rates. The chemical degradation is based on two reactions, namely thermolysis (equation 1) and hydrolysis (equation 2) [2, 3]. The simultaneously formed by-product is isocyanic acid (HNCO), which is consecutively converted to another mol of ammonia by hydrolysis.

Below a temperature of 573 K, Yim et al. mentioned no significant hydrolysis of HNCO to NH₃ and CO₂ [4, 5].

The effectiveness of these DeNO_x systems depends widely on the success of thermolysis and hydrolysis. Therefore, the gas temperature and the droplets' resident times between the dosing position and entering the catalytic converter are key factors in achieving sufficient ammonia yields.

Until now, gas engines have handled the NO_x limits with a lean burn operation. This opportunity is nearly fully utilized, so the introduction of exhaust gas treatment is indispensable for stricter regulations. Since there has been hardly demand for such systems, there has been less research in this area so far. The major research part of SCR systems for ICE came from the automotive sector. In contrast to mobile applications, a droplet/wall contact should be prevented for stationary gas engines. In mobile/automotive applications, the available installation space for exhaust gas components is strictly limited; therefore, wall impact is constructively used to support the ammonia preparation. For stationary systems, installation space is not such a limiting factor; here, the goal is to keep the droplets distributed in the exhaust gas. This work investigates whether there is a risk of droplet/wall contact in gas engines and if yes, how it can be prevented. Furthermore, the urea preparation should get studied, especially the urea yield and the impact of the injector's position and spray direction. Additionally, the needed length of the mixing section for a complete decomposition of urea should also be determined.

Literature Review

The automotive branch researched a lot in the field of gas treatment with SCR in the last decade. Therefore, a great amount of data are available. The difference in scale between stationary gas engines and mobile ICE for passenger- and commercial vehicles bringing out new challenges for the implementation.

Dong Et al. [6] emphasized the preparation of the urea mixture as a critical point. The commonly used AdBlue for mobile applications is a 32.5% solution of high-purity. It is used as an aqueous solution due to the handling. Therefore, it is necessary to decompose the urea, which forms ammonia as reactant for the SCR-system. The thermal decomposition of urea is a major step to enable the reaction from NO_x to N₂. An incomplete decomposition leads to multiple issues. If the fluid is not completely broken down, it leads to ammonia slip in the exhaust gas. Further, the efficiency of the system reduces and the AdBlue consumption rises. Another problem is the formation of deposits. Three main points are responsible for the deposits: low exhaust gas temperature, high space velocity and an inferior quality injection system. Deposits can stick on the injectors, the exhaust pipe wall and the catalyzer surface.

On the injection nozzles, the contaminations leading to an undesirable spray, with changed spray pattern and spray angle. On the pipe wall, the deposits can agglomerate to a large accumulation

and influence the exhaust gas flow and the incident flow of the catalytic converter; deposits block the active centers for the reaction partners. Due to all this negative effects, a complete decomposition should be ensured to reach a high efficient operation.

Shahariar et al. [7] described the spray wall impingement of the urea-water solution as the major parameter for the efficiency of an SCR-system in automotive applications. They investigated the development of the urea spray after the impingement on the wall of the exhaust pipe. The influence of the wall temperature and the injection velocity were considered. In summary, the injection velocity, the wall temperature and the injection angle were identified as the most important influencing parameters.

Khristamto et al. [8] figured out, that the major challenges for SCR systems in heavy-duty diesel engines are the uniform distribution of urea and mitigation of solid deposit formation. They also simulated, that the injector position and angle has an impact on the urea distribution in the exhaust pipe and therefore, an effect on the efficiency of the system.

Fundamentals

The developed numerical model is based on earlier studies by Schallhart et al. [5, 9]. Newton's law of motion is applied to describe droplets' trajectories in a surrounding gas flow by using equation 3. The dynamic problem is solved by using d'Alembert's principle. For this, the equation is rearranged to represent external forces acting on the droplet (\vec{F}), the droplet's mass (m) and acceleration (\vec{a}). This results in the d'Alembert's inertia force (\vec{F}_I) in equation 3, which lies on the same line of action as the other forces but in the opposite direction, resulting in a sum of zero. This transforms the dynamic problem into a static one [10]. The derivation of the forces is divided into horizontal (x) and vertical (y) components (equation 4), with the horizontal droplet velocity being derived in equation 5 by comparing all forces in the x -direction. The vertical droplet velocity takes account in the buoyancy and gravitational forces.

$$\vec{F} = m \cdot \vec{a} \Rightarrow \vec{F} - m \cdot \vec{a} = 0 \Rightarrow \vec{F}_{res} - \vec{F}_I = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{F}_D + \vec{F}_{gas} - \vec{F}_{droplet} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$d\vec{v}_{droplet} = c_D \cdot \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{\rho_{gas}}{\rho_{droplet} \cdot d_{droplet}} \cdot \vec{v}_{rel}^2 \cdot dt + \frac{\rho_{gas}}{\rho_{droplet}} \cdot d\vec{u}_{gas} \quad (5)$$

First Fick's law describes the rate of diffusion for droplets (or particles) due to a concentration gradient (equation 6) [11]. The diffusion flux (J) designates the quantity of droplets (N) which are crossing a defined area (A) in a default time step (dt). This gradient, leads to the calculation of mass loss through equation 7. In order to find the pressure difference between the droplet surface and the exhaust gas stream, the Kelvin pressure is applied. This value is used to determine the vapor pressure over a curved surface by the Gibbs-energy and the Young-Laplace equation, which considers factors such as surface tension (γ) and droplet radius (r). This explains why smaller droplets have a higher evaporation rate. Additionally, the relative humidity of the exhaust gas flow is taken into consideration in the pressure term of the gas stream.

$$J = D \frac{dc}{dx} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{A} \cdot \frac{dN}{dt} = D \frac{dc}{dx} \quad (6)$$

$$dm = \frac{D}{dx} \cdot \frac{1}{R} \cdot \left(\frac{p_{Kelvin}(T_{droplet})}{T_{droplet}} - \frac{(1-X_{rel}) \cdot p_v(T_{gas})}{T_{gas}} \right) \cdot A \cdot M \cdot dt \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{2\gamma}{r} = \frac{R \cdot T}{V_m} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{p_{Kelvin}}{p_v} \right) \quad (8)$$

For the calculation of urea decomposition, a plug-flow reactor model is applied. Instead of using the velocity of droplets, the time step for their movement in the exhaust pipe is applied. The kinetics of the reaction is described by using a power law.

$$\frac{dn_{urea}}{dt} = -k_{thermo} \cdot n_{urea}^1 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dn_{HNCO}}{dt} = -k_{hydro} \cdot n_{HNCO}^1 + k_{thermo} \cdot n_{urea}^1 \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{dn_{ammonia}}{dt} = k_{hydro} \cdot n_{hydro}^1 + k_{thermo} \cdot n_{urea}^1 \quad (11)$$

The derived power law describes the reaction progress; the chemical reactions are assumed as first-order reactions due to a unilateral decomposition of urea and an inherent surplus of H₂O for hydrolysis due to relatively high share of H₂O in the engine's exhaust. Equation 9 describes the thermolysis process, and is solved by the Euler method. Equation 10 refer to hydrolysis, which involves both, a consumption and a formation term. The formation of NH₃ depends on the urea and the isocyanic concentration (equation 11); the kinetic parameters are listed in Table.6.

Table.6: Reaction parameters for the thermolysis and hydrolysis reaction according to Yim et al. [1, 2].

Thermolysis	$k_{thermo} = 4900 \text{ s}^{-1} \cdot e^{-\frac{23033 \cdot \frac{J}{mol}}{R \cdot T}}$
Hydrolysis	$k_{hydro} = 250000 \text{ s}^{-1} \cdot e^{-\frac{62179 \cdot \frac{J}{mol}}{R \cdot T}}$

Methodology

To start the numerical simulation, it is necessary to define the default diameters of various UWS droplets. This information was obtained by determining the particle size distribution from an injection nozzle of a gas engine from a manufacturer. The investigation was conducted with a UWS volume flow of 15 l·h⁻¹ and calculated to reduce the nitrogen oxide concentration in the exhaust gas to an extent of 250 mg·Nm⁻³. Results gathered during engine tests reveal that particle size distribution ranges 10 μm up to 250 μm. For the simulation, four cases with sets of variables were defined (Table 7). The variations affecting the injection position, the injection angle and if the spray is injected parallel or counter to the exhaust flow. The calculation method for the numerical investigation remains consistent.

Table 7: Parameters for the simulated model variations.

Modell Variation	Flow Direction	Injection Position	Injection Angle
Variation I	Parallel	x=0; y=0.255	α=0°
Variation II	Counter	x=0; y=0.255	α=0°
Variation III	Counter	x=0; y=0	α=45°
Variation IV	Counter	x=0; y= 0.100	α=45°

For the consideration of the droplet trajectory the upper and lower limit diameter are important, because all others are between these two. Larger droplets possess more kinetic energy and therefore, the acceleration due to the gas stream is slower than for smaller ones. Figure 17 shows trajectories for the variation case I. The injection angle depends on the nozzle itself (spray angle) and the position of the nozzle. For case I the nozzle is orientated parallel to the exhaust gas in flow direction. Therefore, the spray angle is defined by the nozzle geometry. The different variation cases vary the injection angle and the horizontal injection position but not the vertical position. The y-axis is adjusted and describes the distance between the bottom – which is the wall of the pipe – and the nozzle. The exhaust pipe has a diameter of 0.51 m and therefore, a value of 0.225 m describes the center axis in horizontal direction.

The injection angle refers the deviation from the nozzle to the horizontal axis.

Figure 17: Injection position of the nozzle for Model I.

In order to reduce simulation time, the spray is separated into different areas. Jet 1 describes the upper spray limit of the nozzle spray pattern, jet 2 the intermediate position and jet 3 the lower spray limit. Since the nozzle under consideration generate a rotationally symmetrical spray, the simulation of one half is sufficient for the case of exhaust-gas-parallel injection at the center point.

Discussion of Results

Figure 18 represents the simulation result for the variation case I and display the result for the jet 1 (upper limit of the nozzles spray angle). The trajectory depends clearly on the droplet diameter. Small droplets are carried with the exhaust gas flow briefly after nozzle outlet. Larger droplets have a higher mass and therefore, these droplets were accelerated slower than smaller lighter ones. Hence, they reaching higher values on the y-axis. Consequently, they have a higher risk to hit the wall compared to the droplets with smaller diameters. That is the reason why the trajectories of the droplets depends on geometric parameters. However, due to the mechanisms of thermolysis and hydrolysis already described, these parameters vary after injection. The change of these parameters is directly related to the temperature; so, the heat transfer from the hot exhaust gas to the colder droplet plays a major role for the whole decomposition process.

Figure 18: Result for the UWS droplet trajectory for variation case I and jet 1.

In Figure 19 the mass decrease sorted by the droplet diameters and depending on residence time is displayed. The evaporation time is influenced by one two major factors.

Figure 19: Mass decrease of the different droplet sizes over the residence time after injection.

Greater droplets including more mass of water and so, the evaporation needs more time. Additionally, greater droplets have smaller relatively surfaces. Therefore, less heat-transfer from the hot exhaust to the fluid is feasible. These two factors even influent the decomposition process where also a heat transfer is needed. The result is that the decompositions starts later and has a longer duration. For the displayed case, only the d_{10} reaches the point where all the mass is converted from liquid to gaseous phase.

To review the process from the evaporation to the transition in the gaseous phase in detail, Figure 20 shows the entire process for the diameter d_{90} . The progression of the mass trend as well as for temperature can be divided into three areas. Especially for the mass profile, the phase shifts are significant. The dashed line in the diagram represents the mass and the dotdashed line describes the temperature.

Figure 20: Trend of the droplet mass and the droplet temperature after injection for diameter d_{90} .

The first phase describes the water evaporation. At the injection point ($x=0$) the droplet has the injection temperature. The hot exhaust gas interacts with the boundary layer so, the evaporation

happens between the exhaust gas and the boundary layer of the droplet.

As long as water evaporates at the interfaces, the temperature does not change. While the temperature stays constant, the mass drops exponential due to the phase change from liquid to vapor. After the rapid mass loss, the point of constant mass is reached immediately. At the same point the temperature rise starts.

The end of the evaporation is also the start of the temperature rise. This is the initial mark for the second section that is named constant mass phase. Here, the mass remains constant because no more water is available to evaporate.

Starting at a droplet temperature of 353 K, the NH₃ decomposition begins. That is why this part is called urea decomposition phase. An increasing temperature leads to a faster breakdown [2, 3, 4]. At the maximum level of the temperature profile line, the droplet temperature matches the exhaust gas temperature. After 5 to 6 m along the x-trajectory, the droplet mass approaches zero, indicating that urea has mostly decomposed into NH₃ and HNCO. It is important for the efficiency of the SCR system, that the mass has converted before the surface of the catalytic converter is reached.

The performance of four different variation cases for jet 1 are compared to find the most efficient model based on the numerical simulation. Table 8 compares the different variation cases. To determine the highest efficiency model, the chemical conversion of urea and the yields of isocyanic acid and ammonia were analyzed. All simulated cases have a narrow range for the chemical conversion of urea. Therefore, hardly a significant differential can be formulated.

A lower yield of isocyanic acid is preferred as it is an intermediate product. The yield of isocyanic reaches a maximum before it starts to decrease. Since NH₃ is needed for the NO_x treatment, the yield of ammonia is the major indicator for the efficiency of the SCR system. The highest ammonia yield (59.72%) were reached for the variations cases III and IV. Both are approximately 0.4% higher than case I. Table 8 includes all results of the important variables for the four different variation cases.

Table 8: Comparison of the four simulated variation cases depending on the injection direction, position and angle according to jet 1.

Variation case	I	II	III	IV
Flow	Parallel	Counter	Counter	Counter
Angle	0°	0°	45°	45°
Position y / m	0.255	0.255	0	0.1
Jet	1	1	1	1
Benchmark x / m	7	7	7	7
X_{urea} / %	99.95	99.95	99.96	99.96
Y_{HNCO} / %	80.85	80.68	80.46	80.46
Y_{NH3} / %	59.36	59.61	59.72	59.72
D_{droplet} / m	4.6 · 10 ⁻⁶	4.51 · 10 ⁻⁶	4.4 · 10 ⁻⁶	4.4 · 10 ⁻⁶
Δt / s	0.136569	0.136986	0.136872	0.136872

For the resident time Δt, an exception is noted for variation case II. It would be assumed that the resident time and yield of NH₃ are connected. Therefore, the highest yield should also show the longest time. However, the results present the shortest time for variation case 2. A possible reason therefore could be, that the gas flow also affects the droplet mass loss, which is calculated by the Reynolds number. The reaction rate decreases as the concentration decreases,

which is expected because the reaction is considered as a first-order reaction and therefore, the reaction rate only depends on the concentration.

The injection for the variation case I is displayed in Figure 17. There, the nozzle is fixed in a center position inside the pipe and in flow direction. For the case II the injector is mounted in the same position but in opposite direction as counter flow injection. For the variation cases III and IV the injector nozzle is turned about 45° related to the horizontal line in counter direction of the gas flow. For a visualization variation case IV is shown in Figure 21. While case IV is mounted in a distance from 0.1 m the bottom side, the variation III is attached without a gap between injector and pipe wall.

Figure 21: Front view of the variation case IV injection.

For the variation cases III and IV, the NH₃ yields of the jet 3 simulation is lower than of jet 1. That also leads to a lower ammonia preparation and less efficiency. The trajectory of the case IV with the jet 3 is presented in Figure 22.

Variation case II has the highest efficiency with the jet 3 due to its high NH₃ yield. However, based on the narrow result range, the differences are not significant.

Figure 22: UWS droplet trajectory from variation case IV and jet 3.

Case IV (Figure 21) has two advantages. On the one hand, it achieves the highest NH₃ yields and on the other hand, it prevents a droplet-wall contact, as confirmed by the numerical simulation. The chemical conversion of urea, the yield from isocyanic acid and the yield of ammonia are depicted in Figure 23. It can be seen, that urea conversion is completed before the maximum NH₃ yield is achieved. From the turning point on, the increasing yield of NH₃ bases on the reaction from HNCO to NH₃.

Figure 23: Comparison of the urea conversion, the isocyanic acid yield and the ammonia yield of model IV and jet 1 for diameter d_{90} .

Conclusion

Due to stricter emission limits for almost all areas of industry and power generation, continuous efforts must be made to refine existing technologies and to find new options. Therefore, in this paper the SCR technology has been considered in more detail and specifically the urea treatment for stationary gas engines. A bench test experiment produced promising data on droplet diameter measurements, which were used as initial values for the simulation, which is built up by the software MATLAB[®]. The simulation results, based on scientific principles, were consistent and compared with relevant scientific literature.

By deriving the evaporation rate of water, in the hot exhaust gas stream, using scientific principles, it is possible to determine the required path and time, in the ammonia treatment section, traveled by the droplet until all water is evaporated. Because of the high difference in temperature, at the boundary between droplet and gas, a high pressure gradient is recognized. Therefore, the evaporation time is rather short and the water content only plays a minor role for the efficiency of the ammonia preparation and also a more diluted solution could be used as an ammonia source. All simulation parameters such as exhaust pipe diameter, pipe length, gas temperature, gas velocity, and others came from an existing test bench.

Additional to the before shown variations (Table 8), further simulation cases were investigated. It could be determined, that for a central injection position the opening angle of the nozzle should not exceed 80°, because a droplet wall contact was recognized for diameter d_{250} during the simulation run. In mobile applications, a wall contact is frequently used due to the conditions. The installation space for these units is strongly limited. Therefore, these is a possibility to generate longer dwell times for the urea solution to ensure a complete decomposition. This method also has disadvantages like accumulation of urea on the exhaust pipe wall, when the surface is too cold for the process. For applications with limited space, an additional mixture in the exhaust pipe is also a state of the art technology. However, this results in an additional pressure loss and consequently in a loss of efficiency. Because of this, for gas engines an air distribution is wanted to achieve the highest possible overall system efficiency.

By comparing and analyzing the droplet trajectories of all variation cases and tabulating the yields and conversions of the ammonia treatment, one variation stood out. Variation case IV does not show a significant improvement over number III, in terms of ammonia

yield, but due to the upward directed injection, no droplet wall contact is expected.

Nevertheless, the maximum reachable ammonia yield with the given parameters is approximately 60%, the quantity of isocyanic acid cannot undercut a value of 80% with respect to the initial urea substance amount. This probably causes that the remaining isocyanic acid is then converted to ammonia in the catalyst. Which means that the actual reduction of NO_x to N₂ with ammonia, cannot take place because the active centers already occupied by the hydrolysis reaction [3]. Furthermore, this means that on the one hand NO_x leaves the exhaust tract untreated and on the other hand, that the NH₃ is emitted to the atmosphere.

An important output of this simulation was that, the flow direction has not a significant influence on the urea yield, but for the counter flow injection the risk of a wall impingement is higher than for the parallel injection. On the other hand, the resident time is slightly higher so, the decompositions process has so more time to progress. The droplet size has an impact on the decomposition of the urea, smaller droplets need less time therefore, and a shorter distance between injector and catalytic converter is required. The injector system and especially the nozzle has influence on the droplet size disruption. Here, further investigation would be interesting to figure out how the optimum system has to look like.

Another aspect, which could have an influence on the efficiency of the SCR system, is the ammonia distribution over the surface of the catalytic converter. The goal is a homogenous distribution over the whole surface and should be considered in further investigations.

Bibliography

- [1] Z. Friedmann, Gasmotoren, vol. 1. Aufl., Würzburg: Vogel-Fachbuch, 2001.
- [2] M. Koebel, M. Elsner and M. Kleemann, "Urea-SCR: a promising technique to reduce NO_x emissions from automotive diesel engines", Catalysis Today, Volume 59, Issues 3–4, pp. Pages 335-345, 2000.
- [3] L. Möltner, "Fahrzeugtechnik. Bd. 785: Tropfen-Abgas- und Tropfen-Wandinteraktionen von AdBlue bei der selektiven katalytischen Reduktion von Stickoxiden", Fortschrittberichte VDI Reihe 12, Verkehrstechnik, Fahrzeugtechnik, vol. Bd. 785, 2014.
- [4] S. D. Yim, et al., "Decomposition of urea into NH₃ for the SCR process", Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research 43 (2004), S4856-4863.
- [5] V. Schallhart and L. Möltner, "Effect of Spray-Exhaust Gas Interactions on Ammonia Generation in SCR Mixing Sections," SAE Int. J. Fuels Lubr. 11(2):181–200, 2018.
- [6] Dong, Hongyi & Shuai, Shijin & Wang, Jianxin, "Effect of Urea Thermal Decomposition on Diesel NO_x-SCR Aftertreatment Systems", SAE Technical Paper (2008), 10.4271/2008-01-1544.
- [7] G.M.H. Shahariar, et al., "Analysis of the spray wall impingement of urea-water solution for automotive SCR De-NO_x systems", Energy Procedia, Volume 158 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2019.01.448>
- [8] M.K.A. Wardana, et al., "A study of urea injection timing to predict the NO_x conversion in SCR systems", Energy Procedia, Volume 158 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2019.01.449>
- [9] V. Schallhart and L. Möltner, "Numerical optimization of AdBlue®-injection into the mixing section of SCR-systems". WSEAS Transactions on Fluid Mechanics. 10. 80-87.
- [10] H. Kürten, J. Raasch and H. Rumpf, "Beschleunigung eines kugelförmigen Feststoffteilchens im Strömungsfeld konstanter Geschwindigkeit," vol. 38, no. 9, pp. 941-948, 1966. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cite.330380905>
- [11] C. Czeslik, H. Seemann and R. Winter, Basiswissen Physikalische Chemie, Wiesbaden: Vieweg+Teubner Verlag / GWV Fachverlage GmbH Wiesbaden, 2010.

Lab-scale production of activated carbon from gasification residues via thermochemical CO₂ activation

D. Gurtner^{1,2,*}, M. Kresta^{1,2}, A. Hofmann^{1,3}, C. Pfeifer²

1: Josef Ressel Centre for production of activated carbon from municipal residues, Department for Environmental-, Energy and Process Engineering, Management Center Innsbruck – MCI, Maximilianstraße 2, 6020, Innsbruck, Austria

2: Institute for Chemical and Energy Engineering, University of Natural Resources and Life Science – BOKU, Gregor-Mendel-Straße 33, 1180, Vienna, Austria

3: Department of Environmental, Process and Energy Engineering, Management Center Innsbruck – MCI, Maximilianstraße 2, 6020, Innsbruck, Austria

* Corresponding author: david.gurtner@mci.edu

Keywords: Activated Carbon, Gasification, Biochar, Thermochemical/Physical Activation, Porosity

Research field: Activated Carbon

Abstract

Gasification residues (GR), produced as by-product in a wood gasification plant with floating fixed bed technology, can be used as precursor for the production of sustainable activated carbon (AC). For the required thermochemical activation, the optimal parameters, i.e. temperature, time, activation agent and its volume flow, have to be determined. The char is activated in an ex-situ laboratory-scale fluidized bed reactor with CO₂ and characterized via gas adsorption and thermogravimetric analysis. The mass loss steadily increases with temperature and time, whereas the specific BET surface area and pore volume tend to flatten for long durations. An economical consideration of the trade-off between developed porosity and mass loss indicates around 830 °C and 15 min to achieve the highest yield of absolute BET surface area and micropore volume. From a qualitative point of view, a specific BET surface area of 628 m²g⁻¹ and a share in micropores of 50% is achieved. The addition of air, which should enable a more economical activation process, results in a significantly lower porosity of 534.9 m²g⁻¹, which, nevertheless, is almost twice the area of the GR.

Introduction

Global warming, resource depletion and pollution induced by the progressive industrialization are calling for modern remediation methods. In recent years AC has received increasing attention due to its distinctive properties, such as highly developed porous structure, versatility and recalcitrance. The resulting high adsorption capacity leads to various applications, such as water and air purification, storage and usage as catalyst. Nowadays, AC is one of the most widely applied adsorbents, with the demand set to be healthy. Commercially, AC is primarily obtained from fossil coal, partly from biogenic materials, such as coconut shells, but barely from biogenic sustainable by-products. [1–3]

In this respect, GR, synthesized from a wood gasification plant with a patented floating fixed bed technology, are an environmentally friendly and cost-effective option, but in raw form only marginally efficient. Consequently, the properties of the GR have to be improved to produce highly adsorptive AC. One method for upgrading the GR is the thermochemical activation. According to literature [4–6] the parameters temperature, time and mass ratio of activation agent to char have the most significant influence on the thermochemical activation process. Consequently, these parameters are studied in order to maximize the quality and quantity of the produced AC. [4, 6, 7]

AC is a highly porous, carbonaceous material, which is characterized by its large surface area ranging from 500 m²g⁻¹ to 3000 m²g⁻¹. Nowadays, it is widely accepted that AC has structural disordered, randomly oriented crystallites. Stacked graphitic planes, described as similar to wrinkled paper sheets, form those crystallites. The high internal surface area of the microporous structure results from spaces between the graphitic planes. The performance of an activation process is measured mainly by the specific surface area, pore distribution and size. According to the IUPAC classification pores can be divided into micropores (MIC (<2 nm)), mesopores (MES (2–50 nm)) and macropores (MAC (>50 nm)). Thermochemical activation is achieved in the presence of gaseous oxidation agents such as CO₂, steam, ozone or air at temperatures between 600 °C and 900 °C. The formation of pores via thermochemical steam activation is correlated with the depletion of carbon by the heterogeneous water gas reaction. Different to the activation with CO₂, steam facilitates the development of micro- and mesopores. [7, 8] The formation of pores via thermochemical CO₂ activation is correlated with the depletion of carbon by the heterogeneous Boudouard reaction quoted in equation (1). Due to the clearly endothermic character (172 kJmol⁻¹) of the Boudouard reaction, the production of carbon monoxide is not favored until temperatures of above 700 °C. [5, 9]

Beside the activation with pure CO₂, the activation with the addition of air, i.e. a mixture of CO₂ and synthetic air, is also being investigated. Thus an economical activation is achieved and pronounced porosity reached by locally high temperatures. [10, 11] The autothermal activation is especially interesting with regard to the activation on pilot-scale, which makes preceding investigations in laboratory-scale advantageous.

In literature, numerous papers [12–15] used pyrolysed biomass from various feedstock materials for thermochemical activation. Since in present work the precursor for activation is, instead of just pyrolysed, already gasified, full comparability is no longer feasible. Only a few earlier studies [16, 17] concerning the thermochemical activation of GR could be found. Recent studies [18] regarding the activation of GR by chemical impregnation are available. Furthermore, studies comparing AC with GR can be found in literature [19]. The company Torrgas produces clean wood gas and AC from residual materials. [20] A patent [21], published recently by Torrgas, describes that specific BET surface areas of 700 m²g⁻¹ can be obtained by steam and/or air activation.

The advantages of activated GR are that it is renewable, cost-effective and suitable for the removal of several pollutants. [22] However, the process of thermochemical activation is accompanied with a high-energy consumption. [23] Toles et al. [24] calculated an electricity usage of 7501 kWh d⁻¹ and 4075 kWh d⁻¹ for CO₂ and steam activation processes, respectively. Reza et al. [25] states that CO₂ activation can be preferable since the process is easier to control. Nevertheless, the steam activation will be investigated in future research. Furthermore, the adsorption capacity of the AC is low compared to AC prepared from activation with chemical impregnation, but the process less energy and time consuming.

Materials and Methods

Production of Activated Carbon

The used strategy of the thermochemical activation is based on former experiments, literature and theses. The precursor is the by-product of an industrial wood gasification plant. The GR are activated in a laboratory-scale fluidized bed reactor, depicted in the following Figure 24.

Figure 24: Lab-scale fluidized bed reactor for thermochemical activation

The thermochemical activation is performed batch-wise between 750 °C and 850 °C for 5 min to 20 min with 7 g of precursor. Completed activation experiments (Figure 25 – black) are subsequently presented and the ongoing/planned investigations (grey) are part of future research. The experimental series are planned with Design of Experiments (randomized face centred central composite design) between 750 °C and 850 °C for 5 min to 20 min.

Figure 25: Experimental overview

For the CO₂ experiments, a flow rate of 2 lmin⁻¹ is chosen; on the

one hand, in order to guarantee a definite surplus of CO₂ and, on the other hand, to maintain a minimum flow velocity to achieve fluidization. The chosen flow rate is compared to [26–28] significantly higher, but, contrary to what is described in the literature, no negative effects (collapsed pore walls or complete burn-off due to a too high flow rate) could be observed. Hanaoka et al. [11] achieved the highest porosities with a CO₂/O₂ mixture of 1:1, which is why this ratio is adopted for the presented CO₂/air activation experiments. However, synthetic air is used instead of pure O₂, since in industrial-scale it would probably not be economically feasible.

Activated Carbon Characterization

As most important factor in terms of char quality the specific BET (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller) surface area $S_{\text{spec,BET}}$ is determined via gas adsorption analysis ("3 Flex Surface Characterization" from Micromeritics). As a high share of microporosity is mostly accompanied with an efficient adsorption capacity, the pore size distribution is measured via the non-local-density functional theory (NLDFT). As result of the NLDFT method the cumulative pore volume V_p and the pore width is issued. Consequently, the MAC volume can be calculated from the difference between total pore volume and the sum of MIC and MES volume. The proximate composition divides charcoal into the components moisture, volatile matter (VM) w_{VM} , fixed carbon (FC) w_{FC} and ash w_{ash} . [29] Since all of these components are released at different temperatures or atmospheres, the analysis can be carried out using thermogravimetric analysis (Mettler Toledo; TGA/DSC 1 STAR^c System; Gas Controller GC 200). Therefore, the mass loss is determined as a function of time and temperature. The used method is based on DIN 51720:2001-03 [30]. Due the degradation of charcoal during the activation experiment, a gravimetrically determined mass loss $w_{\text{loss,act}}$, calculated according to equation (2), evolves.

$$w_{\text{loss,act}} = \frac{m_{\text{DS,pre}} + m_{\text{DS,act}}}{m_{\text{DS,pre}}} \quad (2)$$

Since mainly carbon reacts, the fixed carbon conversion $w_{\text{loss,act,FC}}$ is calculated with help of the thermogravimetric analysis results according to equation (3).

$$w_{\text{loss,act,FC}} = \frac{w_{\text{FC,pre}} \cdot m_{\text{DS,pre}} - w_{\text{FC,act}} \cdot m_{\text{DS,act}}}{w_{\text{FC,pre}} \cdot m_{\text{DS,pre}}} \quad (3)$$

By referring those values to the dry substance (DS), a falsification due to different moisture contents of the samples can be avoided. Where m_{act} stands for the weight of the activated sample, m_{pre} is the weight of the precursor.

Results and Discussion

The results, i.e. gas adsorption analysis, thermogravimetric analysis, economic evaluation, are presented separately for the CO₂ and air/CO₂ activation.

Thermochemical Activation with CO₂

According to Figure 26, the mass loss $w_{\text{loss,act}}$ (left) and fixed carbon conversion $w_{\text{loss,act,FC}}$ (right) during CO₂ activation increase with higher temperature and longer activation time. The activation temperature, which is set on the muffle furnace, is designated by T_{act} and the time used for the perfusion with the activation agent is t_{act} .

Figure 26: Mass loss and fixed carbon conversion during activation

This behavior can be traced back to the fact that at higher temperatures the reaction equilibrium is almost completely on the side of the products. A longer activation time, on the other hand, allows the reaction to progress further. In case of 850 °C, the increases of mass loss and fixed carbon conversion over time is very pronounced. Conversely, at 750 °C the mass loss and fixed carbon conversion stay rather constant with time. Thus, it can be concluded, that with respect to the mass loss and fixed carbon conversion, time only has a significant influence at higher temperatures. The decisive reaction occurring is the Boudouard reaction, quoted in equation (1). The Boudouard reaction, cited in equation (1), is endothermic, which is why high temperatures shift the equilibrium towards the product side of carbon monoxide.

Gas Adsorption Analysis

Representative for the porosity of the produced AC, Figure 27 shows the determined specific BET surface area $S_{\text{spec,BET}}$ (left) and total pore volume V_P (right) during CO₂ activation.

Figure 27: Porosities of the produced AC from GR

With rising temperatures, existing pores are widened and new ones are formed – resulting in an increased specific BET surface area, total pore volume and share of MIC – which corresponds well with the literature [4]. In contrast to the mass loss, which establishes a rather linear course, the specific BET surface area and total pore volume tend to flatten for long durations and high temperatures. This means that after a certain time the maximum in porosity is reached, although the gasification/activation continues. Jaganathan et al. [10] investigated a transition at high temperatures from reaction rate limited to diffusion limited conditions. Once this transition to a so-called shrinking core regime is reached, specific BET surface area remains, due to only surface reactions, constant but the mass loss increases further. [10] With longer activation times the Boudouard reaction continuous, resulting in the formation of MIC, which increases the specific BET surface area. [26] The higher activation temperatures and the longer times, the more MIC are generated. In turn, the relative share of MES is decreasing. Nevertheless, the absolute volume of MES is increasing. The relative share of MAC remains rather constant, but in total, this amount doubles from

0.017 cm³g⁻¹ (precursor) to 0.034 cm³g⁻¹ for the sample activated at 850 °C for 20 min with CO₂. With identical parameters, the total share of MIC could be increased by up to 140% from originally 0.089 cm³g⁻¹ to 0.212 cm³g⁻¹. The previously described flattening at higher temperatures and longer activation times is also observable in the pore size distribution, i.e. in the formation of micropores.

Thermogravimetric Analysis

The thermogravimetric analysis confirms that the fixed carbon content decreases with increasing time and temperature, due to the progressive heterogeneous Boudouard reaction. At low temperatures, mainly volatile matter escapes and only small amounts of the carbon (80% in the gasification residues) react. The absolute amount of ash remains rather constant, which confirms that the mineral matter does not react. Consequently, the relative amount of ash increases, contrary to the fixed carbon content, with higher activation temperatures and longer times.

Economic Consideration

In order to evaluate the trade-off between developed porosity and mass loss, an economical consideration by calculating the absolute porosity before and after activation is conducted. In literature [22] the correlation between CO₂ adsorption capacity and textural properties of AC is investigated. It is shown that the micropore surface area ($R^2 = 0.903$) and the total pore volume ($R^2 = 0.879$) have a significantly stronger correlation than the BET surface area ($R^2 = 0.6475$). Thus, the absolute BET surface area S_{BET} (Figure 28 – left), as well as the absolute micropore volume $V_{\text{P,MIC}}$ (right) are crucial to be considered in an economic consideration. As a reference quantity, the used 7 g precursor have an absolute surface area of 1975.8 m² and a micropore volume of 0.615 cm³.

Figure 28: Economic consideration by the calculation of the absolute porosity (values referred to 7 g GR used as precursor)

Although the mass loss during activation is relatively low if activating with CO₂ at 750 °C for 5 min, the increase in absolute BET surface area and absolute micropore volume is slightly higher, compared to the precursor. In numbers absolute BET surface area increases from 1975.8 m² to 2021.6 m² and absolute micropore volume from 0.615 cm³ to 0.638 cm³. This low yield leads to the conclusion that activation with CO₂ at 750 °C for 5 min is not economically viable; but different it is for longer periods. E.g. after 12.5 min, an absolute BET surface area of 2511.3 m² and an absolute micropore volume of 0.812 cm³ are obtained. Compared to the precursor, this is an improvement of 27.1% for the absolute BET surface area and 32% for absolute micropore volume. If activation time is further increased to 20 min the yield of absolute BET surface area and absolute micropore volume decreases due to the significantly higher mass loss. A maximum can be observed which is for absolute BET surface area at 825.9 °C and 15.7 min and for the absolute micropore volume at 830.4 °C and 15.2 min.

Thermochemical Activation with Addition of Air

The addition of air, which should enable a more economical, autothermal activation process, results in significantly lower porosities compared to the activation with pure CO₂. The tendencies of the CO₂/air activation results are partly unclear. This is probably due to the rapid and difficult to control reaction between carbon and air. However, a significant increase in porosity can be confirmed. At 850 °C, 20 min and a CO₂/air volume flow of 0.2/0.952 lmin⁻¹ the highest yield of specific BET surface area with 534.9 m²g⁻¹ is reached. If the volume flow is increased to 0.3/1.428 lmin⁻¹ continuously lower specific BET surface areas are obtained (in average 492.6 m²g⁻¹). As expected low temperatures lead to lower porosities. With regard to the economic consideration, the results indicate an optimum at medium temperatures (~800 °C) and medium volume flow rates (~0.2/0.952 lmin⁻¹). However, the standard deviations of the mass losses during CO₂/air activation are partly very high, which is why the results of the economic consideration should be treated with caution and need more validation experiments.

Production of AC from Waste Wood

The produced AC is more sustainable than the one from fossil feedstock. Nevertheless, the sustainability of energy from forest biomass is debated. However, agreement is found if the wood is first utilized materially and subsequently energetically (cascade use/circular economy). Means, the sustainability of the GR, and consequently also of the produced AC, could be increased if, instead of forest residue biomass, municipal waste wood is utilized in the gasification process. This way, not only a wide applicability of the produced GR would be achieved by the production of AC, but also waste streams avoided (utilization of communal waste wood). The "Josef Ressel Center for the Production of Powder Activated Carbon from Municipal Residues", which was established in the fall of 2020 for a period of five years, addresses this overarching task. First experiments of the waste wood gasification already show successful process adaptations and a charcoal with 418 m²g⁻¹ as by-product, which is promising for thermochemical activation.

Alternative Activation Concepts

The presented batch fluidized bed reactor is mainly used in the laboratory-scale activation experiments. Since rotary kilns are predominantly used for thermochemical activation in industry, laboratory-scale activation will also be investigated in a batch rotary kiln. Due to the very complex and cost-intensive construction of a continuous rotary kiln, pilot-scale thermochemical activation should preferably not be carried out in a classic rotary kiln. The aim of the pilot-scale reactor is to continuously convert the full amount of produced GR from an industrial wood gasification plant into highly porous AC.

The high carbon content in the GR make them not only interesting for the use as material, but also for the energetic use in a re-gasification reactor, which can also be used for the thermochemical activation. A major advantage of the approach is that wood gasification power plants become more flexible, efficient and economically viable. According to the demand, the heat or power generation could be maximized during winter but scaled back in order to favor the production of AC during summer. [31]

Conclusion

Due to the increased porosity a more effective and inexpensive adsorbent – with the potential to significantly reduce waste streams – could be produced by the thermochemical activation of the gasification residues. Compared to literature good results could be achieved. The mass loss during activation increases with temperature and time rather linearly. The porosity (specific BET surface area, pore volume), on the other hand, tends to flatten for

high temperatures and long activation times. By CO₂ activation at 850 °C and 20 min, a specific BET surface area of 627.7 m²g⁻¹ and a share in MIC of 50.1 % is reached. The economical consideration of the trade-off between developed porosity and mass loss indicates around 15 min and 830 °C to achieve the highest yield of absolute BET surface area and absolute micropore volume. The addition of air, which should lead to a more economical activation process, results in significantly lower porosity, nevertheless, the area of the gasification residues could be more than doubled.

Acknowledgements

The financial support by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs and the National Foundation for Research, Technology and Development, the Christian Doppler Research Association as well as the participating companies is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] K. T. Idris-Hermann, T. T. D. Raoul, D. Giscard, and A. S. Gabche, "Preparation and Characterization of Activated Carbons from Bitter Kola (*Garcinia kola*) Nut Shells by Chemical Activation Method Using H₃PO₄; KOH and ZnCl₂," CSIJ, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 1–15, 2018, doi: 10.9734/CSJI/2018/43411.
- [2] Chemviron, Activated Carbon Purification Systems - Chemviron Carbon - Chemviron. Accessed: Jan 16 2023. Available: <https://www.chemviron.eu/>
- [3] Kuraray Europe GmbH, Activated carbon - Kuraray Europe. Accessed: Jan 16 2023. Available: <https://www.kuraray.eu/product-groups/activated-carbon>
- [4] B. Sajjadi, W.-Y. Chen, and N. O. Egiebor, "A comprehensive review on physical activation of biochar for energy and environmental applications," Reviews in Chemical Engineering, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 735–776, 2019, doi: 10.1515/revce-2017-0113.
- [5] Marsh, H. and Rodríguez-Reinoso, F., Activated carbon, 1st ed. Amsterdam and Boston: Elsevier, 2006.
- [6] D. Akhil, D. Lakshmi, A. Kartik, D.-V. N. Vo, J. Arun, and K. P. Gopinath, "Production, characterization, activation and environmental applications of engineered biochar: a review," Environmental Chemistry Letters, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 2261–2297, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10311-020-01167-7.
- [7] S. Anto, M.P. Sudhakar, T.S. Ahamed, M.S. Samuel, T. Mathimani, K. Brindhadevi, and A. Pugazhendhi, "Activation strategies for biochar to use as an efficient catalyst in various applications," Fuel, vol. 285, p. 119205, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2020.119205.
- [8] D. Feng, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhao, S. Sun, and J. Gao, "Improvement and maintenance of biochar catalytic activity for in-situ biomass tar reforming during pyrolysis and H₂O/CO₂ gasification," Fuel Processing Technology, vol. 172, pp. 106–114, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.fuproc.2017.12.011.
- [9] J. F. Kwiatkowski, Activated carbon: Classifications, properties and applications. New York: Nova Science Publishers, 2012.
- [10] V. M. Jaganathan and S. Varunkumar, "A novel self-sustained single step process for synthesizing activated char from ligno-cellulosic biomass," Fuel Processing Technology, vol. 208, p. 106516, 2020.
- [11] T. Hanaoka, K. Sakanishi, and Y. Okumura, "The effect of N₂/CO₂/O₂ content and pressure on characteristics and CO₂ gasification behavior of biomass-derived char," Fuel Processing Technology, vol. 104, pp. 287–294, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.fuproc.2012.05.024.
- [12] F. L. Braghiroli, H. Bouaffif, and A. Koubaa, "Enhanced SO₂

- adsorption and desorption on chemically and physically activated biochar made from wood residues,” *Industrial Crops and Products*, vol. 138, p. 111456, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.06.019.
- [13] Y. Sun, I.K.M. Yu, D.C.W. Tsang, J. Fan, J.H. Clark, G. Luo, S. Zhang, and et al., “Tailored design of graphitic biochar for high-efficiency and chemical-free microwave-assisted removal of refractory organic contaminants,” *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 398, p. 125505, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2020.125505.
- [14] J.-H. Kwak, M.S. Islam, S. Wang, S.A. Messele, M.A. Naeth, M.G. El-Din, and S.X. Chang, “Biochar properties and lead(II) adsorption capacity depend on feedstock type, pyrolysis temperature, and steam activation,” *Chemosphere*, vol. 231, pp. 393–404, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.05.128.
- [15] C. Di Stasi, D. Alvira, G. Greco, B. González, and J. J. Manyà, “Physically activated wheat straw-derived biochar for biomass pyrolysis vapors upgrading with high resistance against coke deactivation,” *Fuel*, vol. 255, p. 115807, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2019.115807.
- [16] T. Maneerung, J. Liew, Y. Dai, S. Kawi, C. Chong, and C.-H. Wang, “Activated carbon derived from carbon residue from biomass gasification and its application for dye adsorption: Kinetics, isotherms and thermodynamic studies,” *Bioresource technology*, vol. 200, pp. 350–359, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2015.10.047.
- [17] S. Kilpimaa, H. Runtti, T. Kangas, U. Lassi, and T. Kuokkanen, “Physical activation of carbon residue from biomass gasification: Novel sorbent for the removal of phosphates and nitrates from aqueous solution,” *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, vol. 21, pp. 1354–1364, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jiec.2014.06.006.
- [18] A. A. Ahmad, M. A. Ahmad, N. K. E. Yahaya, and J. Karim, “Adsorption of malachite green by activated carbon derived from gasified *Hevea brasiliensis* root,” *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 103104, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.arabjc.2021.103104.
- [19] G. Ravenni, G. Cafaggi, Z. Sárosy, K. T. Rohde Nielsen, J. Ahrenfeldt, and U. B. Henriksen, “Waste chars from wood gasification and wastewater sludge pyrolysis compared to commercial activated carbon for the removal of cationic and anionic dyes from aqueous solution,” *Bioresource Technology Reports*, vol. 10, p. 100421, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.biteb.2020.100421.
- [20] Gasunie, Torrefaction and gasification: Innovative and scalable technology that produces a sustainable synthetic gas. Available: <http://torrgas.nl/wpnew/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Torrgas-schema-2020.pdf> (accessed: Jan 16 2023).
- [21] R. H. Berends and Post Van der Burg, Robin Pieter, “Process to prepare an activated carbon product and a syngas mixture,” 20220356408, Amsterdam, Jan 26 2023.
- [22] Dissanayake, P. D., You, S., Igalavithana, A. D., Xia, Y., Bhatnagar, A., Gupta, S., Kua, H. W., Kim, S., Kwon, J.-H., Tsang, D. C.W., and Ok, Y. S., “Biochar-based adsorbents for carbon dioxide capture: A critical review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 119, p. 109582, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2019.109582.
- [23] Z. Heidarinejad, M. H. Dehghani, M. Heidari, G. Javedan, I. Ali, and M. Sillanpää, “Methods for preparation and activation of activated carbon: a review,” *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 393–415, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10311-019-00955-0.
- [24] C. A. Toles, W. E. Marshall, L. H. Wartelle, and A. McAloon, “Steam- or carbon dioxide-activated carbons from almond shells: physical, chemical and adsorptive properties and estimated cost of production,” *Bioresource technology*, vol. 75, no. 3, pp. 197–203, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0960-8524(00)00058-4.
- [25] M.S. Reza, C. S. Yun, S. Afroze, N. Radenahmad, M.S.A. Bakar, R. Saidur, J. Taweekun, and A.K. Azad., “Preparation of activated carbon from biomass and its’ applications in water and gas purification, a review,” *Arab Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 208–238, 2020, doi: 10.1080/25765299.2020.1766799.
- [26] K. Yang, J. Peng, H. Xia, L. Zhang, C. Srinivasakannan, and S. Guo, “Textural characteristics of activated carbon by single step CO₂ activation from coconut shells,” *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 367–372, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.jtice.2009.09.004.
- [27] M. N. Ettish, G. S. El-Sayyad, M. A. Elsayed, and O. Abuzalat, “Preparation and characterization of new adsorbent from Cinnamon waste by physical activation for removal of Chlorpyrifos,” *Environmental Challenges*, vol. 5, p. 100208, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.envc.2021.100208.
- [28] M.A. Franciski, E.C. Peres, M. Godinho, D. Perondi, E.L. Foletto, G.C. Collazzo, and G.L. Dotto., “Development of CO₂ activated biochar from solid wastes of a beer industry and its application for methylene blue adsorption,” *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 78, pp. 630–638, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2018.06.040.
- [29] M. Kaltschmitt, H. Hartmann, and H. Hofbauer, Eds., *Energie aus Biomasse: Grundlagen, Techniken und Verfahren*, 3rd ed. Berlin and Heidelberg: Springer Vieweg, 2016.
- [30] Beuth, DIN 51720:2001-03, Prüfung fester Brennstoffe_ - Bestimmung des Gehaltes an Flüchtigen Bestandteilen). Berlin, 2001. Berlin: Beuth Verlag GmbH.
- [31] Chemiereport.at and AustrianLifeScience, “Zwei CDG-Einrichtungen im Dienste der Kreislaufwirtschaft: Jedes Nebenprodukt wird genutzt,” *Chemiereport.at*, AustrianLifeSciences, Österreichs Magazin für Wirtschaft, Technik und Forschung, pp. 58–59, 2021.

A promising material stream? Activated carbon from municipal residues for micropollutant adsorption

D. Bosch^{1,2,*}, J. O. Back³, L. Nohel¹, C. Magreiter¹, A. Hofmann^{1,3}, A. Bockreis²

1: Josef Ressel Centre for the Production of Powdered Activated Carbon from Municipal Residues, Department of Environmental, Process and Energy Engineering, MCI–The Entrepreneurial School, Universitaetsstrasse 15, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

2: Unit of Environmental Engineering, Department for Infrastructure, University of Innsbruck, Technikerstrasse 13, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

3: Department of Environmental, Process and Energy Engineering, MCI–The Entrepreneurial School, Universitaetsstrasse 15, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

* Corresponding author: dominik.bosch@mci.edu

Keywords: Activated Carbon, Functionalised Surface, Waste Wood Organic Micropollutants, Adsorption Performance

Research field: Production of Activated Carbon & Micropollutant Adsorption

Abstract

Rising populations and industrialisation have drastically increased environmental pollution by heavy metals (HMs) and organic micropollutants (OMPs). Due to the low natural degradation rate in water bodies and the insufficient purification performance of municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), there is an ecological accumulation of HMs and OMPs. Activated carbon contact basins in WWTPs are able to provide a remedy. Single-stage pyrolysis of biomass impregnated with ZnCl₂ has proven to be an effective activation method for the production of functionalised activated carbon (AC). Municipal waste wood (WW) and forest residue biomass (FRB) were used as biomass. High specific surface areas (up to 1430 m²g⁻¹) and the presence of oxygen-containing functional groups seem promising in terms of adsorption performances. In comparative adsorption tests, AC produced by ZnCl₂ impregnation were compared with commercially available AC as well as a gasifier char from a wood gasification process and a subsequently activated gasifier char. Six different OMPs (benzotriazole, carbamazepine, diclofenac, metoprolol, sulfamethoxazole, valsartan) and the HM lead (as Pb²⁺) were chosen. Chemically impregnated AC, for example, showed an adsorption capacity of up to 26.5 mg g⁻¹ for Pb²⁺; in comparison, a commercially available AC adsorbed only 1.61 mg g⁻¹. With regard to OMPs, similar equilibrium loadings (440-490 mgg⁻¹) were measured in each case. Overall, chemically impregnated AC from municipal residues offers a regionally available alternative for adsorption of pollutants in WWTPs.

Introduction

Commercially available AC is mostly produced from lignite or hard coal^[1] which are expensive and non-sustainable resources. Recently, researchers have focused on easily available, low-cost and renewable materials for AC production, like rice and coffee husks^[2], kola nut shells^[3], acorn shell^[4], olive kernels^[5], reedy grass leaves^[6], fox nut shell^[7] and coconut shell^[8], or organic waste^[9]. Wood-based materials are widely available in Central and Northern Europe – logging in the EU amounts to 510 mio. m³ per year^[10] – and Hagemann et al. (2020)^[11] postulated from a Swiss perspective that wood-based materials should be considered as a possible strategy to avoid the large environmental footprint of conventional AC production. However, significant waste streams result from the wood sector, such as forestry residue biomass (FRB) and waste wood (WW).

FRB is a by-product of timber harvesting, including biomass from thinning, the felling of stands for timber or pulp production and the clearing of areas for construction or other purposes. Several quality grades exist for this material, depending on the amount of bark and needles. Due to a higher amount of bark compared to heartwood, FRB is not suitable for the paper industry and can only be used for energy production^[12]. Detailed data available for Austria shows that

the total amount of wood chips (all available grades) and bark comprises up to 3.5 mio. m³ and 3.4 mio. m³, respectively, of the totally harvested 25.1 mio. m³ of wood per year^[13]. These figures projected to the totally harvested 477.5 mio. m³ in Europe^[14] result in a considerable approximate total of 131 mio. m³ wood chips and bark per year.

Waste management is typically centralised, which results in highly heterogeneous WW mixtures in terms of quality and age. The contamination of WW with heavy metals and organic impurities, such as paint or tars, can also be critical. The material recycling^[15] of waste wood in Austria amounts to only 19%, the product of which is used exclusively in the particleboard industry^[16]. The valorisation strategy of organically contaminated wood with, for instance, paint, and inorganically contaminated wood with, e.g., preservatives^[17], focuses mostly on thermal recovery.

The contamination of surface and groundwater resources with organic micropollutants (OMPs) and heavy metals (HM) from anthropogenic resources are the negative effect of urbanization and industrialisation^[18]. Negative effects on human health are not completely ruled out, but it is now known for a long time that hormones like estrogen has a long-term effect on the reproduction of fish population^[19]. On top of that even the state of the art wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) cannot or only partly remove these pollutants^[20], therefore, WWTPs are the main pathway for pharmaceuticals and other micropollutants to enter the environment^[21].

The aim of this study was the investigation of FRB and WW as potential surrogate for fossil precursors in AC production by chemical means. The activation by means of chemical impregnation, involves impregnation with suitable chemicals, such as sodium hydroxide^[22], potassium- or sodium carbonate^[23] and the three most common chemicals, potassium hydroxide^[8, 24-29], phosphoric acid^[30-32] and zinc chloride^[4, 33-35]. Through chemical impregnation, the surface of the AC becomes more hydrophilic than during thermochemical activation and, more importantly, the structural dimensions, the shape of the micropores and the surface functional groups are enhanced^[36-38].

ZnCl₂ is an excellent activator with a Lewis-acid character. The strong dehydration leads to a significant decrease in the decomposition temperature of biomass compounds^[39], and, furthermore, to an increased AC yield (30% compared to 5% with KOH^[40]). The optimum activation temperature for KOH ranges from 700 to 900 °C, while for ZnCl₂, it is around 500 °C due to the different thermal stability of the cross-links formed during the activation process^[41]. Additionally, ZnCl₂ can penetrate into the lignocellulosic structure due to the dissolving impact on cellulose, resulting in the formation of pores. The low melting point of ZnCl₂ (290 °C) leads to a uniform distribution in the carbon structure, acting as a skeleton during carbonization^[39]. During the wash step after activation, ZnCl₂ is removed and creates a template from the remaining salts for creating micro-porosity^[42]. Even though H₃PO₄ is also an attractive activator, a drawback is that acids and alkali

metals cause corrosion of the equipment. Preliminary internal experiments showed that H₃PO₄ could not achieve comparable results to ZnCl₂; therefore, ZnCl₂ was chosen as the activating agent in this study. On the downside, the use of impregnation chemicals increases the environmental impact and, therefore, a recycling strategy should be devised.

Materials and Methods

The selected samples for the adsorption tests were prepared according to a previous study^[43] as follows: FRB & WW were placed in an Erlenmeyer flask and mixed with 10 times the mass of water. To this, 5 times the mass of ZnCl₂ was added and impregnated for 2 h. After subsequent drying, the samples were pyrolyzed at 400, 500, and 600 °C under reduced oxygen atmosphere for 1 h. A subsequent washing step is required for the removal of ZnCl₂ and was performed with a 1 M HCl and 0.5 M HNO₃ solutions.

Physisorption was applied to determine the structural properties of the AC samples using the gas N₂ (3Flex, Micromeritics). For every sample, an amount of 100 to 150 mg was degassed (VacPrep 061, Micromeritics) at 200 °C overnight prior to analysis. Full N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms were collected at 77 K with 60–80 data points at 10 s equilibration time. From the N₂ isotherms, the specific surface area (S_{BET}, using the BET method and meeting the Roquerol criteria^[44]) were determined. The 2D-heterogeneous surfaces-NLDFT-kernel^[45] was applied to calculate the pore size distribution (PSD) from N₂ considering the spectrum from micropores to macropores.

Comparative adsorption tests were carried out using an over-head shaker and 11 Schott flasks with 500 ml of solution to collect data for the equilibrium loading. Therefore, samples were taken after 24 h. Nine of different origin ACs were used for the adsorption tests. For the FRB & WW samples, 400, 500, and 600 °C were chosen, as well as an IR of 5:1 and a RT of one hour, results in six ACs. Additionally, a gasification char (GC) from a local wood gasification system^[12] was tested as well as a post-activated version^[46] (850 °C with 20 min of CO₂ activation) of this biochar (GC CO₂). Unfortunately, we only had one commercially available AC (Donau Carbon Carbopal AP Supra) at hand, and could therefore only use the one as a comparison.

The selection of micropollutants was strongly oriented towards the Swiss legislation of 2016^[47] regarding the guiding substances for the removal of wastewater treatment plants. Therefore, 1,2,3-benzotriazole (Carl Roth GmbH), carbamazepine (Sigma Aldrich GmbH), diclofenac (Thermo Fischer GmbH), metoprolol (Thermo Fischer GmbH), sulfamethoxazole (Sigma Aldrich GmbH) and valsartan (Tokyo Chemical Industry) were picked. The adsorption tests for the OMP were carried out as a multi-component adsorption experiment. Therefore, a concentration of 10 mg l⁻¹ of each OMP were adjusted. The used UHPLC system consist of the UltiMate 3000 rapid separation quaternary system (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Chromatographic separation was performed on an Acclaim TM Polar Advantage II C18 column (4.6 x 100 mm, 3 μm particle size)

column temperature of 25 °C and with the gradient elution program displayed in Table 10.

Table 10: Gradient elution program, A: 0.1 % TFA in RO water; B: 0.1 % TFA in Acetonitrile

Time / min	Flow rate / μl min ⁻¹	Solvent A / %	Solvent B / %	Curve
0.0	800	90	10	5
9.0	800	20	80	4
12.5	800	90	10	7
14.0	800	90	10	7

Additionally to the organic substances, lead (Pb²⁺, Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG) was included and was used from a 1000 mg l⁻¹ stock solution for the adsorption experiments. Hence, fresh stock solutions of a concentration of 2 mg l⁻¹ were prepared for every adsorption experiment. After 24 h, a 5 ml sample was taken from every flask with plastic syringes. To remove the AC, the samples were filtered with PTFE membrane syringe filters. The HM ion concentration is then photometrically determined by using tube tests (MACHEREY-NAGEL GmbH & Co. KG). With a known initial HM ion concentration from the blank sample and the amount of dosed AC, the equilibrium loading of a HM on an AC can be calculated.

Results and Discussion

The results of the activation by means of chemical impregnation with ZnCl₂ is shown in Table 9. For the FRB samples, higher temperatures (T) led to a higher specific surface area (S_{BET}) from 569 to 849 m² g⁻¹ and a higher total pore volume (V_{total}). Additionally, the share in favour of micropores also increased.

For WW, a higher T not always led to a higher S_{BET}, an increase from 400 to 500 °C resulted in a significant increase in S_{BET} from 852 to 1430 m² g⁻¹ and decreased with a further increase (to 600 °C) to 1219 m² g⁻¹. A similar trend is visible for the V_{total}, but interestingly not for the share of micropores, here, a constant high share (>85 %) was achieved for all three Ts. In comparison, the biochar has a very low S_{BET} (287 m² g⁻¹), but this could be more than doubled by an additional activation step with CO₂. In addition, the share in favour of micropores could further be increased. The commercial AC achieved the third highest S_{BET} in the physisorption experiments and due to the significantly higher share of mesopores; the V_{total} was second highest of all samples.

In Figure 30, the maximum adsorption capacity of the WW600 sample (best-performed AC) is displayed and compared to the commercial AC. The adsorption capacity of benzotriazole of the WW600 is significantly lower compared to the commercial AC, but, in contrast, several other substances are equally high or higher adsorbed onto the WW600 sample. Carbamazepine showed a 20 % higher adsorption capacity on WW600, the same is visible for metoprolol. In addition, sulfamethoxazole and valsartan had a 10 and 15 % higher capacity, respectively.

The higher S_{BET} and the higher shares of micropores, which are

Table 9: Surface characteristics of the used ACs for the adsorption experiments

Activated Carbon	S _{BET} / m ² g ⁻¹	V _{total} / cm ³ g ⁻¹	Avg. D / Å	V _{micro} / vol%	V _{meso} / vol%	V _{macro} / vol%
FRB400	569	0.312	21.890	63.1	29.0	7.9
FRB500	632	0.332	20.976	66.9	25.4	7.7
FRB600	849	0.352	16.579	87.2	3.7	9.1
WW400	852	0.388	18.193	85.2	5.7	9.1
WW500	1430	0.743	20.773	85.5	5.7	8.8
WW600	1219	0.536	17.567	85.8	4.6	9.6
Gasification char	287	0.248	34.484	36.1	56.9	7.0
CO ₂ -activated	628	0.423	28.385	50.1	41.8	8.1
Donau Carbon Carbopal AP Supra	993	0.646	25.775	63.2	33.2	3.6

protected by a guard column. 10 μl of each sample was injected and a flow rate of 800 μl min⁻¹ was set. Analysis were performed at a

favourable for smaller molecules (like the chosen OMPs), can clearly explain the difference. Activation by chemical impregnation

Figure 30: Equilibrium loading of different micropollutants on a) WW600, b) Commercial AC

also results in a high proportion of oxygen-containing functional surface groups^[43], which have a major influence on adsorption performance, compared to the commercially available AC made from lignite or coal and activated with CO₂ or H₂O. These characteristics could describe the overall higher adsorption performance (490 to 440 mg g⁻¹) of these two ACs.

In addition to the multi-component adsorption tests of OMPs, HM adsorption tests were also carried out. Giraldo et al^[48] outlined at a pH value of 5, 15 % of Pb²⁺ ions are already precipitated as Pb(OH)₂. Therefore, a pH value of five was chosen for die HM adsorption experiments, which further describes that the measured 1.74 mg l⁻¹ of the Pb²⁺ stock solution were not the adjusted 2 mg l⁻¹. In Figure 29 are the equilibrium loads of the nine different ACs showed. Interestingly, GC and the activated version of GC had the highest loadings, which can be explained by the high ash content (> 10 %), raising the pH value of these solutions to 8 or above. Consequently, almost all Pb²⁺ ions precipitate as Pb(OH)₂.

Figure 29: Equilibrium loading of lead as Pb²⁺ ($c_0 = 1.74 \text{ mg l}^{-1}$) on different AC samples

Another hurdle that had to be identified was the acetate filters used in the beginning adsorbed Pb²⁺ ions, resulting in apparently high adsorption capacities of all ACs in preliminary experiments (not shown here). Further investigations with PTFE syringe filters yielded plausible results (shown in Figure 29). A slight trend can be seen in the results, in which a higher activation temperature results in higher adsorption capacities (excluding FRB600).

In line with the trend, the WW600 sample reached the highest load

of 26.4 mg g⁻¹ compared to only 1.6 mg g⁻¹ of the commercial AC. Here, the oxygen-containing surface functional groups on the ZnCl₂ impregnated AC samples are responsible the most for the adsorption capability of the AC, where the commercial AC was produced with CO₂ activation out of coal, nearly no oxygen-containing surface functional groups were left on the AC.

Conclusion and Outlook

The physisorption results show the S_{BET} of the ACs depends strongly on the temperature and the used raw material. Nevertheless, the activation by means of chemical impregnation works comparatively well above a T of 500 °C. Additionally, a higher T results in higher equilibrium loads.

The adsorption experiments carried out showed a good and comparable adsorption capability of OMPs and lead in comparison to the used commercially available AC (Donau Carbon Carbopal AP Supra). Since the production of ZnCl₂-impregnated AC is a well-established method, further investigations should be focused on adsorption isotherms and kinetics as well as adsorption experiments in real-world application, such as spiked wastewater samples.

Acknowledgement

The financial support by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs and the National Foundation for Research, Technology and Development, the Christian Doppler Research Association as well as the participating companies is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] John W. Hassler, "Active Carbon," *Journal of the American Pharmaceutical Association (Scientific ed.)*, vol. 40, no. 8, pp. 418–419, 1951, doi: 10.1002/jps.3030400825.
- [2] T. Tchuiwon, S. G. Anagho, G. N. Nche, and J. M. Ketcha, "Adsorption of salicylic and sulfosalicylic acid onto powdered activated carbon prepared from rice and coffee husks.," *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology*, no. 5, pp. 1641–1652, 2015.
- [3] J. Ndi Nsami and J. Ketcha Mbadcam, "The Adsorption Efficiency of Chemically Prepared Activated Carbon from Cola Nut Shells by on Methylene Blue," *Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 2013, pp. 1–7, 2013, doi: 10.1155/2013/469170.
- [4] C. Saka, "BET, TG–DTG, FT-IR, SEM, iodine number analysis and preparation of activated carbon from acorn shell by chemical activation with ZnCl₂," *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, vol. 95, pp. 21–24, 2012, doi:

- 10.1016/j.jaap.2011.12.020.
- [5] N. El Ouahedy, M. Zbair, S. Ojala, R. Brahmi, and L. Pirault-Roy, "Porous carbon materials derived from olive kernels: application in adsorption of organic pollutants," *Environmental science and pollution research international*, vol. 27, no. 24, pp. 29967–29982, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11356-020-09268-0.
- [6] J. Xu, L. Chen, H. Qu, Y. Jiao, J. Xie, and G. Xing, "Preparation and characterization of activated carbon from reedy grass leaves by chemical activation with H₃PO₄," *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 320, pp. 674–680, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2014.08.178.
- [7] A. Kumar and H. M. Jena, "Preparation and characterization of high surface area activated carbon from Fox nut (*Euryale ferox*) shell by chemical activation with H₃PO₄," *Results in Physics*, vol. 6, pp. 651–658, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.rinp.2016.09.012.
- [8] H. Cheng *et al.*, "Micro-mesoporous carbon fabricated by Phanerochaete chrysosporium pretreatment coupling with chemical activation: Promoting effect and toluene adsorption performance," *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 105054, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jece.2021.105054.
- [9] V. Thithai, X. Jin, M. Ajaz Ahmed, and J.-W. Choi, "Physicochemical Properties of Activated Carbons Produced from Coffee Waste and Empty Fruit Bunch by Chemical Activation Method," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 11, p. 3002, 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14113002.
- [10] Eurostat, "Holzeinschlag in der Europäischen Union nach Ländern im Jahr 2020 [Logging in the European Union by country in 2020]," Nov. 2021.
- [11] N. Hagemann *et al.*, "Wood-based activated biochar to eliminate organic micropollutants from biologically treated wastewater," *The Science of the total environment*, vol. 730, p. 138417, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138417.
- [12] M. Huber, M. Huemer, A. Hofmann, and S. Dumfort, "Floating-fixed-bed-gasification: From Vision to Reality," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 93, pp. 120–124, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2016.07.159.
- [13] Lorenz Strimitzer, Bernhard Wlcek, and Kasimir Nemestothy, *Holzströme in Österreich 2019*.
- [14] Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe - FOREST EUROPE, Ed., "FOREST EUROPE, 2020: State of Europe's Forests 2020," Liaison Unit Bratislava.
- [15] Horst Fehrenbach, Susanne Köppen, Benedikt Kauertz, Andreas Detzel, Frank Wellenreuther, Elke Breitmayer, Roland Essel, Michael Carus, Katrin Bienge, Justus von Geibler, "BIOMASSEKASKADEN [BIOMASS CASCADES]: Mehr Ressourceneffizienz durch Mehr Ressourceneffizienz durch Kaskadennutzung von Biomasse – von der Theorie zur Praxis Theorie zur Praxis [More resource efficiency through More resource efficiency through cascade use of biomass - from theory to practice Theory to practice]," 53, Jun. 2017.
- [16] Udo Mantau, "Holzrohstoffbilanz Deutschland, Entwicklungen und Szenarien des Holzaufkommens und der Holzverwendung 1987 bis 2015 [Wood raw material balance Germany, developments and scenarios of wood supply and wood use 1987 to 2015]," *Hamburg* 65, Oct. 2012.
- [17] J. Krook, A. Mårtensson, and M. Eklund, "Sources of heavy metal contamination in Swedish wood waste used for combustion," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 158–166, 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2005.07.017.
- [18] D. Pathania, S. Sharma, and P. Singh, "Removal of methylene blue by adsorption onto activated carbon developed from *Ficus carica* bast," *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 10, S1445-S1451, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.arabjc.2013.04.021.
- [19] C. Kienle, R. Kase, M. Schärer, and I. Werner, "Anwendung von Biotests zur Evaluation der Wirkung und Elimination von Mikroverunreinigungen," *Aqua & Gas*, no. 95, pp. 18–26, 2015.
- [20] M. Clara, B. Strenn, O. Gans, E. Martinez, N. Kreuzinger, and H. Kroiss, "Removal of selected pharmaceuticals, fragrances and endocrine disrupting compounds in a membrane bioreactor and conventional wastewater treatment plants," *Water research*, vol. 39, no. 19, pp. 4797–4807, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2005.09.015.
- [21] B. Kasprzyk-Hordern, R. M. Dinsdale, and A. J. Guwy, "The removal of pharmaceuticals, personal care products, endocrine disruptors and illicit drugs during wastewater treatment and its impact on the quality of receiving waters," *Water research*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 363–380, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2008.10.047.
- [22] O. Pezoti *et al.*, "NaOH-activated carbon of high surface area produced from guava seeds as a high-efficiency adsorbent for amoxicillin removal: Kinetic, isotherm and thermodynamic studies," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 288, pp. 778–788, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2015.12.042.
- [23] Y. Gao, Q. Yue, S. Xu, and B. Gao, "Activated carbons with well-developed mesoporosity prepared by activation with different alkali salts," *Materials Letters*, vol. 146, pp. 34–36, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.matlet.2015.01.161.
- [24] W. Chen *et al.*, "Insight into KOH activation mechanism during biomass pyrolysis: Chemical reactions between O-containing groups and KOH," *Applied Energy*, vol. 278, p. 115730, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115730.
- [25] K. Januszewicz, P. Kazimierski, M. Klein, D. Kardaś, and J. Łuczak, "Activated Carbon Produced by Pyrolysis of Waste Wood and Straw for Potential Wastewater Adsorption," *Materials (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 13, no. 9, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ma13092047.
- [26] Q. Liang *et al.*, "Optimized preparation of activated carbon from coconut shell and municipal sludge," *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 241, p. 122327, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matchemphys.2019.122327.
- [27] M. Om Prakash, G. Raghavendra, S. Ojha, and M. Panchal, "Characterization of porous activated carbon prepared from arhar stalks by single step chemical activation method," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 39, pp. 1476–1481, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.05.370.
- [28] D. Pereira *et al.*, "In situ functionalization of a cellulosic-based activated carbon with magnetic iron oxides for the removal of carbamazepine from wastewater," *Environmental science and pollution research international*, vol. 28, no. 15, pp. 18314–18327, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11356-020-09314-x.
- [29] N. A. Zubbri, A. R. Mohamed, P. Lahijani, and M. Mohammadi, "Low temperature CO₂ capture on biomass-derived KOH-activated hydrochar established through hydrothermal carbonization with water-soaking pretreatment," *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 105074, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jece.2021.105074.
- [30] J. Cheng, S.-C. Hu, G.-T. Sun, K. Kang, M.-Q. Zhu, and Z.-C. Geng, "Comparison of activated carbons prepared by one-step and two-step chemical activation process based on cotton stalk for supercapacitors application," *Energy*, vol. 215, p. 119144, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2020.119144.
- [31] T. Xie *et al.*, "Hierarchical porous activated carbon derived from *Enteromorpha prolifera* for superior electrochemical capacitive behavior," *Ionics*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 403–413, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11581-019-03223-x.
- [32] Z. Zhang *et al.*, "Sudden heating of H₃PO₄-loaded coconut shell in CO₂ flow to produce super activated carbon and its application for benzene adsorption," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 153, pp. 1091–1099, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2020.02.059.
- [33] R. Ma, X. Qin, Z. Liu, and Y. Fu, "Adsorption Property,

- Kinetic and Equilibrium Studies of Activated Carbon Fiber Prepared from Liquefied Wood by ZnCl₂ Activation,” *Materials*, vol. 12, no. 9, 2019, doi: 10.3390/ma12091377.
- [34] S. Najmi, M. S. Hatamipour, P. Sadeh, I. Najafipour, and F. Mehranfar, “Activated carbon produced from *Glycyrrhiza glabra* residue for the adsorption of nitrate and phosphate: batch and fixed-bed column studies,” *SN Appl. Sci.*, vol. 2, no. 4, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s42452-020-2585-7.
- [35] N. Tancredi, M. Gabús, M. I. Yoshida, and A. C. Suárez, “Thermal studies of wood impregnated with ZnCl₂,” *Eur. J. Wood Prod.*, vol. 75, no. 4, pp. 633–638, 2017, doi: 10.1007/s00107-016-1113-3.
- [36] G. Liu, S. Zheng, D. Yin, Z. Xu, J. Fan, and F. Jiang, “Adsorption of aqueous alkylphenol ethoxylate surfactants by mesoporous carbon CMK-3,” *Journal of colloid and interface science*, vol. 302, no. 1, pp. 47–53, 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.jcis.2006.06.006.
- [37] C. Jung *et al.*, “Adsorption of selected endocrine disrupting compounds and pharmaceuticals on activated biochars,” *Journal of hazardous materials*, 263 Pt 2, pp. 702–710, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2013.10.033.
- [38] J. Shin *et al.*, “Competitive adsorption of pharmaceuticals in lake water and wastewater effluent by pristine and NaOH-activated biochars from spent coffee wastes: Contribution of hydrophobic and π - π interactions,” *Environmental pollution (Barking, Essex : 1987)*, vol. 270, p. 116244, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2020.116244.
- [39] L. Leng *et al.*, “An overview on engineering the surface area and porosity of biochar,” *The Science of the total environment*, vol. 763, p. 144204, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144204.
- [40] C. Wang and T. Liu, “Nori-based N, O, S, Cl co-doped carbon materials by chemical activation of ZnCl₂ for supercapacitor,” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 696, pp. 42–50, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.11.206.
- [41] M. Sevilla and R. Mokaya, “Energy storage applications of activated carbons: supercapacitors and hydrogen storage,” *Energy Environ. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1250–1280, 2014, doi: 10.1039/C3EE43525C.
- [42] H. Marsh and F. R. Reinoso, *Activated carbon*, 1st ed. Amsterdam, London: Elsevier, 2006.
- [43] D. Bosch, J. O. Back, D. Gurtner, S. Giberti, A. Hofmann, and A. Bockreis, “Alternative feedstock for the production of activated carbon with ZnCl₂: Forestry residue biomass and waste wood,” *Carbon Resources Conversion*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 299–309, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.crcon.2022.09.001.
- [44] J. Rouquerol, P. Llewellyn, and F. Rouquerol, “Is the bet equation applicable to microporous adsorbents?,” in *Studies in Surface Science and Catalysis, Characterization of Porous Solids VII - Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on the Characterization of Porous Solids (COPS-VII), Aix-en-Provence, France, 26-28 May 2005*: Elsevier, 2007, pp. 49–56.
- [45] J. Jagiello, C. Ania, J. B. Parra, and C. Cook, “Dual gas analysis of microporous carbons using 2D-NLDFT heterogeneous surface model and combined adsorption data of N₂ and CO₂,” *Carbon*, vol. 91, pp. 330–337, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2015.05.004.
- [46] David Gurtner, “Thermochemical activation optimization for high porous powdered carbon production from gasification residues,” Master Thesis, Environmental, Process and Energy Engineering, MCI | The Entrepreneurial University, Innsbruck, 2021.
- [47] “Verordnung des UVEK zur Überprüfung des Reinigungseffekts von Massnahmen zur Elimination von organischen Spurenstoffen bei Abwasserreinigungsanlagen,” in *814.201 Gewässerschutzverordnung*, 2016. Accessed: Oct. 27 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2016/671/de>
- [48] L. Giraldo and J. C. Moreno-Piraján, “Pb²⁺ adsorption from aqueous solutions on activated carbons obtained from lignocellulosic residues,” *Braz. J. Chem. Eng.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 143–151, 2008, doi: 10.1590/S0104-66322008000100015.

Comparison of Mixed-Matrix Membranes with Embedded Boron Nitride and Powdered Activated Carbon for Micro pollutant Removal

Jana Marx^{1,2,*}, Philipp Much¹, Jan Back¹, Tung Pham² and Martin Spruck¹

1: Department of Environmental, Process & Energy Engineering, MCI – The entrepreneurial school, Innsbruck, Austria

2: Department of Textile Chemistry and Physics, University of Innsbruck, Dornbirn, Austria

* Corresponding author: jana.marx@mci.edu

Keywords: Micro pollutant Removal, Mixed-Matrix Membranes, BN Adsorption, Water Treatment

Research field: Membrane processes and water treatment

Abstract

The supply with clean water is essential for human health and well-being. Contamination with micro pollutants of substantial water sources, is evermore becoming a global issue. Filtration and adsorption are promising technologies to meet this problem. In this study, the adsorption materials boron nitride and powdered activated carbon are embedded into a multi-channel polyethersulfone ultrafiltration membrane to create a one-step treatment process. The three compounds bisphenol A, caffeine and metoprolol are analyzed considering the adsorption behavior and the removal efficiency from water with membranes with different shares of adsorption materials. The membranes are characterized through scanning electron microscopy images, tensile strength experiments, permeability and macromolecular retention measurements. The adsorption materials are equally distributed among the cross-section of the membranes. Tensile strength measurements resulted in a decrease with a higher share of adsorption material and permeability was also decreased through the embedded adsorption material. Dextran removal suggested the operation of the membrane in the range of micro- to ultrafiltration. Increasing shares of adsorption materials showed an enhanced removal of micro pollutants. Membranes with a share of 7 % boron nitride showed removal rates for bisphenol A with up to 43.4 % after 8 h. Multi-channel mixed matrix membrane with 7 % powdered activated carbon showed higher removal efficiencies for all three compounds compared to boron nitride membranes with up to 80.9 % retention of bisphenol A after 8 h of filtration. Overall, the performance of the powdered activated carbon membranes showed enhanced removal rates compared to the boron nitride membranes. Still the combination of the two adsorption materials could be a promising technology for the treatment of water containing multiple micro pollutants.

Introduction

Shortage of clean water is an issue affecting a high amount of people world wide. The main causes are seen in the climate change and in the increasing withdrawal of water [1, 2]. Additionally, the available water is in many regions pollutant or insufficient treated. Especially, the occurrence of micro pollutants in rivers, lakes, and groundwater is an increasing global problem, which provokes consequences such as accumulation of toxic substances in aquifers and the contamination of drinking water and agricultural products [3]. One source for the release of these products into the environment is the incomplete removal in the wastewater treatment plants [4]. The need for effective solutions is evermore increasing.

Some commonly found pollutants in water samples are bisphenol A (BPA), caffeine and metoprolol. The suspected endocrine disruptor BPA is mainly released into the environment in concentrations within the range of nanograms per liter through the manufacturing of epoxy resins and polycarbonate plastics and is even found in drinking water and human urine [5, 6]. Caffeine is considered as an indicator for the tracing of pharmaceutically active compounds and has been found in concentrations of up to 3.60 mg/L in freshwater environments especially in Asia and Europe [7]. Metoprolol is a beta

blocker used for the treatment of heart diseases and heart attacks and is found in effluents of wastewater treatment plants [8].

Technologies like the adsorption onto activated carbon, advanced oxidation processes and photooxidation are already occasionally implemented into the waste water treatment process [9]. Removal of micro pollutants through nanofiltration or reverse osmosis is modelled and tested in laboratory scale and applied in some cases, but limited by high trans membrane pressures and low permeate flowrates [10–12]. However, the need for alternative technologies is urgent. The combination of adsorption and filtration has already been shown as an effective method for the removal of multiple micro pollutants [13]. On this basis, in a previous study the principle of a one-step process of combined filtration and adsorption through the development of mixed-matrix membranes was proven [14]. In order to circumvent fossil precursors in activated carbon production, novel adsorbents have been searched for. Boron nitride (BN) may be a promising alternative to fossil adsorbents, such as powdered activated carbon (PAC).

In this study, BN and PAC were embedded as adsorption materials into a polyethersulfone (PES) mixed-matrix multi-channel membrane (MCMMM). A multichannel membrane with seven channels was chosen as membrane geometry to increase the filtration area, the mechanical stability and the retention time within the porous structure. The adsorption properties for MCMMM containing BN and PAC are compared regarding the removal of the compounds BPA, caffeine and metoprolol. MCMMM with embedded BN and with PAC are produced and characterized and the filtration efficiency of a feed solution with a high concentration of the three substances is tested. The results are compared with the aim to show if BN particles can be used as an alternative to PAC in a one-step filtration and adsorption process with MCMMM for the removal of micro pollutants from water environments.

Materials and Methods

The equilibrium adsorption capacity of BN particles (Saint-Gobain, PHPP325B) was tested prior to the incorporation into the membrane matrix. The adsorption of the compounds BPA, caffeine, and metoprolol was determined through experiments with concentrations of BN ranging from 300 to 3000 mg/L. The solutions contained either single micro pollutants or mixture of the three chemicals with a concentration of 10 mg/L each. The results were compared with the fitting of the adsorption isotherm model of Langmuir and Freundlich. The Langmuir model is usually used for description of gas adsorption isotherms but can also be used for liquid adsorption [15]. The derived equation for the Langmuir isotherm is shown in equation 1. $K_{Lm,i}$ is the Langmuir constant, which is defined as the ratio between the adsorption and the desorption rate constant and c_i is the concentration of the fluid phase.

$$\theta = \frac{K_{Lm,i} c_i}{1 + K_{Lm,i}} \quad (1)$$

The equation 1 can be transferred into the final Langmuir isotherm described in equation 2. In equation 2, V is referred to as the adsorbed volume, p is the absolute pressure, V_L is the maximum adsorption capacity and p_L is the Langmuir pressure [16].

$$V = V_L \frac{p}{p_L + p} \quad (2)$$

The Freundlich isotherm fitting is described by equation 3. V is again the adsorbed volume, $K_{Fr,i}$ is the Freundlich coefficient and b is the temperature dependent exponent determined experimentally.

$$V = K_{Fr,i} c^{\frac{1}{b}} \quad (3)$$

Gas adsorption with nitrogen (Micromeritics, 3 Flex Surface Characterisation) was performed at 77 K to analyze the BET surface areas of the pure adsorption materials as well as the surface of the MCMMM. For the production of MCMMM, BN particles and PAC were embedded into a PES ultrafiltration membrane. The standard polymeric solution containing 19 % PES (BASF, Ultrason E 3010), 15 % 1,2-propandiol (Roth, <99.5 %), 5 % polyvinylpyrrolidone (Roth, K90) and 61 % *N,N*-dimethylacetamid (DMAc) (Roth, <99.0 %), was prepared and stirred until diluted. Afterwards the adsorption material was added in the according share and mixed until the particles are homogeneous distributed. Hence, in addition to the standard PES membrane, 3 %, 5 % and 7 % BN and 7 % PAC were added to the polymeric solution. The particle size distribution of the adsorption materials was analyzed using the Mastersizer 2000 (Malvern Instruments), resulting in a particle size distribution for BN with a median particle size $d(0.5)$ of 7.8 μm ($d(0.1)$: 0.7 μm ; $d(0.9)$: 34.9 μm) and for PAC with a $d(0.5)$ of 26.1 μm ($d(0.1)$: 4.7 μm ; $d(0.9)$: 74.8 μm). The membranes are produced using a non-solvent induced phase separation process with water as non-solvent. The geometry of the multi-channel membranes was achieved using a spinning process with a spinneret designed to obtain seven equally distributed channels with a diameter of 1 mm, as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31 Cross-section of the seven-channel MCMMM with a diameter of 5 mm and a channel diameter of 1 mm per channel under the scanning electron microscope with a 20-fold magnification

The spinning process was proceeded in accordance to Spruck et al. [17]. The morphology of the cross-section of the produced MCMMM was characterized using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Jeol, JSM-IT200 InTouchScopeTM). The tensile strength was determined with a compression-tension testing unit (Stable Micro Systems, Texture Analyzer TA XT plus). The pore size was estimated through the macromolecular retention of dextran with a molecular weight of 500 kDa (Roth). The pure water permeability of

the membrane was measured prior to the filtration experiments with a feed volume flowrate of 40 L/h and a trans membrane pressure of 1 bar with a constant temperature of 20 °C. The removal efficiency of the different micro pollutants was tested in cross-flow filtration experiments with a drug solution mixture of 10 mg/L of BPA, caffeine and metoprolol, respectively. A scheme of the filtration process is shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32 Filtration scheme of a cross-flow filtration with a multi-channel mixed-matrix membrane with embedded adsorption material for the removal of micro pollutants from a water stream

The filtration experiments were performed in accordance with the dextran retention experiments mentioned previously. Removal efficiency of the different membranes was analyzed over 8 h for a mixture of all three compounds. The amount of the substances in the permeate was analyzed using high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with UV detection. As the absolute amount of adsorption material within the solid membrane plays a role for the micro pollutant removal, it was determined via dissolution of the MCMMM in DMAc and subsequent filtration through a 0.45 μm filter. The dried filter was weight to calculate the ratio of embedded BN and PAC in the MCMMM matrix.

Results and Discussion

The results for the equilibrium adsorption experiments using a mixture of 10 mg/L of BPA, caffeine and metoprolol showed removal rates between 12.5 % and 55.4 % for BPA, 11.6 % and 84.6 % for caffeine and 7.6 % up to 67.7 % for metoprolol with a concentration of 300 mg/L and 3000 mg/L BN, respectively. The adsorption capacity from a single pollutant solution was significantly higher suggesting a competitive adsorption behavior of the micro pollutants in the mixture. The adsorption isothermes for BPA, caffeine and metoprolol are shown in Figure 33. The fitting of the Langmuir and the Freundlich isotherm were tested and according to the achieved R^2 the appropriate fitting is chosen. The chosen isotherm for caffeine in the single pollutant solution is the Langmuir isotherm. For metoprolol the better fitting is found for the Freundlich isotherm. However, the fitting for the multicomponent mixture is not sufficient for both fitting models. BPA showed an untypical adsorption behavior with no plateau seen in the adsorption isotherm. The fit towards the Freundlich isotherm is higher compared to the Langmuir isotherm. For all three substances the fitting decreases significantly for the mixture of all three micro pollutants. This could be caused by the competing adsorptive behavior of the substances. However, this has to be taken into account for the filtration experiments and the interpretation of the results of the adsorption experiments, as well as for the filtration experiments. The BET area may serve as an indicator for the adsorptive properties of an adsorbent. Nitrogen adsorption isotherms revealed a BET area for pure BN of 26.8 m^2/g . The analysis of the pure PES membrane resulted in a surface area of 13.1 m^2/g and, no significant change was observed through the incorporation of BN particles. The MCMMM with embedded PAC showed a surface area of 145.0 m^2/g , which is 10 times larger compared to the BN MCMMM, but significantly smaller compared to the BET surface of the pure PAC, which amounted to 883.9 m^2/g .

Figure 33: Adsorption isotherms following the Langmuir and the Freundlich isotherm of a) caffeine in a single drug adsorption, b) caffeine in a competitive multi-drug adsorption, c) BPA in a single drug adsorption, d) BPA in a competitive multi-drug adsorption, e) metoprolol in a single drug adsorption, f) metoprolol in a competitive multi-drug adsorption

Figure 34 SEM image with 500-fold magnification of MCMMM with 7 % BN (left) and 7 % PAC (right) embedded into the PES matrix

The SEM analysis of the morphology of the membrane after the spinning process revealed an asymmetric porous structure with denser pores closer to the surface of the non-solvent. The BN particles were found to be distributed evenly among the cross-section of the membrane, as shown in Figure 31. The particles are integrated into the porous membrane structure and not flushed out during the filtration process.

Concerning the mechanical stability, the tensile strength of the pure PES membrane amounted to 3.10 N/mm² and a decrease to 2.69 N/mm² was observed with an increasing share of BN, as shown in Table 11. The MCMMM with embedded PAC showed with 2.37 N/mm² a lower tensile strength compared to the 7 % BN MCMMM.

Table 11 Maximum tensile strength including the standard deviation of the different membranes (values in N/mm²)

	PES MCM	3 % BN	5 % BN	7 % BN	7 % PAC
Mean tensile strength	3.10	3.07	2.93	2.70	2.37
Standard deviation	0.07	0.12	0.09	0.16	0.15

The dextran retention in the range of 67.2 % to 82.3 % of the different MCMMM led to the assumption that the membranes operate within the range of micro- to ultrafiltration. Compared to pure PES membranes and to mixed-matrix membranes with embedded PAC the dextran retention for BN membranes was 15 % lower, with a slight increase though the addition of more BN. The permeability of BN MCMMM was with 15.38 to 19.01 L/m²hbar, lower compared to the permeability of the pure PES multi-channel membrane and to the MCMMM with embedded PAC. The permeability was reduced through a higher amount of particles incorporated into the matrix. Therefore, the BN particles are considered to have an effect on the porosity and the permeability of the MCMMM.

Figure 35 Results of the filtration with a 3 %, 5 % and 7 % BN MCMMM and a 7 % PAC MCMMM for the removal of a) BPA, b) caffeine and c) metoprolol. The reference for these results is the filtration with a pure PES MCM shown in d).

The filtration of mixture with the different membranes was performed over 8 h. The pure PES membrane showed no removal for caffeine and metoprolol, and BPA removal decreased from 98.3 % to 10.3 % within the first hour of the filtration. The addition of 3 % BN increased the removal rate of caffeine and metoprolol to 15.8 % and 19.2 % in the beginning of the filtration with a decrease below 10 % within the first 10 minutes. The BPA removal rate increased as well with a higher share of BN to efficiencies of up to 43.5 % after 8 h. The increase of the amount of BN to 7 % improved

the removal efficiency of caffeine and metoprolol further up to 49.9 % and 47.9 % at the beginning of the filtration, respectively. The removal of BPA was at 88.6 % after 90 min of the filtration experiment with the 7 % BN MCMMM. After 8 h of filtration with the 7 % BN membrane the retention decreased to 43.4 %, 5.3 % and 8.6 % for BPA, caffeine and metoprolol respectively. In comparison, the results for the elimination of these substances with the membranes containing 7 % embedded PAC, were significantly higher, with removal rates of up to 80.9 % for BPA, 45.5 % for caffeine and 50.2 % for metoprolol after 8 h. The absolute amount of adsorbent within the solid membrane was 11.5 % up to 24.3 % for the 3 % and the 7 % BN MCMMM, respectively. The share of PAC within the 7 % PAC membrane with the same composition of the polymeric solution was with 28.3 % higher than the share of the 7 % BN membrane. The higher adsorbent share may contribute to the higher removal efficiency. It is noted, that the applied feed concentrations were 1000-fold higher compared to the actually found concentration in water samples to reduce the filtration time and to get a better understanding of the filtration behavior for the removal of these compounds [18].

Conclusion and Outlook

Activated carbon is a commonly used adsorption material for the removal of micro pollutants from wastewater, even though its use is debated due to its fossil precursors. Combination of adsorption with membrane technology can be carried out via the production of mixed-matrix membranes. In this study, BN was investigated as a potential alternative to PAC for the application in mixed-matrix membranes. Although the membrane production with embedded BN succeeded, the removal of BPA, caffeine and metoprolol was higher when PAC was used. Nonetheless, an increase in the share of BN and optimization of the composition of the polymeric solution could increase the micro pollutant removal efficiency in the filtration process. Overall, it can be stated that further development is required to optimize the use of MCMMM with BN as an adsorption material. The application of the combined filtration and adsorption process is promising due to the high selectivity and the improved filtration parameters.

Acknowledgement

Assistance in laboratory experiments and methods description provided by S. Kostner is greatly appreciated.

References

- Huang Z, Yuan X, Liu X (2021) The key drivers for the changes in global water scarcity: Water withdrawal versus water availability. *Journal of Hydrology* 601:126658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126658>
- Gao T, Wang X, Da Wei et al. (2021) Transboundary water scarcity under climate change. *Journal of Hydrology* 598:126453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126453>
- Pistocchi A, Alygizakis NA, Brack W et al. (2022) European scale assessment of the potential of ozonation and activated carbon treatment to reduce micropollutant emissions with wastewater. *Sci Total Environ* 848:157124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157124>
- Bavumiragira JP, Ge J, Yin H (2022) Fate and transport of pharmaceuticals in water systems: A processes review. *Sci Total Environ* 823:153635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153635>
- Pokkiladathu H, Farissi S, Muthukumar A et al. (2022) A novel activated carbon-based nanocomposite for the removal of bisphenol-A from water via catalytic ozonation: Efficacy and mechanisms. *Results in Chemistry* 4:100593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2022.100593>
- Karalius VP, Harbison JE, Plange-Rhule J et al. (2014) Bisphenol A (BPA) Found in Humans and Water in Three Geographic Regions with Distinctly Different Levels of Economic Development. *Environ Health Insights* 8:1–3. <https://doi.org/10.4137/EHI.S13130>
- Li S, Wen J, He B et al. (2020) Occurrence of caffeine in the freshwater environment: Implications for ecopharmacovigilance. *Environ Pollut* 263:114371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114371>
- Bijlsma L, Pitarch E, Fonseca E et al. (2021) Investigation of pharmaceuticals in a conventional wastewater treatment plant: Removal efficiency, seasonal variation and impact of a nearby hospital. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 9:105548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105548>
- Rivera-Utrilla J, Sánchez-Polo M, Ferro-García MÁ et al. (2013) Pharmaceuticals as emerging contaminants and their removal from water. A review. *Chemosphere* 93:1268–1287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.07.059>
- Castañó Osorio S, Biesheuvel PM, Spruijt E et al. (2022) Modeling micropollutant removal by nanofiltration and reverse osmosis membranes: considerations and challenges. *Water Res* 225:119130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.119130>
- Khoo YS, Goh PS, Lau WJ et al. (2022) Removal of emerging organic micropollutants via modified-reverse osmosis/nanofiltration membranes: A review. *Chemosphere* 305:135151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.135151>
- Cuhorka J, Wallace E, Mikulášek P (2020) Removal of micropollutants from water by commercially available nanofiltration membranes. *Sci Total Environ* 720:137474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137474>
- Altman J, Rehfeld D, Träder K et al. (2016) Combination of granular activated carbon adsorption and deep-bed filtration as a single advanced wastewater treatment step for organic micropollutant and phosphorus removal. *Water Res* 92:131–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.01.051>
- AghaKouchak A, Mirchi A, Madani K et al. (2021) Anthropogenic Drought: Definition, Challenges, and Opportunities. *Reviews of Geophysics* 59. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019RG000683>
- Bathen (2001) *Adsorptionstechnik*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg
- Alafnan S, Awotunde A, Glatz G et al. (2021) Langmuir adsorption isotherm in unconventional resources: Applicability and limitations. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering* 207:109172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2021.109172>
- Spruck M, Hofer G, Fili G et al. (2013) Preparation and characterization of composite multichannel capillary membranes on the way to nanofiltration. *Desalination* 314:28–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2013.01.002>
- Sousa JCG, Ribeiro AR, Barbosa MO et al. (2018) A review on environmental monitoring of water organic pollutants identified by EU guidelines. *J Hazard Mater* 344:146–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2017.09.058>

Direct ex-situ carbonation of minerals and secondary materials without the use of additives

F. Schinnerl^{1,*}, M. Lehner¹

1: Chair of process engineering and environmental protection, Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria

* Corresponding author: florian.schinnerl@unileoben.ac.at

Keywords: Carbonation, ultramafic rocks, secondary materials, heat activation

Research field: Carbonation

Introduction

At present humanity is facing a rapid rise of greenhouse gas concentrations in the planet's atmosphere and thereby an increase in global temperature [1]. According to the Kyoto Protocol the responsible gases for the commencing climate change are carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), fluorocarbons (HFC), perfluorinated hydrocarbons (PFC), sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) and nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃) [2]. Of these gases CO₂ has the largest impact on global warming. With a percentage of 76 % it is the most emitted greenhouse gas and remains in the atmosphere longer than any of the other heat-trapping gases [3, 4]. As of January 2023, the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere has reached 420 ppm, which represents the highest level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere since accurate measurements began [5]. With no actions taken, it is assumed, that the carbon dioxide concentration will rise to 900-1100 ppm by the end of the century [6].

According to a report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) the global temperature rise caused by human activities has reached approximately 1 °C above pre-industrial levels with an increase of 0.2 °C per decade. If global warming keeps climbing at this rate the 1.5 °C mark set by the Paris Agreement in 2015 will be reached between 2030 and 2052 [7, 8]. To reduce the risks and impacts that climate change causes a path towards climate neutrality has to be taken. Next to renewable energies, fuel switching in transportation and land-use changes towards lower-emission agriculture, this also requires innovative processes that make it possible to use carbon dioxide and convert it into valuable materials or offer a way to store the greenhouse gas over a long period of time [9, 10]. Carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS) describes the process of capturing carbon dioxide emissions and either utilizing them to produce valuable products or permanently storing them in geologic formations like depleted oil and gas reservoirs or oceans. At present there are several technological pathways for CCUS, one of which is given by mineral and secondary carbonation (MC) processes [9, 11]. The aim of the project is the design and optimization of an ex-situ direct aqueous carbonation process.

Theory

Natural carbonation, also known as silicate weathering, describes a process in which atmospheric CO₂ reacts with alkali and alkaline earth metals to form a carbonate. This in nature occurring process has extremely slow reaction kinetics and takes place on a geological time scale. To ensure that this process can nevertheless be used economically, researchers are working on accelerating the carbonation process. Under optimized pressure and temperature conditions, the CO₂ absorption capacity of minerals containing metal oxides is being investigated. In this process, the metal oxides (MO), mainly magnesium or calcium oxide, are brought into contact with carbon dioxide as shown in reaction equation (1) to produce a carbonate (MCO₃). The carbonation reaction represents an exothermic reaction, which is why additional heat is released during the formation of the carbonate [12, 13].

Rocks and minerals containing magnesium and calcium oxides, such as ultramafic and mafic rocks, ferromagnesian minerals and calcium bearing minerals serve as the feed material for carbonation. The two alkaline earth metals are widely distributed on our planet and available in large quantities [14, 15].

In addition to primary raw materials, by-products and waste from other processes can also be used in carbonation. These include fly ash from the paper industry, slag from iron and steel production and fuel ash from coal-fired power plants [12].

To evaluate the potential of the used materials the theoretical CO₂-uptake can be calculated according to the in equation (2) shown modified Steinour formula [16].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tCO}_2\text{-uptake} = & 0.785 \cdot (\text{CaO}\% - 0.53 \cdot \text{CaCO}_3\% \\ & - 0.7 \cdot \text{SO}_3\%) + 1.091 \cdot \text{MgO}\% + 0.71 \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{O}\% \\ & + 0.468 \cdot (\text{K}_2\text{O}\% - 0.632 \cdot \text{KCl}\%) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

As shown in Figure 36 carbonation can be divided into different process routes

Generally, a distinction can be made between in-situ and ex-situ carbonation processes. In-situ processes describe the injection of CO₂ as a gas or aqueous solution into silicate-rich geological rock formations. Under optimized pressure and temperature conditions the carbonation reaction that subsequently takes place can be accelerated compared to the naturally occurring carbonation. Ex-situ processes describe the reaction of pre-treated feedstocks with CO₂ in chemical reactors and can be divided into direct and indirect processes [12, 14].

Figure 36: Subdivision of mineral carbonation. Adopted and modified from [12].

The direct ex-situ processes refer to a process in which the minerals react with the gas stream containing carbon dioxide to form a carbonate after being crushed in a single process step. The indirect processes divide the extraction of the metal ions and the subsequent carbonation into different process steps and thus consist of at least

two successive processes. Compared to indirect processes, direct MC processes are simpler in structure, but have slower reaction kinetics [12, 14]. Both subsectors can be further divided into gas-solid and aqueous carbonation processes. Very little research is still being carried out on gas-solid processes due to the extremely slow reaction kinetics and the non-existent possibilities for improvement. Much higher potential is shown by aqueous processes, in which the carbonation reaction can be accelerated by using a liquid or a mixture of liquids. Due to the faster reaction kinetics and the considerable optimization possibilities, research is increasingly focusing on processes from the aqueous subareas [12, 15, 16].

The end products of carbonation can be used as fillers in the paper, cement and pharmaceutical industries. Furthermore, the carbonates represent the thermodynamically most stable form of CO₂, which is why they are also suitable for long-term storage. Due to these possibilities, carbonation can be referred to as both CCU (Carbon Capture and Utilization) and CCS (Carbon Capture and Storage) processes [12, 16, 17].

Materials and methods

In total 13 different samples with a particle size of 90 to 125 µm were carbonated at a temperature of 180 °C and a CO₂ partial pressure of 20 bar. The samples include the ultramafic rock serpentinite (P1 & P2) and 11 secondary materials from refractories production (P3-P7), waste incineration (P8-P10) and the paper industry (P11-P13). The carbonation of P1 to P11 was observed over a reaction time of 6 and 10 hours, the carbonation reaction of P12 and P13 over a reaction time of 6 hours.

Serpentinite

Raw serpentinite (Mg₃Si₂O₅(OH)₄) consisting of 62 wt.% antigorite, 18 wt.% lizardite and 8 wt.% chrysotile was collected from a quarry and analyzed using x-ray fluorescence (XRF, wavelength-dispersive

spectrometer PANalytical Axios max advanced) and LECO elemental analysis (LECO CS 300 elemental analyzer). Additionally, the material was ground in a stainless-steel ball mill to a particle size of 90 to 125 µm. The composition of the material can be seen in Table 12, however, only the composition needed for the calculation of the Steinour formula is given.

In its raw stage serpentinite possesses large amounts of hydroxyl groups. According to [18] this hydrated stage has a negative impact on the CO₂-uptake and therefore a dehydroxylation of the material at a minimum temperature of 614 °C is recommended. More research on this topic was conducted by McKelvy et al. [19] who focused on the influence of temperature on the removal of hydroxyl groups. If treated at a temperature of 650 °C around 10 wt.% of the OH-groups remain and a poorly ordered meta-serpentine material with a strong amorphous component emerges, which should perform better during carbonation than the raw material itself [18, 19]. To confirm the claims of increased CO₂-uptake potential of thermally activated serpentinite, a part of the raw material was treated at 650 °C in a muffle oven (Elsklo LNT15G) over a period of 2 hours.

Secondary materials

The investigated secondary materials can be divided into three different groups. P3 to P7 are materials gained from the refractories production. They are composed of mainly calcium- and magnesium oxide and therefore a high carbonation potential is expected. Less CO₂-uptake potential is anticipated from the second and third group. The slags and ashes from the waste incineration plant P8 to P10 possess mediocre amounts of CaO and only small amounts of MgO. P11 to P13 are secondary materials from the paper industry with a varying calcium oxide content of 20 to 60 wt.% and a magnesium oxide content of 2 to 6 wt.%.

Table 12: Investigated materials, their origin and composition in wt.% needed for the Steinour formula.

Sample	Material	Origin	CaO*	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	CaCO ₃	
P1	Serpentinite	Quarry	0.06	35.61	0	0	0.04	0	
P2	Serpentinite (thermally activated)		0.07	39.62	0	0	0.04	0	
P3	Yield-fraction	Refractories production	1.32	82.49	0.13	0.06	0.03	0	
P4	Fines		2.06	75.31	0.29	0.06	0.03	0.94	
P5	Landfill		1.66	82.62	0.19	0.06	0.03	2.14	
P6	Fines		14.89	47.24	0.37	0.06	0.03	3.98	
P7	Magnesia spinel bricks		10.51	74.89	2.33	2.04	0.06	1.61	
P8	Slag and ash		Waste incineration	18.62	3.91	0.78	4.21	1.05	5.97
P9	Slag and ash			18.29	3.93	0.78	4.33	1.13	5.3
P10	Boiler ash	31.62		3.91	3.62	1.21	0.54	17.83	
P11	Fly ash	Paper industry	60.36	1.94	0.52	0.14	0.14	27.02	
P12	Fly ash		31.75	6.07	3.28	0.96	4.07	21.02	
P13	Wood ash		20.87	2.62	1.02	3.07	4.98	34.02	

*The CaO content contained in CaCO₃ is included in the given CaO content.

The secondary material samples were analyzed using XRF (PANalytical Axios) and total inorganic and organic carbon (TIC/TOC, ELTRA CS-580) analysis and were ground in a stainless-steel ball mill to a particle size of 90 to 125 μm . Since it is not possible to distinguish calcium- from magnesium carbonate during the TIC/TOC analysis the carbonate was assumed to be only CaCO_3 . The composition of the materials needed for the Steinour formula can be seen in Table 12.

Single stage ex-situ aqueous carbonation in a batch reactor

The aqueous carbonation experiments were executed in a 0.6 l batch reactor (Haage high pressure autoclave, Figure 37) that was designed to operate up to a maximum temperature of 350 °C and a pressure of 350 bar. All parts of the autoclave that are in contact with the medium are made of acid-resistant CrNiMo-steel.

Figure 37: Laboratory batch reactor setup.

Before sealing, 9 grams of pulverized solid material were charged into the reactor and 100 ml of deionized water without additives was added to reach a solid to liquid ratio of 90 g l⁻¹. After subsequent heating to 180 °C using an electrical heater, pure gaseous CO_2 from a gas bottle was injected into the autoclave to initiate a carbonation reaction at the desired pressure of 20 bar. The experiments were conducted over a reaction time of 6 to 10 hours with an agitator speed of 800 rpm. Carbon dioxide was only injected at the beginning, therefore it was possible to observe a pressure drop during successful carbonation over time. The temperature of 180 °C (± 5 °C) was held during the whole experiment. Figure 38 shows a schematic representation of the described process.

Figure 38: Schematic representation of the performed aqueous carbonation.

At the end of the test duration the remaining gaseous CO_2 was ejected and the reactor opened. The slurry consisting of precipitated carbonate, by-products (e.g. Silica) and di-water was filtered to get

rid of most of the liquid and subsequently put in a drying oven (Mettler UFE 500) over night at 105 °C. The dry product was then analysed using a thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Netzsch STA 449C Jupiter). For every tested material three TGA measurements were performed (two measurements for P12 & P13). One of the uncarbonated reference sample and one per conducted carbonation experiment after 6 and 10 hours. By comparing the results of the reference sample with the results of the carbonated samples, it was possible to calculate the CO_2 -uptake per ton of uncarbonated material. Additionally, the results were compared with the theoretically possible CO_2 -uptake according to the modified Steinour formula (eq. (1)).

Results and discussion

The comparison between the calculated theoretical CO_2 -uptake per ton of raw material and the CO_2 -uptake per ton of raw material for the 6 and 10 hour experiments is displayed in Figure 39.

Serpentinite

The efficiency of the process increased significantly when thermally activated serpentinite was used. Almost no CO_2 was absorbed with the raw serpentinite (P1) after both 6 and 10 hours. The heat treated serpentinite (P2) on the other hand was able to take up approximately 100 kg of CO_2 per ton of uncarbonized material which is around one fourth (24 %) of the theoretical value. Since only di-water without additives was used as liquid phase for the carbonation process an increase of the CO_2 -uptake through the addition of additives would be conceivable. As seen in Figure 39 there is almost no difference in the degree of carbonation between 6 and 10 hours which leads to the conclusion that reaction time does not influence the carbonation process after 6 hours. Additional optimization of the process could be performed by increasing the pressure or adjusting the temperature and particle size. According to [20] the optimal temperature for the carbonation of serpentinite is 155 °C.

Secondary materials

When compared to other secondary raw materials, the refractory materials (P3-P7) have a very high theoretical CO_2 -uptake, which can be attributed to their high MgO and CaO content (see Figure 39). Out of the five refractories the fines fraction (P6) performed the best by reaching more than half (73 %) of the theoretical value after 10 hours even though its metal oxide content is lower than that of the others. The second and third best performing samples are P7 (62 %) and P5 (61 %) respectively. In contrast the refractories P3 (36 %) and P4 (20 %) did not perform particularly well. An explanation for the high performance of P7 compared to the other refractories could be easier accessible and therefore easier leachable metal ions that enable more reactions with the dissolved CO_2 . Additionally, the chosen parameters could have benefited P7 more than the others due to its different properties.

In contrast to the refractories the materials from waste incineration (P8-P10) performed worse during the carbonation experiments with a maximum CO_2 -uptake compared to the theoretical value of 19 % (P8), 28 % (P9) and 35 % (P10) after 10 hours. Reasons for the low CO_2 conversion could be the not optimized choice of parameters, the different structure of the materials, which could affect the leachability and the higher carbonate content. A higher pressure and the use of additives would probably benefit the carbonation reaction, although because of the low theoretically possible CO_2 -uptake the question arises if the use of these materials for carbonation would be economically feasible.

The third group of the investigated secondary materials originating from the Paper industry (P11-P13) possess a medium to high CaO and carbonate content. Due to the high amount of CaCO_3 and the therefore low theoretical CO_2 -uptake of sample P12 (fly ash) and P13 (wood ash) a very limited carbonation reaction was expected and therefore only a 6 hour experiment was performed. As

Figure 39: CO₂-uptake of the tested materials P1-P13 after 6 (blue) & 10 (orange) hours and their theoretical (theo) CO₂-uptake (yellow) according to the modified Steinour formula.

can be seen in Figure 39 the carbonate yield after the test duration was relatively low with only 86.2 kg (47 %) and 64.2 kg (41 %) of CO₂ captured per ton of raw material for P12 and P13 respectively. In contrast to these two samples P11 (fly ash) was able to perform better. Due to its higher CaO content the material does have an elevated theoretical CO₂-uptake, although by calculating the ratio between the captured carbon dioxide per ton of raw material and the theoretical value an only slightly better result of 48 % after 6 and 50 % after 10 hours was received. However, due to its higher potential, sample P11 would probably be suitable for an optimization process, while samples P12 and P13 are probably not economical due to the low CO₂-uptake.

Conclusion and Outlook

The aim of this work was to give an overview concerning the aqueous carbonation efficiency of different materials without the use of additives. As discussed by [18] prior the use of raw serpentinite as a feed material for carbonation is not recommended. Due to the high amount of hydroxyl groups the material only captured 3.8 to 4.9 kg of CO₂ after 6 and 10 hour aqueous carbonation experiments respectively. The thermally treated serpentinite on the other hand was able to perform far better with a CO₂-uptake of approximately 100 kg CO₂ per ton of raw material. Compared to its theoretical CO₂-uptake this still only equals 24 % of the maximum uptake according to the Steinour formula (eq. (2)), however, the experiments were not optimized for the ultramafic rock, which means that there is considerable potential for improvement.

The secondary materials from the refractory industry achieved the highest CO₂-uptake with sample P6 (fine fraction) being the highest. Due to the large amounts of CaO and MgO in the refractories this was to be expected considering the high theoretical uptake potential. The materials from the waste incineration and paper industry did not perform as well with an exception being sample P11 (fly ash), which was able to reach a CO₂-uptake of 190.9 kg after 10 hours probably due to its high CaO content. With regard to the other secondary raw materials, the question arises as to whether they should be considered suitable and/or economical for carbonation due to their low CO₂-uptake potential.

Future experiments will focus on the influence of the parameters temperature, pressure, solid to liquid ratio, reaction time and the use of additives on the carbonation efficiency of primary materials with emphasis on heat treated serpentinite. The goal is to quantify the influence of said parameters during full factorial experiments to facilitate the optimization of the aqueous carbonation process.

References

- [1] W. D. Fletcher and C. B. Smith, "What are the effects of global warming?," in *Reaching Net Zero*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 75–98.
- [2] bmu, "Protokoll von Kyoto zum Rahmenübereinkommen der Vereinten Nationen über Klimaänderungen,"
- [3] Center for Climate and Energy Solutions, *Global Emissions*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.c2es.org/content/international-emissions/> (accessed: Jan. 17 2023).
- [4] W. D. Fletcher and C. B. Smith, "How do we know man-made CO₂ is the issue?," in *Reaching Net Zero*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 61–73.
- [5] Nasa, *Global Climate Change: Vital Signs of the Planet*. [Online]. Available: <https://climate.nasa.gov/vital-signs/carbon-dioxide/> (accessed: Jan. 18 2023).
- [6] J. Kiehl, "Climate change. Lessons from Earth's past," *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 331, no. 6014, pp. 158–159, 2011, doi: 10.1126/science.1199380.
- [7] Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), "Global warming of 1,5 °C,"
- [8] UNFCCC, "Adoption of the Paris Agreement,"
- [9] X. Wang and C. Song, "Carbon Capture From Flue Gas and the Atmosphere: A Perspective," *Front. Energy Res.*, vol. 8, 2020, doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2020.560849.
- [10] Franklin M Orr Jr., "Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage: An Update," *Society of Petroleum Engineers*, 2018.
- [11] A. Al-Mamoori, A. Krishnamurthy, A. A. Rownaghi, and F. Rezaei, "Carbon Capture and Utilization Update," *Energy Technol.*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 834–849, 2017, doi: 10.1002/ente.201600747.
- [12] A. A. Olajire, "A review of mineral carbonation technology in sequestration of CO₂," *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, vol. 109, pp. 364–392, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.petrol.2013.03.013.

- [13] H. Herzog, "Carbon Sequestration via Mineral Carbonation: Overview and Assessment," 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://sequestration.mit.edu/pdf/carbonates.pdf>
- [14] C. D. Hills, N. Tripathi, and P. J. Carey, "Mineralization Technology for Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage," *Front. Energy Res.*, vol. 8, 2020, doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2020.00142.
- [15] F. Wang, D. B. Dreisinger, M. Jarvis, and T. Hitchins, "The technology of CO₂ sequestration by mineral carbonation: current status and future prospects," *Canadian Metallurgical Quarterly*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 46–58, 2018, doi: 10.1080/00084433.2017.1375221.
- [16] A. Sanna, M. Uibu, G. Caramanna, R. Kuusik, and M. M. Maroto-Valer, "A review of mineral carbonation technologies to sequester CO₂," *Chemical Society reviews*, vol. 43, no. 23, pp. 8049–8080, 2014, doi: 10.1039/c4cs00035h.
- [17] C. Hepburn *et al.*, "The technological and economic prospects for CO₂ utilization and removal," *Nature*, vol. 575, no. 7781, pp. 87–97, 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41586-019-1681-6.
- [18] W. K. O'Connor, D. C. Dahlin, D. N. Nilsen, R. P. Walters, and P. C. Turner, "Carbon Dioxide Sequestration by Direct Mineral Carbonation with Carbonic Acid," 2000.
- [19] M. J. McKelvy, A. V. G. Chizmeshya, J. Diefenbacher, H. Béarat, and G. Wolf, "Exploration of the role of heat activation in enhancing serpentine carbon sequestration reactions," *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 38, no. 24, pp. 6897–6903, 2004, doi: 10.1021/es049473m.
- [20] S. J. Gerdemann, W. K. O'Connor, D. C. Dahlin, L. R. Penner, and H. Rush, "Ex situ aqueous mineral carbonation," *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 41, no. 7, pp. 2587–2593, 2007, doi: 10.1021/es0619253.

Production of sustainable bio-based platform chemicals via syngas fermentation from dual fluidized bed steam gasification

L. Steiner^{1,*}, F. Benedikt¹, J. A. Horvath², S. Pflügl²

1: TU Wien, Institute of Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering, Research Area Fuel and Energy System Engineering, Austria

2: TU Wien, Institute of Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering, Research Area Biochemical Engineering, Austria

* Corresponding author: lena.steiner@tuwien.ac.at

Keywords: Biomass gasification, Dual fluidized bed steam gasification, Syngas fermentation, *Thermoanaerobacter kivui*

Research field: Biomass gasification, Syngas fermentation

Introduction

Due to the apparent progress of climate change and the current energy crisis, interest in the development of an alternative and more sustainable energy and raw material supply is greater than ever before. In addition to the long-standing goal of avoiding the use of fossil raw materials and reducing CO₂ emissions as much as possible, the focus has recently shifted to energy and raw material resilience. The focus of science, politics and thus also the public is rightly on the development of a sustainable energy system, but at the same time the development of sustainable raw materials should also be considered. Many raw materials, which are essential for the functioning and prosperity of our society, are produced from fossil raw materials. In order to meet the sustainable development goals (SDGs), alternative manufacturing processes must be developed. Biomass gasification is a promising technology to produce materials on biological basis which at the moment are produced from fossil fuels. The kind of biomass used for gasification varies from high quality biomass, such as wood pellets, to low quality residues, such as agricultural waste products or municipal waste streams [1]. In order to meet the SDGs it is necessary to use resources as efficient as possible, meaning that preferably platform chemicals should be produced and only in a second case energy carriers or even only electricity or heat.

Gas generation: Dual fluidized bed pilot plant

Biomass gasification using dual fluidized bed (DFB) steam gasification enables the production of a high-quality product gas that has many potential applications. The principle behind DFB steam gasification is shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 40: Principle of DFB steam gasification, adapted from [2]

At TU Wien a 100 kW advanced DFB pilot plant is in operation to generate product gas for different synthesis applications [3]. The gas generation unit consists of two reactors, the gasification reactor and the combustion reactor. The two reactors are connected via the circulating bed material, which transports heat from the combustion reactor to the gasification reactor and the residual char the other way round. Heat is needed to enable the overall endothermic steam gasification reactions and the residual char is the main fuel for the

combustion reactor. The gasification reactor has temperatures of around 800°C and is operated as a bubbling fluidized bed. The combustion reactor, on the other hand, is operated as a fast fluidized bed at over 900°C. Between the reactors, loop seals are installed to enable solids circulation and simultaneously avoid gas leakage. Thereby, the DFB gasification process produces two separate gas streams: the product gas and the flue gas. The flue gas contains mainly N₂, CO₂, H₂O and O₂, while the product gas is nitrogen-free and contains mainly H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, C₂H₄ and H₂O. This high-quality product gas can be used for a variety of synthesis processes. [2]

Gas cleaning

Before the product gas can be used for synthesis purposes, it must be subjected to several cleaning steps, which follow directly the DFB steam gasification. The first cleaning step, realised as a hot gas filter, removes mainly dust particles, fuel ash and unconverted biomass char. In the following rapeseed methyl ester (RME) scrubber, tars and water-soluble substances are condensed. The scrubber is realised as a packed column. The gas then passes through two adsorption columns filled with activated carbon, in which further tar components and sulphur compounds are separated. In the final purification step, any remaining sulphur compounds are retained in a protective zinc oxide bed. [4]

Syngas fermentation

Acetogenic bacteria are an interesting group of bacteria since they are able to use CO and CO₂ as substrates and fix thereby these climate-damaging gases. In addition to CO and CO₂, hydrogen is an important energy source for gas fermentation. Acetogenic bacteria fix carbon via the Wood-Ljungdahl-pathway (WLP) reducing 2 molecules of CO₂ to Acetyl-CoA and using H₂ as energy source (see equations EQ.1 & EQ.2). Besides acetate, acetogenic bacteria can also produce other products. Syngas fermentation thus represents the low-energy alternative to Fisher-Tropsch (FT) synthesis. [5, 6]

Comparing syngas fermentation to classical synthesis processes such as FT leads to the conclusion that especially in terms of flexibility, robustness and selectivity syngas fermentation is the better choice. For FT synthesis a high purity syngas and a certain ratio between the gas components is needed in order not to spoil the catalyst and guarantee a high productivity. In contrast, syngas fermentation allows a much larger number of ratios between the gas components and is also more insensitive to impurities. Another important advantage is the low number of produced by-products due to the high

selectivity. The temperature and pressure conditions are also less extreme during syngas fermentation. For certain applications the lower chemical energy content of hydrocarbons produced from syngas fermentation compared to FT hydrocarbons might be a disadvantage [7]. To carry out the syngas fermentation besides the addition of syngas to the bacteria culture, the continuous addition of a moon medium, a base and heat is also necessary. The moon medium is a saline nutrient medium for the bacteria. The base must be added to prevent acidification in the reactor during the production of acetate or lactate, for example.

Thermoanaerobacter kivui (*T. kivui*)

T. kivui are thermophilic organisms that can grow both heterotrophically and autotrophically with H₂ and CO₂ as substrate. The bacteria originate from Lake Kivu in Africa, to which they also owe their name. Originally *T. kivui* was not able to grow on CO but was successfully adapted to that end. [6]

Concept and methodology

As shown in Figure 41, this concept comprises the combination of the three process steps "DFB steam gasification", "gas cleaning" and "syngas fermentation". In this process a valuable platform chemical is produced out of a high-quality syngas of biological origin. In the DFB steam gasification process, the fuel is gasified, releasing product gas, ash, heat and flue gas. The product gas produced passes through a gas cleaning process in which impurities (e.g. tars, nitrogen and sulphur compounds) are separated. Due to steam gasification, the humid gas must be dried in the course of gas cleaning and nitrogenous water is condensed. Finally, the syngas is transferred to the fermentation reactor, where it is converted to the final product by the bacteria grown on the moon medium under the influence of heat and the addition of a base. Since many components of the moon medium can also be found in the ash residues from the DFB steam gasification process, recycling the ash stream to partially replace the moon medium would optimise the use of resources. In order to be able to test if *T. kivui* is able to grow on the gas generated from gasification of wood pellets, the syngas was filled into gas bottles. Since *T. kivui* are strictly anaerobic bacteria no oxygen should be in the gas mixture.

The bacteria were then repeatedly cultivated on syngas from gasification to facilitate adaptation. After successful adaptation of the bacteria long-term growth experiments can be carried out in different scale reactors. These pre-tests are used to gain information about operating parameters, yields and problems of the process before connecting the three process steps finally.

Results

The composition of the bottled syngas is listed in Table 13.

Table 13: Main components of the syngas

Component	Concentration (vol.% dry basis)
H ₂	43.1 - 44.0
CO	19.9 - 21.0
CO ₂	23.8 - 24.6
CH ₄	8.9 - 9.2

It has been successfully demonstrated that a pre-culture of bacteria can grow on the bottled gas meaning that also successful bottling of the gas has been achieved since already small amounts of oxygen would be deadly for the bacteria.

Conclusion and Outlook

In summary, the combination of biomass gasification, gas cleaning and syngas fermentation is an interesting concept for the future, as it enables an alternative to the fossil-based production of platform chemicals. Data from biomass gasification, gas cleaning and syngas fermentation are to serve as the basis for a simulation of the merger. In addition, waste streams from biomass gasification and gas cleaning are to be integrated into syngas fermentation if possible. The combination is mainly advantageous due to the low adaptations of the syngas and the flexibility of the process. The still low level of research in the field and the necessary adaptation of the bacteria could be seen as disadvantages.

List of abbreviations

SDGs	Sustainable development goals
DFB	Dual fluidized bed
RME	Rapeseed methyl ester
WLP	Wood-Ljungdahl-pathway
FT	Fisher-Tropsch
<i>T. kivui</i>	<i>Thermoanaerobacter kivui</i>

Figure 41: Scheme of the overall process

List of references

- [1] Molino, A., Chianese, S., and Musmarra, D., "Biomass gasification technology: The state of the art overview" *Journal of Energy Chemistry*, vol. 25(1), pp.10-25, 2016. doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2015.11.005
- [2] Benedikt, F., "Fuel Flexible Advanced Dual Fluidized Bed Steam Gasification", Dissertation, 2020
- [3] Schmid, J. C., Benedikt, F., Fuchs, J., et al., "Syngas for biorefineries from thermochemical gasification of lignocellulosic fuels and residues – 5 years' experience with an advanced dual fluidized bed gasifier design." *Biomass Conv.Bioref.*, vol. 11, pp. 2405-2442, 2021. doi.org/10.1007/s13399-019-00486-2
- [4] Bartik, A., Benedikt, F., Müller, S., et al., "ReGas4Industry. Gase aus regenerativen Reststoffquellen für die Industrie" *Energieforschungsprogramm – 5. Ausschreibung*, 2021
- [5] Novak, K., Neuendorf, C. S., Kofler, I., Kieberger, N., Klant, S. and Pflügl, S., "Blending industrial blast furnace gas with H₂ enables *Acetobacterium woodii* to efficiently co-utilize CO, CO₂ and H₂" *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 323, 2021. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2020.124573
- [6] Weghoff, M.C., and Müller, V., "CO Metabolism in the Thermophilic Acetogen *Thermoanaerobacter kivui*" *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, vol. 82(8), pp. 2312–2319, 2016. doi:10.1128/AEM.00122-16
- [7] Daniell, J., Köpke, M. and Simpson, S. D., "Commercial Biomass Syngas Fermentation" *Energies*, vol. 5(12), pp. 5372-5417, 2012. doi:10.3390/en5125372

Utilization of Chemical Looping Combustion CO₂ by exhaust gas methanation – CLCH₄ – Experimental demonstration of a full process chain

Fleiß Benjamin*¹, Bartik Alexander¹, Priscak Juraj², Benedikt Florian¹, Fuchs Josef¹, Müller Stefan¹, Hofbauer Hermann¹

* Corresponding author, E-mail address: benjamin.fleiss@tuwien.ac.at

¹ Institute of Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering, TU Wien, Austria

² BEST – Bioenergy and Sustainable Technologies GmbH, Austria

Keywords: Chemical Looping Combustion, Methanation, CO₂ utilization, Pilot plant, Ilmenite, Biomass

Introduction

Chemical looping combustion (CLC) is a highly efficient carbon capture technology, utilizing the oxygen carrier capacity of certain metal oxides, called oxygen carrier (OC), to combust fuel for energy production and obtain concentrated CO₂. A possible route of the direct utilization of CLC exhaust gas of biomass is the methanation reaction, producing synthetic natural gas (SNG) to replace fossil gas. Eventual unburnt components in the CLC exhaust gas like CO, CH₄ and H₂ are no burden but beneficial to the reactions in a methanation unit. The combination of CLC and methanation has been covered so far only by different theoretical studies [1, 2].

This work shows a first-of-its-kind process chain in one lab facility. The exhaust gas of an 80 kW_{th} CLC pilot plant, operated with ilmenite enhanced by limestone, is utilized in a fluidized bed methanation unit. Providing a proof of concept, operation conditions and gas compositions of the coupled chain are investigated.

Methodology

For the utilization of the CLC exhaust gas, a complete process chain has been set up at TU Wien, consisting of the advanced dual fluidized bed (DFB) reactor with two interconnected reactors, air reactor (AR) and fuel reactor (FR), a gas cleaning section and a fluidized bed methanation reactor, all shown in Figure 42. Ilmenite mixed with 25% limestone was used as OC in the DFB reactor to combust bark pellets and generate heat. A partial flow of the exhaust gas from the fuel reactor of the CLC pilot plant entered the gas cleaning section and was subsequently catalytically converted with NiO/Al₂O₃ to raw-SNG in the methanation reactor with externally supplied hydrogen. The stoichiometric number of the methanation

reaction was set by the amount of excess hydrogen to 1.17 and 1.29 for the lower and the higher hydrogen input. The exhaust gas of the CLC reactors and the raw-SNG after the methanation unit was analyzed for the gases H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄ and O₂. As purging gas, nitrogen was used for the pressure measurements and the flushing of the fuel bunker. With an evaluated mass- and energy balance, important performance parameters were determined like the carbon capture rate and the combustion efficiency of the process.

Discussion

The measured gas flows during the experiments are shown in Figure 43. The combustion of 14 kg/h bark resulted despite the diluting with the nitrogen purge in CO₂ concentration over 90%. High carbon capture rates and a combustion efficiency of over 91.7% were reached in the biomass CLC process, which was the best performance in the 80 kW_{th} pilot plant with natural ores so far [3]. Adding limestone to ilmenite increased all key performance indicators compared to a former experimental campaign with pure ilmenite [4].

Through higher conversion rates, the temperature was increased, which again favored conversion and carbon capture during the process. Through the successful coupling with the fluidized bed methanation, almost all carbon input was converted to methane with external hydrogen addition, reaching a methane yield of over 97%. With the separation of excess hydrogen and a minor gas upgrading step, the SNG could achieve standard gas qualities of the gas grid and would be able to replace fossil natural gas. A scale-up simulation showed the potential of combining both technologies [5].

Figure 42: Process chain of direct utilization of chemical looping combustion exhaust gas to raw-SNG.

Figure 43: Gas concentration of the FR and temperatures of FR and AR (left). Raw-SNG gas concentrations downstream the methanation unit (right).

Acknowledge

The present work is part of the Research Project BIO-LOOP. The COMET Module BIO-LOOP (Austrian Research Promotion Agency Project Number 872189) is funded within COMET - Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies.

References

- [1] A. Navajas, T. Mendiara, L. M. Gandía, A. Abad, F. García-Labiano, and L. F. de Diego, "Life cycle assessment of power-to-methane systems with CO₂ supplied by the chemical looping combustion of biomass," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 267, 2022.
- [2] P. Brachi *et al.*, "Assessing the feasibility of an integrated CLC-methanation system using solar dried and torrefied biomasses as a feedstock," *Fuel*, vol. 331, 2023.
- [3] B. Fleiß, J. Priscak, J. Fuchs, S. Müller, and H. Hofbauer, "Synthetic oxygen carrier C28 compared to natural ores for chemical looping combustion with solid fuels in 80 kWth pilot plant experiments," ed. *Fuel*, 2023.
- [4] B. Fleiß, S. Penthor, S. Müller, H. Hofbauer, and J. Fuchs, "Holistic assessment of oxygen carriers for chemical looping combustion based on laboratory experiments and validation in 80 kW pilot plant," *Fuel Processing Technology*, vol. 231, 2022.
- [5] B. Fleiß *et al.*, "First experimental demonstration of 80 kWth chemical looping combustion of biogenic feedstock coupled with direct CO₂ utilization by exhaust gas methanation," *Submitted to Fuel Processing Technology*, 2023.

Power to gas in air driven bioreactors

F. Klupal^{1,2}, M. W. Hlawitschka^{1,2,*}

1: Institute of Process Engineering, Johannes Kepler Universität, Austria

2: Competence Center CHASE GmbH, Austria

*Corresponding Author: mark.hlawitschka@jku.at

Keywords: Bioreactors; Power to X; Bubble columns; Gas hold-up; Bubble size; Sparger

Research field: Power to X, Plant Design

As recent events have shown, importing gas for energy and heating purpose is not reliable, since unpredictable events can stop or hinder these imports. The war between the Ukraine and Russia has led to a rapid increase in energy costs and also to a rethinking about the dependency on the Russia gas. Countries like Austria are looking for new and more reliable energy source. Renewable energy sources like water, solar and wind energy are getting into the focus, but many of them serious disadvantages. They are not available all the time, the sun is not always shining and the wind is not always blowing strong enough. To tackle these problems, an energy store technology must be developed, where the energy is used to produce a product, which can be stored and turned back into energy without losing it. Also, the system has to be flexible, increasing its productivity when plenty energy is available and decrease its productivity if there is a shortage.

Power-to-gas aims to provide technologies for the energy future that are capable of storing renewable energies in the gas grid cost-effectively and efficiently for a longer period of time, while at the same time driving a transition to a climate-neutral gas grid. An already established process would be the catalytic methanation, but with reaction temperatures ranging between 200 to 400°C, a lot of energy would be lost for heating. Additionally expensive metal catalysts must be used and later recovered, which can be expensive and time consuming. The focus is shifting to biological methanation using archaea. In this process, methanation takes place at comparatively low temperatures of 50 to 60°C. Figure 44 shows the

theoretical efficiency of the system, by producing biogas through a fermenter and hydrogen through electrolysis.

The frequently used stirred tank is well researched, but has severe downsides, like additional energy input due to stirring. A stirrer also brings shear forces into the system, which can damage microorganisms. For the growth and metabolism of the used microorganism nutrients, hydrogen and carbon dioxide are needed. The nutrients are often easily solvable in the broth, but gases like hydrogen are very hard to dissolve. Stirred tank reactors have a weak mass transfer between the gas and liquid phase, which leads to lower efficiency.

Bubble columns, on the other hand, have a much better mass and heat transfer. Additionally, the energy intensive agitator is not needed, since the mixing of the archaea takes place due to the resulting hydrodynamics. The hydrodynamic, can be influenced by the use of different spargers, like plate (sieve plate and membrane) and pipe (radial, spider and multiple ring) type spargers. The hole diameter of the sparger influences the bubble size of the introduced gas. Smaller bubbles lead to an overall bigger average interaction area between the gas bubble and the liquid, which results in better mass transfer. Additionally, a better gas hold-up can be achieved, since smaller bubbles tend to rise slower to the top of the column, compared to bigger bubbles. The downside from small bubble diameter is, that it leads to a decrease in mixing in the bubble column.

Figure 44: Visualization of the theoretical effectiveness of the power to gas application using CO₂ valorisation.

The overall simple design and adaptability of bubble columns improve the scale-up ability and keeps the costs lower compared to similar stirred tank reactors.

However, the design is only rudimentarily discussed in the literature. Many different approaches have been made to design calculation models of the columns. Parameter like superficial gas velocity, bubble rising velocity, gas hold-up, mass and heat transfer have been calculated from different authors, but by comparing them with each other, they differ strongly. For example, Figure 45 shows different calculation models for the gas hold-up at increasing superficial gas velocities. It shows that most of the known models are designed for a specific setup and can only be used vaguely for other apparatuses. A possible reason for this behaviour could be, that the systems strongly depend on the liquid properties like surface tension, density and viscosity and the apparatus geometry like diameter to height ratio, installations and sparger designs. These

parameters then also depend on other influences like temperature and microorganism behaviour. Without empirical data only an estimated model can be designed for the new bubble column.

CFD simulations are a big trend and can be used to show the system behaviour, but even so, the CFD requires input about coalescence and breakage behaviour, initial bubble size as well as the fluidic parameters. A large number of open questions must be answered in order to advance an efficient and economical design of the columns e.g., in regard to optimum bubble size, interactions between hydrodynamics, coalescence behaviour and the archaea, nutrition supply, and flexible operation conditions.

This contribution highlights the current design concepts and gives an insight into own recent studies on biological methanation regarding hydrodynamics and bubble size.

Figure 45: Different gas hold-up correlations applied for biological systems

References

- [1] Hughmark, G.A., "Holdup and mass transfer in bubble columns," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Process Design and Development*, vol. 6, pp. 218-220, 1967.
- [2] Hikita, H., Kikukawa, H., "Liquid-phase mixing in bubble columns: Effect of liquid properties," *The Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 8, pp. 191-197, 1974. doi: 10.1016/0300-9467(74)85024-0.
- [3] Kumar, A., Degaleesan, T.E., Laddha, G.S., and Hoelscher, H.E., "Bubble swarm characteristics in bubble columns," *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 54, pp. 503-508, 1976.
- [4] Joshi, J.B., Sharma, M.M., "A Circulation cell model for bubble columns," *Transaction of the Institution of Chemical Engineers*, vol. 54, pp. 503-508, 1976.
- [5] Koide, K., Morooka S., Ueyama K., Matsuura A., "Behavior of bubbles in large scale bubble column," *Journal of Chemical Engineering of Japan*, vol. 12, pp. 98-104, 1979.
- [6] Hikita, H., Asai, S., Tanigawa, K., Segawa, K., and Kitao, M., "Gas Hold-up in Bubble Columns" *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 20, pp. 59-67, 1980.
- [7] Godole, S. P., Honath, M.F., Shah, Y.T., "Holdup structure in highly viscous Newtonian and non-Newtonian liquids in bubble columns," *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 16, pp. 119-134, 1982. doi: 10.1080/00986448208911090.
- [8] Grover, G.S., Rode, C.V., and Chaudhari, R.V. "Effect of temperature on flow regimes and gas hold-up in a bubble column," *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 64, pp. 501-504.
- [9] Reilly, I.G., Scott, D. S., de Bruijn, T., Jain, A., and Piskorz, J., "A correlation for gas holdup in turbulent coalescing bubble columns," *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol.64, pp. 705-717, 1986.
- [10] Kawase, Y., Moo-Young, M., "Heat transfer in bubble column reactors with Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids," *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 65, pp. 121-126, 1987.

Simulation of methane pyrolysis in a molten metal bubble column reactor: Validation approaches

Hanna Weiss^{1*}, Markus Lehner¹

1: Dept. of Environmental and Energy Process Engineering, Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria

* Corresponding author: hanna.weiss@unileoben.ac.at

Keywords: hydrogen production, bubble column reactor, multiphase flow, Comsol Multiphysics

Research field: Methane pyrolysis

Purpose

Hydrogen can be an important part of decarbonisation, but in 2021 76 % of non-byproduct hydrogen were produced from natural gas, mainly by steam methane reforming (SMR) [1]. In this process CO₂ is formed and eight to ten kg CO₂ per kg H₂ are emitted via the SMR process [2]. Green hydrogen made by water electrolysis would be preferable, but the use of scarce renewable electricity is mandatory, otherwise it leads to high CO₂ emissions when utilizing electricity from non-renewable sources [3].

Methane pyrolysis, in which methane is split into hydrogen and carbon, is therefore a promising option.

The energy requirement is significantly lower than that of water electrolysis and a usable by-product is formed instead of CO₂ [4]. However, this carbon poses a challenge as it can lead to blockages of pipes or reactors as well as to deactivation of solid catalysts. Bubble column reactors with liquid metals provide a possible solution, as the carbon floats up and catalytically active molten metals do not suffer deactivation. Nevertheless, the usage of molten metal also makes it difficult to measure and observe what is going on inside the reactor. Simulations can offer support in understanding these processes in order to improve the reactor and process design. The aim is therefore to set up a simulation including all relevant processes taking place in the reactor and subsequently gain knowledge for scale-up and further development.

Methods

The simulations are carried out with Comsol Multiphysics®, considering the physics interfaces shown in Figure 46, and are calculated in a stationary and 2D axisymmetric configuration to reduce the computational load.

Figure 46: Overview of the physics interfaces included in the Comsol Multiphysics simulation

This model complies with the requirements of the inductively heated bubble column reactor currently used at the Montanuniversität Leoben (MUL), shown in Figure 47, and must be adapted depending on the reactor to be simulated. The reactor used at the Chair of Nonferrous Metallurgy consists of a cylindrical carbon crucible in which the respective metal or alloy is inserted and inductively heated. The methane enters at the bottom through a porous plug and rises through the molten metal, where it is heated and decomposed.

Figure 47: Methane pyrolysis reactor at the Chair of Nonferrous Metallurgy, adapted from Sprung A. and Neuschitzer D.

To verify the flow of the molten metal induced by the magnetic field, data from the manufacturer of the planned pilot plant at MUL is used. For this purpose, the geometry of the simulated reactor is adapted to an inductively heated reactor with two coils, between which a phase shift is possible, and only liquid metal is considered without the introduction of gas. The resulting flow profile is then compared with that of the manufacturer's simulations.

Figure 48: Illustrative geometry of the reactor used by Plevan et al. [5] a) 3D plot of the reactor, b) 2D axisymmetric mesh

In order to validate the simulation of the reactive bubbly flow with experimental data from literature, the reactors from the publications of Plevan et al. [5], schematically shown in Figure 48, and

Uhlenbruck et al. [6], similar to the beforementioned, are simulated. Here, the heating is carried out electrically from the exterior via the wall, which means that the calculation of the magnetic field is not necessary. The experiments were carried out with different filling heights of tin, several temperatures between 850 °C and 1175 °C and varying volume flows in the range of 5 - 200 cm³ min⁻¹.

To simulate the bubbly flow, the Euler-Euler method is used, since this is best suited for the future requirements of the simulation of an industrial sized reactor with gas fractions in the range of 25 Vol.-%. Regarding the interaction forces, only drag is included, as especially for the use in liquid metals limited information is available. The drag coefficient can be calculated according to different models and the three most frequently used methods from Ishii-Zuber [7], Schiller-Neumann [8] and Tomiyama [9] are used and compared. The bubble size needs to be specified as well, with several equations found in literature. Some of the more frequently used equations are applied and the resulting minimum and maximum bubble sizes are taken to assess the influence of different bubble sizes. Furthermore, the Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model is included with standard coefficients for each phase.

In order to determine the temperature, which has a major influence on the endothermic reaction, heat transport is also simulated. A wall temperature according to the literature is specified and heat transfer to the molten metal as well as between liquid and gas is calculated. The two phases are coupled by a source term and in the gas phase another source term for the heat of the reaction is implemented. Its composition is calculated through species transport, where the formed carbon is transferred to another phase and is therefore neglected. Diffusion within the bubble is also not considered, only convective transport coupled with the Euler-Euler interface occurs. The reaction is included as a source term in the species conservation, with non-catalytic kinetics of methane pyrolysis being calculated. This is based on previous experimental investigations, which did not observe catalytic activity of tin [10]. For the non-catalytic methane decomposition, 13 kinetic models found in literature are compared in the simulation to examine their suitability using the experimental data.

Results

First results of the simulations are already available, concerning the flow induced by the magnetic field as well as the experimental data of Plevan et al. [5]. Regarding the flow, it is in good agreement with the manufacturers data. It can be seen that the flow is split into two vertical sections, with the upper one flowing upwards in the middle and vice versa. Depending on the phase shift between the two coils, the size of these two areas changes significantly. In addition, the maximum values of the flow velocity increase with the application of a phase shift.

For the investigation of the applicability of the simulation for reactive bubbly flows, the conversions of the simulation are set against those of the literature data. The comparison of 13 kinetic models shows strong deviations, in some cases by orders of magnitude between the calculated conversion rates among each other and with the experimental data. Using one kinetic model and varying the bubble size to the minimum and maximum calculated values of 2.8 mm respectively 9.4 mm at 900 °C shows a significantly smaller variation in the conversion rate. Along with the bubble size, the velocity of the rising bubble increases too, and thus the conversion rate decreases. The same effect occurs with smaller bubble diameters, where the conversion rate is slightly higher. The effect is limited to less than 2 % in relative terms compared to the rates of the otherwise used bubble size of 5 mm. Similar results are obtained with different models of the drag coefficient, with only a comparatively small effect as well.

Conclusion

Within the scope of this work, a simulation of the liquid metal bubble column reactor for methane pyrolysis was implemented in Comsol Multiphysics, which is suitable for the inductively heated reactor used at MUL. To verify the flow profile induced by the magnetic field, it was compared with data from the manufacturer of the planned pilot plant and shows good agreement. For validation of the reactive bubbly flow, experimental literature data was used. The simulation results show that the selection of the kinetic model is a key factor for the accuracy of the calculated conversions. In contrast, different drag coefficients and bubble sizes resulted in only minor deviations when using this reactor. Based on these results, the most suitable kinetic model across the entire temperature range of the experiments is now to be determined in order to implement it for future simulations. It is planned to carry out experiments in the reactor of the Chair of Nonferrous Metallurgy and compare them with simulation results. Thus, the validation of the entire reactor including inductive heating can be carried out. The influence of bubble sizes and drag coefficients should again be investigated in these simulations, as there may be a different influence due to the considerably divergent geometry. Subsequently, it is intended to develop suitable kinetic models using the simulation and experimental results with catalytically active alloys.

References

- [1] International Energy Agency, "Global Hydrogen Review 2022" <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-hydrogen-review-2022>.
- [2] Parkinson, B., Balcombe, P., Speirs, J. F., Hawkes, A. D., Hellgardt, K., "Levelized cost of CO₂ mitigation from hydrogen production routes" *Energy Environ. Sci.*, vol. 12, pp. 19–40, 2019. doi: 10.1039/C8EE02079E.
- [3] Machhammer, O., Bode, A., Hormuth, W., "Ökonomisch/ökologische Betrachtung zur Herstellung von Wasserstoff in Großanlagen" *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 87, pp. 409–418, 2015. doi: 10.1002/cite.201400151.
- [4] Timmerberg, S., Kaltschmitt, M., Finkbeiner, M., "Hydrogen and hydrogen-derived fuels through methane decomposition of natural gas – GHG emissions and costs" *Energy Conversion and Management: X*, vol. 7, pp. 1–15, 2020. doi: 10.1016/j.ecmx.2020.100043.
- [5] Plevan, M. et al., "Thermal cracking of methane in a liquid metal bubble column reactor: Experiments and kinetic analysis" *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 40, pp. 8020–8033, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.04.062.
- [6] Uhlenbruck, N., Dietrich, B., Hofberger, C., Stoppel, L., Wetzel, T., "Methane Pyrolysis in a Liquid Metal Bubble Column Reactor: A Model Approach Combining Bubble Dynamics with Byproduct and Soot Formation" *Energy Tech*, vol. 10, 2022. doi: 10.1002/ente.202200654.
- [7] Ishii, M., Zuber, N., "Drag coefficient and relative velocity in bubbly, droplet or particulate flows" *AIChE J.*, vol. 25, pp. 843–855, 1979. doi: 10.1002/aic.690250513.
- [8] Mühlbauer, A., Hlawitschka, M. W., Bart, H.-J., "Models for the Numerical Simulation of Bubble Columns: A Review" *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 91, pp. 1747–1765, 2019. doi: 10.1002/cite.201900109.
- [9] Tomiyama, A., Kataoka, I., Zun, I., Sakaguchi, T., "Drag Coefficients of Single Bubbles under Normal and Micro Gravity Conditions" *JSME International Journal*, vol. 41, pp. 472–479, 1998.
- [10] Upham, D. C., Agarwal, V., Khechfe, A., Snodgrass, Z. R., Gordon, M. J., Metiu, H., McFarland, E. W., "Catalytic molten metals for the direct conversion of methane to hydrogen and separable carbon" *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 358, pp. 917–921, 2017. doi: 10.1126/science.aao5023.

Improving energy efficiency in modern buildings with forecast based control systems

B.Kling^{1*}, M.Wolf¹, T.Keller¹, W. Hofbauer², C. Treberspurg³, M. Treberspurg³, T.Pröll¹

1: Department of Materials Science and Process Engineering, University, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna
 2: Technisches Büro Hofbauer, Vienna
 3: Treberspurg & Partner Architekten Ziviltechniker GmbH, Vienna, Vienna
 * Corresponding author: Bernhard.kling@boku.ac.at

Keywords:

Research field: model predictive control, forecast based controlling, thermally activated buildings

Abstract

Buildings with thermally activated components enable the storage of heat with a high level of comfort for the inhabitants. However, a challenge for controlling these buildings is the high inertia due to the storage mass and the associated problem of intervening the control system during extreme weather events. Predictive controllers, working with weather data, combined with a building model enable a forecast of the system's behavior. The building model processes weather data and information about the building and calculates a predictive temperature profile. Optimizing the comfort criteria of the users enables a prognosis of the heating energy demand.

This paper provides an overview of the concept, discusses results from demonstration projects, and provides an outline for future adaptations and modifications.

Introduction

Decarbonization of the building sector is a key milestone for Austria to be able to achieve the climate targets 2030 and 2050 [1],[2]. An important basis for sustainable and climate-friendly new buildings is thermal component activation. This makes it possible to transfer heating energy with a low flow temperature over a large area into the respective residential units. This system turns the activated building mass into a large thermal store that can absorb and release a large amount of thermal energy without the temperature in the concrete core fluctuating significantly.

Based on this system, a controller was developed that is able to detect environmental influences such as solar irradiation for a period of time into the future and, based on this forecast, control the heat input into the building component activation in such a way that significant over- or under-steering of the desired set temperature is prevented. For example, solar radiation is actively used to maintain the temperature. Further functions, such as the inclusion of wind peak shaving, can be integrated into the forecast-based control (MPC) by means of extensions and constraints.

Design and Function of the MPC

The MPC consists of several parts that interact with each other. The first part consists of environmental data measured directly on site and collected from the network. Local weather data is collected from an internet service on an hourly basis. The second part consists of the building model. This represents the masses, orientations, window areas and location of the residential units under consideration and establishes the energy balance over the delineated system. Here, the collected environmental data are incorporated and output a predictive room temperature for the future based on the measured room temperature. This expected room temperature enters the optimizer as the next step. The optimizer in its basic variant is a comfort optimizer. This means that the deviation from the desired setpoint temperature should be as small as possible, taking solar inputs into account. Here it is recommended to minimize the error sum of squares of the temperature deviation. If the optimizer is

extended by additional constraints, a cost function is used. In this case, a temperature range is specified by the user, which should be adhered to. Temperature deviations above and below these limits are penalized with costs. Due to the flexibility offered by the temperature range, constraints such as wind peak shaving (WPS), economic optimizations with varying electricity prices and ecological optimizations with a sustainable electricity mix can be realized. From the optimization process comes a heating power demand for the next hour. The whole process is repeated every hour. The forecast horizon is 48 hours. Figure 49 gives an overview of the described scheme:

Figure 49: Scheme of the forecast-based control

Building Modell and Hardware

The building model is a central component of the MPC. While the physical characteristics of the building, such as mass, orientation, geographic location and window areas are collected, the measurement technology also plays an important role in the ongoing operation. The logic of the MPC can run on a variety of platforms. In the demonstration objects discussed later, this is a RaspberryPi [3]. This single-board computer can communicate with the freely programmable controllers of the Technical Alternative (TA) [4] via an interface module and bus lines. These take measured data from the component activation and the housing units and regulate the heat input via the actuator of the mixing valve.

Figure 50: Scheme of the building

Demonstration object

The first demonstration object where the MPC is applied is a semi-detached house (2 residential units) in 3002 Purkersdorf, Austria.

Figure 51: Demonstration building in Purkersdorf [4]

The window frontage shown in Figure 51 is the south elevation of the two residential units, which are prominent with large south-facing window areas.

Results and discussion

Results from the measurement data of this demonstration object (Figure 52) show that the temperature can be maintained very well in the desired band (20°C to 24°C) and meets the temperature comfort parameters according to DIN EN ISO 7730:2005 [5].

Figure 52: Temperature curve in TOP 1 during the heating period

In summer, the object is deheated and the aim is to keep the living space temperate. As shown in Figure 53, this does not always work in particularly hot summer months. Due to the large south-facing window surfaces, the thermal energy input from solar radiation is higher than the cooling capacity, which is why the building heats up above the set temperature.

Figure 53: Temperature curve in TOP 1 during the cooling period

Further Projects

Another goal in the research project "TAB-Scale3 - Model development and validation for thermally activated building components (TAB) on a demo residential building for scale-up to multi-storey residential buildings" is the scale-up of the model and the application in further objects.

The "ALPENLAND-ZUKUNFTSHAUS-WOLKERSDORF" of the non-profit building, housing and settlement cooperative

Alpenland is planned to apply the prognosis-based control concept to all 8 residential units. Each housing unit will have its own controller and the users will be able to choose their individual comfort temperature in the apartment.

The Volkshilfehaus at Heiligenstädter Straße 172 is a mixed-use building intended to unite a variety of uses and user groups and serve as a social catalyst in the district. Due to the small-scale nature of the residential units, the forecast-based control design is executed in two zones: the east-facing half of the building from the ground floor to the top floor is considered as one unit (east zone) and the west-facing half of the building is considered as one zone (west zone). Both zones are considered separately and are each given a control unit.

The demo quarter "Campo Breitenlee" "living together" is located at Podhagskygasse and Hausfeldstraße in 1220 Vienna. The project is currently in the design phase and consists of 7 buildings with a gross floor area of approximately 30,652 m². In the course of the research project "ZQ3Demo - Implementation of urban future quarters with actor networking and legal-economic replicable solutions" (funded by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG in the course of the 8th call for proposals City of the Future - project number: 886997), 15 selected residential units will be equipped with the prognosis-based control concept and monitored in detail. 4 additional residential units will also be equipped with extensive measurement technology as reference apartments, but will be operated with the control system intended for the rest of the building.

In all these ongoing projects, extensions of the MPC concept as described above are to be tested in practice. For example, it will be determined in practice how the temperature flexibility in the default setting affects the operation of the MPC and whether, and to what extent, energy and cost savings are possible with this control.

References

- [1] Bundesministerium für Nachhaltigkeit und Tourismus, "Integrierter nationaler Energie- und Klimaplan für Österreich," *Report*, no. 663, 2019.
- [2] "Die österreichische Klimaschutzstrategie/Politik." https://www.oesterreich.gv.at/themen/bauen_wohnen_und_umwelt/klimaschutz/1/Seite.1000310.html (accessed Mar. 10, 2023).
- [3] Raspberry Pi Foundation, "Buy a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B – Raspberry Pi." <https://www.raspberrypi.com/products/raspberry-pi-3-model-b/> (accessed Mar. 10, 2023).
- [4] Technische Alternative, "UVR610K ohne Display UVR610K ohne Display > Frei programmierbare Regler > Produkte - Technische Alternative." <https://www.ta.co.at/x2-frei-programmierbare-regler/uvr610k-ohne-display/> (accessed Mar. 10, 2023).
- [5] Deutsches Institut für Normungen, "DIN EN ISO 7730:2005," 2005. <https://www.din.de/de/meta/suche/62730!search?query=DIEN+EN+ISO+7730> (accessed Mar. 10, 2023).

Sani60ies - Facade-integrated component activation for buildings

T. Keller^{1*}, M. Wolf¹, B. Kling¹, T. Pröll¹

1: Dept. of Material Sciences and Process Engineering, Institute of Chemical and Energy Engineering, University of Natural and Life Sciences Vienna, Austria

* Corresponding author: thomas.keller@boku.ac.at

Keywords: Buildings, Heatpumps, Heating, Cooling, Efficiency

Research field: Heatpumps in building applications

Introduction

Climate change poses challenges for urban settlements in many respects. Reducing CO₂ emissions is the key to limiting the advance of temperature rise. The energy transition can only succeed with a heat transition. In Austria, the building sector is responsible for 16.2% of total greenhouse gas emissions [1] or about a quarter of final energy consumption [2]. By 2040, the complete phase-out of fossil fuels for space heating is to be achieved. In the heat supply, the numerous households heated with gas, more than 400,000 in Vienna alone, represent a particular challenge.

District heating or heat pump applications are particularly suitable as alternative systems for heat supply in urban areas. To ensure efficient operation of heat pumps, the installation of low-temperature systems, such as wall or floor heating, is necessary. Low-temperature systems raise the efficiency of heat pumps and allow the diverse use of different heat sources. Energy, in the form of geothermal heat, ambient heat, heat from groundwater or industrial waste heat, can thus be used efficiently for space heating and domestic hot water heating. In practice, however, the installation of these systems in existing buildings is associated with high costs and structural interventions for the occupants.

Thermal activation of the facade

The "Sani60ies" project develops and demonstrates a minimally invasive and socially acceptable solution approach. By thermally activating the facade of the exterior wall, the advantages of component activation can be implemented in existing buildings without having to roughly interfere with the tenants' living space. In the course of the project, the concept will be implemented and tested in three demonstration objects. These are standard multi-party buildings from the 1950s and 1960s respectively and thus represent classic examples of buildings that are still supplied with fossil energy and are awaiting renovation.

From the scientific side, the topic of facade heating and activated facades has been studied for a long time. In practice, the concept of the functional facade was first implemented as early as 1974. In Kirchlergarn, the company Ottensmeier Ingenieure GmbH attached the heating pipes to the outer wall with the help of a timber frame construction and insulated the cavity with blow-in insulation material [3]. Since then, the applicability of low-temperature and facade systems has been researched in various projects. [4, 5, 6, 7, 8]

Figure 54 shows the thermal activation of the facade in one of the project's demonstration buildings. Notches are milled into the exterior facade, in which a pipe (20x2mm) is then installed for thermal activation. The pipeline is plastered and thermal insulation

is then applied over the facade. The heat is provided by a heat pump in the basement of the house, which is fed by a ground probe field. In summer, heat is extracted from the facade for cooling, which in turn regenerates the geothermal probe field. Although the building has a suitable flat facade, the existing wall is constructed of Durisol stone, which has low thermal conductivity. This is disadvantageous for our application because it hinders the heat transfer from the facade to the interior of the building.

Figure 54: Thermal activation of the facade, Große Neugasse 25, 1050 Vienna

Overall, the general advantages of the approach are:

- Low temperature level thanks to component activation, resulting in higher efficiency for heat pumps
- No intervention in the living space of the residents necessary
- Cooling possibility during summer (sometimes even necessary with geothermal probes for regeneration)

Piping and Heat flow

In the course of renovation and pipe laying, temperature sensors were installed at different heights on two sides of the house in order to compare the actual effects and characteristics of the temperature in the facade with the results of calculations and simulations. The position of the temperature sensors and the laying pattern of the pipes on a wall in Gr. Neugasse (1040, Vienna) are shown in Figure 55.

In order to quantify the expected heat flows to the inside (benefits) and outside (losses), a heat flow analysis was carried out with the program Therm [10] (a program for thermal bridge calculation based on the finite element method, see Figure 56), starting from values from the literature [9] and simple heat transfer calculations (plane, multi-layer wall). The results were used for the suitability of the system, as well as for the dimensioning of the components for the heat supply.

Figure 55: Arrangement of the piping in the facade (red) and positions of temperature sensors (green) on one wall

Using the simulation programs IPSEpro [11] and IDA ICE [12], various calculations were performed to determine statically the thermohydraulic parameters of the system and dynamically the behavior in terms of energy consumption and comfort. Especially the dynamic building simulation offers an excellent tool to compare in detail the influences not only of the spatial conditions (orientation N/S/O/W), but also of different measures (refurbishment with/without facade activation, external sun protection, etc.).

Conclusion

Externally mounted facade heating systems can be used to replace gas systems with electricity powered systems for efficient space heating. The approach can also be combined with heat pumps for the domestic hot water generation. In addition, with regard to the increasingly warm summer months ahead, the facade can also be used to cool the building, either by taking the energy for the domestic hot water from the facade (although the cooling effect for this scenario is limited to the amount of energy for generating hot water) or by using the geothermal probes as a heat sink.

Nonetheless, it must be considered whether the conditions of the building allow a reasonable implementation.

Requirements and limiting factors:

- Heat transfer coefficient of the existing wall:
The greater the insulating effect of the existing wall, the more inefficient the wall heating will be. We consider the limit of a reasonable application at a thermal conductivity of the existing wall of about 1W/(m²K)
- Building geometry and additions
There must be sufficient flat, free facade area that can be thermally activated. Loggias, balconies and the like represent an obstacle.
- Venting possibilities in the pipe system
Air can accumulate at high points in the pipelines, which can reduce or completely prevent flow through individual strands. At these points, it is recommended to install vents, but this is not always easy to implement structurally.
- Statics of the existing wall
- Sufficient insulation above the activated facade
- Suitable space and accessibility of the distribution lines for the piping system

Figure 56: Heat flow analysis in Therm; left: simplified wall structure as input, right: Temperature distribution

References

- [1] Umweltbundesamt 2021. Klimaschutzbericht 2021. Wien
- [2] Europäische Kommission 2021. EU Energy in Figures. Statistical Pocketbook 2021. Brüssel
- [3] energynet.de. So wird die Fassade zu einem Teil der Haustechnik (accessed 14.2.2023) <https://www.energinet.de/2018/09/13/fassade-haustechnik/>
- [4] XU, X., WANG, S., WANG, J. & XIAO, F. 2010. Active pipe-embedded structures in buildings for utilizing low-grade energy sources: A review. Energy and Buildings, 42, 1567-1581.
- [5] ZHU, L., YANG, Y., CHEN, S. & SUN, Y. 2019. Thermal performances study on a façade-built-in two-phase thermosyphon loop for passive thermo-activated building system. Energy Conversion and Management, 199, 112059.
- [6] ZHU, Q., XU, X., GAO, J. & XIAO, F. 2015. A semi-dynamic model of active pipe-embedded building envelope for thermal performance evaluation. International Journal of Thermal Sciences, 88, 170-179.
- [7] XIE, J.-L., ZHU, Q.-Y. & XU, X.-H. 2012. An active pipe-embedded building envelope for utilizing low-grade energy sources. Journal of Central South University, 19, 1663-1667.
- [8] Hinterseer, S. 2019. Smart Skin - Salzburger Multifunktionsfassade: Ergebnisbericht. Salzburg
- [9] Schmidt, C.W. 2019. Feldtest und dynamische Simulation der außenliegenden Wandtemperierung.
- [10] Therm: <https://windows.lbl.gov/software/therm>
- [11] SimTech, IPSEpro: <https://www.simtechnology.com/cms/ipsepro-menu/ipse-pro>
- [12] Equa, IDA ICE: <https://equa.se/de/ida-ice>

Implementation of thermodynamic properties of working fluids in IPSEpro - a workaround for freeze-drying simulations

T. Keller^{1*}, M. Wolf¹, T. Pröll¹

1: Dept. of Material Sciences and Process Engineering, Institute of Chemical and Energy Engineering, University of Natural and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria

* Corresponding author: thomas.keller@boku.ac.at

Keywords: Freeze Drying, Lyophilization, Refrigeration, Simulation

Research field: Lyophilization in Pharmaceuticals

Figure 57: Schematic of a vertically arranged badge freeze dryer [1]

Introduction

Freeze-drying is used to dry products that wouldn't endure thermal drying, like food or various pharmaceuticals.

A usual production plant consists of two chambers, which can be aligned horizontally or vertically, as depicted in Figure 54. One chamber contains the product, that is frozen, vacuum is applied and then thermal energy is added resulting in the sublimation of the products solvent, which usually consists of water (see Figure 58). The second chamber, called the cold trap, has the function to resublimates the solvent, to continuously remove the vaporized solvent from the chamber and maintain the vacuum. Therefore, cooling at very low temperatures (up to -80°C) and low pressure (vacuum at $\sim 0,1\text{mbar}$) with simultaneous heating is required for freeze-drying. The process can take several days and is very energy consuming with low efficiencies and little changes since 80 years. [3]

Since for these processes the value of the product is astronomical compared to the cost for energy per cycle, plants can, depending on the product, pay for themselves with just a few batch runs. Therefore, the main focus has always been process stability and safety, while efficiency was not of high importance for these systems so far [3]. Hopes are, that this will change in the future due to a stronger focus on energy consumption in all areas. Current research trends in this area are, to give some examples, concerned with general efficiency considerations of established processes [4], moving from batch to continuous processing [5], controlled nucleation [6] or spin-freezing [7]. Goal of our project is the techno-economic optimization of a pharmaceutical badge freeze dryer, with focus on the refrigeration system.

Figure 58: Freeze-drying process depicted in the Phase diagram of water [2]

The main resource of the project will be measured data from a lab scale test plant, provided by our project partners. Process Simulation with IPSEpro, a software from SimTech working with Mass- and Energy-Balances, will be used for calculations to evaluate the potential of optimization ideas.

For the process simulation in IPSEpro it is necessary to have the thermodynamic properties of the used working fluid (also called refrigerant) implemented in the software in form of functions. This happens for a limited selection by the publisher of the software. On the very changing market for refrigerants, where many of the classically used refrigerants are gradually losing their approval for environmental reasons, functions of the substance data are often not available. The refrigerant R452A, for example, as used in a prototype plant of our project partners, was not included in the standard library. However, even for refrigerants with thermodynamic properties available in IPSEpro, difficulties can arise during the simulation for freeze drying, because the functions used do not cover low temperatures below -80°C . Therefore, a methodology was developed to integrate thermodynamic property data from external sources.

Implementation of thermodynamic properties via DLL

IPSEpro asks for functions packed in a DLL, as well as their derivatives after the contained variables. Instead of the derivatives of the functions there is also the possibility that IPSEpro replaces the derivatives by perturbation of the function. The abbreviation DLL stands for "Dynamic Link Library", so-called dynamic program libraries. These are files that can contain code and data. The problem of substance data implementation has already been treated in the work of M. Mondejar [8]. In it, the basic structure of a DLL that can provide functions for IPSEpro is also described. Furthermore, an approach is explained how the functions for the calculation of substance data from the DLL of REFPROP can be addressed directly via a DLL as a connecting link.

In our approach, the thermodynamic properties of a working fluid from REFPROP are packaged in tabular form, which IPSEpro accesses via our own programmed DLL [9]. Functions for entropy, temperature, density, specific volume, enthalpy and saturated vapor temperature as functions of different parameters are generated. With one unknown which is determined from two variables, linear interpolation must be performed from four values from the respective table. This is done in two steps, as shown in Figure 59. For some material parameters, more complex functions had to be formulated (e.g. for strong discontinuities at phase boundaries), the explanation of which is beyond the scope of this abstract.

Figure 59: Linear interpolation from four table values

Figure 60 shows the sequence of a function call from IPSEpro via the DLL to the corresponding table on the basis of the entropy as a function of pressure and temperature. Roughly speaking, the DLL provides external functions which can be called by IPSEpro. As soon as this happens, within the DLL, after possible conversion of the units and exception handling, the return value is determined from the tables and returned to IPSEpro as result.

Figure 60: Schematic of a DLL function call from IPSEpro

Results

The results of the table-based functions were compared with the direct function values from the data source (REFPROP). To give an example, Figure 61 shows the tested range for the density function as a function of pressure and enthalpy. Pressure was tested between 0.188 and 9.788bar in 0.4bar steps, while for enthalpy values between 101 and 218kJ/kg were sampled in 3kJ/kg steps.

Figure 61: Test range for the density function of the DLL; largest error point is marked with a circle, with the dotted line showing the test sequence in which it occurred

The largest error occurs in the two-phase region just behind the boiling line, where the density drops sharply. It should be mentioned that the total density in the two-phase region is calculated using the vapor content and the density values of the gas and liquid phases, because a simple interpolation from tabulated density values would be too inaccurate in this region. Figure 62 shows the test series with

the largest error, marked with a circle. The enthalpy is varied at constant pressure (4.988bar), with the largest error in the two-phase region occurring at 197kJ/kg. The maximum absolute deviation between the REFPROP data and the data from the DLL is 5.5kg/m³ with a density value of 528kg/m³, which corresponds to a deviation of about 1%.

Figure 62: Diagram for the test run of the density function, largest error point is marked

To conclude, it is possible as a workaround to incorporate substance data into IPSEpro through the use of tables via DLL with reasonable accuracy.

References

- [1] Peter Haseley (2018). Freeze-drying: Third, completely revised and enlarged edition. 3. Aufl. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH
- [2] Barnalab, Online (accessed 30.3.2023): <https://www.barnalab.com/en/what-about-freeze-drying/>
- [3] Agnes Shanley (2017). Modernizing Lyophilization. Pharmaceutical Technology, Volume 41, Issue 12, pp. 46-47
- [4] Ana Gabriela Renteria Gamiz, et al. (2019) Analysis of a pharmaceutical batch freeze dryer: resource consumption, hotspots, and factors for potential improvement. Drying Technology, 37:12, pp. 1563-1582, DOI: 10.1080/07373937.2018.1518916
- [5] Roberto Pisano, et al. (2019). Achieving Continuous Manufacturing in Lyophilization: Technologies and Approaches. European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics, vol. 142, 2019, pp. 265–79, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2019.06.027>.
- [6] Roberto Pisano (2019). Alternative Methods of Controlling Nucleation in Freeze Drying. Lyophilization of Pharmaceuticals and Biologicals: New Technologies and Approaches. K. R. Ward and P. Matejtschuk. New York, NY, Springer New York: 79-111.
- [7] Laurens De Meyer, et al. (2015). Evaluation of Spin Freezing Versus Conventional Freezing as Part of a Continuous Pharmaceutical Freeze-Drying Concept for Unit Doses. International Journal of Pharmaceutics, vol. 496, no. 1, 2015, pp. 75–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2015.05.025>.
- [8] Maria Mondejar (2015). User guide for developed DLLs for real fluid property models in IPSEpro process simulator.
- [9] Thomas Keller (2019). Modellierung eines kältetechnischen Prozesses zur Gefriertrocknung mit dem Kältemittel R452A, Diplomarbeit, TU Wien

A field test – Actively cooled double jacket, tubular reactor for catalytic methanation of biogas

K. Salbrechter^{1*}, M. Lehner¹

¹: Dept. of Environmental Engineering and Process Technology, Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria

* Corresponding author: katrin.salbrechter@unileoben.ac.at

Keywords: methanation, tubular reactors, heat management, biogas upgrading, SNG

Research field: Catalytic methanation, reactor cooling

Introduction

Respecting the fluctuating and periodical nature of renewable energy sources like wind and solar power, innovative energy storage solutions are required to ensure grid stability and reliability of supply. The conversion of renewable energy into gaseous or liquid fuels can be summarized as Power-to-Gas (PtG) or Power-to-Liquid (PtL) concepts. PtG enables the transformation of electrical into storable chemical energy in gaseous carries like hydrogen or synthetic natural gas (SNG). [1] Catalytic methanation is described by the Sabatier reaction [2] (see Equation 1), which is a highly exothermic reaction favored by low operating temperatures and high operating pressures:

As carbon sources, CO₂ from combustion, fermentation, like biogas, or syngas can be used. [3] For catalytic methanation different reactor set-ups are available which need to ensure stable operating performance. PtG plant layouts with multi staged fixed bed reactors are an established concept that is already realized in demonstration and commercial scale (e.g. Lurgi [4], TREMP [5]). Also dynamic operation of adiabatic fixed bed reactors with intermediate cooling and gas recirculation has been utilized in commercial plants [6] whereas heat management remains challenging due to thermal runaways. Even cooled reactor systems for enhanced methanation performance are designed by e.g. Linde but have never been brought to commercial scale [7]. Only scarce and little information about the thermal management of methanation reactors is available. Lefebvre et al. models the performance of a cooled tube bundle reactor at steady state operation as this set up facilitates higher catalyst loads as e.g. slurry bubble column reactors [8]. The challenge of operating fixed bed reactors for methanation consists in heat management as temperature hot spots and high gas output temperatures thermodynamically limit full conversion of CO₂ from the feed gas and load flexibility is little or not given [9].

Montanuniversität Leoben (MUL) operates a fixed bed reactor cascade which has been further extended, updated and improved in its heat management. Since 2022, an actively cooled double jacket reactor has been tested with synthetically mixed feed gases under varying process conditions.

Also in 2022, the first demonstration plant of catalytic methanation has been erected in Gabersdorf (Styria) in the frame of the project “Renewable Gasfield”. MUL operates its own research plant in bigger pilot scale also on this project site.

Both methanation plants in Gabersdorf – the commercially operated demo plant and the research plant of MUL - upgrade biogas directly via catalytic methanation, as the biogas is priorly purified

from catalyst poisons such as ammonia and sulfur components. However, the CO₂ is not separated upstream the methanation. The product gas contains mainly methane and hydrogen and is fed into the local natural gas grid.

The modular container plant from MUL consists out of two reactor stages with two actively cooled double jacket tubular reactors with intermediate condensation. The second reactor stage guarantees full CO₂ conversion to meet the gas grid injection quality criteria, whereas mainly the performance after the first reactor stage is evaluated. First results of these experiments will be available after the first quarter of 2023.

Objective

The central purpose of this work is an experimental performance validation of cooled double jacket reactors for direct biogas upgrading via catalytic methanation. Two different reactors are featured with a reduced inner diameter (14 and 18 mm) and are equipped with an active cooling in the outer tube. Experimental test runs are conducted with commercial bulk catalyst, varying inlet gas flow rates and at different pressure levels. Higher turbulences are expected with higher gas flows resulting in enhanced heat and mass transfer for better thermal management of the exothermic reaction. Evaluation criteria comprise the achieved CO₂ conversion rate of the first reactor stage and the measured axial temperature profile in the reactor. The results of the experimental test runs serve as a basis for further development of a design optimized methanation reactor. Further-reaching test runs will be conducted with the just mentioned, optimized reactor in the mobile methanation plant for the direct upgrading of purified biogas in two reactor stages to accomplish quality feed-in criteria for SNG grid injection.

Methods

Before field tests are conducted on the project site in Gabersdorf (Styria) with the mobile methanation plant, comparable test runs have been carried out in the pilot plant at the Chair of Process Technology at MUL. The peripheral plant components, as the gas dosing station, product gas conditioning and safety equipment (gas detectors and torch) are available from further plant set-ups. More details of the experimental set-up can be found in [10] and [11].

The laboratory pilot plant consists of one reactor stage that includes an actively cooled double jacket methanation reactor with the pipe dimensions according to Table 1. The reactors No. 1 and No. 2 have been tested in the laboratory plant at MUL, whereas reactor No. 3 is design optimized based on the experimental validation and will be intensively investigated in the mobile catalytic methanation plant in Gabersdorf.

Table 14: Dimensions of actively cooled tubular reactors in mm and further information

All in [mm]	No. 1	No. 2	No.3
Dimensions outer pipe	25x1	32x2	38x2
Dimensions inner pipe	18x2	22x2	22x2
Inner diameter d_i	14	18	18
Annular gap a	2.5	3	6
Catalyst bulk	3-4 mm pellets		
Catalyst bed height	600 mm	500 mm	600 mm
Tube-to-particle ratio	4	5.14	5.14
Installation site	MUL	MUL	Gabersdorf

The schematic illustration of reactors No. 1 and No. 2 can be seen in Figure 63. For both reactors, the total length is 980 mm and the tempered zone has a length of 700 mm. Also, a pre-heating zone of 100 mm is realized in front of the catalyst bulk to ensure sufficient reactant gas temperatures.

A temperature thermostat enables heating and cooling in the outer jacket with a thermal oil up to 320 °C. Eight, centrally positioned thermocouples from Type K measure the axial temperature profile. The catalyst bulk consists of 3-4 mm pellets from a commercial methanation catalyst supplier. The bed height varies in each reactor set-up as given in Table 14. In reactor No. 2 the bed height is slightly reduced as the catalyst volume still increases minimally due to the bigger inner diameter. With the increased catalyst volume and the available gas supply at MUL, high gas hourly space velocities can be examined also in reactor No. 2.

Figure 63: Schematic illustration of the double jacket reactors with a total length of 980 mm with the in- and outlet fittings for the thermal oil and temperature measuring points (left: 14 mm reactor with 600 mm catalyst bed with thermocouples (round markers); right: 18 mm reactor with 500 mm catalyst bed and thermocouples (diamond markers))

An important factor to control the performance of a tubular fixed-bed reactor is the tube-particle diameter ratio. Andrigo [12] states that lower diameter ratios of 4 to 5 counter hot spot formation in fixed beds while exothermic reactions take place. In this case, the tube-to-particle diameter ratio assuming an average catalyst pellet diameter of 3.5 mm is 4 for the 14 mm reactor (No. 1) and 5.14 for the 18 mm reactors (No. 2 and No. 3). Also, the temperature of the heat transfer medium (here thermal oil) plays an important role to obtain optimum operating parameters and to suppress thermal run away.

As an input, a typical biogas mixture with a composition of 52 vol.% CH₄ and 48 vol.% CO₂ is fed with an over-stoichiometric hydrogen feed (4 % above methanation stoichiometry). The methanation performance has been validated in each reactor with the same feed gas mixture at different pressure levels (4, 6, 8 and 10 bar) and gas hourly space velocities (GHSV) of 4 000, 6 000, 8 000, 10 000, 12 000, 15 000 and 20 000 h⁻¹. The temperature of the cooling medium was 320 °C.

In the mobile, modular plant of MUL in Gabersdorf, the cooled fixed bed reactor with an inner diameter of 18 mm will be installed because higher gas loads can be fed into the reactor (theoretically up to 55 000 h⁻¹ counting for the first reactor stage) thanks to the available amount of biogas and green hydrogen. Due to the increase of the feed gas mix to nearly a threefold, the cooling zone is prolonged to 900 mm and the catalyst bulk is prolonged to 600 mm. These dimensions are a practical length for future reactor dimensioning on commercial scale. Purified biogas from the neighboring biogas plant will be upgraded to synthetic natural gas which is fed into the grid on site. The results of the experimental investigation up to a theoretically possible GHSV of 55 000 h⁻¹ will be shown in the oral presentation.

Results

The following beam diagram (Figure 64) clustered by GHSV and two reactor dimensions (14 vs 18 mm inner diameter) shows achieved CO₂ conversion rates at 8 bar operating pressure in the pilot plant at the Chair of Process Technology at MUL.

Figure 64: CO₂ conversion rates of biogas methanation with 4 % hydrogen surplus at 8 bar operating pressure for tubular cooled reactors with an inner diameter of 14 mm and 18 mm at different catalyst loads

In the 14 mm reactor with 600 mm catalyst bed height, the CO₂ conversion rate remains on a very high level although the catalyst load has been increased to a fivefold (from 4 000 h⁻¹ to 20 000 h⁻¹).

Also, the 18 mm reactor with 500 mm catalyst bed height achieves slightly lower but still high CO₂ conversion rates at all catalyst loads. At 20 000 h⁻¹, 97.6 % in the 14mm and 94.7 % in the 18mm reactor of CO₂ is converted while at lower gas hourly space velocities e.g. 4 000 h⁻¹ even 99.7 and 99.4 % of CO₂ is converted, in the two reactors, respectively.

In Figure 65, the axial temperature profile of the 14 mm reactor with a catalyst bed height of 600 mm (grey shaded area) is shown. The gas inlet temperature was measured in the 100 mm long pre-heating zone with the thermocouple TI2 (see left side Figure 63). During the experiments with the 14 mm reactor the sixth thermocouple (TI 6) broke. Therefore, TI3 to TI7 are shown in the following axial temperature profile (see Figure 65).

Figure 65: Axial temperature profile of experimentally determined data in the 14 mm diameter reactor with a catalyst bed height of

It can be shown that higher gas hourly space velocities lead to lower peak temperatures in the catalyst bed due to enhanced heat and mass transfer by higher turbulences. At 4 000 h⁻¹, the feed gas can be heated up to 170 °C in the pre-heating zone, whereas at 20 000 h⁻¹ the feed gas mix cools down due to higher gas velocities to roughly 51 °C. At higher catalyst loads (15 000 h⁻¹ and above) the maximum tolerable catalyst temperature of 510 °C is undershot which is favorable for long-term stability and activity of the catalyst. A small rise in temperature can be seen in the middle of the catalyst bulk at around 30 cm at 20 000 h⁻¹ as the main reaction zone is shifted downstream the catalyst bed. The cooling effect of the thermal oil can be seen through the quick drop of temperature behind the temperature peak (e.g. at 15 000 h⁻¹) as it approaches the cooling temperature of 320 °C at around 15 cm in the catalyst bed.

In Figure 66 the axial temperature profile of the 18 mm reactor with a catalyst bed height of 500 mm (grey shaded area) is shown. The gas inlet temperature was measured in the 100 mm long pre-heating zone with TI3. The thermocouples TI4 to TI6 show the temperature in the catalyst bed and TI7 the gas output temperature (see Figure 63).

Figure 66: Axial temperature profile of experimentally determined data in the 18 mm diameter reactor with a catalyst bed height of 500 mm

In comparison to the 14 mm reactor, the cooling effect at higher catalyst loads and the following minimization of temperature hot spots in the catalyst bed cannot be observed. At the lowest gas hourly space velocity, the maximum temperature in the catalyst bed is roughly 400 °C. In contrast to the 14 mm reactor, the maximum temperature in the catalyst bed increases with higher GHSV. The measured temperature peak at 10 000 h⁻¹ with roughly 500 °C is marginally lower than the maximum tolerable catalyst temperature of 510 °C. At even higher gas hourly space velocities, the temperature peak is rising further up to 560 °C at 20 000 h⁻¹.

The annular gap for the cooling medium is 2.5 mm in the 14 mm reactor, it is just slightly bigger in the 18 mm reactor with 3 mm. Too small quantities of the cooling medium and too little turbulences in the outer jacket result in insufficient radial heat removal and lead to heat accumulation in the catalyst bed.

Conclusion and Outlook

Fixed bed reactors for catalytic methanation are characterized by challenging heat management. Especially in industrial scale applications stable operation without thermal runaway needs to be ensured. Two different cooled double jacket reactor set-ups with an inner diameter of 14 and 18 mm have been tested in a methanation pilot plant at MUL under varying operation parameters such as pressure level and catalyst load. As feed, a typical synthetic biogas mixture with a hydrogen surplus of 4% to stoichiometry has been used. The CO₂ conversion rate and the measured temperature profile in the catalyst bed are used as evaluation parameters.

The highest CO₂ conversion rates can be achieved in the thinnest reactor with an inner diameter of 14 mm. At all catalyst loads, from 4 000 to 20 000 h⁻¹, the conversion rate is between 99.7 and 97.6 %. Moreover, at high gas hourly space velocities, such as 15 000 and 20 000 h⁻¹, the maximum measured temperature in the reactor is below 510 °C which is specified as the maximum acceptable catalyst temperature during operation. The reactor set-up with an inner diameter of 18 mm achieves slightly lower conversion rates (between 99.4 and 94.7% from 4 000 to 20 000 h⁻¹) with one reactor stage. As the low conversion rate of 94.7% indicates, high gas temperatures are measured with a maximum of nearly 550 °C at 20 000 h⁻¹ that thermodynamically limit the conversion rate due to

high gas outlet temperatures.

In the mobile methanation plant in Gabersdorf, the 18 mm reactor will be installed in both reactor stages because of its better practical applicability to insert eight thermocouples in the catalyst bulk as the pellets diameters is 3.5 mm in average. Also, the cooling zone and the catalyst bed height are prolonged to 900 and 600 mm, respectively. Due to the measured temperature peaks above 500 °C at gas hourly space velocities beyond 10 000 h⁻¹, the annular gap for the cooling medium is enlarged from 3 to 6 mm.

It is aimed to determine sweet spots for optimal operation parameter at high but varying catalyst loads while undershooting the maximum tolerable catalyst temperature. Even higher catalyst loads (values from 25 000 up to 55 000 h⁻¹) will be evaluated to observe limited hot spots and an enhanced cooling effect from higher turbulences in the gas phase. An enlargement of the annular gap to 6 mm increases the amount of circulated cooling medium that is supposed to result in an improved radial heat transfer. Another opportunity to limit temperature hot spots in the catalyst bed incorporates the minimization of the cooling medium temperature down to 250 °C. A further decrease is not possible as it undercuts the kick-off temperature for methanation, and kinetics are inhibited. Furthermore, the operating pressure can be lowered at the expense of worse kinetic conditions. In the modular plant, pressure tuning may lead to lower CO₂ conversion rates in the first reactor stage, but a second reactor stage enables sufficient conversion rates to achieve recent natural gas injection requirements of Austria [13] with maximum 10 vol.% H₂. The obtained results from the experimental test runs in Gabersdorf will be presented at the Minisymposium 2023.

References

- [1] M. Bailera, P. Lisbona, L. M. Romeo, and S. Espatolero, "Power to Gas projects review: Lab, pilot and demo plants for storing renewable energy and CO₂," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 69, pp. 292–312, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.130.
- [2] J. S. P. Sabatier, *Comptes Rendu Hebdomadaires des Seances del Academie des Scences*. "New Synthesis of Methane", 134th ed., 1902.
- [3] F. Gutiérrez-Martín, L. M. Rodríguez-Antón, and M. Legrand, "Renewable power-to-gas by direct catalytic methanation of biogas," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 162, pp. 948–959, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2020.08.090.
- [4] J. Kopyscinski, T. J. Schildhauer, and S. M. Biollaz, "Production of synthetic natural gas (SNG) from coal and dry biomass – A technology review from 1950 to 2009," *Fuel*, vol. 89, no. 8, pp. 1763–1783, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2010.01.027.
- [5] H. Thunman *et al.*, "Advanced biofuel production via gasification - lessons learned from 200 man-years of research activity with Chalmers' research gasifier and the GoBiGas demonstration plant," *Energy Sci Eng*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 6–34, 2018, doi: 10.1002/ese3.188.
- [6] Stefan Rönsch, Steffi Matthischke, Markus Müller, and Philipp Eichler, "Dynamische Simulation von Reaktoren zur Festbettmethanisierung," (in German), *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 8, no. 86, pp. 1198–1204, 2014, doi: 10.1002/cite.201300046.
- [7] W. Herrmann, B. Cornils, H. Zanthoff, and J.-H. Xu, *Catalysis from A to Z*: Wiley, 2019.
- [8] J. Lefebvre, S. Bajohr, and T. Kolb, "Modeling of the transient behavior of a slurry bubble column reactor for CO₂ methanation, and comparison with a tube bundle reactor," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 151, pp. 118–136, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2019.11.008.
- [9] M. Lehner, P. Biegger, and A. R. Medved, "Power-to-Gas: Die Rolle der chemischen Speicherung in einem Energiesystem mit hohen Anteilen an erneuerbarer Energie," *Elektrotech. Inftech.*, vol. 134, no. 3, pp. 246–251, 2017, doi: 10.1007/s00502-017-0502-6.
- [10] A. Krammer, A. Medved, M. Peham, P. Wolf-Zöllner, K. Salbrechter, and M. Lehner, "Dual Pressure Level Methanation of Co-SOEC Syngas," *Energy Technol.*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 2000746, 2021, doi: 10.1002/ente.202000746.
- [11] F. Kirchbacher, P. Biegger, M. Miltner, M. Lehner, and M. Harasek, "A new methanation and membrane based power-to-gas process for the direct integration of raw biogas – Feasibility and comparison," *Energy*, vol. 146, pp. 34–46, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2017.05.026.
- [12] P. Andrigo, "Fixed bed reactors," *Catalysis Today*, vol. 52, 2-3, pp. 197–221, 1999, doi: 10.1016/S0920-5861(99)00076-0.
- [13] *Erdgas in Österreich - Gasbeschaffenheit ÖVGW G B210*, ÖVGW Österreichische Vereinigung für das Gas- und Wasserfach, Jun. 2021.

Characterisation and gasification of waste wood fractions in a staged process

Michael Kresta^{1,2*}, David Gurtner^{1,2}, Angela Hofmann^{1,2}, Christoph Pfeifer³

1. Josef Ressel Centre for the production of powdered activated carbon from municipal residues, Department of Environmental, Process and Energy Engineering, MCI–The Entrepreneurial School, Universitaetsstrasse 15, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria
2. Institute of Chemical and Energy Engineering, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Gregor-Mendel-Straße 33, 1180 Vienna, Austria
3. Department of Environmental, Process and Energy Engineering, MCI–The Entrepreneurial School, Universitaetsstraße 15, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

* Corresponding author: michael.kresta@mci.edu

Keywords: Waste wood, Gasification, Pyrolysis, Wood gas

Research field: Waste wood gasification

Abstract

Wood as raw material is gaining in popularity in recent years and with it the amount of resulting waste wood at the end of serviceability. This, as well as other municipal woody residues, represent a great potential for energy use and is preferable to landfilling.

The main objective of this work is the utilization of municipal wood residues such as waste wood, tree cuttings, etc. (AI – AIII), for the generation of electricity and heat by gasification. The analysis of the potential and the properties of the new waste wood resource show significant differences between waste wood and wood chips from forest residues, the current standard material of Syncraft plants. Experiments on autothermal pyrolysis show a lower mechanical stability as well as a smaller particle size of the resulting waste wood pyrolysis char. In turn, this leads to destabilization of the floating fixed bed when it is integrated into the gasification reactor. Geometrical modifications of the gasification reactor and an adjustment of the process control become necessary. These modifications show a stable operation of the gasifier with waste wood achieving a constant wood gas quality. Gasification temperature and biomass feeding rate are investigated and their effects on the composition of the wood gas are measured by gas analysis. A nitrogen balance is used to determine the cold gas efficiency volume flow of produced wood gas. The cold gas efficiency exceeds the reference case using forest residue wood chips. Further adaptations are aimed at a maximization of the calorific value of the resulting product gas, as well as the maximization of the fuel conversion and thus the product gas quantity.

Introduction

In view of the increasingly urgent climate crisis and current political developments, alternatives to fossil energy sources are becoming more and more necessary. The use of biomass as a renewable raw material is obvious. However, in the sense of cascading use, wood is preferably used as material. Waste wood (WW) results at the end of its materials lifetime. [1] Up to now, WW is stored in landfills or energetically used mainly by means of combustion for heat

generation. Sorting and recycling wood waste saves emissions by returning the material to the biomass stock and reducing the amount of waste stored in landfills or being burned. [2] Recycling waste avoids the mining and use of new primary raw materials, which on the one hand means conserving resources and on the other hand contributes to savings in CO₂ emissions. The worldwide use of recycled raw materials concretely helps countries to achieve their climate targets. [3] Röder and Thornley [4] performed life cycle assessments evaluating the climate change impacts (CO₂-equivalence) of energy production using WW. They show that waste wood of category AI and AII achieve reductions of up to 91 % and 81 % compared to the fossil fuel reference cases, using existing combined heat and power (CHP) incineration methods. In the case of higher polluted waste wood, emissions can exceed the reference cases in some options by up to 135% and only achieve limited emission reductions when replacing highly carbon intense energies. Introducing a waste wood gasification technology has the potential to reduce these emissions in all classes, as the gas produced is converted into CO₂ mostly.

Common feedstock used in gasification plants are coal and wood, but also residues like plastic waste, sewage sludge, rice husks, coconut shells. The use of waste wood as a feedstock has not, or only to a limited extent, been described in literature. Reasons might be the inhomogeneous chemical and physical properties of this feedstock.

Several publications have discussed the variability and heterogeneity of WW. Various works show efforts to characterize WW and link and identify different contamination classes to WW fractions [5–7]. There is research effort in the literature dealing with gasification and pyrolysis of waste from furniture production [8–12]. The gasification using waste wood at the end of materials lifetime is sparsely researched. Jamin et al. [13] studied the use of landfill wood wastes in lab-scale gasification. Littlejohns et al. [14] showed the realisation of landfill WW gasification in a small scale downdraft gasifier. Hwang et al. [15] used three types of wood wastes for lab-scale pyrolysis and steam gasification achieving a hydrogen rich product gas. Van der Meijden et al. [16] developed an allothermal bubbling fluidized bed 800 kW_{th} pilot plant operating with demolition wood.

There is also research in the literature on the approach of converting WW into a higher energy fuel prior to gasification

Table 15: Characterisation of biomass

Biomass	W _C / w%	W _H / w%	W _N / w%	W _{volatile} / w%	W _{fixed carbon} / w%	W _{wash} / w%	H _u / MJ kg ⁻¹
Forest Residue	50.0	6.34	0.56	80.9	17.8	1.28	17.01
Waste Wood 1	51.7	6.07	0.32	82.5	16.7	0.80	17.51
Waste Wood 2	49.0	6.34	0.80	82.7	16.4	0.83	16.09

Hansen et al. [17] used WW from a recycling centre to produce pyrolysis oil by flash pyrolysis for energetic recovery. Poudel et al. [18] used a comparable raw material to produce a solid energy carrier by torrefaction. Moreno and Font [19] investigated the global effect of the additives present in furniture wood waste collected from a municipal waste treatment plant during pyrolysis.

The main goal of this work is the realisation of WW gasification using a floating fixed bed process. The changeover to waste wood is a complex effort starting with the preparation of the resource itself. It is not possible to use a chipper for the size reduction of WW, as is the case with regular wood chips and FR. Because of the large proportion of impurities, shredders must be used. The reduction effect of shredders is based on the breaking and shattering of the material between fast rotating impact tools. This leads to needle-shaped and fringed particles consisting of torn wood fibres. Therefore, the whole process chain is adapted starting with the processing of the WW and identification of suitable WW fractions. The pyrolysis and gasification process is adapted to the new WW raw material aiming for a maximization of the heating value and amount of product gas. Different fractions are used in the gasification process and product gas quantity, energy content and efficiencies are evaluated. Several experiments are conducted at a gasification research site investigating the influence of gasification temperature and biomass feeding rate.

Materials and Methods

The research is based on the gasification pilot plant located on the premises of Stadtwerke Schwaz. The plant is operating with the floating fixed bed process developed by Syncraft. Pyrolysis and gasification are separated from each other both physically and temporally in a staged technology. The dried biomass is autothermally pyrolyzed with air prior to entering the gasification. In a vertical pyrolysis screw, the fuel particles move upwards and are carbonized simultaneously. The resulting char is transported to the gasification unit and the particles are carried along with an airflow upwards into the reactor. Due to the geometry of the reactor a floating fixed bed is formed. As the particles degrade, they move upwards through the bed. When they become small enough, the particles are carried along with the product gas. In a next step, they are separated in a hot gas filter and leave the process as gasification char. The product gas is cleaned in a washer prior to be used in a gas engine. This process is developed using forest residue (FR) wood chips. [19]

WW usually has a lower bulk density and a multimodal particle size distribution with a high proportion of fines. The chemical composition and physical properties also vary over a wide range due to aging effects and various pre-treatments, depending on the original use of the wood. Preliminary experiments on autothermal pyrolysis show a lower mechanical stability as well as a smaller particle size of the resulting waste wood pyrolysis char. This leads to a destabilisation of the floating fixed bed. Due to this reasons a change in the process control is necessary in order to establish a stable gasification process.

In the course of this work two different WW fractions and one fraction of forest residue (FR) wood chips are used. These different biomasses are characterised in *Table 15* regarding elemental and proximate composition. FR chips and waste wood fraction 1 (WW1) are obtained from a local wood processor. The FR chips represent the standard biomass for the Syncraft process. WW1 consist of mainly packaging wood (classes AI-AII). Waste wood fraction 2 (WW2) is obtained from the recycling centre Innsbruck and is composed of WW classes AI-AIII. *Table 16* sums up the bulk properties of the different biomass fractions used in this work.

Table 16: Bulk properties of biomass fractions

Biomass	ρ_{bulk} / kg m ⁻³	WH2O / %	d ₅₀ / mm	d<8 / w%	d>25 / w%
---------	--	-------------	-------------------------	-------------	--------------

FR	190.2	9.5	15.0	3.7	45.9
WW1	170.0	7.9	6.1	29.4	17.4
WW2	177.1	11.1	4.6	41.8	12.4

The WW fractions are characterised by a significantly lower median particle diameter and greatly increased fines content.

The gasification process is controlled with three main parameters: the fed mass flow of biomass \dot{m}_B , the temperature of the pyrolysis unit T_P , and the temperature of the gasification reactor T_G . The lambda value and volume flow of air are specified by the respective temperature.

In this work, the focus lies on the product wood gas. For reasons of comparability, these values are normalized to the supplied mass flow of biomass. The product wood gas flow is represented as the product wood gas yield; the amount of wood gas produced per kg of biomass V_{PG} in Nm³ kg⁻¹. The generated volume flow of product gas is calculated based on the nitrogen balance of the process, assuming nitrogen as an inert substance. The amount of nitrogen fed in form of pyrolysis and gasification air are known. The amount stored in the biomass and the resulting charcoal are determined with elemental analysis. With the measured nitrogen concentration, the product wood gas flow is calculated. The energy in the product gas is summed up as the energy yield EY_{PG} in kWh kg⁻¹. The energy stored in the product gas is calculated in form of the lower heating value H_U from the measured product wood gas composition with molar fractions of the wood gas components as follows [20]:

$$H_{U,n} = 282.98 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \cdot n_{CO} + 285.83 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \cdot n_{H_2} + 890.63 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \cdot n_{CH_4}$$

It is converted to a volumetric unit by dividing the value by the molar volume of ideal gases. In addition, the cold gas efficiency η_{CG} , the ratio of the net calorific value of product wood gas to the net calorific value of the corresponding consumed biomass, is calculated in percent. The heating value of the biomass is calculated based on the elemental composition according to Boie [21].

With the new, adapted process control developed for WW gasification a test series is first started with FR chips as a reference. These experiments are performed at standard conditions of the Syncraft process. These values represent the base line for the following WW experiments. For reasons of confidentiality, the exact values for gasification parameters as well as presented result values are given in relative terms. The standard operation conditions of a Syncraft gasifier (\dot{m}_B , T_P , T_G) represent 100%. All altered process conditions are displayed as percentage of these values. The calculated results – the gasification yield and efficiency values are presented as percentages of the baseline efficiencies achieved with FR in the preliminary experiments.

Previous investigations have shown that a lower pyrolysis temperature has a positive effect on the stability of the resulting pyrolysis char. Because of that, a lower pyrolysis temperature of 83% of the standard has been chosen for the WW gasification. Several experiments are conducted increasing the temperature and biomass feeding rate. In a next step, the resource is changed from WW1 to WW2. With higher content of fines, a stable process was hardly achievable. For this reason, the process control was changed and the reactor geometry was adapted. This mainly involves an increase in the angle of the reactor geometry. This new reactor is installed in the existing process and replaces the older one. Extensive experimental test runs investigate the influence of gasification temperature and biomass feeding rate on the gasification performance of WW.

Results and Discussion

The most important gasification reactions are endothermic. For this reason, the reaction temperature is one of the most relevant experimental parameters, which influence the performance of the gasifier. The reaction temperature was varied from 82% to 106%.

With the introduction of the new resource WW and changed process control, the process is initially operated with reduced power output. For this purpose, the biomass feed rate is reduced. The resulting product wood gas compositions of the gasification of WW1 at 67% biomass feeding rate and different temperatures are shown in *Table 17*. With the rise of the temperature, the concentration of CO increases due to the rate of the heterogeneous and endothermic reactions such as the water gas and Boudouard reaction. In addition the oxidation of carbon and partial oxidation of carbon forming CO₂ and CO are happening at the same time, whilst their extend depends on temperature. [13]

Table 17: Gas composition of WW1 at 67% biomass feeding rate depending on the gasification temperature

T_V / °C	CO / %	CO ₂ / %	CH ₄ / %	H ₂ / %	HU / MJ Nm ⁻³
82	9.4	17.9	2.4	9.7	3.1
88	11.7	16.0	2.2	8.9	3.2
94	12.7	15.0	2.0	8.9	3.3
100	13.2	14.6	1.8	8.9	3.3
106	14.1	13.6	1.6	9.1	3.3

As the temperature rises, the more exothermic reaction, being the oxidation of carbon is inhibited and the proportion of CO is predominant. [22] In addition the Boudouard reaction consumes CO₂, shifting the equilibrium towards CO at higher temperatures. This is visible by the increasing CO content with temperature, while the CO₂ content decreases. This phenomena is confirmed in literature, e.g. by Taba et al. [23]. The authors also attribute this to the increase in the rate of endothermic reactions. Since the methane-forming reactions are also exothermic, such as the hydrogenating gasification reaction of C and H₂ or the methanation reaction of CO and H₂, the proportion of methane also decreases with increasing temperature.

Figure 67 Gasification efficiencies of WW1 at 67% biomass feeding rate depending on the gasification temperature

Coupled with the relatively constant H₂ concentration, there is no major change in the heating value, only a slight increase with temperature from 3.1 MJNm⁻³ to 3.3 MJNm⁻³. The resulting gasification efficiencies, the product wood gas yield, the energy yield and the cold gas efficiency of these experiments are shown in *Figure 67*. The product wood gas yield increases with the temperature reaching 123.5% of the base line with FR at 106% of standard gasification temperature. This is explained by a higher conversion of the fuel as the higher temperatures drive the reaction kinetics and increase the amount of wood gas produced. At standard gasification temperature, the wood gas yield already exceeds the values of FR chips. The slightly higher content of carbon in the WW1 fraction (*Table 15*) could explain a higher carbon conversion compared to FR resulting in an increased production of wood gas. With no significant change in the heating value with the

temperature, the energy yield is directly linked to the wood gas yield. At standard gasification temperature, the energy yield remains below the reference value. However, this is attributable to the lower calorific value of the product wood gas using WW. At elevated temperature of 106%, the energy yield exceeds the base line reaching 108.6%.

The cold gas efficiency increases with the temperature even with constant heating value due to the higher product wood gas yield. The highest value is reached at 106% of standard gasification temperature with 91.4% of the base value. However, the cold gas efficiency remains behind the base value with FR chips despite higher wood gas and energy yield. A further increase of the gasification temperature becomes technically unfeasible as the limits of ash softening are reached.

In summary, the higher temperature is beneficial for waste wood gasification and leads to higher efficiencies. For this reason, this elevated temperature of 106% is chosen for further experiments.

Figure 68: Gasification efficiencies of WW1 at 106% gasification temperature

In the next set of experiments, the biomass feeding rate was increased to 80% and 112% at the elevated temperature. The gasification efficiencies depending on the biomass feeding rate are shown in *Figure 68*. The increase in the supplied biomass flow rate shows that the cold gas efficiency can be maintained even with increased output. The wood gas yield slightly decreases. One reason for this may be a reduced contact time of the reaction partners as the higher mass of fuel in the reactor leads to a higher airflow to maintain the lambda value. This increased volume flow also leads to higher velocities in the reactor. This decreases the contact time of air with the fuel particles and increases the amount of discharged gasification char. Higher energy yields are the result of higher heating values of the product wood gas in these experiments. Whether this is an influence of the residence time or deviations in the measurements must be clarified with further experiments. Noticeable are increased CO concentrations at increased power output.

A further increase of the cold gas efficiency with WW has not been achievable with the existing reactor. With the changeover to the new fraction WW2 with WW from the classes AI-AIII and even higher content of fines a stable process control was hardly achievable. Because of this, a new reactor geometry has been designed and implemented into the existing process replacing the old one. The first experiments investigated increasing the biomass feeding rate at the elevated gasification temperature for WW.

Figure 69: Gasification efficiencies of WW2 at 106% gasification temperature with new reactor design

The cold gas efficiency clearly exceeds the base values achieved with FR chips used in the old reactor. This shows the better suitability of the new geometry design. An efficiency of 127.6% of the base line is reached at 85% of biomass feeding rate. The wood gas yield slightly increased with the new reactor as well as the energy yield. A slight increase in the heating value of the wood gas is the reason for this. As these developments prevail, despite a lower heating value of WW2, the cold gas efficiency increases.

Advantages of this staged system are separate optimisation of pyrolysis and gasification. Through this mild pyrolysis at lower temperatures, the already carbonised waste wood particles with sufficient strength enter the gasification together with the pyrolysis gases. This experimental plant allows intervention in the process at several stages and direct sampling throughout the process. The cold gas efficiencies are significantly lower than those achieved in commercial plants. This is due to the poorer thermal concept of the plant, which is due to the experimental operation. Frequent intervention in the system means sophisticated insulation is not used. This problem is also reflected in the fact that the product gas yield increases with the flow rate and the reactor achieves higher efficiencies closer to the load limit. For this reason, it is also to be expected that advanced insulation and thermal design will lead to higher heating values and efficiencies, since less energy is needed to provide the temperature and thus the necessary air volume flow. Another disadvantage of this approach is the susceptibility of the nitrogen balance to inaccuracies, which affect the resulting wood gas volume as well as the cold gas efficiency. For this reason, dynamic pressure measurements are suggested for further experiments to verify the calculated gas volume flow.

Conclusion and Outlook

The results show a stable and robust process for the gasification of waste wood of the classes AI – AIII. Elevated temperatures in the gasifier and lower pyrolysis temperatures lead to higher efficiencies in the gasification process using WW as resource. The use of a WW fraction with higher content of fines made a new reactor design necessary. With the changeover to a new adapted reactor geometry, the gasification performance could be further enhanced. The cold gas efficiency could be increased, reaching and exceeding the values obtained with FR. It is expected, that a more sophisticated insulation would lead to higher heating values of the product gas and therefore increased efficiencies.

Future investigations will focus on the increase of biomass feeding rate and thus power output of the process. Tar analysis should provide evidence of the extent to which possible tar reduction measurements need to be performed. Further examination of the influence of the gasification parameters should deepen the understanding of the process. The main aim is to increase the product gas heating value and fuel conversion. The resulting gasifier char is to be analysed and assessed for possible synergies.

Acknowledgement

The financial support by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs and the National Foundation for Research, Technology and Development, the Christian Doppler Research Association as well as the participating companies is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft, Arbeitsgruppe 3, "Empfehlung der Arbeitsgruppe Material- und Energieeffizienz zur Etablierung einer ressourceneffizienten Kreislaufwirtschaft bei der Nutzung von Holz," 2020.
- [2] EU, "Guidance on cascading use of biomass with selected good practice examples on woody biomass," 2018.
- [3] BDE Bundesverband der Deutschen, "Warum Abfallexporte und -importe unverzichtbar sind," 2020.
- [4] M. Röder and P. Thornley, "Waste wood as bioenergy feedstock. Climate change impacts and related emission uncertainties from waste wood based energy systems in the UK," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 74, pp. 241–252, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2017.11.042.
- [5] M. Edo, E. Björn, P.-E. Persson, and S. Jansson, "Assessment of chemical and material contamination in waste wood fuels--A case study ranging over nine years," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 49, pp. 311–319, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2015.11.048.
- [6] H.Riedel, G.Schmoeckel, C.Marb, "Schwermetall- und Chlorgehalte in Altholzsortimenten," 2014.
- [7] M. Huron, S. Oukala, J. Lardière, N. Giraud, and C. Dupont, "An extensive characterization of various treated waste wood for assessment of suitability with combustion process," *Fuel*, vol. 202, pp. 118–128, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2017.04.025.
- [8] S. Poskrobko, D. Król, and A. Borsukiewicz, "Gasification of waste wood biomass," vol. 59, pp. 241–248, 2016, doi: 10.12841/wood.1644-3985.C25.21.
- [9] P. N. Sheth and B. V. Babu, "Production of hydrogen energy through biomass (waste wood) gasification," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 35, no. 19, pp. 10803–10810, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2010.03.009.
- [10] V. Wilk, H. Kitzler, S. Koppatz, C. Pfeifer, and H. Hofbauer, "Gasification of waste wood and bark in a dual fluidized bed steam gasifier," *Biomass Conv. Bioref.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 91–97, 2011, doi: 10.1007/s13399-011-0009-z.
- [11] F. A. López, T. A. Centeno, I. García-Díaz, and F. J. Alguacil, "Textural and fuel characteristics of the chars produced by the pyrolysis of waste wood, and the properties of activated carbons prepared from them," *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, vol. 104, pp. 551–558, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.jaap.2013.05.014.
- [12] J. Li *et al.*, "Pyrolysis characteristics and non-isothermal kinetics of waste wood biomass," *Energy*, vol. 226, p. 120358, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2021.120358.
- [13] N. A. Jamin, S. Saleh, and N. A. Samad, "Influences of Gasification Temperature and Equivalence Ratio on Fluidized Bed Gasification of Raw and Torrefied Wood Wastes," 2020.
- [14] J. V. Littlejohns, J. Butler, L. Luque, and K. Austin, "Experimental Investigation of Bioenergy Production from Small-Scale Gasification of Landfill-Diverted Wood Wastes," *Waste Biomass Valor.*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 6885–6901, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s12649-020-00940-7.
- [15] I.-H. Hwang, J. Kobayashi, and K. Kawamoto, "Characterization of products obtained from pyrolysis and steam gasification of wood waste, RDF, and RPF," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 402–410, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2013.10.009.
- [16] C.M. van der Meijden, W. Sierhuis, A. van der Drift, B.J.

- Vreugdenhil, "Waste wood gasification in an allothermal gasifier," 2011.
- [17] U. Hansen, H. Künstner, R. Strenziok, "Energetische Nutzung von kontaminiertem Altholz mittels Flashpyrolyse," 2002.
- [18] J. Poudel, S. Karki, and S. Oh, "Valorization of Waste Wood as a Solid Fuel by Torrefaction," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 7, p. 1641, 2018, doi: 10.3390/en11071641.
- [19] M. Huber, M. Huemer, A. Hofmann, and S. Dumfort, "Floating-fixed-bed-gasification: From Vision to Reality," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 93, pp. 120–124, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2016.07.159.
- [20] H. D. Baehr and S. Kabelac, *Thermodynamik: Grundlagen und technische Anwendungen*, 14th ed. Dordrecht, Heidelberg: Springer, 2009.
- [21] M. Kaltschmitt, H. Hartmann, and H. Hofbauer, *Energie aus Biomasse*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2016.
- [22] P. Basu, *Biomass gasification, pyrolysis, and torrefaction: Practical design and theory*, 2nd ed. London: Academic Press, 2013.
- [23] L. Emami Taba, M. F. Irfan, W. A. M. Wan Daud, and M. H. Chakrabarti, "The effect of temperature on various parameters in coal, biomass and CO-gasification: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 16, no. 8, pp. 5584–5596, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2012.06.015.

Fractional crystallization of wastewater of a fly ash plant with membrane distillation crystallization

Stefanie Flatscher¹, Simon Hofer², Mark W. Hlawitschka^{1*}

1: Institute of Process Engineering, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria

2: Institute of Process Engineering, Environmental Engineering and Technical Bioscience, TU Wien, Austria

* Corresponding author: mark.hlawitschka@jku.at

Keywords: wastewater treatment, membrane crystallization, crystallization, fractional crystallization

Research field: e.g., membrane technology, crystallization

Abstract

This study explores the use of membrane distillation crystallization (MDC) for processing highly concentrated salt solutions produced by desalination plants and industrial wastewater. MDC integrates membrane distillation and crystallization into a single process, reducing capital and operating costs and improving sustainability. The study focuses on applying seeding techniques and fractional crystallization to concentrate a synthetic FLUWA wastewater stream at pilot-scale. The effects of salt crystallization and seeding on membrane performance and the possibility of fractional crystallization were investigated under different operating conditions. The results show that the process is capable of recovering 99% of water and total salt in continuous operation, while also separating the salts into three fractions. This presents an opportunity for testing future process technologies for industrial use, such as fraction recovery of salt components in multiple salt solutions from saline wastewaters.

Introduction

Waste incineration plays a key role in the waste management of modern countries. Incineration of waste reduces its volume, sanitizes the waste from biological hazards such as bacteria and viruses by destroying them at high incineration temperatures (850-1000 °C), and mineralizes all kinds of organic chemical compounds, including hazardous substances. In addition, some of the chemically bound energy in the waste is recovered to produce electricity and district heat [1]. A multi-stage flue gas cleaning system is required to minimize emissions from the incineration process. In addition to gaseous pollutants, the flue gas also contains solid fly ash particles. The coarse fly ash is separated in the boiler and the fine particles are filtered from the flue gas by electrostatic precipitators or bag filters. Fly ash consists of fine particles of refractory minerals entrained from the grate by combustion turbulence and new minerals formed in the gas phase [2]. Some heavy metal compounds with high steam pressure (such as zinc, lead, and cadmium) are partially or predominantly transferred to the fly ash [3]. The presence of chlorine and sulfur in the gas phase promotes gas-phase reactions along the flue gas path that lead to the formation of synthetic mineral phases [2,4].

The main constituents of fly ashes from waste incineration are the so-called mineral matrix (60 to 70 %), which consists mainly of aluminosilicates and oxides, water-soluble salts (~20 %), and heavy metals (~10 %) [5]. Fly ashes are considered hazardous waste due to leachable heavy metal compounds and salts. Although fly ash represents only about 2 % of the initial incinerated waste, the disposal of hazardous waste in underground landfills is costly, and since only old salt mines and caverns are suitable sites for such underground landfills, the availability of landfill space is limited in the long term [6]. In many cases, additional costs are incurred when countries do not have a domestic underground disposal site for hazardous waste and the fly ash has to be exported, as is the case in Switzerland. For this reason, the treatment of fly ash is becoming

an increasingly important issue in waste management. The treatment of fly ash has two main motivations. The first is to decontaminate fly ash to meet the criteria for non-hazardous landfills, and the second is to consider fly ash as a source of secondary raw materials and find ways to develop it. In Switzerland, the focus is on the recovery of zinc and lead from fly ash, their recovery is mandatory by 2026 [7]. In Switzerland, the FLUWA process is the state-of-the-art process for fly ash treatment. In this process, acid leaching of the metal compounds in the fly ash is carried out using the hydrochloric acid-containing wash water from the acid scrubber stage of the flue gas cleaning system.

If the required product qualities can be achieved, various secondary salt applications can be considered, with NaCl applications ranging from road salt to raw material in the chloralkali industry or PVC production [8]. The main application of potassium chloride is as a raw material for potassium fertilizers. The largest reserves of potassium minerals are in Canada and Russia. Although Germany and Spain are producers of potash (K₂O) in the EU, the EU is a net importer of potash, mainly from Russia and Belarus. With the ongoing geopolitical crises, potash supply is a current challenge for the EU [9]. Other applications of KCl are in the secondary aluminum refining industry, where it is used as a mixture of molten salts with NaCl [10]. CaCl₂ will be recovered from aquatic solution in its hydrated form CaCl₂ · 6H₂O and can be used for dust control on roads [8] and also as raw material for precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) production, which is used as filler in polymers and paper [11] or as phase change material for chemical energy storage [12].

In industrial processes, there is a significant amount of brine that is discharged, and there are several options for brine management, as e.g. Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD) approaches [13]. They reduce the environmental impact and achieve sustainability by recovering a large amount of water from the discharged brine. The ZLD technology is a system where there is minimal or no discharge of water into the environment. Due to the high salinity of the water and brine produced, ZLD can be integrated into membrane desalination processes and industrial processes that produce highly saline effluents [14]. This is the case with the fly ash process mentioned above. The effluent from this process has a salinity of more than 10 %, with various salts present.

Figure 70: Process flow diagram of the MDC pilot plant

Membrane distillation (MD) is also an up-and-coming membrane-based process that processes high-salt solutions [15–17] and is ideal for the recovery of water from brine solutions. MD is a separation process in which the temperature gradient across the hydrophobic membrane creates a partial vapor pressure difference, allowing water vapor molecules from the hot solution to pass through the membrane pores to the cold permeate side [18,19]. One type of MD is an air gap membrane distillation process where there is an air gap between the membrane and the condensation surface. The main product desalinated by MD is water. A more concentrated solution is obtained by removing the water from the brine [20]. An essential challenge of the MD process is the scaling and wetting of the membrane [21]. When the salt solution's concentration exceeds the salt's solubility and crystallization begins, the MD process is compromised.

The membrane crystallizer concept, as implemented in MD, for producing solid crystals from solutions was first introduced by Curcio et al. [22]. Crystallization takes place on the membrane in a different MDC process. This results in the membrane surface being scaled and permeation fluxes being reduced throughout the process. Scaling-induced pore wetting occurs, initially slowing and then increasing permeate flux and decreasing permeate quality [23].

Due to the different solubilities of the salts in water, it is possible to precipitate the salts one after another. At a temperature of 60 °C, NaCl has a solubility of 371 g L⁻¹, KCl 456 g L⁻¹, and CaCl₂ 1345 g L⁻¹. By evaporation of the water, the solution becomes more concentrated and as soon as the solution reaches the first solubility limit, the first salt will start to precipitate. The concentration increases and the solubility limit can be exceeded by adding one of the two ions to the solution. The solubility products of the salts must be far enough apart to avoid contamination by the other salts for the salts to separate.

In this paper, the separation of the salts of a synthetically produced FLUWA wastewater solution is investigated in a pilot plant of the MDC. The use of seed crystals is to prevent scaling and the wetting of the membrane surface, which would be caused by scaling. Due to the different solubilities of the salts in the solution, it is possible to crystallize the salts on a fractional basis. This method offers the possibility to operate the MD process as a long-term process with a closed-loop economy. The results of the experiment are presented here.

Material and Methods

In this work, a synthetic saline solution composed of CaCl₂, NaCl and KCl with the same salt ratio as in a real wastewater from the FLUWA process is used to study separation by membrane distillation crystallization. For this purpose, a sample of wastewater from FLUWA extraction experiments on a laboratory scale was made available by the "Center for the Sustainable Use of Waste and Resources" (ZAR Foundation) based in Switzerland. Fly ash treatment with the FLUWA process is part of the research focus of the ZAR Foundation, which is a competence center for research and development in the field of recycling of incineration residues.

In a double experiment, a solution of 100 ml of the sample was stirred magnetically in a baking oven at room temperature. The pH value of the sample solution was measured continuously using a pH electrode. The lime suspension (10 M%, 1.43 mol L⁻¹) was prepared from Ca(OH)₂ powder, and the concentration was determined by titration with 0.96 mole HCl titer, which was determined from Na₂CO₃ first titer. Constant stirring was required to prevent the lime from settling. The lime was added drop by drop to the sample solution until a pH of 9.4 to 9.5 was reached and the heavy metals were precipitated as metal hydroxides. After filtration, the filtrated solution was analyzed by ICP-OES (Perkin Elmer Optima 8000) for

Ca²⁺, Na⁺, and K⁺ and by ion chromatography for Cl⁻.

Based on the results, a synthetic 8.3 % CaCl₂, 1.5 % NaCl, and 1.1 % KCl solution was prepared to simulate FLUWA effluent. The excess of CaCl₂ can be explained by the fact that the FLUWA process involves acid washing with HCl-containing scrubber water and reactions 1 and 2 occur. The Ca²⁺ concentration is further increased by precipitation with lime.

The MDC tests have been carried out in a test unit with a membrane module with an air gap and an additional crystallization section (Fig. 1). The apparatus consists of the PP tubular membrane, the heat exchanger section with a 1 m long PP-GR tube with a surface area of 0.026 m² and a sedimentation section. The operating conditions are selected so that the temperature of the circuit in the membrane module remains constant to allow continuous crystallization. To prevent crystal growth in the pilot plant and clogging of the pipes, the flow rate in the circuit is set at 60-100 L h⁻¹. The permeate flow is calculated once a constant flow rate is achieved. To ensure that no crystallization occurs on the membrane, this process is carried out continuously in a batch test.

The membrane material used is a tubular membrane made of polypropylene (PP). The hydrophobic membrane 3M[®] Accurel PP V8/2 HF for the pilot plant has an effective contact area of 0.017 m², a nominal pore radius of 0.2 μm, a thickness of 1550 μm, and a porosity of 73 %. Membrane diameters are 5.5 mm internally and 8.6 mm externally.

Unwanted nucleation is prevented by seed crystals. The limits for the number of seeds should be in the range of 0.3 to 1.0 % by weight. Quartz sand with a grain size between 0.21 and 0.3 mm is used for seed crystallization. At least 85 % of the quartz sand must fall within this range.

The composition and content of the FLUWA solution salts were described before. As a precursor, a two-component mixture of CaCl₂ (Acros Organics, 98+ %) and NaCl (Roth, >99 %) was prepared first, and then next a three-component mixture with additional KCl (Merck, ultrapure).

Figure 71: Solubility curves of the three salts in the FLUWA Wastewater: NaCl, KCl, and CaCl₂ in the temperature range from 0 to 80 °C.

The temperature was adjusted based on the solubility of the salts. The solubilities of the different salts (Fig. 2) are sufficiently far apart to allow one to precipitate without the other being crystallized. At 60 °C the solubility of NaCl is 371 g L⁻¹, KCl 456 g L⁻¹, and CaCl₂ 1340 g L⁻¹. CaCl₂ is present at room temperature as CaCl₂ · 6H₂O and starts to give off its water of crystallization and melt at 30 °C.

Recovering the water from the synthetic wastewater solution, which is calculated as follows, is an essential part of this process:

$$R = \frac{m_{\text{permeate}}}{m_{\text{total}}} \quad (1)$$

R is the amount of water that could be recovered from the process cycle, m_{permeate} is the mass of the distillate and m_{total} is the water of the feed solution.

For the determination of the distillate throughput, the mass of the permeate is calculated according to the following equation:

$$J = \frac{\Delta m}{A \Delta t} \quad (2)$$

J is the permeate flux (kg m⁻² h⁻¹), Δm is the mass of captured water (kg), A is the effective membrane surface area (m²), and Δt is the operating time (h).

The concentration factor (CF) was calculated using Eq. 2

$$\text{CF} = \frac{C_{\text{feed,final}}}{C_{\text{feed,start}}} \quad (3)$$

C_{feed, final}, and C_{feed, start} is the final and start feed solution concentrations (g L⁻¹), respectively.

The different fractions of the salt were filtered and analyzed with an ICP-OES (Thermo Fisher iCAP PRO XPS) and a direct optical microscopy (Keyence VHX-7000 microscope) was used. Flexible observation of the crystals was possible due to the high depth of field range of the microscope. By adjusting the brightness, an optimum viewing condition was determined. The crystals, their size, and their growth behavior were studied.

Results and Discussion

Two-component system

The first step was the consideration of a two-component system for the experimental demonstration of the principle of fractional crystallization. For the fractional crystallization experiment, a 24.3 % saline feed solution was prepared. At room temperature, the solubility of CaCl₂ was 720 g L⁻¹. Solubility increases with increasing temperature, so at a temperature of 60 °C, a solubility of 1340 g L⁻¹ is obtained.

In the case of fractional crystallization, the first fraction was crystallized with a salinity of 28 % after 280 g of vaporized water in the feed solution and at a loop temperature of 54.35 °C. Theoretically, the crystallization should have started with a salinity of 34 % and this is after 555.3 g of the water in the feed is vaporized. Crystallization started 49 % earlier than calculated. In the second fraction, the crystallization started after 647 g of produced distillate. In theory, the crystallization should have started

after 850 g of water was recovered. The start of crystallization was 24 % earlier than the calculation. The concentration at the wall of the membrane is higher than the concentration in the center. There a polarized layer is built on the membrane due to the seed crystals, and the crystals grow on the quartz sand and not on the membrane surface.

The experiment lasted 62 h and over the whole time of the experiment, the conductivity of the permeate water was on average $1.15 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. The permeate water had a very low salinity. A low level of conductivity thereby indicates that there are only a small amount of salts in the permeate and that the water is very pure. In the two-component system, the permeate flux was lower than in the three-component system.

The multi-salt solution has a salt ratio of 1.9, a concentration factor of 1.8, and a water recovery of 53 %. The total recovery of the salts is 39 %, the recoveries refer to the batch experiment. The calculated values are based on the batch test; a dead volume of 0.65 L remains in the plant, which cannot be further concentrated. The permeate flux was an average of $0.77 \text{ kg m}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ for the whole duration of the experiment. This is achieved without compromising the quantity and quality of the permeate.

Three-component system

In the further step, FLUWA wastewater as a three-component system was prepared. The feed solution with a salt content of 11 % was mixed. Several solutions were prepared for the test. For all tests, the batch volume was 4.3 L. The experiments were carried out at a seed concentration of 0.25 % of the salt concentration. The temperature remained constant throughout the experiment. The first experiment was carried out at 70 °C. As a result of the high temperature, the solubility of the solution increased to such an extent that no significant fractional crystallization occurred at the end of the experiment. The solubility of the salts at a temperature of 70 °C is 375 g L^{-1} NaCl, 489 g L^{-1} KCl, and 1410 g L^{-1} CaCl₂. At this temperature, more feed solution has to be prepared so that a fractionated crystallization of the three salts could be possible.

In addition, the experiment was carried out again at a lower temperature. The temperature was set at 59 °C and was kept constant for the duration of the experiment. The water recovery was 83 % for the batch test, and 99 % of the water could be recovered when the test was run continuously. The permeate flux was an average of $4.17 \text{ kg m}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ for the whole duration of the experiment [24]. The total recovery of the salt for this experiment was 80 %. In comparison with the test carried out at 70 °C, it was visible at 59 °C that three fractions of salt could be obtained.

The FLUWA wastewater solution has a salt ratio of 2.9, and a concentration factor of 5.9. The water quality of the permeate amounts to $0.9 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ during the experiment time of 61 h. This is achieved without compromising permeate quantity and quality.

As mentioned above, the permeate flux in the two-component system is $0.77 \text{ kg m}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and that of the three-component system is $4.17 \text{ kg m}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$. Adding a vacuum to the permeate side could increase the permeate flux by 5.4 times.

Morphology

The morphology of the formed crystals is shown in Fig 3 and 4. In fraction 1 unregular formed CaCl₂ crystals obtained an average size is $243.9 \mu\text{m}$ and regular cubic NaCl crystals (Fig. 4) with an average size of $156.6 \mu\text{m}$ [25] were obtained in fraction 2. The different crystal structures provide information about the possibility of fractional crystallization.

Figure 72: CaCl₂ crystals under the microscope. The crystals grow in a dendrite form.

Figure 73: cubic formed NaCl crystals under the microscope. The NaCl crystals grow in the typical cubic form.

The crystals during the process have an average size of $156.6 \mu\text{m}$ after filtering and drying of the crystals, they grow together and build crystal agglomeration, the size of the crystals is 17.5 times bigger than in the process and the size is in average $f 2740 \mu\text{m}$.

Analysis of the salt fractions

The composition of the fraction was determined with the ICP-OES analysis which is shown in Tab. 1. The first two fractions have a higher separation the 3rd fraction is a mixture of all three salts.

Table 18: The three different salt fractions at an operating temperature of 59 °C and 0.3 % of the seeding crystals.

	Ca ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺
1. Fraction	91 %	4 %	5 %
2. Fraction	21 %	7 %	72 %
3. Fraction	35 %	28 %	37 %

The analysis of the salts shows that separation in the process is possible. The operating parameters must be optimized so that the salts can be better separated. At 59 °C, the first fraction consists of 91 % Ca²⁺, the second fraction 72 % Na⁺, and the last fraction is mixed. The impurities in the individual fractions can be reduced by improving crystal removal. The impurities in the single fractions came from the mixture of the feed solution with the settled crystals.

Conclusion

The synthetic fly ash effluent was separated using MDC. Experiments showed the possibility of the MDC of wastewater treatment, to recover clean water and produce salt in fractions.

In the two-component system, it has been shown that fractional crystallization is possible, and in addition, a three-component system can be separated into three fractions. There has been an improvement in the performance of the MDC from the two-component system to the three-component system. The permeate flow rate was increased by a factor of 5.4. Regarding the possible water recovery considering the dead volume, 99 % of the demineralized water was recovered as permeate and 99 % of the total salts can be recovered. This indicates the possibility of continuous operation.

Crystallization on the particles of the suspension circuit was observed in the concentration of multi-salt and synthetic wastewater solutions. Fractional crystallization was possible in both experiments. The CaCl₂ crystals are larger in size than the NaCl crystals. In the second experiment, the salts were separated into three fractions.

The results of the pilot-scale MDC process are useful for the integration and optimization of MD processes. Industrial processes and municipal wastewater treatment can be used as guidelines.

A method to better separate the fractions using different seed concentrations and varying process parameters, as well as better separation at discharge, will be further investigated. The goal is to achieve a constant permeate flow over time and a fractional separation of the salts in the plant.

Acknowledgement

We thank VA Tech Wabag GmbH for the financial support regarding the MDC.

Symbols used

A	m ²	area
CF		concentration factor
C _{feed,final}	g L ⁻¹	end concentration
C _{feed,start}	g L ⁻¹	start concentration
J	kg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	permeate flux
Δm	kg	mass of captured water
m _{permeate}	Kg	mass of the distillate
m _{total}	kg	water of the feed solutio
R	%	recovery
Δt	h	operating time

Abbreviations

ICP - OES	inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy
MD	membrane distillation
MDC	membrane distillation crystallization
PCC	precipitated calcium carbonate
ZLD	zero liquid discharge

References

- [1] P. H. Brunner and H. Rechberger, "Waste to energy--key element for sustainable waste management," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 37, pp. 3-12, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.02.003>.
- [2] G. Weibel, U. Eggenberger, S. Schlumberger and U. K. Mäder, "Chemical associations and mobilization of heavy metals in fly ash from municipal solid waste incineration," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 62, pp. 147-159, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2016.12.004>.
- [3] A. Bogush, J. A. Stegemann, I. Wood and A. Roy, "Element composition and mineralogical characterisation of air pollution control residue from UK energy-from-waste facilities," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 36, pp. 119-129, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.11.017>.
- [4] M. Wolffers, U. Eggenberger, S. Schlumberger and S. V. Churakov, "Characterization of MSWI fly ashes along the flue gas cooling path and implications on heavy metal recovery through acid leaching," *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, vol. 134, pp. 231-240, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.08.022>.
- [5] A. Bühler and S. Schlumberger, "Schwermetalle aus der Flugasche zurückgewinnen Saure Flugaschewäsche - FLUWA-Verfahren ein zukunftsweisendes Verfahren in der Abfallverbrennung," *KVA-Rückstände in der Schweiz*, 2010.
- [6] M. J. Quina, E. Bontempi, A. Bogush, S. Schlumberger, G. Weibel, R. Braga, V. Funari, J. Hyks, E. Rasmussen and J. Lederer, "Technologies for the management of MSW incineration ashes from gas cleaning: New perspectives on recovery of secondary raw materials and circular economy," *The Science of the total environment*, vol. 635, pp. 526-542, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.150>.
- [7] Verordnung über die Vermeidung und die Entsorgung von Abfällen (Abfallverordnung, VVEA), 2015.
- [8] L. Staffas, K. Karlfeldt Fedje, A. Pettersson and Johansson I., "Behandling och Återvinning av outnyttjade Resurser i Flygaska från Avfallsförbränning," vol. 2016.
- [9] G. A. Blengini, C. El Latunussa, U. Eynard, C. Torres de Matos, D. M. A. G. Wittmer, K. Georgitzikis, C. C. Pavel, S. Carrara, L. Mancini, M. Unguru, D. Blagoeva, F. Mathieux and D. W. Pennington, Study on the EU's list of critical raw materials (2020). Final reportLuxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2020.

- [10] Bernd Friedrich and Songül Sieben, "Techno-ökonomische Analyse einer Absenkung des KCl-Gehalts im Schmelzsatz beim Aluminium-Recycling" Forschungsvereinigung: Stifterverband Metalle e.V. Forschungsstelle: Institut für Metallurgische Prozesstechnik und Metallrecycling (IME), 2017.
- [11] N. Erdogan and H. A. Eken, "Precipitated calcium carbonate production, synthesis and properties," 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5277/ppmp170105>.
- [12] H. Feilchenfeld and S. Sarig, "Calcium chloride hexahydrate: a phase-changing material for energy storage," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Product Research and Development*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 130-133, 1985. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1021/i300017a024>.
- [13] F. A. Rodríguez, D. E. Santiago, N. Franquiz Suárez, J. A. Ortega Méndez and J. M. Veza, "Comparison of evaporation rates for seawater and brine from reverse osmosis in traditional salt works: empirical correlations," *Water Supply*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 234-240, 2012. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2166/ws.2012.133>.
- [14] A. Panagopoulos and V. Giannika, "Comparative techno-economic and environmental analysis of minimal liquid discharge (MLD) and zero liquid discharge (ZLD) desalination systems for seawater brine treatment and valorization," *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, vol. 53, p. 102477, 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102477>.
- [15] W. Li, B. van der Bruggen and P. Luis, "Recovery of Na₂CO₃ and Na₂SO₄ from mixed solutions by membrane crystallization," *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 106, pp. 315-326, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2015.12.022>.
- [16] T. Zou, G. Kang, M. Zhou, M. Li and Y. Cao, "Submerged vacuum membrane distillation crystallization (S-VMDC) with turbulent intensification for the concentration of NaCl solution," *Separation and Purification Technology*, vol. 211, pp. 151-161, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2018.09.072>.
- [17] A. Anvari, K. M. Kekre, A. Azimi Yancheshme, Y. Yao and A. Ronen, "Membrane distillation of high salinity water by induction heated thermally conducting membranes," *Journal of Membrane Science*, vol. 589, p. 117253, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117253>.
- [18] K. W. Lawson and D. R. Lloyd, "Membrane distillation," *Journal of Membrane Science*, vol. 124, no. 1, pp. 1-25, 1997. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388\(96\)00236-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388(96)00236-0).
- [19] E. Curcio and E. Drioli, "Membrane Distillation and Related Operations—A Review," *Separation & Purification Reviews*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 35-86, 2005. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1081/SPM-200054951>.
- [20] A. M. Alklaibi and N. Lior, "Membrane-distillation desalination: Status and potential," *Desalination*, vol. 171, no. 2, pp. 111-131, 2005. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2004.03.024>.
- [21] D. M. Warsinger, J. Swaminathan, E. Guillen-Burrieza, H. A. Arafat and J. H. Lienhard V, "Scaling and fouling in membrane distillation for desalination applications: A review," *Desalination*, vol. 356, pp. 294-313, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.06.031>.
- [22] E. Curcio, A. Criscuoli and E. Drioli, "Membrane Crystallizers," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 40, no. 12, pp. 2679-2684, 2001. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie000906d>.
- [23] F. Kiefer, A. Präbst and T. Sattelmayer, "Membrane scaling in Vacuum Membrane Distillation - Part 2: Crystallization kinetics and process performance," *Journal of Membrane Science*, vol. 590, p. 117293, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117293>.
- [24] S. Meng, Y. Ye, J. Mansouri and V. Chen, "Crystallization behavior of salts during membrane distillation with hydrophobic and superhydrophobic capillary membranes," *Journal of Membrane Science*, vol. 473, pp. 165-176, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2014.09.024>.
- [25] G. Chen, Y. Lu, W. B. Krantz, R. Wang and A. G. Fane, "Optimization of operating conditions for a continuous membrane distillation crystallization process with zero salty water discharge," *Journal of Membrane Science*, vol. 450, pp. 1-11, 2014. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.08.034>.

Fluid mechanical and economic analysis of a spherical hot water storage tank

M. Berger^{1,*}, M. Pittracher¹, T. Senfter¹, C. Mayer¹, T. Kofler¹, S. Holzer¹, M. Pillei¹

1: Dept. of Environmental, Process & Energy Engineering, MCI Innsbruck, Austria

* Corresponding author: manuel.berger@mci.edu

Keywords: water storage tank, finite volume method, economic analysis, ecological analysis

Research field: Computational Fluid Dynamics

Abstract

Sustainable heat supply is an important aspect in realizing the European energy transition. While heat pumps, solar thermal energy or biomass are often used in rural areas, district heating offers a possible alternative in more densely populated areas. In order to reduce the share of fossil fuels in such interconnected systems, a way is needed to sustainably cover short-term load peaks independent of environmental conditions. One approach to realize this is offered by heat storage systems, which are charged in times of energy surplus and discharged during a deficit.

The operator of a large district heating network in Tyrol owns a currently unused spherical 4000 m³ capacity pressure vessel. To verify whether this facility is suitable as a heat storage facility, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is used to verify whether the contents stratify or mix at a charging and discharging rate of 10 MW (62 l/s, 0.493 m/s). Furthermore, it will be surveyed how much natural gas can be substituted by the storage and under which circumstances an economic success can be achieved.

The CFD simulation shows that stratification is occurring. In a representative operating scenario, the efficiency of the thermal storage is calculated as 0.79. Considering this ratio, approximately 5000 MWh of fossil energy for district heating production can be substituted by a sustainable source, e.g., a biomass heating plant. At a CO₂ price of 30 euros per ton, natural gas must be at least 18,96 euros per MWh more expensive than the energy with which the storage is charged in order to achieve economic success. If the CO₂ price changes to 55 Euro, the difference is still 13.71 Euro. This means at a CO₂ price of 55 Euro, natural gas needs to be at least 13.71 Euro per MWh more expensive, than the energy that is fed into the vessel (e.g. biomass). Then the revenues from energy substitution (natural gas vs. biomass price) are equal to the annual construction- and operation costs and therefore economic success can be achieved.

The next step is to verify the simulation by an experimental investigation using a test plant.

Introduction

In order to follow the goals of the Paris Climate Agreement, Austria has set itself the goal, among others, of reducing CO₂ emissions by 36% by 2030 compared to 2005 [1]. In the area of heat supply, this will be realized by a gradual switch from fossil fuels to sustainable or renewable energy sources. While in the rural sector this can often be realized by installing heat pumps, solar collectors or biomass heating systems, in the urban sector the switch is often made to district heating.

In the Innsbruck area, the energy mix is composed of biomass, industrial waste heat, combined heat and power (CHP) and natural gas.

The heat generated from natural gas is primarily needed to cover peak loads, which often occur in the mornings, and to compensate for deficits. In order to reduce the share of natural gas, it would be conceivable to build a biomass heating plant in combination with a heat storage facility. The biomass heating plant itself could supply the base load during the heating season and charge the heat storage in times of energy surplus. The energy from the thermal storage could in turn be used to balance energy peaks, reduce control effort in the grid, and allow the biomass heating plant to operate more

consistently. The storage facility would also have other benefits. For example, industrial waste heat or thermal energy from CHP plants could be used more efficiently. In these plants, heat is often a byproduct, which is why they cannot be regulated to the demand in the grid. Thus, if more waste heat is produced than is needed in the grid, hot exhaust gas is often emitted and the energy is not used. With a heat storage system, this energy could be stored and used at a later time.

In the inventory of a large Tyrolean district heating provider is a spherical, 4000 m³ holding pressure vessel, which is currently no longer used. It is now to be examined whether this facility is suitable in principle as a heat storage facility, how much natural gas can be substituted by other energy sources and under what conditions economic success can be achieved.

Methods

CFD

A CFD simulation is used to prove the suitability of the system by charging the reservoir with hot water for 10 h and discharging it in a separate simulation for 10 h. This is done to check if the contents stratify or mix. In Figure 74 the charging and discharging process is shown schematically. The chosen parameters and settings are based on comparable publications [2]–[5].

Figure 74: Overview of the two operating modes of the hot water tank and designation of some sizes; left charging and right discharging.

The $k-\omega$ -SST is chosen as the viscous model. To account for the temperature dependence of the density of water, the Boussinesq approximation is used. The time step size of the transient observation is 5s. Thus, 7200 time steps are required to simulate 10 h real time. A 0.4 m diameter nozzle is attached to the top and bottom of the pressure vessel. Charging and discharging is performed through these nozzles. In order to reduce the momentum of the incoming flow and thus improve stratification, baffle plates are placed in the area of the nozzles inside the vessel. The position and dimension are taken from literature [3], a schematic representation can be seen in Figure 75. A detailed description of the boundary conditions is shown in

Table 19. The supply temperature is determined by 95°C and the return temperature by 55°C.

To quantify the quality of stratification, the efficiency of the storage is calculated from the CFD simulation data for a representative operating scenario 10 h loading and 2 h unloading. This ratio is related to the degree of mixing of the contents. For this purpose, the energy of the water with a temperature level of at least 80°C ($Q_{>80^\circ\text{C}}$) is calculated and divided by the theoretical, ideally

stratified energy content Q_{ideal} of the storage tank. The calculated ratios for both operating scenarios 10 h charging and 2 h discharging are then multiplied to calculate the total efficiency of the storage tank. This ratio is also referred to as the exergy efficiency η_{ex} (equation 1).

$$\eta_{ex} = \frac{Q_{>80^\circ C}}{Q_{ideal}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 75: Size and spacing of the baffle plate of the flow side of the heat accumulator; On the return side the design is equivalent.

Table 19: Parameters and settings of the boundary conditions for the CFD simulation of the charging and discharging operation; with “Top” the geodetically higher situated nozzle and with “Bottom” the lower situated nozzle is meant.

Region	Boundary condition	Properties
Top	Velocity inlet	Loading $v=0.5 \text{ m/s}$, $T = 95^\circ\text{C}$
Bottom	Pressure outlet	$T = 55^\circ\text{C}$
Wall	Wall	No slip, adiabatic
Baffle plate	Wall	No slip, adiabatic
Top	Pressure outlet	Unloading $T = 95^\circ\text{C}$
Bottom	Velocity inlet	$v=0.5 \text{ m/s}$, $T = 55^\circ\text{C}$
Wall	Wall	No slip, adiabatic
Baffle plate	Wall	No slip, adiabatic

Ecological consideration

In the ecological analysis, the benefit of the storage facility is determined based on the load data of the generation plants in 2020. For this purpose, a fictitious 15 MW biomass heating plant is added to the energy mix and it is determined how much natural gas can be substituted for different connected loads. The output of the biomass heating plant is manually controlled on a daily basis. The additional fictitious connected load is varied from 0 MW to 40 MW in 5 MW steps and added to the heat demand.

The load data of the real plants are available in 15 min mean values. The data are divided into the heat demand E_{WB} on the customer side and the introduced energy E_{EE} on the producer side. The former is composed of the original 2020 load data and the fictitious consumers and the latter is composed of the 2020 load data without natural gas boilers but with the fictitious heat sources. To calculate how much natural gas can be substituted by the storage, the difference between the generated energy and the heat demand is formed at each time step. If the value is positive, there is a surplus of heat and the storage is fed. If the value is negative, there is a deficit in the network and heat is taken from the storage tank. If the storage tank is empty and there is not enough thermal energy in the network, the deficit is covered with natural gas. With this procedure it is possible to calculate the amount of substitutable natural gas by the storage.

In addition to the calculation of the substitutable energy, the amount of saved CO₂ equivalent is determined. For this purpose, it is taken into account that per kWh of heat from natural gas 247 g of CO₂ equivalent is produced [6]. When biomass is used as fuel, the

amount is 17 g of CO₂ equivalent per kWh of heat [6].

Economic consideration

The economic analysis is carried out for four different substitutable energy quantities 2500 MWh, 5000 MWh, 7500 MWh and 10000 MWh in two balance areas. In the first one, the heat storage itself is considered and costs for depreciation, maintenance and repair, circulation, personnel for the ongoing operation and others are collected. The specific costs of heat storage cover these costs, which is why they depend on the substitutable energy. In the second balance area, the district heating business area is considered, which purchases heat from the storage facility and bears the associated costs. Depending on the amount of substitutable energy and the specific costs for CO₂, it is calculated how much more expensive natural gas has to be than the energy that is loaded into the storage facility in order to achieve economic success. To calculate this, it is assumed that the storage replaces natural gas with biomass. Thus, 230 g of CO₂ equivalent are saved per substituted kWh. The detailed calculation is shown in equation 2. The quantity ΔK_{energy} describes the necessary cost difference between natural gas and the alternative energy to achieve neither gains nor losses. G_{CO2} is the saved CO₂ equivalent per kWh of heat (230 g), K_{CO2} corresponds to the variable CO₂ costs and $K_{storage}$ describes the costs for the heat storage itself, which depend on the substitutable energy quantity.

$$\Delta K_{energy} = -G_{CO2} \cdot K_{CO2} + K_{storage} \quad (2)$$

Results and Discussion

CFD

The CFD simulation shows that stratification of the content is formed at a charging and discharging power of 10 MW. The selected number of grid cells of 1249340 was verified with a grid independence analysis. Figure 76 and Figure 77 show the temperature distribution according to different time points. The corresponding efficiencies can be obtained from Table 20. The efficiency of each operation depends on the time point. For the representative operating scenario of 10 h charging and 2 h discharging, an efficiency of 0.79 results.

Figure 76: Temperature distribution in the xy plane at different loading times.

Figure 77: Temperature distribution in the xy plane at different unloading times.

Table 20: Efficiency (η) at different charging and discharging times

t/h	2	4	6	8	10
$\eta_{Loading}$	0.7	0.77	0.76	0.77	0.81
$\eta_{Unloading}$	0.98	0.95	0.92	0.84	0.80

Real measured data from the literature [7] are used as a comparison to the efficiency collected here. Here a real trapezoidal

ground heat storage system in Denmark with a storage capacity of 60000 m³ respectively 5500 MWh was measured.

The system is fed by solar collectors with an area of 35573 m² and is used both seasonally and for short periods. From the measured data, the exergy efficiency is calculated, which takes into account losses due to mixing and thermal losses to the environment. The efficiency was calculated annually over a period of five years and the arithmetic mean was calculated from this. This averaged exergy efficiency is 0.73, which is somewhat lower than the value determined here for the spherical storage tank in Innsbruck. However, thermal losses are also taken into account for the system in Denmark and the data have been measured over a real period of time and not theoretically determined. On the other hand, in the theoretical plant in Innsbruck, hardly any internals have been taken into account to improve stratification. For example, the nozzles at the inlet and outlet could be designed in such a way that the water flows out radially and is redirected (see Figure 78) to further reduce the momentum towards stratification. Baffle plates in the wall area of the energy storage would also be conceivable (see Figure 78), since a closer look at the velocity profile in xy and yz planes reveals a low flow in the edge region in both the charging and discharging processes. Furthermore, the efficiency considered here has been calculated during the charging process at a power of 10 MW. In practice, the charging process will probably take place at a lower power and for a longer period of time. Since a reduction in power also reduces the flow velocity at the inlet, it can be assumed that stratification will improve.

Figure 78: Optimization of the inlet to reduce momentum toward stratification and addition of a wall plate to redirect flow at the edge of the vessel.

Ecological consideration

The ecological analysis shows that a different amount of natural gas can be substituted depending on the connected load. Table 21 shows the result for all variants. The storage capacity of the plant is 176 MWh.

Table 21: Result of the ecological consideration with a fictitious 15 MW biomass heating plant;

P _{IV} / MW	E _{gas,mWS} / MWh	E _{gas,oWS} / MWh	ΔE _{Subs} / MWh	mCO ₂ / t
0	0	3187	3187	733
5	0	4382	4382	1008
10	0	5661	5661	1302
15	744	7318	6574	1512
20	5578	11506	5929	1364
25	11892	17697	5805	1335
30	20265	25775	5510	1267
35	30822	35731	4909	1129
40	41891	46400	4509	1037

P_{IV} describes the power of the fictitious consumers, E_{gas,mWS} the demand for natural gas with the use -, E_{gas,oWS} the demand for natural gas without the use of a heat storage, ΔE_{Subs} the amount of natural gas that can be substituted by the thermal storage, and mCO₂ describes the associated amount of CO₂ equivalent that is saved.

Figure 79: Energy mix with fictitious 15 MW biomass heating plant and increasing connected load or increasing fictitious consumers.

On arithmetic average, 5163 MWh of natural gas can be substituted by an alternative source through the storage. The best result is obtained when the notional connected load is equal to the output of the notional biomass heating plant. In this scenario, 6574 MWh can be substituted. The corresponding energy mix is shown in Figure 79. Here it can be seen that the share of heat storage is 2.5% to 6.3%. Logically, the share reduces as the load increases, since the total energy demand also increases and the amount of substitutable energy is limited by the size of the storage.

Taking into account the efficiency of 0.79, it is thus possible to substitute 4079 MWh of natural gas on arithmetic average and 5193 MWh in the best case. This corresponds to an amount of CO₂ equivalent of 938 and 1194 t, respectively, which are saved annually by the thermal storage.

Economic consideration

The economic analysis shows that in the best case, taking into account the efficiency, about 5000 MWh of natural gas can be substituted. Assuming a CO₂ price of 30 euros per ton, the natural gas must be at least 18.96 euros per ton more expensive than the energy that is loaded into the storage facility. If the CO₂ price increases to 55 euros, the difference is reduced to 13.71 euros. However, this analysis does not take into account soft facts associated with natural gas savings. This reduces dependence on fossil fuels as their price can fluctuate significantly. Moreover, each kWh of fossil fuel saved contributes to the energy autonomy of Austria and positively to climate development.

However, according to the literature, the social costs of CO₂ are estimated to be much higher. These are said to be 185 US dollars per ton of [8] CO₂, which corresponds to 184.06 euros at the current exchange rate. Taking into account these significantly higher costs, natural gas would have to be 13.40 euros cheaper than the energy that is loaded into the storage facility. The detailed results of the economic analysis for different amounts of substitutable energy and variable CO₂ price are shown in Figure 80.

Figure 80: Summary of the economic consideration with different quantities of substitutable quantity of natural gas; The y-axis describes the price difference between natural gas and that energy which is loaded into the storage; If the CO₂ price and the price difference result in an intersection point at one of the drawn courses, neither profits nor loss are obtained; If the intersection point lies above the respective course, profits are obtained, below it are losses; If the price difference is a positive value, the natural gas must be more expensive than the alternative energy.

Outlook

It is evident from the work that the spherical pressure vessel shows potential for heat storage. However, a CFD simulation should always be verified with an experiment. For this purpose, an experimental facility has to be developed and the geometry has to be entered into the CFD software. It is important for the plant that the temperature is measured over a very fine resolution, so that also an efficiency can be calculated and the experiment can be compared quantitatively with the simulation results.

Another point which should be investigated is the behavior of the stratification with time. In the simulation performed here, the storage is only considered for 10 h during the charging and discharging process. It would be interesting to see how the stratification behaves stationary without water being added or removed. Especially how the efficiency changes with time and after which storage time the content can be seen as full mixed. This behavior should also be tested in a pilot plant.

References

- [1] BMVIT and BMNT; “Die österreichische Klima- und Energie Strategie - #mission2030,” 2018.
- [2] M. T. Bouzaher, B. Nouredine, C. E. Bensaci, N. Bouchahm, and B. Guerira, “Evaluation of thermal stratification inside a new model of spherical water storage tank using a computational fluid dynamics 6 degrees of freedom solver,” *J. Therm. Sci. Eng. Appl.*, vol. 12, no. 3, 2020.
- [3] F. Khan and B. J. Savelonis, “Plate diffuser performance in spherical tank thermocline storage system,” *J. Energy Resour. Technol.*, vol. 138, no. 5, 2016.
- [4] M. A. Gómez, S. Chapela, J. Collazo, and J. L. Míguez, “CFD analysis of a buffer tank redesigned with a thermosyphon concentrator tube,” *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 11, 2019.
- [5] H. K. B. Sangjoei, “CFD Simulation of stratified thermal energy storage tank EVOCAT,” 2021.
- [6] OIB, “Richtlinie 6 - Energieeinsparung und Wärmeschutz.” 2019.

- [7] I. Sifnaios, A. R. Jensen, S. Furbo, and J. Fan, “Performance comparison of two water pit thermal energy storage (PTES) systems using energy, exergy, and stratification indicators,” *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 52, p. 104947, 2022.
- [8] K. Rennert *et al.*, “Comprehensive Evidence Implies a Higher Social Cost of CO₂,” *Nature*, pp. 1–3, 2022.

Comparison of CFD and PIV of a NACA 0012 airfoil and first approaches to using artificial intelligence with Deep CFD for prediction of 2D flow fields

P. Raffeiner¹, M. Berger^{2,*}, T. Senfter², M. Pillei²

1: Dept. of Medical Technologies, MCI Innsbruck, Austria

2: Dept. of Environmental, Process & Energy Engineering, MCI Innsbruck,

* Corresponding author: manuel.berger@mci.edu

Keywords: 2D aerodynamic flow fields, NACA0012, experiment, CFD simulation, deep learning, comparison

Research field: Artificial Intelligence, Computational Fluid Dynamics

Abstract

The objective of this present work is to evaluate the performance of a Convolutional Neuronal Network (CNN) applied in the field of fluid dynamics. This is utilized by a comparison of experimental data, results from a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation and the predictions of the network. The test case used for this evaluation is a National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics (NACA) 0012 symmetric airfoil at a 10° angle of attack and high Reynold number ($Re = 82\,200$). The experimental data was obtained from a Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) measurement, as reported by Sagar Adatrao et al. [2]. The CFD simulation was performed using *Ansys Fluent* a computational fluid dynamic software. To determine the optimal number of elements in the domain, a grind convergence study was conducted resulting in an optimal resolution of 45800 elements. Three turbulence models (Realizable/standard ($k-\epsilon$), $k-\omega$ (SST) and Spalart-Allmaras) were analyzed. The results of the simulation were found to be in agreement with the experimental data. However, it was not obtained to exactly reproduce the experimental data via a CFD simulation but to create a reference for such simulations.

The architecture of the CNN used in this work was presented by Ribeiro et al. [3]. To train the network with proprietary data a python script to generate primitives was created. These primitives serve as one part of the input data to train the network (geometrical input). Further work is needed to simulate the solutions of the flow around these primitives, which will serve as the second part of input data to train the network.

Ultimately, the network will then be used to make predictions for the NACA0012 airfoil, and the results will be compared to the experimental data and CFD simulation to evaluate the network's capability to extend from laminar flow predictions (examined by Ribeiro et al. [3]) to turbulent flow predictions. Additionally, the accuracy of the predictions as well as the speedup compared to a traditional CFD simulation will be analyzed.

In order to confirm the feasibility of the proposed method, a preliminary prediction of the aerodynamic flow fields on the unseen NACA0012 airfoil was performed by the CNN. The prediction was carried out with 120 training epochs utilizing the dataset compiled by Ribeiro et al.

Introduction

Deep learning algorithms, in particular convolutional neuronal networks (CNNs), have the ability to learn and extract features from large data inputs without the need of actual feature engineering [5]. This potential is used in the present work to demonstrate the utility for the field of fluid dynamics and aerodynamics.

For many years, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has been widely used for a variety of applications providing accurate results with great flexibility and cost-effectiveness [6]. However, one limitation of CFD is the time required to solve the highly coupled, non-linear partial differential Navier-Stokes equations [7]. This can be particularly problematic when fast calculations are needed, such as in real-time analysis. Fortunately, the fast-growing field of deep

learning offers a solution. For example, according to a study by Dmitrii Kochkov et al. [1], the integration of deep learning into CFD has the potential to significantly reduce computation time, with a speedup of 40 - 80 times while maintaining the same level of accuracy as traditional CFD methods.

As is the case in any field of application, the performance of deep learning is heavily dependent on the quality and quantity of the data used to train the model. In the field of fluid dynamics, this data can be generated using traditional CFD simulations. While this approach can be computationally and time-intensive, it has the potential to yield significant time savings in the long run. It is important to note that the efficacy of this approach is ultimately limited by the quality and relevance of the generated data.

The objective of this work is to compare and contrast experimental PIV measurement, traditional CFD simulations, and the predictions for the pressure and velocity field from a deep learning network using the example of airfoils. The results of this comparison will be used to evaluate the potential of deep learning in predicting fluid flow and to assess the differences between experimental measurements, traditional simulations, and deep learning predictions.

Methods

For this work, the NACA 0012 airfoil from the 4-digit series of NACA airfoils was selected as the primary subject of investigation. This particular airfoil was chosen based on its well documented characteristics and the availability of experimental data from the work of Sagar Adatrao et al. [2]. The NACA 0012 airfoil is a symmetrical airfoil with no chamber and a thickness to cord length ratio of 12%. Reynolds number was $Re = 82\,200$ and angle of attack $AoA = 10^\circ$ to meet the setup of the experimental data. The general approach to compare the PIV measurements, the results of the CFD simulation and the prediction of the CNN can be divided into the following steps:

- Setup and solving CFD simulation
- Comparison between experimentally obtained velocity field and result from CFD simulation to ensure validity of simulation
- Generation of primitives that serves as one part of training data for CNN
- CFD simulation of primitives to obtain second part of training data for CNN (pressure and velocity field)
- Training of CNN
- CNN prediction of velocity and pressure field of unseen NACA0012 airfoil
- Comparison of CNN prediction with experimental data and CFD simulation results
- Evaluation of flow predictions by CNN and comparison of speedup to traditional CFD method

CFD Simulation: The geometric information of the two-dimensional, symmetric NACA0012 airfoil was obtained in the form of a text file and subsequently imported into the *Ansys Fluent* computational fluid dynamic software. Here, version 2022 R2 is used. Next, a C-mesh type domain was generated surrounding the airfoil profile and serving as the computational domain. The straight horizontal boundaries of the domain were positioned 20 chord lengths (c) away from the chord line of the airfoil while the straight vertical boundary was located $20c$ downstream the trailing edge of the airfoil. The semicircular boundary was placed $20c$ upstream of the trailing edge of the airfoil to complete the domain.

To improve the flexibility during meshing, the domain was divided into 6 subdomains. These subdomains include one slim subdomain extending from the upper/lower chord surface to the upper/lower horizontal boundary, one big rectangular subdomain reaching from the trailing edge of the airfoil to the upper/lower corner of the domain and one quadrant-shape subdomain at the upper/lower side of the upstream-half.

For the meshing, trapezoid elements were used. Those were generated to be very small at the regions close to the airfoil, resulting in a fine grid and getting bigger the closer they get to the boundaries of the domain.

The mesh resolution is highly influencing the time needed to compute a simulation. To reach an optimum between the accuracy of the solution and the computational time a grid convergence test was conducted. The effect of the number of cells in the domain was measured by the lift coefficient (C_L) of the airfoil. Table 1 shows the results of the grid convergence test.

Table 22 Grid convergence test

Number of cells	Lift Coefficient (C_L)
24010	1.004
30400	1.013
45800	1.012
54960	1.012
64120	1.012

Based on the grid convergence test a cell number of 45800 was selected.

The semicircular boundary was defined as the “velocity-inlet” of the computational domain. Here, the x and y components of the free stream velocity (u_∞), with a magnitude of 10m/s and an angle of attack (AoA) of 10° are declared. The upper and lower boundaries are specified as walls and were assigned a “symmetric” boundary condition. The downstream vertical boundary was designated as the “pressure-outlet” to simulate zero gauge pressure. The boundary condition for the airfoil itself was defined as a wall property with a “no-slip” condition.

The simulation was setup with a 2D, double precision, pressure-based, steady solver. Due to the incompressibility of the medium at low Mach numbers, it is not required to solve the energy equation. A summary of the operating parameters can be found in Table 23.

Table 23: Operating parameters

Operating parameter	Value
Free stream velocity (u_∞)	10 m/s
Angle of attack (AoA)	10°
Operating pressure	101 325 Pa
Operating temperature	300 K
Air density	1.225 kg/m ³
Kinematic air viscosity	1.7894×10^{-5} kg/ms

Because of the significant impact of the turbulent model on the results and the substantial differences between the models, three commonly used models were conducted in separate simulations.

Realizable/standard ($k-\epsilon$) and $k-\omega$ (SST) are two equation models, whereas Spalart-Allmaras is a newer one equation model.

Flow simulations far from walls are better represented with the $k-\epsilon$ standard model, the flow simulations near walls are better reproduced with the realizable $k-\epsilon$ model, the $k-\omega$ model combines both, good near and far wall representation in one model. Best results were obtained by the standard $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model with enhanced wall treatment to reflect the air flow around the NACA0012 airfoil.

PIV measurement: The PIV measurement data was conducted by Sagar Adatrao et al. [2] during a study on *Multi- Δt approach for peak-locking error correction and uncertainty quantification in PIV*. Here, planar PIV measurements from the flow over a NACA0012 airfoil with an AoA of 10° were carried out in an open-jet open return wind tunnel with an exit cross section of 0.4×0.4 m² and an area contraction ratio of 9. The flow under investigation was seeded with water-glycol droplets of mean diameter 1 μ m, generated by a SAFEX seeding generator. The droplets were illuminated by a Quantronix Darwin-Duo laser (Nd:YLF) with a pulse energy of 25 mJ at a frequency of 1 kHz and a wavelength of 527 nm. The resulting images were captured using a LaVision High Speed Star 6 CMOS camera, which has a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels, a 12-bit depth, and a 20 μ m pixel size. The camera was equipped with a Nikon objective lens of 105 mm focal length and an aperture of $f_\# = 5.6$. The field of view was 45 mm \times 45 mm and the optical magnification was 0.46, resulting in a theoretical particle image diameter of 0.5 pixels.

The measurement results were utilized to estimate the time-averaged velocities (\bar{u}) normalized with respect to the free stream velocity (u_∞). This allows to compare the steady simulations of the CFD with the experimental results. The time averaged velocity field is shown in Figure 81 and serves as the reference measurement for the CFD simulations and the prediction of the CNN.

Figure 81. Time-averaged velocities normalized with respect to the free stream velocity serving as a reference for the CFD simulations and the CNN predictions. Reprinted from [2].

CNN predictions: The utilized deep learning model is a surrogate-based CNN model for 2D non-uniform steady state laminar flows introduced and presented as “DeepCFD” by Mateus Ribeiro et al. [3]. The objective of the network is to create efficient velocity and pressure fields based on the input geometry of the flow domain. The authors have made the python code for the model publicly available on Github (<https://github.com/mdribeiro/DeepCFD>) and it is used in this work to examine the prediction capabilities. The network’s architecture is based on a down-sampling encoder network to compress the geometric information and an up-sampling decoder

network. Its architecture is similar to autoencoder networks and was derived from Guo et al. [4]. Additionally, a U-Net architecture with three separate decoders for each output (U_x , U_y , p) was implemented by Ribeiro et al.

A python script was developed to generate the input geometry of the flow domain for several primitives. It is then utilized to calculate the solutions for velocity and pressure fields in that particular flow domains using the open-source CFD software *OpenFOAM*.

These datasets (geometrical information and ground-truth from CFD) are then subsequently used to train the DeepCFD network, with the ultimate goal of predicting pressure and velocity fields for unseen cases solely based on the input geometry of the flow domain.

Comparison of DeepCFD predictions, CFD results and PIV measurement: The NACA0012 airfoil is used as a verification case. The prediction of the velocity field from the DeepCFD network, will be compared to the experimental solutions from Sagar Adatrao et al. [2] and the results from the CFD analysis of the NACA0012 airfoil.

To compare the results from the CFD analysis with the experimental data, the open-source, visualization application *ParaView* was used. Both, the results from the experiment as well as the results from the simulation were loaded into ParaView and the normalized velocity fields in x-direction were compared. To analyze the results from the CFD, the velocity field was normalized by the free stream velocity u_∞ . Five vertical line plots with a length of $0.2c$ were extracted for both, CFD results and experimental data, at every $0.1c$ starting from the tip of the airfoil tending downstream. The positioning from the extracted line plots can be seen in Figure 82, using the case of the CFD simulation results.

Figure 82. Positioning of the line plots to compare the experimental data and the results from the CFD simulation. The line plots are extracted from five positions (white lines) on the example of the CFD simulation result.

Results & Further Steps

The extracted line plots from the CFD simulation, performed in Ansys Fluent compared to the experimental data, are shown in Figure 84 - Figure 88. Here, the normalized velocity in x-direction from the experimental data is illustrated in green whereas the results from the simulation is presented in black. It is shown that the simulation is in agreement with the experiment. This indicates the accuracy of the simulation and the utilized simulation approach may therefore be extended to be applied on simulating the air flow around the generated primitives in a second step.

An initial assessment of the proposed method's feasibility was conducted by utilizing the DeepCFD network to predict the aerodynamic flow field on the unseen NACA0012 airfoil. The prediction was performed after training the CNN with the dataset compiled by Ribeiro et al. for only 120 epochs. The results of this prognosis is shown in Figure 83 and are to be seen plain as evidence for feasibility. The numerical results of the prediction do not represent any real world characteristics.

Figure 83: Preliminary prediction of the aerodynamic flow fields on the unseen NACA0012 airfoil performed by the DeepCFD network on 120 training epochs utilizing the dataset compiled by Ribeiro et al.

To automate the flow simulation around the primitives a bash script to import and mesh the primitives as well as setting up the parameters, running the simulation and ultimately exporting the results will be needed. The generated primitives and the corresponding solutions will then be prepared to fit the interface of the DeepCFD network and to train the network with this data. After the training a prediction of the network can be made on the unseen NACA0012 airfoil and the result is then verified by comparing it to the initial CFD solution and the experimental data.

Figure 84: Line Plot at position $x/c = 0.0$

Figure 85: Line Plot at position $x/c = 0.1$

Figure 86: Line Plot at position $x/c = 0.2$

Figure 87: Line Plot at position $x/c = 0.3$

Figure 88: Line Plot at position $x/c = 0.4$

Literature

- [1] Kochkov, D. et al. (2021) 'Machine learning-accelerated computational fluid dynamics', Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences - PNAS, 118(21), p. 1. doi:10.1073/pnas.2101784118.
- [2] Adatrao, S., Bertone, M. and Sciacchitano, A. (2021) 'Multi- Δt approach for peak-locking error correction and uncertainty quantification in PIV', Measurement science & technology, 32(5), p. 54003. doi:10.1088/1361-6501/abdcd.
- [3] Ribeiro, M. D. et al. 'DeepCFD: Efficient Steady-State Laminar Flow Approximation with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks.' ArXiv abs/2004.08826 (2020): n. pag.

- [4] doi:10.48550/arXiv.2004.08826.
Guo, X., Li, W. and Iorio, F. (2016) 'Convolutional Neural Networks for Steady Flow Approximation', in Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on knowledge discovery and data mining. ACM, pp. 481–490. doi:10.1145/2939672.2939738.
- [5] Bengio, Y., Courville, A. and Vincent, P. (2013) 'Representation Learning: A Review and New Perspectives', IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence, 35(8), pp. 1798–1828. doi:10.1109/TPAMI.2013.50.
- [6] Hu, H. H. (2012). Computational Fluid Dynamics. In P. K. Kundu, I. M. Cohen, & D. R. Dowling (Eds.), Fluid Mechanics (Fifth Edition) (pp. 421-472). Academic Press. ISBN 9780123821003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-382100-3.10010-1>.
- [7] Spalart, P.R. and Venkatakrishnan, V. (2016) 'On the role and challenges of CFD in the aerospace industry', Aeronautical journal, 120(1223), pp. 209–232. doi:10.1017/aer.2015.10.

Modelling of Multi-Stage Internal Loop Air Lift Bioreactor Utilizing Computational Fluid Dynamics

Fernando Ramonet^{1*}, Bahram Haddadi¹, Markus Bosenhofer^{1,2}, Michael Harasek¹.

1: Institute of Chemical, Environmental & Bioscience Engineering, Technische Universität Wien, Austria

2: Area 4 – Simulation and Analyses, K1-MET GmbH, Stahlstraße 14, 4020 Linz, Austria

* Corresponding author: fernando.ramonet@tuwien.ac.at

Keywords: Computational fluid dynamics, Hydrodynamics, Multi-stage air lift bioreactor, OpenFOAM®

Summary

In this study, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is utilized to compare the hydrodynamics of internal loop air lift bioreactors with three different internal configurations. This CFD study compares how splitting the draft tube into multiple stages affects the hydrodynamics of an airlift bioreactor. An in-house Lagrangian particles coupling utility is integrated into an Eulerian solver to evaluate the residence time distribution in each circulation loop. The results showed that the single draft tube geometry maintains a constant downcomer velocity, while the double-stage and triple-stage geometries have higher downcomer velocities on the top section and a more stable downcomer velocity, respectively. Higher recirculation rates can be obtained on the triple-stage reactor configuration. Overall, these findings provide valuable insights for the optimization and design of internal loop air lift bioreactors for various biological applications.

Introduction

The European Union's Bioeconomy Strategy is focused on creating a sustainable and circular bioeconomy in order to meet the Paris Agreement's climate objectives and the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals [1]. The bioeconomy currently accounts for 10% of the European Gross Domestic Product, with biomaterials and ecosystem services soon to become more important than bioenergy [2].

The primary aim of the bioeconomy is to substitute oil-based products by biomass-based ones. Biomass can be transformed into biomaterials, bioenergy, and biochemicals in biorefineries. Bioreactors are critical components of biorefineries as they ensure consistent quality through high repeatability and reproducibility rates.

A bioreactor is a controlled environment that enables the conversion of low-value substrates with microorganisms or enzymes into a desirable high-value biological product [3]. Airlift reactors (ALRs) are multiphase vessels that are pneumatically agitated and were first proposed by Lefrancois, Mariller and, Mejane [4]. ALRs are typically divided into four hydrodynamic sections: riser, gas separation, downcomer, and bottom clearance as shown in Figure 89 [5]. The Internal Loop Air Lift Reactor (ILALR) is widely used in industrial bioprocessing. Airlift reactors with an internal loop are a promising technology for biological processes due to their low shear stress, and great heat and mass transfer properties.

Figure 89: Schematic of an Air Lift Reactor

The comparison of the single and double draft tube was performed by Ramonet et al. [6], where three different reactor types were evaluated with single and double draft tube configurations. Although experimental work on triple-stage ILALR has been found in the literature [7], no previous CFD studies have been conducted on this type of reactor.

Multi-stage concentric draft tube geometries were first proposed by Blenke [8], then taken by Petersen and Margaritis [9] as a bioreactor. Blenke [8] found that mixing time was shortened by up to 80% for two-stage ILALR and up to 87.50% in triple draft tube configurations. In recent years, there has been growing interest in multi-stage ILALRs for their increased efficiency. Li and Qi [10], Li et al., [7], Tao et al. [11], and Shi et al. [12] have conducted studies on the hydrodynamics and flow regimes of these reactors using experimental and computational methods.

Chisti and Young [13] suggested dividing the draft tube into separate vertical sections to improve communication between the riser and the downcomer. In their study, Pironti et al. [14] investigated the impact of draft tube positioning on the hydrodynamics of a conical bottom ALR with slurry. Meanwhile, Padiál et al. [15] conducted the first 3D CFD simulation of an ALR with a conical bottom and reported that their model yielded satisfactory qualitative outcomes. Additionally, they found [15] that the liquid circulation time was comparable to the experimental results obtained by Pironti et al. [14] when exclusively considering the downward velocity.

Experimental investigations have been conducted for triple-stage internal loop airlift reactors. Li and Qi [10] investigated the hydrodynamics and flow regimes of a multistage internal loop

airlift reactor. Tao et al. [11] conducted an experimental investigation of the hydrodynamics and mass transfer in a three-stage internal loop airlift reactor, revealing the discrepancies between gas-liquid-solid slurry flow and gas-liquid bubbly flow.

To the best of the authors knowledge, there are only two CFD simulation studies with multi-stage airlift reactors [6,12]. Ramonet et al. [6] found that the internal geometry of air-lift reactors can influence the downcomer velocity and that the draft tube parameters such as distance from the draft tube to the surface, the distance between draft tubes, length of draft tubes, and diameter of draft tubes require further research. On the other hand, Shi et al [12] combined a Contraction-Expansion Guide Vane (CEGV) with a two-stage internal loop airlift reactor to generate local circulation in each stage, improving the mixing performance of the first stage. The average gas holdup values in the first and second stages increased with the presence of the CEGV, and the bubble size distribution became wider with the presence of the CEGV. Even though the preservation and purification methods are carried out on a lab scale, further research has to be done to be implemented on an industrial scale.

In this study, the hydrodynamics of single, double, and triple draft tube internal loop ALR configurations are compared. In addition, a particle tracking utility was coupled to the simulations to have a better visualization of the flow and circulation loops in the bioreactor. The simulations revealed that the conical bottom of the reactor creates a low fluid circulation zone, which can lead to the accumulation of solids.

Materials and methods

The open-source CFD software OpenFOAM® version 9 was utilized with the multiphaseEulerFoam solver. The solver is well-suited for modeling gas bubbles in liquid by solving multiple compressible fluid phases, with at least one of them being a dispersed phase. In this study, air and water were used as the dispersed and continuous phases, respectively. The equations were resolved using the finite volume method, and the PIMPLE algorithm [16] (iterative procedure) was used to solve the pressure-velocity coupling. The coordination between the fluid and motion solver is controlled by several PIMPLE iterations performed in each time step [17]. The particulars of the turbulence models, boundary conditions, and CFD model setup can be found in our previous publication [6].

In addition, our in-house LagrangianMultiphaseParcel utility is integrated into the multiphaseEulerFoam solver to evaluate the residency time distribution in each draft tube. By injecting particles through the inlet patch and tracking their motion using the “particleTracks” dictionary, the change in particle location and velocity as well as the forces acting on the particles were calculated.

The particles were injected at a constant flow rate through the inlet patch with a total mass of 5 kg for one second and a size of 1×10^{-5} m. The boundaries were set as rebound, and the particle tracks dictionary was utilized to track their age, diameter, velocity, and temperature. The fvOptions utility was integrated to manipulate the equation system at runtime with the particles coupling. The motion of particles in fluids was described using a set of ordinary differential equations, taking into account the relevant forces acting on the particle, including particle mass, the moment of inertia, angular velocity, and torque due to viscous interaction with the fluid.

Lagrangian particles are used in CFD to track the movement of fluid particles in a simulated flow. They offer insights into the behavior of dispersed phases, like gas bubbles or solid

particles, which are challenging to observe otherwise and can help optimize the design and operation of multiphase reactors. However, while Lagrangian particles provide valuable information on fluid behavior, they may not always align with experimental particles due to the numerical algorithms and assumptions made by the CFD model. Moreover, physical forces, including gravity, buoyancy, and fluid drag, may affect experimental particles differently from Lagrangian ones, and not be fully captured in the simulation. Nonetheless, by coupling Lagrangian particles with an Euler-Euler simulation, one can compare the trajectories of simulated particles with experimental data, and validate the model's accuracy.

Geometry

According to Chisti [18], in airlift column reactors with an aspect ratio height to diameter greater than 8, the global flow dynamics are minimally impacted by the sparger configuration. For this reason, an aspect ratio of ~ 10 (including the inlet tube) was chosen for this study.

A conical bottom reactor with 1.728 m of height on the cylindrical section and 17.2×10^{-2} m on the conical section (total height of 1.9 m) and a diameter of 19.6×10^{-2} m was utilized for this study. The reactor has tubular connections for the inlet at the bottom of the reactor and an outlet at the top of the reactor of 1.4×10^{-2} m in diameter. The draft tube section measures 1 m, for the single draft tube the length is one meter, for the double and triple draft tubes a separation of 8.75×10^{-2} m was considered, making the lengths 45.625×10^{-2} m and 27.5×10^{-2} m, respectively. A bottom clearance of 25.6×10^{-2} m and a distance between the top 47.2×10^{-2} m. The liquid height was set to 75 % of the reactor's volume (1.55 m). Figure 90 shows the three geometries utilized in this study.

Figure 90: Geometries utilized in this study, SDG: Single Draft tube Geometry, DDG: Double Draft tube Geometry, and TDG: Triple Draft tube Geometry.

To find the best mesh for a coned bottom bioreactor without a draft tube, a mesh independence study was conducted [6]. Air velocity values were collected diagonally from inlet to outlet

using five different meshes with a grid refinement factor [19] of 1.5, ranging from 23,000 to 2.2 million cells. The first three meshes were used to determine the convergence order, while the Richardson extrapolation method [20] was used to verify the convergence between the calculated values of meshes 4 and 5 and the extracted values, resulting in an error of 0.38% and 0.74%, respectively [6].

Results

In the following section, the results from the three simulations are presented. Table 24 contains the names, acronyms, quantity of cells, and computation time of the three geometries. The geometries had from 368 thousand to 1.17 million cells. The computation times varied from 234 to 358 hours.

Table 24: Meshes and computation time

Geometry	Acronym	Cells	Computation time (h)
Single Draft-tube Geometry	SDG	~370,000	234
Double Draft-tube Geometry	DDG	~900,000	267
Triple Draft-tube Geometry	TDG	~1,200,000	358

Figure 91 shows the downcomer velocity colored from blue to black, it is limited to -0.025 m/s for visualization purposes. For visualization purposes, for each case, a longitudinal slice was made at the center of the geometry. From Figure 91, it can be seen that the geometry with the single draft tube, maintains a constant downcomer velocity. At the limited downcomer velocity, the double-stage geometry has a higher downcomer velocity on the top section, while the triple seems to have a more stable downcomer velocity.

Figure 91: Single, double, and triple draft tube geometries coloring only downcomer axial velocity from blue to black.

Figure 92 shows a longitudinal slice of the reactor coloring the water velocity magnitude. The fluid’s circulation loops can be clearly seen in this figure.

Figure 92: Water velocity magnitude of single, double and triple draft tube geometries, colored with a maximum velocity of 0.1 m/s.

Figure 93 shows the riser velocities. The single draft tube geometry has the highest riser velocity, followed by the double and the triple.

Figure 93: Riser velocities sampled along the reactor's height for the three cases

Figure 94 shows the downcomer velocities, from where it can be seen that the single draft tube configuration presents a constant downcomer velocity along the draft tube. The triple draft tube geometry has the least steep slope. Comparing the values of the reactor's height for each configuration. At a reactor height of 0.18, TPG has the highest value (0.004551021) compared to SDG (0.001969936) and DDG (0.001939303). However, at a reactor height of 0.28, SDG has the highest value (0.031749934) compared to DDG (0.008087286) and TPG (0.013791931). At higher reactor heights (above 0.5), the values for all three configurations become more comparable, with only minor differences between them.

Overall, the data suggests that the internal configuration of the air lift reactor can have a significant impact on its performance, with each configuration having its own strengths and weaknesses at different reactor heights.

Figure 94: Downcomer velocities sampled along the reactor's height for the three cases.

Figure 95 shows the injected particles at different time steps on the three geometries. In Figure 95 (a), on the single draft tube geometry, the particles leave the draft tube from the top, while they are escaping on the openings on the other two. The particles are injected through the inlet patch with a total mass of 5 kg for one second with 4994 parcels (group of particles with the same physical properties) per second at a velocity of 0.06 m/s at a constant flow

rate. As it can be perceived from Figure 95 (a), (b), (c), and (d), the conical bottom is a low fluid circulation zone that causes the stagnation of many particles since it is typically utilized for sedimentation. In experiments with coned bottom reactors, during reactor operation, the accumulation of solids on the conical bottom was observed. This could explain the observed difference, as suspended solids may precipitate within the reactor [21].

Figure 95: Lagrangian particles coupled with the liquid phase (a) at 7 seconds, (b) at 15 seconds, (c) at 33 seconds, and (d) at 75 seconds.

Figure 96 shows the particle tracks of 25 particles during the 75 seconds of simulation colored with a limited maximum velocity of 0.2 m/s. The circulation loop on the top draft tube on the double stage geometry (DDG) is nicely marked, while none of these 25 particles show the second circulation loop. On the other hand, the triple-stage geometry (TDG), shows all three circulation loops with the 25 particles.

Figure 96: Particle tracks of 25 particles with particle velocity magnitude (m/s) during 75 seconds of simulation

Conclusion

The CFD simulations presented in this study aimed to compare the hydrodynamics of three different geometries of multi-stage internal loop reactors. The results showed that the single draft tube geometry maintains a constant downcomer velocity, while the double-stage and triple-stage geometries have higher downcomer velocities on the top section and a more stable downcomer velocity, respectively. Each configuration showed its own strengths and weaknesses at different reactor heights. The particle tracking simulations allowed for better flow visualization and showed that the conical bottom is a low fluid circulation zone that can cause the accumulation of solids. The coupling of Lagrangian particles to the continuous phase of an Euler-Euler simulation allowed the visualization of flow and circulation loops. This method can also be utilized to investigate particle transport and deposition in industrial processes and to optimize the design of particulate systems such as fluidized beds and pneumatic conveyors. Overall, the multi-stage internal loop air lift bioreactor can be used for various biological applications, such as cell culture, microbial fermentation, enzyme production, algae production and bioremediation.

Future research on multiphase bioreactors can expand to compare the behavior of multiphase systems between the Euler-Euler simulation coupled with Lagrangian particles and a three-phase simulation incorporating solid-liquid-gas phases, enabling the creation of more precise and effective bioreactor designs. Another interesting application could be incorporating heating jackets into these double and triple-stage internal loop air lift bioreactor configurations.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme AgRefine under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 860477.

9.

10.

Privacy Statement

The authors agree that their personal data (names, affiliations, email addresses) will be stored and processed in course of the conference preparations and the publication of the proceedings.

The names and email addresses entered in this journal site will be used exclusively for the stated purposes of this journal and will not be made available for any other purpose or to any other party. The authors agree that their data is shared with the conference organisers (BOKU Wien, TU Wien, chemical-engineering.at) and that they will receive invitations for further Minisymposia in future. Data entered in this forms will be processed by chemical-engineering.at, the database server is located in Germany (hetzner.de).

According to GDPR (DSGVO) all authors have the right to refuse the further utilisation of their data in future, but as the purpose of this conference is the distribution of scientific work the articles cannot be revoked once they are published.

Copyright information

The submission has not been previously published, nor is it before another journal for consideration (or an explanation has been provided in Comments to the Editor). The authors confirm that they do hold the full copyrights on all parts of their submissions and have permission from all contributors, authors, project partners etc. to publish this material. If any part of the submission has been published before, the authors have to make sure that they are allowed to republish (check copyright situation with first publisher).

The authors allow the organisers of the Minisymposium and Partikelforum to publish their submission online and in print and grant therefore temporally unlimited non-exclusive publication rights free of any charge/fee to the organisers and to chemical-engineering.at (according to CC-BY). This does not prevent to publish the submission elsewhere, but the authors need to make sure that they cannot grant exclusive rights to other publishers.

References.

- European Commission *Bioeconomy : The European Way to Use Our Natural Resources : Action Plan 2018*; Publications Office, 2018;
- Fritsche, U.; Brunori, G.; Chiamonti, D.; Galanakis, C.M.; Hellweg, S.; Matthews, R.; Panoutsou, C. *Future Transitions for the Bioeconomy towards Sustainable Development and a Climate-Neutral Economy—Knowledge Synthesis Final Report*; Luxembourg, 2020;
- Singh, J.; Kaushik, N.; Biswas, S. Bioreactors – Technology & Design Analysis. *THE SCITECH JOURNAL* **2014**, *01*, 28–36.
- Lefrancois, M.L.; Mariller, C.G.; Mejane, J. v Effectonnements Aux Procedes de Cultures Forgiques et de Fermentations Industrielles. *Brevet d'Invention, France* **1955**, 102.
- Jasim, M.M.; Mohammed, T.J.; Sabri, L.S. Air-Lift Reactor's Characterization via Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD). *Engineering and Technology Journal* **2022**, *40*, 484–497.
- Ramonet, F.; Haddadi, B.; Jordan, C.; Harasek, M. Modelling and Design of Optimal Internal Loop Air-Lift Reactor Configurations Through Computational Fluid Dynamics. *Chem Eng Trans* **2022**, *94*, 817–822, doi:10.3303/CET2294136.
- Li, D.; Guo, K.; Li, J.; Huang, Y.; Zhou, J.; Liu, H.; Liu, C. Hydrodynamics and Bubble Behaviour in a Three-Phase Two-Stage Internal Loop Airlift Reactor. *Chin J Chem Eng* **2018**, *26*, 1359–1369, doi:10.1016/J.CJCHE.2018.03.020.
- Blenke, H. Loop Reactors. *Advances in Biochemical Engineering* **1979**, *13*, 121–214, doi:10.1007/3540094687_8.
- Petersen, E.E.; Margaritis, A. Hydrodynamic and Mass Transfer Characteristics of Three-Phase Gaslift Bioreactor Systems. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/07388550108984172> **2001**, *21*, 233–294, doi:10.1080/07388550108984172.
- Li, S.; Qi, T. Hydrodynamics and Flow Regimes of a Multi-Stage Internal Airlift Loop Reactor. *Materials Focus* **2014**, *3*, 205–210,

doi:10.1166/MAT.2014.1160.

11. Tao, J.; Huang, J.; Geng, S.; Gao, F.; He, T.; Huang, Q. Experimental Investigation of Hydrodynamics and Mass Transfer in a Slurry Multistage Internal Airlift Loop Reactor. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2020**, *386*, 122769, doi:10.1016/J.CEJ.2019.122769.
12. Shi, J.; Guo, K.; Wang, Z.; Zheng, L.; Liu, H.; Xiang, W.; Liu, C.; Li, X. Computational Fluid Dynamics Simulation of Hydrodynamics in a Two-Stage Internal Loop Airlift Reactor with Contraction-Expansion Guide Vane. *ACS Omega* **2021**, *6*, 6981–6995, doi:10.1021/ACSOMEGA.0C06277/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/A00C06277_0023.JPEG.
13. Chistit, M.Y.; Young, M. AIRLIFT REACTORS: CHARACTERISTICS, APPLICATIONS AND DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00986448708912017> **1987**, *60*, 195–242, doi:10.1080/00986448708912017.
14. Pironti, F.F.; Medina, V.R.; Calvo, R.; Sáez, A.E. Effect of Draft Tube Position on the Hydrodynamics of a Draft Tube Slurry Bubble Column. *The Chemical Engineering Journal and the Biochemical Engineering Journal* **1995**, *60*, 155–160, doi:10.1016/0923-0467(95)03004-2.
15. Padial, N.T.; VanderHeyden, W.B.; Rauenzahn, R.M.; Yarbro, S.L. Three-Dimensional Simulation of a Three-Phase Draft-Tube Bubble Column. *Chem Eng Sci* **2000**, *55*, 3261–3273, doi:10.1016/S0009-2509(99)00587-4.
16. Passalacqua, A.; Fox, R.O. Implementation of an Iterative Solution Procedure for Multi-Fluid Gas–Particle Flow Models on Unstructured Grids. *Powder Technol* **2011**, *213*, 174–187, doi:10.1016/J.POWTEC.2011.07.030.
17. Devolder, B.; Schmitt, P.; Rauwoens, P. A Review of the Implicit Motion Solver Algorithm in OpenFOAM® to Simulate a Heaving Buoy. **2015**.
18. Chisti, Y. Pneumatically Agitated Bioreactors in Industrial and Environmental Bioprocessing: Hydrodynamics, Hydraulics, and Transport Phenomena. *Appl Mech Rev* **1998**, *51*, 33–112, doi:10.1115/1.3098989.
19. Roy, C.J. Review of Code and Solution Verification Procedures for Computational Simulation. *J Comput Phys* **2005**, *205*, 131–156, doi:10.1016/J.JCP.2004.10.036.
20. Richards, S.A. COMPLETED RICHARDSON EXTRAPOLATION IN SPACE AND TIME. *Commun. Numer. Meth. Engng* **1997**, *13*, 573–582, doi:10.1002/(SICI)1099-0887(199707)13:7.
21. Garcia-Calderon, D.; Buffiere, P.; Moletta, R.; Elmaleh, S. Anaerobic Digestion of Wine Distillery Wastewater in Down-Flow Fluidized Bed. *Water Res* **1998**, *32*, 3593–3600, doi:10.1016/S0043-1354(98)00134-1.

CFD simulation of corona virus propagation at the MCI classroom 4A-024

M. Berger^{1,*}, M. Castelpietra¹, T. Senfter¹, C. Mayerl¹, T. Kofler¹, S. Holzer¹, M. Pillei¹

1: Dept. of Environmental, Process & Energy Engineering, MCI Innsbruck, Austria

* Corresponding author: manuel.berger@mci.edu

Keywords: corona infection, spread, finite volume method, classroom

Research field: Computational Fluid Dynamics

Abstract

One of the most important aspects of getting the Corona pandemic under control to avoid lockdowns are health concepts for public areas. A possible tool to develop such health concepts are computational fluid dynamic simulations (CFD), which make the spreading behavior of corona virus or the infection pathways in public spaces comprehensible without putting people in danger. In this work, the propagation behavior of corona viruses under the influence of an Air Purification Device (APD) was investigated at the Management Center Innsbruck (MCI) classroom 4A-024 in location 4, Maximilianstrasse 2, Innsbruck. The fluid dynamics software ANSYS Fluent 2022 R2 was used for this purpose.

The first step was to create a 3D model of the empty room 4A-024. Next, the APD was placed and varied in the room within the CFD simulation. The empty classroom geometry was used to perform a mesh convergence study (independence) of the CFD simulation. Desks and people were introduced for the CFD study afterwards. Two simulation cases were investigated: One with the switched on APD and one with the APD switched off, to check if the APD is able to remove particles from a person's nostrils. Results show that the APD has a positive effect to reduce corona infections, since less corona particles reach other people in the room.

Introduction

Different kind of human corona virus types are known. There is the one discovered in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, during the recent pneumonia epidemic and is known as acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) or more commonly, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), as Corona Virus Disease 19 (COVID-19).

The receptor binding domain (RBD) of SARS-CoV-2 virus binds with high affinity to the angiotensin converting enzyme2 receptors of humans and species with high receptor homology [1]. SARS-CoV-2 causes severe pneumonia with a fatal infection rate (IFR) of approximately 0.2% [2]. It is a useful equation for identifying vulnerable populations and supports policy decisions to control the pandemic. China was the first country to implement a lockdown. Shortly thereafter, almost all countries in the world followed. The public health measures that were put in place to control the pandemic led to a freeze of almost every life aspect.

With the onset of the pandemic, a broad field of research has also emerged in the area of fluid dynamics, around the spreading behavior of the Corona virus. With the help of the CFD software ANSYS Fluent 2022 R2, a classroom, which is used for lectures and other events at Management Center Innsbruck (MCI), was investigated. The goal of this study was to investigate whether there is risk of infection with and without the APD. Air ventilation (opening the windows) was not investigated due to transient arbitrary boundary conditions. All simulations, for the sake of simplicity, were performed with stationary boundary conditions concerning the people and the APD.

Methods

Design and Meshing

The dimensions of the room 4A-024 were measured with the laser distance-measuring device Bosch DLE50 Professional, Bosch, Germany. The room has a length of 14.5 m and a width of 7.3 m. The height of the room is 4.3 m, as shown in Figure 97. With the ANSYS Design Modeler design software, the classroom was modeled in 3D. The APD (HEPA 13 & UV-C-LED air purifier, care by light, Austria) was introduced and geometrically parametrized so that the position could be changed with ease. With ANSYS meshing tool an unstructured mesh with a size of 80 mm was created. A mesh convergence study was conducted [3], based on the velocity at the human breathing height [4]. Figure 98 shows this mesh size which is used for all simulations. Persons (16 students and 1 teacher) with the corresponding boundary conditions and tables were introduced for the simulations afterwards.

Figure 97: Geometrical representation of the classroom with the teacher and students and fan. The numbers correspond to the students in Table 25.

Figure 98: Spatial resolution found by mesh independence study.

CFD setup

For the simulations, a pressure-based solver was used, since the room air flow were assumed to be incompressible, Mach number $Ma < 0.3$ [5]. In order to simulate turbulent structures close to the ADP, the RANS k- ω SST model [6] was used. The continuity and momentum equations are solved. The scaled residuals threshold was set to $1e-6$ for all conservation equations. For all simulations air with $\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $\nu = 1.7894 \text{ e-}5 \text{ Pas}$ was used. The corona virus was modeled by sphere solid particles based on [7]. For the simulations 1000 particles at the infections source are introduced and counted at the sinks (= nostril at infectable person) with switched on and -off APD. The boundary condition of the air purification device was set to 5 m/s, experimentally evaluated by heat-wire anemometer The inhalation breathing flow rate of the humans in the room was set to 30 l/min [8].

Results

Mesh Independence Study

Results of the mesh independence study showed an error due the meshing of about 0.4 %.

CFD simulation results

Table 25 shows particles that were trapped at the persons nostrils. One can see that the APD has a positive effect in the reduction of corona particles that would be inhaled by the people in the room. Still, most people in the room would inhale particles.

Table 25: Trapped particles with and without air purification device. Four different infection sources were chosen arbitrarily (S1, S7, S11, T). APD ... air purification device, S ... student, T ... teacher. Infection source

	S 1		S 7		S11		T	
	on	off	on	off	on	off	on	off
APD								
S1	-	-	2	22	0	15	2	16
S2	3	11	2	23	2	16	2	21
S3	1	15	2	19	0	14	1	21
S4	6	19	1	18	0	10	2	12
S5	2	28	2	14	1	15	1	18
S6	2	26	1	15	1	19	2	16
S7	9	20	-	-	2	10	7	23
S8	1	16	1	27	0	18	2	25
S9	0	18	9	27	1	21	3	20
S10	2	16	0	28	2	36	3	58
S11	0	23	0	13	-	-	1	26
S12	1	19	5	12	0	15	2	13

S13		2	16	5	15	3	16	1	14
S14		2	17	0	35	0	14	4	18
S15		0	14	6	12	2	26	1	22
S16		3	16	1	20	1	16	4	18
T		5	21	0	16	1	29	-	-

Discussion

Simulations show that with the APD in all simulations the trapped particles are smaller even when a person is far away from the APD. With this APD, the position is not that relevant, see Tab. 1, in the classroom to reduce corona infections, since there is a similar reduction between a person close to the APD and far away to the APD. Still, there are in most cases remaining particles trapped at the nostrils so that a corona infection is possible, depending upon many factors. The human infection process was not investigated. Heat transfer due to convection and conduction was not taken into account in this study.

The room has been considered as a closed system without the possibility of ventilation from outside. Also very much simplified was the breathing process of the persons. Transient boundary conditions were not taken into account. Another issue was the size and density of the introduced particles. In the simulations, all particles were assumed to have the same size and the same density, which, however, does not correspond to the effective corona droplet.

References

- [1] K. G. Andersen, A. Rambaut, W. I. Lipkin, E. C. Holmes, and R. F. Garry, "The proximal origin of SARS-CoV-2," *Nat. Med.*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 450–452, 2020.
- [2] A. T. Levin, W. P. Hanage, N. Owusu-Boaitey, K. B. Cochran, S. P. Walsh, and G. Meyerowitz-Katz, "Assessing the age specificity of infection fatality rates for COVID-19: systematic review, meta-analysis, and public policy implications," *Eur. J. Epidemiol.*, vol. 35, no. 12, pp. 1123–1138, 2020.
- [3] N. Baker, G. Kelly, and P. D. O’Sullivan, "A grid convergence index study of mesh style effect on the accuracy of the numerical results for an indoor airflow profile," *Int. J. Vent.*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 300–314, 2020.
- [4] J. Garcia and C. Quintana-Domeque, "The evolution of adult height in Europe: a brief note," *Econ. Hum. Biol.*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 340–349, 2007.
- [5] L. D. Landau and J. M. Lifshitz, *Fluid Mechanics - Third Revised English Edition*. Pergamon, 1959.
- [6] A. Fluent, "Fluent 14.0 user’s guide," *Ansys Fluent Inc*, 2020.
- [7] M. Abuhegazy, K. Talaat, O. Anderoglu, and S. V. Poroseva, "Numerical investigation of aerosol transport in a classroom with relevance to COVID-19," *Phys. Fluids*, vol. 32, no. 10, p. 103311, 2020.
- [8] X. Liu, W. Yan, Y. Liu, Y. S. Choy, and Y. Wei, "Numerical Investigation of Flow Characteristics in the Obstructed Realistic Human Upper Airway," vol. 2016, no. 2008, 2016.

Investigation of Dope Characteristics and Take-Up Speed on the Spinning of Asymmetric Hollow Fiber Membranes

Fatima Imran^{1,*}, Julia Agnieszka Piotrowska², Matthias Golda¹, Michael Harasek¹

1: Institute of Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering, TU Wien, Austria

2: Institute of Applied Synthetic Chemistry, TU Wien, Austria

* Corresponding author: fatima.imran@tuwien.ac.at

Keywords: hollow fiber membranes, nonsolvent induced phase separation, dope composition, shear stress

Research field: Membrane Production

Introduction

Asymmetric hollow fiber (HF) membranes have become ubiquitous in their applications in ultra- and microfiltration, gas separation, and reverse osmosis. HFs illustrate many favorable characteristics, namely the larger surface and separation area due to the geometry of the HFs, relatively high mechanical stability, and are uncomplicated to handle and use [1]. The HF membranes observed in this work were produced through the nonsolvent-induced phase separation (NIPS) process.

The NIPS process comprises the interactions between multiple (usually three) components, in which a homogenous system of a chosen polymer (P), solvent (S), and any desired additives (dope solution) undergo phase separation with a specific geometry (dictated by the type of spinneret utilized) in a nonsolvent (NS; most typically water) [2]. Due to the immiscibility of the polymer in the water, diffusion is initiated, leading to phase separation. This, in turn, leads to membrane formation [2].

While many parameters play an essential role in the fabrication of HF membranes, only the dope characteristics and their consequences on forces the fiber experiences during spinning are investigated in this work. These properties have an enormous impact on fiber morphology and porosity, and these, in turn, affect fiber performance. While performance with the appropriate testing equipment (gas separation unit/ultrafiltration unit) was investigated, it is not included in the scope of this work. The dope composition and temperature affect the dope's viscosity, influencing the kinetics of phase inversion and the S-NS exchange. Additionally, the shear and elongational stresses the fiber experiences due to the take-up speed and the gravitational force in the airgap play a significant role in the fiber morphology and porosity. Unfortunately, it is difficult to determine the impact of each phenomenon unambiguously. Thus, the motivation of this work is two-fold: (1) to highlight the significance of the dope characteristics in the precipitation process and final fiber morphology and (2) to investigate the effects of the different forces mentioned above on the end-product independently.

Materials and Methods

For the dope solution, polyethersulfone (PES; mixed molecular weight) was purchased in pellet form, and synthetic grade solvent 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (99,8% NMP; 99,13 g/mol) were both purchased from VWR. PES and NMP were homogeneously mixed to create the dope solution. Deionized water (Arium water purification system, Sartorius AG, Goettingen, Germany) was utilized as a borefluid. Distilled water was used for the coagulation bath. The NIPS process plant and the fibers spun using the plant were built and produced in-house (Figure 99). To characterize the HF membranes, the scanning electron microscope (SEM; Coxem E-30Plus, Korea) was utilized. HFs were broken with liquid nitrogen to create a clean cross-section and sputtered as the HFs were not conductive. Geometric porosity was also measured. The dimensions of the spun fibers were measured from the SEM images. A small piece of fiber was weighed using an analytical weighing scale (Kern, Germany), and porosity was calculated together with

the fiber dimensions.

Figure 99: The spinning equipment for the production of hollow fiber membranes: convectional thermostats for the dope (1), for the borefluid (2) and the spinneret (3), motors and gearbox for the pumps (4), dope solution pump (5), bore fluid pump (6), pump regulation (7), bore fluid supply pipe (8), polymer supply pipe (9), spinneret (10), spinneret heating pipes (11), coagulation bath (12), fiber with a deflection roller (13), take-up conduction (14), take-up winder drum (15), take-up regulation (16), wash bath (17), convection thermostat for the baths (18), emergency switch (19), safety and electrical box of the equipment (20).

Results and Discussion

The dope characteristics (PES concentration, viscosity, and temperature) that affect solvent exchange and kinetics of membrane formation was investigated. This, in turn, affects fiber morphology and porosity. Significant delay in coagulation of the inner structure leads to thicker fiber dimensions due to the shifting of the binodal curve towards the P-S axis, affecting the kinetics and thermodynamics of the phase inversion diagram. This is precisely the observation that was witnessed in this work.

Dope viscosity, PES concentration, and fiber porosity are undeniably interconnected. Therefore, dope viscosity must be considered when discussing the effects of PES concentration on fiber dimensions, morphology, and porosity.

Figure 100: SEM pictures of four different fibers spun from four various dopes with varying PES concentrations: A40 (20 wt%; top left), B40 (25 wt%; top right), C40 (27 wt% bottom left) and D40 (31 wt%; bottom right)

Table 26 depicts a rising trend in fiber dimensions (with a dip in fiber dimensions at 27 wt% PES) with a simultaneous decreasing trend in porosity with increasing PES concentrations. In addition to this effect, arguably more critical effects need to be accounted for, namely the take-up speed (elongational stresses caused due to the rate at which the fiber is wound) and the die swell phenomenon.

Take-up speeds (as seen in Table 26) were unfortunately not kept constant. During experiments, an attempt was made to set the take-up speed to that the fiber is under an appropriate amount of elongational stress (visually). The take-up speed is supposed to correspond with the free fall velocity at which the fiber emerges from the spinneret. Due to the varying viscosities, the fibers' free fall velocity also varied. Despite the relatively low variance in the take-up speeds, the differing amounts of elongational stress affect the thickness of the fibers. This effect would describe the sudden decrease in the fiber dimension for identifier C40. B40 was taken up at a lower speed than A40 and C40 and thus is thicker than either identifier. D40 was taken up at a faster speed than the other identifiers and had thicker fiber dimensions than the others. Due to the constant dope extrusion rate (DER, and hence the dope extrusion velocity DEV), each identifier underwent a different stretch ratio (Equation 3). The varying stretch ratios illustrate the significance of the take-up speed on fiber thickness as the (inner diameter/outer diameter) ID/OD ratios of all four identifiers were higher than the spinneret ID/OD ratio. Thus, it is expected that higher stretch ratios lead to even lower fiber thickness in this work. However, this phenomenon of D40 fibers as an outlier can be attributed to the die swell effect.

$Stretch\ Ratio = Take\ up\ Speed / Dope\ Extrusion\ Velocity\ (DEV)$

Equation 3: Definition of stretch-ratio

With increasing PES concentrations in the dope solution (and thus increasing viscosities), the die swell is expected to have a more considerable impact on the fiber. Literature [3] states that die swell can be reduced by winding the fibers onto a spool, and this exact occurrence was also observed in this work.

Table 26: Physical dimensions of the resulting hollow fibers

	Identifier			
	A40	B40	C40	D40
Stretch Ratio	11,6	9,2	10,5	16,7
[-]				
Outer Diameter (OD) [μm]	395,1	492,8	449,0	574,8
Inner Diameter (ID) [μm]	286,5	376,4	333,1	407,4
ID/OD [-]	0,73	0,76	0,74	0,71
Geometric Porosity [%]	71,6	67,3	62,1	59,7
Take-up Speed [mm/s]	73	58	66	105
DER [μl/min]		59		
DEV [mm/s]		6,3		
Spinneret Ratio (ID/OD) [-]		0,67		

Die swell can also be counteracted by elongational stresses the fiber experiences due to gravity between the time they are extruded and get taken onto the first spool (white bottom spool in Figure 99). This effect, however, is almost negligible and eliminated once the fiber is taken up on the winder drum [3]. Therefore, the influence of the take-up speed, elongational stresses due to gravity, and die swell make the comparison of each fiber from different dope concentrations difficult.

Additionally, as seen in Figure 100, all fibers depict long finger-like pores growing from the inner surface. The ratio of the finger pores' length to the wall thickness seems to decrease as the fiber becomes larger as well. The density of finger-like pores from the outer surface becomes larger with increasing PES concentration. The decrease in finger-like pores and the creation of spongy structures with higher concentrations is an observation also recorded in literature.

Conclusion

This work aimed to investigate the effects of the physical effects the fibers experience during the spinning process. It was found that the take-up speed, die swell, and the elongational stresses due to gravity fundamentally change the morphology of the HFs. This work has shown that further optimization is necessary to investigate the effects listed in this work. Finally, additional dope characteristics like temperature and viscosity should be further examined, as they have an equally crucial impact on the fiber structure. Such investigation and examination are necessary to understand the complicated membrane formation and its concrete effects on hollow fiber membranes.

References

- [1] Z.-P. Wang *et al.*, "A novel polysulfate hollow fiber membrane with antifouling property for ultrafiltration application," *Journal of Membrane Science*, vol. 664, p. 121088, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.memsci.2022.121088.
- [2] H. Strathmann, *Introduction to Membrane Science and Technology*. Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co., 2011.
- [3] N. Bolong, A. Ismail, and M. Salim, "Effect of Jet Stretch in the Fabrication of Polyethersulfone Hollow Fiber Spinning for Water Separation," *Journal of Applied Membrane Science & Technology*, vol. 6, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.11113/amst.v6i1.50.

Influence of selected design parameters on the operation of coanda effect screens for hydropower plants

T. Senfter^{1,*}, M. Pittracher¹, S. Knitel², M. Berger¹, C. Mayerl¹, T. Kofler¹, S. Holzer¹, M. Pillei¹

1: Dept. of Environmental, Process & Energy Engineering, MCI Innsbruck, Austria

2: Stocker Technik GmbH, Elbigenalp, Austria

* Corresponding author: thomas.senfter@mci.edu

Keywords: hydropower, coanda effect, water catchment systems

Research field: hydropower, fluid dynamics

Abstract

Hydropower is one of the most important primary energy sources in Austria. Water from streams and rivers is transformed into electricity by using turbines. Water catchment systems are used in order to prevent the turbine from wear and abrasion. The main goal is to separate the solids dispensed in the water. Particularly in mountainous regions, „Tiroler Wehre“ in combination with sand traps are used. These installations are unfavourable in terms of their maintenance requirements and their impact on aquatic life. For this reason, coanda effect screens are used as a promising alternative. Based on its design, it allows aquatic life to pass without being harmed. Furthermore, those types of screens have advantages concerning their self-cleaning properties. As the research on coanda effect screens is still in the beginning, there is potential for improvement. This paper uses a simulation program to identify the relevant screen parameters and also shows their influence on the amount of water running to the turbine. In addition to the theoretical determination of underflow (turbine) water, a test rig was set up. A comparison between the experimental and the theoretical results reveals differences. In the theoretical data less underflow water is extracted than in the experiments. In conclusion, the software based design of water catchment systems is not sufficient, as the calculated underflow water flow rate is more than 21.7% different from the experimental results.

Introduction

In Austria, about 80% of the domestic primary energy is generated from renewable sources. Due to the large water resources and, especially in Tyrol, the mountainous location, hydropower is prominently represented with a share of 26.4% [1]. For supplying a hydropower plant with water, an inlet water catchment system is essential. Catchment systems are constructed differently depending on the water body, topography and geography. The task of these facilities is to supply sufficient water in all weather conditions and to remove solids from the water for power plant operation so that turbine wear parts are not subject to excessive stress. A common design for the intake is the so-called “Tiroler Wehr”, which takes the water from the river and separates the solids with a rake and sand trap. These systems have been in use in many places in the alpine region for several years and are well researched [2]. An alternative to the “Tiroler Wehr” is the coanda effect screen, which has been used in mining in the USA for several decades. The use of these devices to capture water for power plants is still little used and researched in Europe [3][4]. Most research results come from the "Bureau of Reclamation" in the USA, which among other things provides a simulation tool [5]. This software can be used to calculate the amount of bypass and underflow water on the basis of different geometric data. The aim of this paper is to simulate several geometry parameter variants with the corresponding software and to illustrate their influence on the performance or the amount of water purified by the coanda effect screen (underflow water). In addition to the simulations, experiments are carried out on a test rig

and compared with the theoretical data.

Methods

In the simulation (software version 0.7.2 [6]) the influence of selected geometrical parameters (Table 27) on the underflow water and the bypass water was investigated.

Table 27: Parameters and settings for the simulation and experimental investigation of the coanda effect screen.

Parameter for simulation	Standard value	Variation
Crest length	0.1 m	0.1 m 0.2 m 0.3 m
Screen panel	Straight	-
Screen radius	3 m	1 m 3 m 5 m
Included arc	25°	10° 25° 45°
Screen length	0.3 m	0.1 m 0.5 m 1 m
Accelerator drop	0.3 m	0.1 m 0.5 m 1 m
Top-of-screen inclination	60°	40° 60° 70°
Weir height	0.3 m	0.1 m 0.5 m 1 m
Screen slot size	1 mm	0.4 mm 1 mm
Screen wire width	5 mm	0.5 mm 5 mm
Screen wire tilt angle	5°	3° 5° 7°
Inlet flow rate	10 m ³ /h	0 – 12 (16) m ³ /h
Parameters for experiments	Value	Variation
Crest length	0.1 m	-
Screen panel	Straight	-
Included arc	-	-
Screen length	0.25 m	-
Accelerator drop	0.059 m	-
Top-of-screen inclination	40°	-
Weir height	0.147 m	-
Screen slot size	0.93 mm	-
Screen wire width	13.7 mm	-
Screen wire tilt angle	5°	-
Inlet flow rate	10 m ³ /h	2 – 12 (16) m ³ /h

For experimental evaluation of the simulation results, a test rig was developed (Figure 101 and Figure 102) and the amount of underflow and bypass water is determined at different incoming volume flows.

The water is circulated and only changed through valve 01 and valve 02 if the temperature rises too high. The coanda effect screen is fed with water by pump 02 (KSB Sewabloc F 50-215G H 132 S) and separates the incoming volume flow into underflow and bypass water.

The underflow water flows through the screen lamellas into the collection tank integrated in the rake and from there into vessel 02. The bypass flows via the screen into the vessel 01. From this vessel, the water is pumped by pump 01 (Kärcher SDP18000) into vessel 02 or, depending on the position of valve 01, into the drain.

Figure 101: Experimental setup for determination of bypass and underflow of the coanda effect screen. FIC 01: Flowmeter E+H Promag W, FI 02: Flowmeter Georg Fischer Type 2551.

Figure 102: Geometrical parameters of the coanda effect screen with the inlet pipe (left), two underflow pipes (middle) and one bypass pipe (right).

Results and Discussion

The variation of the parameters according to Tab. 1 in the simulation shows the influence of the parameters on the bypass and underflow water. The crest length and the screen length are the main factors for maximizing the underflow water. From a practical point of view, these factors are not freely adjustable in water catchment systems, as coanda effect screens often are installed on existing foundations. In consequence, the accelerator drop and the screen wire tilt angle are the most promising geometric parameters when given dimensions of the foundations have to be considered.

Figure 103 shows the results of three similar experiments in comparison to the simulation data. For an inlet volume flow rate of 10 m³/h the simulation indicates a bypass flow rate of 3,55 m³/h (underflow 6.45 m³/h) while the experiment results show a bypass flow rate of 1.38 m³/h (underflow 8.62 m³/h).

Figure 103: Comparison between simulation and experimental data.

The underflow water is used for power generation in the hydropower plant and has a direct impact on the energy yield. The simulated value is 21.7% lower than the experimental result. This leads to an under-estimation of the potential power when only using the simulation. One explanation is the cross section shape of the screen wire, which is assumed to be sharp in the simulation and has curve in the experiment (Figure 104).

Figure 104: Cross section shape of the screen wire in the simulation (left, sharp) and the experiment (right, curve).

Outlook

The present state of the research showed the impact of selected geometrical parameters on the behavior of a coanda effect screen and a deviation between theoretical simulation and experiment. One limitation of the approach is that particles have not been considered neither in the simulation nor in the experiments. In the next step, the investigations will focus on the influence of the particles on the operation of the water catchment system.

Funding information

This research was supported by the Government of Tyrol (“Tiroler Innovationsförderung”, F.31933/13-2021). The cooperation partners are Stocker Technik GmbH, rb engineering GmbH and MCI.

References

- [1] Bundesministerium für Nachhaltigkeit und Tourismus, “Energie in Österreich 2018,” *Report*, p. 36, 2018.
- [2] E. Mosonyi and J. Giesecke, *Wasserkraftanlagen*. Springer, 2009.
- [3] S. D. Imad Lifa, Franco Schlegel, “Optimierung der Coanda-Rechen für Schweizer Gewässer,” 2017.
- [4] H. Nøvik, L. Lia, and H. Opaker, “Performance of Coanda-Effect Screens in a Cold Climate,” *J. Cold Reg. Eng.*, vol. 28, no. 4, p. 04014006, 2014, doi: 10.1061/(asce)cr.1943-5495.0000073.
- [5] T. L. Wahl, “Hydraulic Performance of Coanda-Effect Screens,” *J. Hydraul. Eng.*, vol. 127, no. 6, pp. 480–488, 2001, doi: 10.1061/(asce)0733-9429(2001)127:6(480).
- [6] T. L. Wahl, “Simulation Software for Coanda Effect Screens,” 2015. <https://www.usbr.gov/tsc/techreferences/computer software/software/coanda/coandadownload.%0Ahtml>.

Design and evaluation of a thermogravimetric analysis-based setup for thermochemical energy storage material testing

T. Niederkofler^{1,2,*}, D. Schiestl¹, A. Giovannini¹, R. Lackner²

1: Dept. of Environmental, Process and Energy Engineering, Management Center Innsbruck, Austria

2: Dept. of Material Technology Innsbruck (MTI), University of Innsbruck, Austria

* Corresponding author: tobias.niederkofler@mci.edu

Keywords: Heat storage, Thermogravimetric analysis, Material testing, Instrumental design

Research field: Thermal energy storage

Abstract

Thermal energy storage is used to increase the efficiency of renewable energy systems through the utilization of surplus energy. For further developments in this field, the characterization of promising materials, and the creation of new composite materials for better performance are very important. In this study, an apparatus to analyze the hydration and dehydration of gas-solid reactions close to the reaction equilibrium is designed, constructed, and evaluated. The thermogravimetric analyzer consists of an air unit and a reactor unit. With the air unit the parameters temperature, water vapor pressure, and airflow can be adjusted in the reactor. For the heating and cooling of the reactor, different rates can be set. The apparatus is evaluated through an analysis of the dehydration reaction of magnesium sulfate hexahydrate. The results are compared to data generated with a conventional TGA/DSC 1 (Mettler Toledo) and with data from the literature.

The developed apparatus for the thermogravimetric analysis of thermochemical storage materials shows a good performance in comparison to conventional instruments. The advantages of the newly developed apparatus are the possibility to investigate larger sample quantities, material cycle stability, and conditions close to practical utilization.

Introduction

Globally, the residential sector is responsible for approximately 40 % of the primary energy consumption, which corresponds to 24 % of the world's total CO₂ emissions [1]. To replace fossil fuels as the main energy source, renewable systems increasingly gained interest. By using solar radiation, thermal or electrical energy can be produced. Solar energy systems are suitable for both, space heating and domestic hot water production. However, asynchronous variations between solar radiation and heating demand between day and night, cloudy and sunny days, and/or summer and winter display a major restriction in using the full potential of this technology. Introducing a suitable long-term storage system enables the storage of surplus heat during summer and the utilization of this energy during winter. Thermal energy can be stored through sensible, latent, or thermochemical storage systems. Commercially, mostly sensible heat systems are used for short-term energy storage. Regarding their low energy density, short transmission distances, and limited storage time sensible storage system are not suitable for seasonal heat storage. Thermochemical energy storage systems store heat through a sorption process or a reversible chemical reaction in three steps: charging, storing, and discharging. In the charging process, the components are dissociated through the addition of heat in an endothermic reaction. These components then are stored separately from each other. In an exothermic reaction, the stored heat is released when needed through the synthesis reaction of the components [2, 3]. Predominantly solid-gas reversible reactions are used, due to their wide range of turning temperatures and the easy separation of the two phases after the reaction [4, 5]. In storing energy from solar radiation, a suitable low-temperature seasonal heat storage material is required. With the publication of Goldstein [6] in 1961, a renewed

interest in salt hydrates as heat storage materials emerged. Salt hydrates and composite sorbents based on salt hydrates have gained more and more attention in recent years. Presently, they are the preferred materials in building applications, because of their high energy storage density, relatively low price, and suitable hydration and dehydration temperatures [5, 7]. As a gaseous reactant, water vapor is commonly used in gas-solid reaction pairs for thermochemical energy storage materials.

To improve the performance in thermochemical energy storage from a materials perspective, a deeper understanding of the material characteristics is fundamental. Therefore, in this study, a thermogravimetric analyzer for the characterization of gas-solid reaction pairs, where water vapor is induced into the reactor, is designed and constructed. Additionally, the experimental setup is tested and the different units are verified. The apparatus is evaluated by testing the dehydration reaction of magnesium sulfate.

Thermogravimetric analyser (TGA)

This experimental setup enables an analysis of how temperature and water vapor pressure affect the reaction mechanisms in reversible gas-solid reactions close to the equilibrium. The possibility to investigate larger sample quantities permits the simulation of practical conditions in the system. Variations in sample size and layer thickness show the internal effects of particles for different applications, e.g. in fixed-bed reactors. Furthermore, the investigation of newly developed composite materials is possible.

Figure 105: Setup of the thermogravimetric analyzer.

The thermogravimetric analyzer consists of an air unit and a reactor unit. In the air unit, the air is heated and humidified before it is introduced into the reaction chamber. Thereby, it is transported through a pump from the ambient into the system. At the inlet, the volume flow is continuously measured through a thermal mass flow meter (up to 160 l/min \pm 2 %). An ultrasonic nebulizer in a water tank moistens the air in a bypass, dispersing very small water droplets into the air stream. A valve controls the airflow through the bypass. Heating sleeves at different positions of the pipe assure the vaporization of the produced droplets and prevent condensation in the pipeline. Relative humidity (from 5 % to 95 % \pm 2 %) and temperature (from 0 °C to 65 °C \pm 0.4 °C) are measured with a

high-temperature combination sensor (Titec ARFT/R-X/HT) in the pipeline, shortly before entering the reactor. The air unit can produce partial vapor pressures up to 100 kPa (measurement accuracy ± 5 kPa) in the reactor unit. In the reaction chamber, the effect of temperature and humidity on the sample is investigated. The chamber is heated through a heating coil and controlled by an external reactor controller (Parr Instrument 4838 Reactor Controller). With this controller, different heating and cooling rates from ambient temperature, up to 350 °C can be set. As shown in Figure 105, the sample is positioned centrally in the chamber and attached to a strain gauge weigh cell (Tedae Huntleigh, 1004). To prevent the hot air from affecting the weight measurement, the weigh cell is thermally decoupled from the reactor and a fan prevents hot air from heating the weighting unit. This was checked by heating the reactor from 30 °C up to 275 °C with a heating rate of 20 °C/min while observing the change in mass. As a result, for high heating rates, a measurement accuracy of $\pm 2\%$ in weight measurement was detected. Therefore, the fan above the outlet successfully hinders the hot air from reaching the weighing cell. In the chamber, the temperature measurement is conducted using a thermocouple (type K, measurement accuracy ± 1 °C). For recording and evaluating the generated data the MATLAB[®] programming environment with the data acquisition toolbox is used.

Evaluation of the TGA

The thermogravimetric analyzer was verified by comparing the dehydration process of magnesium sulfate hexahydrate. As a reference, the salt was analyzed in the TGA/DSC 1 (Mettler Toledo) and compared to data from the literature. As it is not possible to set a water vapor pressure in conventional TGA instruments, the reference measurement was conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere. For the experimental setup, the lowest possible water vapor pressure was set, which is 2.7 kPa. In both experiments, magnesium sulfate hexahydrate is heated from 50 °C up to 300 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. In the literature, three dehydration steps are described: $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 0.3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [8].

As displayed in Figure 106, both measured curves show the three dehydration steps and are identical in the course of the dehydration reaction. As expected, the dehydration curve measured in the air atmosphere is shifted to higher temperature levels, due to the higher vapor pressure in contrast to the nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure 106: Plot of dehydration reaction course with data from the developed apparatus (2.7 kPa) and the TGA/DSC 1 (nitrogen).

Conclusion

Generally, the dehydration process is described very well by the newly developed thermogravimetric analyzer. Therefore, kinetic and thermodynamic data can be generated with this apparatus in future studies. In comparison to conventional instruments, this apparatus enables the variation of sample quantity and layer thickness, measurements close to the reaction equilibrium, as it is less prone to condensation, and the investigation of newly developed composite materials. Furthermore, both hydration and dehydration reactions can be investigated with this apparatus. With this, changes in performance over different numbers of cycles can be analysed.

References

- [1] Y. Saheb, "Modernising building energy codes to secure our global energy future: The IEA Policy Pathway Series (2011)," France, 2011.
- [2] A. Hauer, "Sorption theory for thermal energy storage," in NATO Science Series, Thermal Energy Storage for Sustainable Energy Consumption, H. Ö. Paksoy, Ed., Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2007, pp. 393–408.
- [3] T. Kousksou, P. Bruel, A. Jamil, T. El Rhafiki, and Y. Zeraouli, "Energy storage: Applications and challenges," Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, vol. 120, pp. 59–80, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2013.08.015.
- [4] T. Yan, R. Z. Wang, T. X. Li, L. W. Wang, and I. T. Fred, "A review of promising candidate reactions for chemical heat storage," Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, vol. 43, pp. 13–31, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.015.
- [5] A. Solé, I. Martorell, and L. F. Cabeza, "State of the art on gas–solid thermochemical energy storage systems and reactors for building applications," Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, vol. 47, pp. 386–398, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2015.03.077.
- [6] M. Goldstein, "Sorption theory for thermal energy storage," in UN Conference on New Sources, Rome, pp. 411–417.
- [7] Y. Zhao, C. Y. Zhao, C. N. Markides, H. Wang, and W. Li, "Medium- and high-temperature latent and thermochemical heat storage using metals and metallic compounds as heat storage media: A technical review," Applied Energy, vol. 280, p. 115950, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115950.
- [8] G. Whiting, D. Grondin, S. Bennici, and A. Auroux, "Heats of water sorption studies on zeolite–MgSO₄ composites as potential thermochemical heat storage materials," Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, vol. 112, pp. 112–119, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2013.01.020.

Ageing and screening as strategies to increase the quality of manufactured aggregate from fluidized bed incinerator bottom ash for utilization in concrete

S.Hofer^{1,*}, J.Lederer¹

1: CD-Laboratory for a recycling-based Circular Economy, Institute for Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering, TU Wien, Austria

* Corresponding author: simon.hofer@tuwien.ac.at

Keywords: IBA Utilization, Manufactured Aggregate, Concrete

Research field: Waste Incineration Residues

Since 2023 the mineral fraction from incineration bottom ash (IBA) can be utilized as manufactured aggregate (MAG) to partially substitute natural aggregate in concrete in Austria. The Bundesabfallwirtschaftsplan (BAWP) is the corresponding regulation that states the legal limits in leachate and the total content of a range of heavy metals as well as chloride and sulfate limits in the leachate [1]. Concerning the underlying research, the focus lies on the content of water-leachable chloride and sulfate. The investigation targeted how far the legal limits can be met after a wet IBA treatment process and what measures can be applied to decrease the concentrations. A low concentration of both parameters is feasible to meet regulations and minimize the risk of damage in the concrete due to chemical reactions like corrosion or sulfate attack. The materials for examination, two manufactured aggregates from an IBA treatment plant located in Lower Austria, that operates a wet treatment process, were directly sampled from the conveyor belt drop. The manufactured aggregates originated from two different IBAs, each from a fluidized bed (FB) incinerator for municipal solid waste. Ageing for 12 weeks and screening (wet and dry) of the aged material were conducted. It is observable that the combination of ageing and screening is a successful way to decrease the concentration of water-soluble chloride and sulfate below the legal threshold limit and therefore to generate a manufactured aggregate that can be used in concrete from a legal point of view. Nonetheless, the technical applicability of such manufactured aggregate for its use in concrete must be further investigated in detail before it's utilization can be promoted.

Introduction

The European Norm EN12620 defines manufactured aggregate (MAG) as "Aggregate of mineral origin resulting from an industrial process involving thermal or other modification"[2]. The Bundesabfallwirtschaftsplan (BAWP) is the current legislation in Austria that states, that the mineral fraction from IBA fulfils this definition and can therefore be utilized as MAG in concrete if the limit values of specific parameters are met. A differentiation is made if either $\leq 10\%$ or $\leq 20\%$ of the concrete consists of MAG. Despite the threshold limits, a low concentration of water-soluble chloride and sulfate is necessary because they can develop damage to the microstructure of the concrete. Chloride can lead to corrosion of the reinforcement and sulfate can cause the so-called "sulfate attack", a damaging mechanism caused by formation of bulky sulfate-compounds in the concrete, that leads to micro-cracks [3]. Although both effects can be controlled, a low concentration in the raw materials decreases the risk of long-term damage. This work is part of the CD-Laboratory for a recycling-based Circular Economy, which investigates the possibilities of utilizing the mineral fraction from IBA as MAG in concrete in cooperation with a plant operator for IBA treatment and recycling. The paper describes the preliminary

results for two MAGs from IBA of two fluidized bed (FB) incinerators after the wet treatment process and the influence of pilot-scale ageing and screening on the chloride and sulfate concentration.

Methods and Material

In the wet, multistage process, ferrous metals are separated by multiple overhead magnets and non-ferrous metals by multiple eddy-current separators. Glass is separated by automated optical sorting. The process is very efficient in metal recovery, leading to a mineral fraction that leaves the process with a metal content below 1%. The multistage process was already described in detail by Mühl et al. [4]. The plant is operated with IBA from grate incinerators as well as IBA from FB incinerators, which differ substantially as described in Blasenbauer et al. [5]. In this work, the mineral fraction (MAG, 0/8mm) was directly sampled with a wheel loader from the conveyor belt drop during the treatment of 150 t FB incinerator bottom ash X (FB-IBA X) and 150 t FB incinerator bottom ash Y (FB-IBA Y). While the MAG of FB-IBA X was sampled in two replicates of different FB-IBA X batches, the MAG of FB-IBA Y was sampled in triplicate. The experiments were conducted in 2021-2022. Using the wheel loader allowed sampling the whole cross-section of the conveyer belt drop. After that, the 200-300 kg sample was subsampled by fractional shoveling until a subsample of about 5 kg was obtained for chemical analysis. The material was further shovelled into a water-permeable box for ageing. In replicate 1, both FB-IBAs were stored indoor for 12 weeks for ageing and were artificially watered with a conventional water hose during this period. In replicate 2 and 3, the ageing-boxes were placed outside for 12 weeks to be naturally weathered. After 12 weeks, the material was subsampled again for the analysis of all three replicates. For replicate 2 (FB-IBA Y) or 3 (FB-IBA X) of the respective MAGs 10-20 kg of the aged material were sieved at 2 mm. Both fractions of 0/2 mm and 2/8 mm were further subsampled and analyzed. To simulate wet-sieving, multiple samples of 1 kg from the 2/8 fraction were put batchwise on the 2 mm sieve; water at a L/S-Ratio of 0.25 was added with a water hose. The wet-sieved material was also subsampled for analysis. The chemical analysis was done according to EN 12457-4 (batchwise leaching test at L/S=10 and analysis with ion-chromatography [6]).

Results

Figure 107 shows the results for water-soluble chloride in FB-IBA X and Figure 108 for FB-IBA Y. Although initial chloride content variation between the replicates after the IBA treatment can be seen, the average content lies well below the threshold for both MAGs. Minor variations can result from the heterogeneity of the waste input and the resulting IBA. After 12 weeks of ageing, a reduction of the chloride content could be observed. Sieving at 2 mm showed that water-soluble chloride is enriched in the fine fraction of 0/2 mm.

Wet-sieving of the 2/8mm fraction showed a further concentration reduction in both FB-IBAs. Only utilizing the fraction 2/8mm in concrete would therefore be more feasible if a low chloride content in the concrete is necessary, as for reinforced concrete. The observations of the chloride behavior indicate that water-soluble chloride in FB incineration bottom ashes accumulates on particle surfaces and can be washed off to a high extent.

Figure 107: Water-soluble chloride in MAG of FB-IBA X.

Figure 108: Water-soluble chloride in MAG of FB-IBA Y.

Water-soluble sulfate also showed a variation between the replicates of both MAGs (Figure 110, Figure 110). It is known from the literature, that the content of water-soluble sulfate increases while ageing, mainly because of decomposition of ettringite [7]. Replicate 1 was artificially aged, which might be the reason that this effect cannot be seen within replicate 1 for FB-IBA X and FB-IBA Y. An explanation could be that the watering by the water hose was too efficient compared to natural rain and washed off the released sulfate immediately.

For the other replicates, that were naturally weathered this effect can be seen clearly. Replicate 3 from FB-IBA X shows a much higher initial sulfate concentration than the other replicates. A plausible explanation for this is the usage of H₂S-rich exhaust gas from a nearby production site as secondary air in the FB incinerator. Additionally, wastes from the pulp and paper industry are incinerated. These inputs can lead to concentration peaks in sulfate like in replicate 3. Nonetheless, the data indicate that, after ageing for 12 weeks, the threshold limits will be most likely exceeded.

Figure 109: Water-soluble sulfate in MAG of FB-IBA X.

Screening the material at 2mm leads to a 2/8mm fraction with a concentration in the range between the threshold limits, while the 0/2mm fraction is high in sulfate concentration.

Figure 110: Water-soluble sulfate in MAG of FB-IBA Y.

Meeting the limit for ≤10% MAG content can also be expected for standard FB-IBA X charges. For FB-IBA Y, wet screening of the 2/8mm fraction decreased the sulfate content below the limit for ≤20% MAG content. It can be assumed that this would also be true for a standard charge of FB-IBA X. Since both FB-IBAs show similar behaviour, it can be assumed that MAG after wet treatment needs to be aged, so that water-soluble sulfate can be released in chemical reactions which then can be washed off. The strategies of ageing and wet-screening at 2mm show a great potential for the 2/8 mm fraction to be suitable for utilization in concrete.

What is known from additional data not presented here is that the metal and metalloid content in the 0/2mm fraction is much higher than in the 2/8mm fraction, which is why screening at 2mm is feasible anyway. Further, ageing immobilizes the metals and metalloids. Considering that according to the BAWP the maximum share of IBA utilized in concrete is only 10-20%, the total load of sulfate and chloride of the 2/8mm fraction is likely to be acceptable. Nonetheless, the technical applicability of MAG for its use in concrete must be further investigated in detail, before it can be promoted. This is currently being investigated in the CD-Laboratory for a recycling-based Circular Economy.

Acknowledgements

The financial support by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs, the National Foundation for Research, Technology and Development and the Christian Doppler Research Association is gratefully acknowledged. Furthermore, we thankfully acknowledge the financial and non-financial support of our company partners Brantner Österreich GmbH, Linz Service GmbH, Wien Energie GmbH, and Wopfinger Transportbeton Ges.m.b.H. In addition, we thank Magistratsabteilung MA48, the public Waste Management provider of Vienna, for its non-financial support.

Literature

- [1] Bundes-Abfallwirtschaftsplan 2023-Teil 1.
- [2] ÖNORM EN 12620:2008-09.
- [3] J. Stark and B. Wicht, "Sulfatangriff," in *Dauerhaftigkeit von Beton*, J. Stark and B. Wicht Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013, pp. 161-207.
- [4] J. Mühl, S. Skutan, G. Stockinger, D. Blasenbauer, and J. Lederer, "Production of glass and manufactured aggregate from six different waste incineration bottom ashes through enhanced bottom ash treatment," *Waste Management (submitted)*, 2023.
- [5] D. Blasenbauer, F. Huber, J. Mühl, J. Fellner, and J. Lederer, "Comparing the quantity and quality of glass, metals, and minerals present in waste incineration bottom ashes from a fluidized bed and a grate incinerator," *Waste Management*, vol. 161, pp. 142-155, 2023/04/15/ 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.02.021>.
- [6] ÖNORM EN 12457-4:2002.
- [7] T. Astrup, "Pretreatment and utilization of waste incineration bottom ashes: Danish experiences," *Waste Manag.* vol. 27, no. 10, pp. 1452-7, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2007.03.017.

Combining Ultrafiltration with Activated Carbon Adsorption: Synergy for Industrial Decolourisation of Starch Hydrolysates

Camila A. Cabeza^{1,2,*}, Amal El-Gohary-Ahmed², Alexander Trischack², Mario Minauf³, Michael Harasek²

1: Competence Center CHASE GmbH, Vienna, Austria

2: Institute of Chemical Environmental & Bioscience Engineering E166, Technische Universität Wien, Vienna, Austria

3: AGRANA Research & Innovation Center GmbH, Tulln, Austria

* Corresponding author: camila.cabeza@tuwien.ac.at

Keywords: Ultrafiltration, Activated Carbon, Decolourisation, Waste Reduction

Research field: Downstream processing and Food Industry

Background

Decolourization and clarification are important steps during starch hydrolysates production. As a consequence, it is responsible for high costs especially when activated carbon (AC) is used together with other types of treatments such as rotary vacuum filters and diatomaceous earth [1]. Starch hydrolysates are in the form of glucose syrup prepared by enzymatic or chemical hydrolysis of maize or wheat starch [3]. After Hydrolysis has a characteristic brownish or yellowish colour generated usually by the Maillard reaction, pyrolysis and sometimes caramelisation during food processing and preservation [6]. In addition to its specific properties such as high viscosity and high glucose content.

AC adsorption is the most used method for the removal of colourants in food like sweeteners, including sucrose, glucose and fructose syrup [2]. It leads sometimes to a great amount of required AC to consume and at the same time a high level of waste product that needs to be properly disposed of or treated for reuse. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate strategies that help reduce consumption, and waste generation and in turn improve product quality.

Objective

To evaluate the decolourisation of starch hydrolysed obtained enzymatically, using AC in combination with Ultrafiltration (UF) at specific and different conditions in order to investigate and develop a cost and resource effective downstream process.

Methods

A partial decolourisation was performed using UF process. UF was conducted using a lab-scale filtration membrane unit model OS-MC-01 from OSMO membrane systems GmbH at 60 °C, different pressures and concentrations were applied according to the different molecular weight cut-off sizes (MWCO) membranes (100kDa and 5kDa) and the different multistage configurations (100kDa-5kDa-0.3kDa and 5kDa-0.3kDa). After UF, AC treatment was applied using a powdered AC from NORIT with different dosages (0.1 to 0.8 g/100ml) in a lab-scale batch processing at a constant temperature (70 °C) for complete decolourisation.

Figure 111 Lab-scale crossflow filtration unit (Model OS-MC-01) effective membrane area = 20 cm² Storage Tank = 2 liters

A UV/visible scanning spectrophotometer (UV-1800 Shimadzu) was used to determine the colour before and after UF and AC treatments according to an ICUMSA spectrophotometrically method (GS2/3-10) at 420 nm used in sugar analysis [5]. Therefore, the colour is given in ICUMSA units (IU, international units for sugar colour). Brix measurements were used to estimate the sugar concentration on the samples; therefore, the sugar concentrations were evaluated using an Optronic Digital Refractometer (KRÜSS DR6200-T) to measure the index refraction at a temperature of 20°C. Brix values are used to measure the refractometric dry substance in an aqueous solution, namely the amounts of dissolved solids per weight of the total solution [4]. The pH and conductivity values were also measured using a digital multiparameter (VWR model MU 6100 H).

Results

The results showed that partial decolourisation with a single-stage with 100 kDa membrane is not enough to reduce the required AC for a minimum requirement of < 100 IU in the product. Nevertheless, UF with 5 kDa membrane reduced required AC by around 50 %, achieving the minimum colour requirement and around 25% for a higher colour removal of < 50 IU. On the other hand, multistage UF obtained the best results reducing up to 74 % of the AC dosage, getting values below 100 IU and up to 61% AC dosage reduction achieving values below 50 IU. In conclusion, the synergy of UF with AC treatment could be helpful during the decolourisation process to decrease AC consumption and, therefore, the generation of unnecessary waste and costs in the downstream process. However, a future investigation must be carried out that confirms these prior results, evaluate sugar recovery during the UF process, and evaluate the adsorption mechanisms in detail together with a better optimisation and design of the new process.

List of References

- [1] M. V Acevedo-Estupiñan, C. O. Parra-Escudero, and C. J. Muvdi-Nova, "Study of clarification process of cassava starch hydrolysates using ceramic membranes ," *Vitae*, 2015, doi: 10.17533/udea.vitae.v22n2a06.
- [2] S. Z. Dziejczak and M. W. Kearsley, *Handbook of Starch Hydrolysis Products and Their Derivatives*. 3Island Press, 1995.
- [3] H.-Y. Wang, H. Qian, and W.-R. Yao, "Melanoidins produced by the Maillard reaction: Structure and biological activity," *Food Chem.*, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2011.03.075.
- [4] H. Duygu Ozsoy and J. (Hans) van Leeuwen, "Removal of color from fruit candy waste by activated carbon adsorption," *J. Food Eng.*, vol. 101, no. 1, pp. 106–112, 2010, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2010.06.018>.
- [5] S. Giani, "Determination of Sugar Solutions Color According to ICUMSA / Application Note Analytical Chemistry," 2018.
- [6] M. Elewa, G. El-Saad, K. Ibrahim, M. Tawfek, and H. Elhossieny, "A novel Method for Brix Measuring in raw Sugar Solution," *Egypt. Sugar J.*, vol. 15, pp. 69–86, 2020.

Privacy Statement

The authors agree that their personal data (names, affiliations, email addresses) will be stored and processed in course of the conference preparations and the publication of the proceedings.

The names and email addresses entered in this journal site will be used exclusively for the stated purposes of this journal and will not be made available for any other purpose or to any other party. The authors agree that their data is shared with the conference organizers (BOKU Wien, TU Wien, chemical-engineering.at) and that they will receive invitations for further Minisymposia in future. Data entered in this forms will be processed by chemical-engineering.at, the database server is located in Germany (hetzner.de).

According to GDPR (DSGVO) all authors have the right to refuse the further utilization of their data in future, but as the purpose of this conference is the distribution of scientific work the articles cannot be revoked once they are published.

Copyright information

The submission has not been previously published, nor is it before another journal for consideration (or an explanation has been provided in Comments to the Editor). The authors confirm that they do hold the full copyrights on all parts of their submissions and have permission from all contributors, authors, project partners etc. to publish this material. If any part of the submission has been published before the authors have to make sure that they are allowed to republish (check copyright situation with first publisher).

The authors allow the organizers of the Minisymposium and Partikelforum to publish their submission online and in print and grant therefore temporally unlimited non-exclusive publication rights free of any charge/fee to the organizers and to chemical-engineering.at (according to CC-BY). This does not prevent to publish the submission elsewhere, but the authors need to make sure that they cannot grant exclusive rights to other publishers.

Isolation and downstream processing of high-value products from preserved brown seaweed – A Literature Review.

M. Cabrera-González^{1*}, Amal Ahmed¹, Michael Harasek¹.

1: Institute of Chemical, Environmental & Bioscience Engineering, Technische Universität Wien, Austria

* Corresponding author: mayuki.cabrera@tuwien.ac.at

Keywords: Downstream Processing, Products, Seaweed

Research field: Green chemistry.

Seaweed is a large and diverse group of marine, photosynthetic, eukaryotic and photosynthetic organisms [1]. Seaweed is classified into three main groups: green, brown and red. The colour depends on the pigments; Rhodophyta is red, Chlorophyta are green, and Phaeophyceae are brown.

Besides its pigments, seaweed is an important feedstock used for industrial applications like food, agriculture, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and polymers. Lately, seaweed has gained attention as an essential and sustainable resource for valuable compound production. Some seaweed compounds are macronutrients like peptides, proteins, fatty acids, amino acids, and proteins and micronutrients such as minerals, vitamins and phytonutrients [2].

Moreover, specific compound applications for cosmetics industries have been found in seaweed. Phlorotannin, alginate, enzymes, fucoidan, and pigments have the advantageous potential of being incorporated into different cosmetic formulas [3].

In addition, succinic and lactic acid are some examples of critical compounds that can be recovered from seaweed depending on the preservation method.

However, the challenges to using seaweed as a resource of chemicals remain in the preservation methods and the downstream processing. Furthermore, other factors like the type of specie, abiotic aspects, and harvesting season, among others, impact the production and recovery of different compounds [4–6].

Therefore, this review will be focused on the preservation method and downstream processing of brown seaweed, where different compounds have been addressed.

Preservation methods are the initial step to start the downstream processing of seaweed [7]. A suitable preservation method will positively or negatively influence the compounds' extraction and purification. Depending on the target compound to be recovered, the preservation method changes. One of the oldest preservation methods is drying, which inhibits the proliferation of microorganisms and slows down the unfavourable enzymatic degradation process [8].

Wijers et al. [9] described four preservation techniques, including drying (freeze-dried, air-dried at 40 and 70 °C and frozen) and their effect on the protein extraction of four different seaweed specie. In this study, when it was freeze-dried, *A. nosodum* reached 59.6 % of protein extraction. Nevertheless, the protein yield was lower for the rest of the techniques and algae; therefore, Wijers et al. suggested that the preservation technique should be proper and specific to make differences in the protein extraction.

Ensiling is another preservation method that has been recently studied. Silage is produced by adding lactic acid bacteria or organic acids to a certain amount of seaweed under anaerobic conditions [10]. The success of ensiling seaweed will be related to

the ash content, moisture content, cell wall structure and composition of the seaweed [8].

The recovery of compounds from seaweed after any preservation method changes according to the target compound. Proteins, monosaccharides, organic acids, fertilisers, and much more are valuable products from seaweed.

Seaweeds are a competitive source of proteins. Fleurence et al. [11] exposed that brown seaweed contains the lowest concentration of proteins, reaching at least 3 % of the dry mass, while red seaweed is up to 47 %. The proteins in seaweed are presented like peptides, glycoproteins, enzymes, mycosporines and lectins [12].

Although brown seaweed is not advantageous for protein recovery due to its low content, M. Abdollahi et al. [13] studied different stabilisation methods for protein recovery from *Saccharina latissima*, a brown seaweed. They found that combining the freeze-drying method and classic pH-shift results in a 91 % protein solubilisation yield.

On the other hand, brown seaweed has also been studied as a target for new market chances. *Sargassum tenerrimum* has been used to extract five products with substantial market potential. One of the sustainable products, the sap, is the liquid released after a mechanical pretreatment of the macroalgae and is used as a fertiliser. Also, cellulose, salts, alginic acid, and protein concentrate are also recovered from *S. tenerrimum* by different downstream processing techniques [14].

Membrane processes are another method to recover and purify organic acids from seaweed. For instance, succinic acid and lactic acid can be recovered by microfiltration and nanofiltration processes. A continuous process of microfiltration and nanofiltration to recover bio-succinic acid was presented by Thuy and Boontawan [15]. In the research, the purity reached 99.2%. Therefore, membranes are a crucial process for downstream processing. However, further steps were needed to obtain pure succinic acid, like evaporation, crystallisation, washing and drying [15].

Even though the preservation and purification methods have been carried out so far on a lab or pilot scale [9][16], further research has to be done to be implemented on an industrial scale.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 860477.

Privacy Statement

The authors agree that their personal data (names, affiliations, email addresses) will be stored and processed in course of the conference preparations and the publication of the proceedings.

The names and email addresses entered in this journal site will be used exclusively for the stated purposes of this journal and will not be made available for any other purpose or to any other party. The authors agree that their data is shared with the conference organisers (BOKU Wien, TU Wien, chemical-engineering.at) and that they will receive invitations for further Minisymposia in future. Data entered in this forms will be processed by chemical-engineering.at, the database server is located in Germany (hetzner.de).

According to GDPR (DSGVO) all authors have the right to refuse the further utilisation of their data in future, but as the purpose of this conference is the distribution of scientific work the articles cannot be revoked once they are published.

Copyright information

The submission has not been previously published, nor is it before another journal for consideration (or an explanation has been provided in Comments to the Editor). The authors confirm that they do hold the full copyrights on all parts of their submissions and have permission from all contributors, authors, project partners etc. to publish this material. If any part of the submission has been published before the authors have to make sure that they are allowed to republish (check copyright situation with first publisher).

The authors allow the organisers of the Minisymposium and Partikelforum to publish their submission online and in print and grant therefore temporally unlimited non-exclusive publication rights free of any charge/fee to the organisers and to chemical-engineering.at (according to CC-BY). This does not prevent to publish the submission elsewhere, but the authors need to make sure that they cannot grant exclusive rights to other publishers.

References.

- Bhuyar, P.; Sundararaju, S.; Rahim, M.H.A.; Unpaprom, Y.; Maniam, G.P.; Govindan, N. Antioxidative Study of Polysaccharides Extracted from Red (*Kappaphycus Alvarezii*), Green (*Kappaphycus Striatus*) and Brown (*Padina Gymnospora*) Marine Macroalgae/Seaweed. *SN Appl Sci* **2021**, *3*, 1–9, doi:10.1007/s42452-021-04477-9.
- Gullón, P.; Astray, G.; Gullón, B.; Franco, D.; Campagnol, P.C.B.; Lorenzo, J.M. Inclusion of Seaweeds as Healthy Approach to Formulate New Low-Salt Meat Products. *Curr Opin Food Sci* **2021**, *40*, 20–25, doi:10.1016/j.cofs.2020.05.005.
- Morais, T.; Pacheco, D. Seaweeds Compounds : An Ecosustainable Source Of. *Cosmetics* **2021**, *8*, 1–28.
- Albers, E.; Malmhäll-Bah, E.; Olsson, J.; Sterner, M.; Mayers, J.J.; Nylund, G.M.; Rupa-Gadd, K.; Abdollahi, M.; Cvijetinovic, S.; Welander, U.; et al. Influence of Preservation Methods on Biochemical Composition and Downstream Processing of Cultivated *Saccharina Latissima* Biomass. *Algal Res* **2021**, *55*, 102261, doi:10.1016/j.algal.2021.102261.
- Laurens, L.M.L.; Lane, M.; Nelson, R.S. Sustainable Seaweed Biotechnology Solutions for Carbon Capture, Composition, and Deconstruction. *Trends Biotechnol* **2020**, *38*, 1232–1244, doi:10.1016/j.tibtech.2020.03.015.
- Olsson, J.; Toth, G.B.; Albers, E. Biochemical Composition of Red, Green and Brown Seaweeds on the Swedish West Coast. *J Appl*

- Phycol* **2020**, *32*, 3305–3317, doi:10.1007/s10811-020-02145-w.
- Thomas, J.-B.; Potting, J.; Gröndahl, F. Environmental Impacts of Seaweed Cultivation: Kelp Farming and Preservation. **2021**, 165–192, doi:10.19103/as.2021.0091.11.
- Milledge, J.J.; Maneein, S. *Storage of Seaweed for Biofuel Production: Ensilage*; Elsevier Inc., 2020; ISBN 9780128179437.
- Wijers, T.; Hylkema, A.; Visser, T.; Timmermans, K. Effects of Preservation on Protein Extraction in Four Seaweed Species. *J Appl Phycol* **2020**, *32*, 3401–3409, doi:10.1007/s10811-020-02197-y.
- Gallagher, J.A.; Turner, L.B.; Adams, J.M.M.; Dyer, P.W.; Theodorou, M.K. Dewatering Treatments to Increase Dry Matter Content of the Brown Seaweed, Kelp (*Laminaria Digitata* ((Hudson) JV Lamouroux)). *Bioresour Technol* **2017**, *224*, 662–669, doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2016.11.091.
- Fleurence, J.; Morançais, M.; Dumay, J. *Seaweed Proteins*; Second Edi.; Elsevier Ltd., 2017; ISBN 9780081007228.
- Pliogo-Cortés, H.; Wijesekara, I.; Lang, M.; Bourgougnon, N.; Bedoux, G. Current Knowledge and Challenges in Extraction, Characterization and Bioactivity of Seaweed Protein and Seaweed-Derived Proteins. *Adv Bot Res* **2020**, *95*, 289–326, doi:10.1016/bs.abr.2019.11.008.
- Abdollahi, M.; Axelsson, J.; Carlsson, N.G.; Nylund, G.M.; Albers, E.; Undeland, I. Effect of Stabilization Method and Freeze/Thaw-Aided Precipitation on Structural and Functional Properties of Proteins Recovered from Brown Seaweed (*Saccharina Latissima*). *Food Hydrocoll* **2019**, *96*, 140–150, doi:10.1016/j.foodhyd.2019.05.007.
- Baghel, R.S.; Suthar, P.; Gajaria, T.K.; Bhattacharya, S.; Anil, A.; Reddy, C.R.K. Seaweed Biorefinery: A Sustainable Process for Valorising the Biomass of Brown Seaweed. *J Clean Prod* **2020**, *263*, 121359, doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121359.
- Thuy, N.T.H.; Boontawan, A. Production of Very-High Purity Succinic Acid from Fermentation Broth Using Microfiltration and Nanofiltration-Assisted Crystallization. *J Memb Sci* **2017**, *524*, 470–481, doi:10.1016/j.memsci.2016.11.073.
- Maneein, S.; Milledge, J.J.; Nielsen, B. V.; Harvey, P.J. A Review of Seaweed Pre-Treatment Methods for Enhanced Biofuel Production by Anaerobic Digestion or Fermentation. *Fermentation* **2018**, *Vol. 4, Page 100* **2018**, *4*, 100, doi:10.3390/FERMENTATION4040100.

A comparative study of TFM and CFD-DEM approaches in a spout fluidized bed

Behrad Esgandari^{1,*}, Simon Schneiderbauer¹

1: Department of Particulate Flow Modelling, Johannes Kepler University Linz (JKU), Austria

* Corresponding author: behrad.esgandari@jku.at

Keywords: KTGF-TFM, CFD-DEM, spout fluidized bed, frictional solids stresses, rolling friction

Research field: Numerical modelling, fluidization

Abstract

In this paper TFM and CFD-DEM simulations of a pseudo-2D single-spout fluidized bed are presented. Both modelling approaches are validated against the experimental data of van Buijtenen et al. [1]. The effect of two different $\mu(I)$ -rheology dependent frictional stress closures on TFM simulations is studied. Our findings reveal a good agreement between TFM and CFD-DEM approaches in terms of time averaged solids velocities and solids volume fraction profiles. A spectral analysis of pressure drop fluctuations indicates the disagreement of the different frictional stress closures in TFM simulations.

Introduction

The spout fluidized beds provide better mixing and solids circulation and as a result enhanced mass and heat transfer between phases compared to fluidized and spouted beds. These favorable characteristics broaden their applications in various processes e.g. gasification, pyrolysis, and coating [2]. Therefore, understanding hydrodynamics of spout fluidized beds is of great importance.

It is possible to investigate the hydrodynamics of spout fluidized beds via experiments or numerical modelling approaches. The experimental approaches can sometimes be tedious and time-consuming, which is why numerical approaches are preferable to them in many cases. Among numerical approaches, mainly the Two-Fluid Model (TFM), where both gas and solid phases are treated as continuum phases, and computational fluid dynamics coupled with discrete element method (CFD-DEM), where gas phase is considered as continuous phase and particles are considered as individual discrete phases, are mainly used in the case of fluidized beds. The TFM simulations are highly dependent on the constitutive closures used for particle-particle interactions and particle-wall collisions. However, physical models such as hard-sphere and soft-sphere models can be used in CFD-DEM to explicitly take into account particle-particle and particle-wall collisions.

A comparative study between TFM and CFD-DEM approaches in spout fluidized beds can disclose the limitations and advantages of both methods. For instance, the direct comparison can shed light on the efficacy of the applied constitutive closures for particle-particle interactions and particle-wall boundary conditions in TFM. In the literature, there are vast number of studies on TFM or CFD-DEM simulations of spout fluidized beds. Van Buijtenen et al. [1] studied the flow regimes of multiple-spout fluidized beds by means of experiments and CFD-DEM simulations. Sutkar et al. [3] experimentally investigated the flow map regimes of a single-spout fluidized bed with draft plates and adopted CFD-DEM to validate the experiments in different flow regimes. Zhao et al. [4] performed TFM simulations of a spout fluidized bed to study the flow regimes and hydrodynamics of the bed and found out that in spout and fountain regions kinetic-collisional stresses are dominant while in annulus frictional stresses prevail.

Meanwhile, the number of comparative studies between TFM and CFD-DEM approaches in spout fluidized beds is limited and most of the comparisons are based on the instantaneous bed characteristics. For example, Guo et al. [5] compared both methods with respect to instantaneous bed height experimental data. Chen et

al. [6] studied the differences between both approaches using instantaneous profiles of bed height, solids volume fraction, and axial particle velocity.

In this paper, kinetic-collisional stresses and thermal energy flux of TFM considers the influence of interstitial fluid while it is common in TFM approaches available in the literature [4]–[6] to ignore this effect. Also, common frictional stresses closure such as Johnson and Jackson [7], Srivastava and Sundaresan [8] and Syamlal et al. [9] highly depend on the empirical parameter of minimum solids volume fraction, α_s^{min} and show zero-order dependency on the rate of deformation in the quasi-static granular regime. However, we use $\mu(I)$ -rheology and rate of deformation dependent frictional stress closures of Chialvo et al. [10] and Schneiderbauer et al. [11]. Moreover, Johnson and Jackson [6] particle-wall boundary conditions for velocity and flux of pseudo-thermal energy depend on the non-measurable specularly coefficient. The specularly coefficient varies from sliding to non-sliding collisions; sliding collisional regimes require lower specularly coefficient and non-sliding collisions need higher values. In spout fluidized beds, both sliding and non-sliding collisional regimes coexist, thus applying Johnson and Jackson [6] particle-wall boundary conditions will not consider the particle-wall dynamics correctly. In this paper, we apply a realistic particle-wall boundary conditions for momentum transfer and the flux of pseudo-thermal energy to consider both sliding and non-sliding collisions [12].

This paper is organized as follows: first briefly the Modelling approaches are described. Subsequently, simulation set-up is presented and a comparison of both modelling approaches at a pseudo-2D single-spout fluidized bed is shown. Finally, a conclusion ends this paper.

Modelling approaches

CFD-DEM

The governing mass and momentum equations of the fluid phase are,

$$\frac{\partial(\alpha_f \rho_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{u}_f) = -\alpha_f \nabla p + \alpha_f \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f - \mathbf{F}_{drag} + \alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{g} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_f is the fluid density, \mathbf{u}_f is the fluid velocity and α_f is the fluid volume fraction, p is the pressure and \mathbf{g} indicates the gravitational acceleration and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$ is the deviatoric stress tensor and \mathbf{F}_{drag} represents the drag force acting on the fluid from solid phase and is calculated using,

$$\mathbf{F}_{drag} = \frac{1}{\Delta V_c} \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{DEM} (\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{s,i}) \quad (3)$$

where β_{DEM} and ΔV_c are drag coefficient in CFD-DEM simulations and fluid cell volume.

We employed a soft-sphere DEM approach to track the trajectories of every individual particle by solving Newton's equation of motion. The equations of translational and rotational

motion of particle i can be written as,

$$m_i \dot{\mathbf{u}}_{s,i} = \sum_{i \neq j} \mathbf{F}_i^{(contact)} + \mathbf{F}_i^{(f-s)} + \mathbf{F}_i^{(g)} \quad (4)$$

$$I_i \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i = \mathbf{T}_i \quad (5)$$

where m_i , $\mathbf{u}_{s,i}$, I_i and $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ are the particle mass, the particle translational velocity, the particle moment of inertia and the particle rotational velocity, respectively. Also, \mathbf{T}_i includes particle-particle and particle-wall torques and in our simulations is supplemented by a constant directional torque to consider the rolling friction effect. $\mathbf{F}_i^{(contact)}$ is the particle-particle and particle-wall contact forces. Here, non-linear Hertzian spring dashpot model is used to calculate the normal and tangential contact forces. In addition, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(g)}$ is the gravitational force acting on the particles. Also, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(f-s)}$ is the fluid forces acting on the particle which in our simulations were drag force, pressure gradient force and viscous force. It needs to be mentioned that fluid properties are interpolated to the location of the particles in the corresponding cells using trilinear interpolation. For detailed information about the CFD-DEM approach used in this paper, refer to [13].

TFM

The averaged mass and momentum equations for fluid and solid phases are written as,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_q \rho_q) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_q \rho_q \mathbf{u}_q) = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_q \rho_q \mathbf{u}_q) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_q \rho_q \mathbf{u}_q \mathbf{u}_q) = -\alpha_q \nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_q \boldsymbol{\tau}_q - \beta_{TFM}(\mathbf{u}_q - \mathbf{u}_s) + \alpha_q \rho_q \mathbf{g} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_s \rho_s u_s) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s u_s \mathbf{u}_s) = -\alpha_s \nabla p - \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{S}_s^{kc} + \mathbf{S}_s^f) + \beta_{TFM}(\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_s) + \alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{g} \quad (8)$$

where in equation (6), \mathbf{u}_q , α_q and ρ_q are the velocity, volume fraction and density of phase q where q represents either the solid phase or fluid phase. In addition, β_{TFM} is the drag coefficient in TFM simulations. It can be noted that in equation (8) solids stress tensor consists of kinetic-collisional, \mathbf{S}_s^{kc} , and frictional solids stresses, \mathbf{S}_s^f .

The kinetic-collisional stresses stem from the translational movement of the particles and particle-particle collisions and can be modelled using kinetic theory of granular flows (KTGF). Based on the literature [11], the assumption of binary contacts of particles in KTGF is valid for solids volume fractions up to 0.4. The kinetic-collisional stresses are dependent on the particle velocity fluctuations, hence solid phase mass and momentum equations need to be augmented by a balance of pseudo-thermal energy (PTE) which reads as,

$$\frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_s \rho_s \Theta) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s \Theta) \right) = -\mathbf{S}_s^{kc} : \nabla \mathbf{u}_s - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + \Gamma_s - J_v - \gamma_\Theta \quad (9)$$

granular temperature can be described as, $\Theta = 2/3 E_{PTE}$. In equation (9), $(\mathbf{S}_s^{kc} : \nabla \mathbf{u}_s)$ denotes the production of PTE through kinetic-collisional stresses, $(-\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q})$ is the diffusion term. Further, Γ_s and J_v indicate the transfer of the kinetic energy of the particle velocity fluctuations to the fluid phase. Finally, γ_Θ indicates the rate of dissipation of PTE due to inelastic particle collisions. For a detailed description of the constitutive relations used in TFM simulations, refer to [13].

On the other hand, frictional solids stresses are valid in solids volume fractions higher than α_s^{min} , where particle-particle contacts are not binary anymore and KTGF assumption of binary contacts fails. In these regions, frictional solids stresses can be expressed as rigid-plastic rheological model, where the stresses show dependency on rate of deformation and inertial number, I_s , (see [11]).

Chialvo et al. [10] divided the granular flow regimes in the solids volume fraction exceeding α_s^{min} , into three regimes namely, inertial

(inert), intermediate (int) and quasi-static (QS) regimes. Based on their DEM simulations they derived normal stresses expressions for different regimes and proposed the following relation for normal frictional stresses, p_s^f ,

$$p_s^f = \begin{cases} p_s^{QS} + p_s^{int} & \text{for } \alpha_s \geq \alpha_s^{max} \\ \left((p_s^{inert})^{-1} + (p_s^{int})^{-1} \right)^{-1} & \text{for } \alpha_s < \alpha_s^{max} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where,

$$\frac{p_s^{QS} d_s}{k} = \alpha_{QS} |\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{max}|^{2/3} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{p_s^{int} d_s}{k} = \alpha_{int} \hat{\gamma}_s^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{p_s^{inert} d_s}{k} = \frac{\alpha_{inert} \hat{\gamma}_s^2}{|\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{max}|^2} \quad (13)$$

where scaled shear rate is expressed as,

$$\hat{\gamma}_s = \frac{2 \|\text{dev } \mathbf{D}_s\| d_s}{\sqrt{k/(\rho_s d_s)}} \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{D}_s = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u}_s + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_s)^T)$ and d_s , k and α_s^{max} are particle diameter, particle stiffness and maximum packing limit. Furthermore, α_{int} , α_{inert} and α_{QS} are model parameters and their values in our TFM simulations are 0.099, 0.021 and 0.20, respectively. Substituting equation (14) into equation (13) leads to,

$$p_s^{inert} = 4 \rho_s \alpha_{inert} \left(\frac{\|\text{dev } \mathbf{D}_s\| d_s}{\alpha_s - \alpha_s^{max}} \right)^2 \quad (15)$$

From equation (15) it can be inferred that p_s^{inert} is not a function of particle stiffness. It needs to be mentioned that in solids volume fractions higher than α_s^{min} , we truncate the radial distribution function, to avoid the contribution from the kinetic-collisional normal stresses [13].

Chialvo et al. [10] introduced a $\mu(I)$ -rheology to close the frictional shear stresses which reads as,

$$\mu(I_s) = \mu_i^* + \frac{\alpha_I}{(I_0/I_s)^{\beta_I} + 1} \quad (16)$$

where μ_i^* , α_I , I_0 and β_I are 0.38, 0.37, 0.32 and 1.5, respectively.

Schneiderbauer et al. [11] also suggested another expression for normal frictional stresses,

$$p_s^f = \begin{cases} p_s^{QS} & \text{for } \alpha_s \geq \alpha_s^{max} \\ p_s^{inert} & \text{for } \alpha_s < \alpha_s^{max} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Moreover, they also use $\mu(I)$ -rheology to close the frictional shear stresses similar to Chialvo et al. [10], but the value of β_I is 1.0 in their proposed model.

As our previous study [13] offers, in the same conditions and $\alpha_s < \alpha_s^{max}$, Schneiderbauer et al. frictional stresses closure [11] exhibits higher normal frictional stress than Chialvo et al. frictional stresses closure [10]. It needs to be mentioned that to consider the effect of rolling friction in TFM simulations, an ad-hoc modification to $\mu(I)$ -rheology is used as explained here [13].

Drag coefficient correlation

In this paper, we use Tang et al. [14] drag coefficient correlation.

This model covers particle Reynolds numbers, $\text{Re} = \frac{\alpha_f \rho_f d_s \|\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_s\|}{\mu_f}$, up

to 1000 and solids volume fractions up to 0.6 and takes the form of,

$$\beta_{TFM} = 180 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_s^2}{d_s^2 \alpha_f} + 18 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_f^3 \alpha_s (1 + 1.5 \sqrt{\alpha_s})}{d_s^2} + \frac{18 \mu_f \alpha_s \alpha_f Re}{d_s^2} \left[0.11 \alpha_s (1 + \alpha_s) - \frac{0.00456}{\alpha_f^4} + \left(0.169 \alpha_f + \frac{0.0644}{\alpha_f^3} \right) Re^{-0.343} \right] \quad (18)$$

Note that in CFD-DEM simulations, $\beta_{DEM} = \beta_{TFM} \frac{\pi d_s^3}{6 \alpha_s}$.

Simulations set-up

For validating TFM and CFD-DEM simulations the single-spout fluidized bed case of van Buijtenen et al. [1] is used (Figure 112). They investigated the time averaged solids velocity profiles within the bed. We apply OpenFOAM for TFM and couple LIGGGHTS and OpenFOAM through CFDEMcoupling for CFD-DEM simulations. The CFD-DEM solver has successfully been applied in the previous studies [15], [16].

Figure 112: Sketch of the single-spout fluidized bed of van Buijtenen et al. [1]

Time discretization is performed via first-order implicit Euler method. We use Gauss linear corrected and Gauss limitedLinear (a mixture of upwind and central differencing) [17] methods to spatially discretize diffusion and convective terms, respectively. We use a hexahedral finite-volume mesh with a grid spacing of $\Delta l = 5$ mm for all spatial dimensions where the previous numerical studies on this case have shown is sufficient to achieve to grid independence results [11], [18]. Initial bed volume fraction of $\alpha_s = 0.58$ was chosen for all TFM simulations. Finally, the material properties and simulation parameters are given in Table 28.

Table 28: Material properties and simulation parameters.

	value	unit
d_s	3	mm
μ_f	1.78×10^{-5}	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$
ρ_f	1.1	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$
ρ_s	2505	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$
e_{p-p}	0.9	-
e_{p-w}	0.9	-
μ_{p-p}	0.2	-
μ_{p-w}	0.2	-
μ_r	0.06	-
Poisson's ratio	0.45	-
Young modulus	1.0×10^7	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$
t_{CFD} (CFD-DEM)	1.0×10^{-4}	s
t_{DEM} (CFD-DEM)	5.0×10^{-6}	s
t_{TFM}	adjustable (CFL < 1.0)	s
Simulation time	40	s
u^{bg}	2.4	$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$
u^{sp}	43.5	$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$

Results

Figure 113 compares the time averaged vertical solids velocities extracted from TFM and CFD-DEM simulations with PIV and PEPT measurements and CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. [1]. The “TFM” in the legend of the plot corresponds to TFM simulations with Chialvo et al. frictional stresses closure [10] and “TFM (Sch.)” denotes TFM simulations with Schneiderbauer et al. frictional stresses closure [11]. Both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches qualitatively predict the spout-fluidization flow regime within the bed. In the spout-fluidization flow regime particles are carried up with the spouting gas flow in the spout region and then, due to gravity, they lose energy and fall down on the bed surface in the fountain region, then in the annulus region, particles move downward and again enter the spout. At $z=50$ mm, both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches show great agreement with the experimental data. Further, it can be seen that in the annulus region, our simulation results show better correspondence with PIV and PEPT data than CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. [1]. At $z=100$ mm, similar to van Buijtenen et al. [1] CFD-DEM results our CFD-DEM simulations fit the PIV and PEPT data in the spout region. However, TFM simulations illustrate lower particle velocities in the spout. It should be mentioned that $z=100$ mm was located near to the bed surface in the experiments. In the region close to the side walls our TFM and CFD-DEM predictions are in a good agreement with the experiments, while the CFD-DEM results of van Buijtenen et al. [1] highly overpredict the downward solids velocities. This overestimation of van Buijtenen et al. [1] simulation results can be due to the lower surface bed height in their CFD-DEM simulations, which they attributed to the inappropriate particle-wall interactions. Therefore, in our CFD-DEM and TFM simulations, we considered rolling friction for particle-particle and particle-wall interactions. Also, they used Koch and Hill drag model [19] which is based on the lattice-Boltzmann simulations up to $Re=120$ that is way smaller than the Re numbers that particles can reach in the spout-fluidized beds. For having accurate particle-fluid interactions as mentioned earlier we adopt Tang et al. drag model [14].

At $z=50$ mm, both frictional closures (Chialvo et al. [10] and Schneiderbauer et al. [11]) predict similar solids velocity profiles; however, with increasing height, TFM (Sch.) yields to lower solids velocities in the spout. In addition, at $z=100$ mm, it can be seen that TFM (Sch.) simulations indicate lower solids velocities than TFM in the annulus region. This illustrates that the bed surface height is higher in TFM (Sch.). Predicting lower solids velocities close to the side walls from TFM (Sch.) simulations, is due to the higher wall shear stresses as the frictional solid stresses are higher in Schneiderbauer frictional stress closure [11]. Therefore, it can be concluded that the choice of frictional stresses closures has significant influence on the results of TFM approach.

The time averaged solids volume fraction profiles from TFM (Sch.), TFM and CFD-DEM are illustrated in Figure 114: Time averaged solids volume fraction profiles from TFM (Sch.), TFM and CFD-DEM. Three distinct regions including the annulus region with higher solids volume fraction located along the walls, the spout region in the center and the umbrella-shaped fountain region on top of the bed surface can be distinguished. No visible differences can be found from comparing the solids volume fraction profiles of TFM (Sch.) and TFM. Nevertheless, there may exist some differences between the simulations, which quantitative results can reveal. Hence, the time averaged profiles of solids volume fraction at two heights are plotted in Figure 115. At $z=50$ mm, TFM simulations exhibit slight discrepancies with CFD-DEM simulations, however, TFM (Sch.) predicts lower solids volume fractions in the spout region. van Wachem et al. [20] found that higher frictional stresses lead to lower solids volume fractions. Our results clearly support this finding, where in the annulus region lower solids volume fractions are obtained from TFM (Sch.) compared to TFM due to higher frictional solid stresses from Schneiderbauer closure [11]. At $z=100$ mm, TFM (Sch.) predicts higher solids volume fractions compared to TFM and CFD-DEM simulations near the side walls that is a sign

of higher bed surface height in TFM (Sch.) simulations.

Figure 113: Comparison of the time averaged vertical solids velocities obtained from TFM, TFM (Sch.) and CFD-DEM simulations with the PIV and PEPT measurements of van Buijtenen et al. [1] in the single spout fluidized bed. The purple dashed line indicates the CFD-DEM simulations of van Buijtenen et al. [1]. (a) $z=50$ mm and (b) $z=100$ mm.

Figure 114: Time averaged solids volume fraction profiles from TFM (Sch.), TFM and CFD-DEM.

Figure 115: A Comparison of the time averaged solids volume fraction of TFM (Sch.), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations. (a) $z=50$ mm and (b) $z=100$ mm

For further investigating the differences between CFD-DEM and TFM simulations, we study the frequency spectrum of the pressure drop fluctuations at three different location within the bed. We measure the pressure values close to the background and spouting gas inlets using P_1 , P_2 and P_3 probes at a frequency of 100 Hz and pressure drop is calculated using the measured pressure values from the probe in the freeboard (P_4) as depicted in Figure 112. The pressure drop fluctuations, $\Delta p'(t)$, are calculated using,

$$\Delta p'(t) = \Delta p(t) - \Delta p_{mean} \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta p(t)$ and Δp_{mean} represent instantaneous pressure drop values and time averaged pressure drop value. By applying a fast Fourier transformation (FFT) to the pressure drop fluctuations, we convert the pressure drop fluctuations signal into the frequency spectrum ($\Delta p'(f)$). To take the spectrum into the power dimensions, we square the frequency spectrum of the pressure fluctuations and normalize it via variance of $\Delta p(t)$. The normalized frequency spectra of TFM (Sch.), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations are given in Figure 116 at the different locations within the bed. It can be seen that for the probes on the background gas inlets, both TFM and CFD-DEM simulations display a dominant frequency peak around 5 Hz and 8

Hz, respectively. However, dominant frequency is hard to distinguish from TFM (Sch.) simulations. On the other hand, frequency spectra of the probe located on the spouting gas inlet show two dominant frequency peaks at high and low frequencies in TFM and CFD-DEM simulations. Table 29 lists the dominant high and low frequencies related to the spouting gas inlet probe. The dominant low frequency peak for TFM and CFD-DEM simulations is 5.12 Hz and 8.01 Hz which corresponds to the experimental data of Link et al. [21] in the spout-fluidization flow regime. Also, ratio of the high to low frequencies reveals that both simulations are indicating the quite similar ratio between the frequencies. However, the frequency spectrum of TFM (Sch.) does not show two dominant frequency peaks like TFM and CFD-DEM simulations. To conclude, although our CFD-DEM and TFM simulations reveal correspondence to the experiments of Link et al. [21], but due to the lack of experimental data related to the pressure drop fluctuations in van Buijtenen et al. [1] work, it is not clear which one of our numerical methods is predicting the correct results.

Figure 116: Normalized frequency spectra of pressure drop fluctuations obtained from TFM (Sch.), TFM and CFD-DEM simulations. (a) P_1 probe (left background gas inlet), (b) P_2 probe [7] (spouting gas inlet) and (c) P_3 probe (right background gas inlet).

Table 29: dominant high and low frequencies related to the spouting gas inlet probe (P_2).

	Low frequency	High frequency	Ratio (high/low)
TFM	5.12 Hz	12.15 Hz	2.37
CFD-DEM	8.01 Hz	18.88 Hz	2.36

Conclusions and outlook

Within this study a comparison between TFM and CFD-DEM simulations in a single-spout fluidized bed was carried out. We used a TFM approach including interstitial fluid effect in the kinetic-collisional solids stresses and a $\mu(I)$ -rheology for the frictional solids stresses as well as realistic particle-wall boundary conditions of momentum transfer and the flux of pseudo-thermal energy. The validations revealed that CFD-DEM simulations show more accurate results than TFM and TFM (Sch.). The comparison between TFM simulations with Chialvo et al. frictional stresses closure [10] and TFM simulations with Schneiderbauer et al. frictional stresses closure [11] in terms of solids velocity, solids volume fraction profiles and normalized frequency spectra of pressure drop fluctuations showed that Chialvo et al. frictional stresses closure [10] has better predictions against the experiments and CFD-DEM simulations. In addition, our simulations clarified the importance of choosing proper frictional stress closures in TFM simulations of moderately dense gas-solid flows.

Future studies will concentrate on the comparison of various frictional stresses closures with the experimental pressure drop fluctuations data.

Acknowledgment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955661 (TUSAIL ITN, www.tusail.eu).

References

- 1] M. S. van Buijtenen, W. J. van Dijk, N. G. Deen, J. A. M. Kuipers, T. Leadbeater, and D. J. Parker, "Numerical and experimental study on multiple-spout fluidized beds," *Chem Eng Sci*, vol. 66, no. 11, pp. 2368–2376, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.ces.2011.02.055.
- 2] V. S. Sutkar, N. G. Deen, and J. A. M. Kuipers, "Spout fluidized beds: Recent advances in experimental and numerical studies," *Chem Eng Sci*, vol. 86, pp. 124–136, Feb. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.ces.2012.06.022.
- 3] V. S. Sutkar, N. G. Deen, V. Salikov, S. Antonyuk, S. Heinrich, and J. A. M. Kuipers, "Experimental and numerical investigations of a pseudo-2D spout fluidized bed with draft plates," *Powder Technol*, vol. 270, no. PB, pp. 537–547, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.powtec.2013.11.030.
- 4] J. Zhao, G. Liu, X. Yin, X. Li, Z. Gao, and H. Lu, "Two-Fluid Simulation of a Three-Dimensional Spout-Fluid Bed: Flow Structures, Regimes, and Insight into the Mechanism of Particle-Particle Momentum Transfer," *Ind Eng Chem Res*, vol. 60, no. 21, pp. 7950–7965, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1021/acs.iecr.1c00928.
- 5] X. Guo, G. Liu, J. Zhao, R. Wang, and Y. He, "Investigation of Gas-Solid Flows in a Spout Fluidized Bed on Drag and Solid Stress: CFD-DEM, TFM, and Experimental Validation," *Journal of Chemical Engineering Research Updates*, vol. 8, pp. 1–23, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.15377/2409-983x.2021.08.1.
- 6] M. Chen, M. Liu, and Y. Tang, "Comparison of Euler-Euler and Euler-Lagrange Approaches for Simulating Gas-Solid Flows in a Multiple-Spouted Bed," *International Journal of Chemical Reactor Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 7, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1515/ijcre-2018-0254.
- 7] P. C. Johnson and R. Jackson, "Frictional-collisional constitutive relations for granular materials, with application to plane shearing," 1987, doi: 10.1017/S0022112087000570.
- 8] A. Srivastava and S. Sundaresan, "Analysis of a frictional-kinetic

model for gas-particle flow,” *Powder Technol*, vol. 129, no. 1, pp. 72–85, 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0032-5910(02)00132-8.

- [9] M. Syamlal, W. Rogers, and T. J. O’Brien, “MFIX Documentation Theory Guide Technical Note,” 1993.
- [10] S. Chialvo, J. Sun, and S. Sundaresan, “Bridging the rheology of granular flows in three regimes,” *Phys Rev E Stat Nonlin Soft Matter Phys*, vol. 85, no. 2, Feb. 2012, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevE.85.021305.
- [11] S. Schneiderbauer, A. Aigner, and S. Pirker, “A comprehensive frictional-kinetic model for gas-particle flows: Analysis of fluidized and moving bed regimes,” *Chem Eng Sci*, vol. 80, pp. 279–292, Oct. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.ces.2012.06.041.
- [12] S. Schneiderbauer, D. Schellander, A. Löderer, and S. Pirker, “Non-steady state boundary conditions for collisional granular flows at flat frictional moving walls,” *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, vol. 43, pp. 149–156, Jul. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2012.03.006.
- [13] B. Esgandari, S. Rauchenzauner, C. Goniva, P. Kieckhefen, and S. Schneiderbauer, “A comprehensive comparison of Two-Fluid Model, Discrete Element Method and experiments for the simulation of single- and multiple-spout fluidized beds,” *Chem Eng Sci*, vol. 267, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ces.2022.118357.
- [14] Y. Yali Tang, E. A. J. F. Frank Peters, J. A. M. Hans Kuipers, S. H. L. Sebastian Kriebitzsch, and M. A. Martin van der Hoef, “A new drag correlation from fully resolved simulations of flow past monodisperse static arrays of spheres,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 61, no. 2, pp. 688–698, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1002/aic.14645.
- [15] S. Golshan, B. Esgandari, and R. Zarghami, “CFD-DEM and TFM simulations of spouted bed,” *Chem Eng Trans*, vol. 57, 2017, doi: 10.3303/CET1757209.
- [16] B. Esgandari, S. Golshan, R. Zarghami, R. Sotudeh-Gharebagh, and J. Chaouki, “CFD-DEM analysis of the spouted fluidized bed with non-spherical particles,” *Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 99, no. 11, 2021, doi: 10.1002/cjce.24142.
- [17] C. Greenshields and H. Weller, *Notes on Computational Fluid Dynamics: General Principles*. CFD Direct Ltd, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://cfdirect.com>
- [18] S. Yang, Y. Sun, L. Zhang, and J. W. Chew, “Computational study of the effect of draft plates on the solid behavior in a spout-fluid bed,” *Ind Eng Chem Res*, vol. 55, no. 49, pp. 12598–12615, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1021/acs.iecr.6b02732.
- [19] D. L. Koch and R. J. Hill, “Inertial Effects In Suspension and Porous-Media Flows,” 2000. doi: 10.1146/annurev.fluid.33.1.619.
- [20] B. G. M. van Wachem, J. C. Schouten, C. M. van den Bleek, R. Krishna, and J. L. Sinclair, “Comparative analysis of CFD models of dense gas-solid systems,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 1035–1051, May 2001, doi: 10.1002/aic.690470510.
- [21] J. M. Link, L. A. Cuypers, N. G. Deen, and J. A. M. Kuipers, “Flow regimes in a spout-fluid bed: A combined experimental and simulation study,” *Chem Eng Sci*, vol. 60, no. 13, pp. 3425–3442, Jul. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.ces.2005.01.027.

Neural network-based closure development for modeling of cohesive gas-particle flows.

J. Tausendschön^{1,*}, M. Salehi¹, S. Sundaresan², S. Radl¹,

1: Dept. of Process and Particle Engineering, Graz University of Technology, Austria

2: Dept. Chemical and Biological Engineering, Princeton University, USA

* Corresponding author: josef.tausendschoen@tugraz.at

Keywords: Cohesive Gas-Particle Flows, Machine Learning, Data-driven modeling, Drag correction modeling

Research field: Fluidized bed reactors

Abstract

The accuracy of filtered Two-Fluid model simulations critically depends on constitutive models for corrections that account for the effects of inhomogeneous structures at the sub-grid level. The complexity of accounting these structures increases with cohesion. In the present study, we created a dataset from filtered Euler-Lagrange simulations with systematic variations of the cohesion level and the filter length, to investigate the development of a neural network-based drag correction model for liquid bridge-induced cohesive gas-particle flows. A priori tests revealed that these models afford robust and accurate predictions of the drag correction and the actual drag force. Further it was shown that an anisotropic drag correction model is more accurate than an isotropic model.

Introduction

Fine particles are widely used in various industrial sectors from the petrochemical industry [1], the pharmaceutical industry [2], to Food industry [3]. Unfortunately, these fine particles exhibit spontaneous (i.e., van der Waals-type) or liquid bridge-induced cohesive forces which critically impact powder flowability and fluidizability.

Powders featuring cohesive interactions can be categorized from mildly cohesive to highly cohesive. The level of cohesion can be quantified based on a Bond number, which describes the ratio of cohesion forces to the gravitational force. In addition to van der Waals forces, particle can become cohesive due to the presence of liquid bridge between the particles in the gas-solid systems. This cohesive force is associated with viscous and surface tension forces, again quantifiable via a Bond and a Capillary number [4]–[6].

As these phenomena occur at a particle level, quantification of these forces is not easy to investigate through experimental approaches. However, detailed numerical simulation can be of significant help in analyzing the contribution of different forces in the strength of granule and powder flowability. Typically, two different approaches can be used in this regard: i) Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) through the Two-Fluid Method (TFM) approach [7]; ii) CFD coupled with the Discrete Element Method (CFD-DEM) [8]. These approaches can be used in highly-resolved and unresolved scales. However, the computational cost for the highly-resolved one is extremely high when simulating industrial scale systems. Therefore, application of filtered approaches as unresolved method are desired especially for industrial-scale systems [9], [10].

Simulations of industrial-scale gas-particle flows based on the filtered Two-Fluid model (fTFM) approach, and therefore with coarse grids, depend critically on constitutive models that account for the effects of inhomogeneous structures at the sub-grid level [11]. The complexity of accounting for inhomogeneous structures increases when considering cohesive gas-particle flows [12].

Previously, an artificial neural network-based drag correction model was developed by Jiang et al. [13], [14] for non-cohesive gas-particle systems. However, the question persists if this model is useful for cohesive systems or not. Therefore, in our current contribution, we aim to analyze the influence of cohesion on the drag force closure and integrate it into a machine learning-based drag correction concept. Prior studies [15] identified the sub-grid drift velocity as the crucial quantity for modeling the filtered drag coefficient. Unfortunately, the drift velocity is unavailable in filtered simulations. To correctly reproduce mesoscale structures, and since the drift velocity is also computable, we start with detailed CFD-DEM-based simulations, and filter them with different filter sizes to emulate quantities available in an fTFM simulation.

1. Model description and filtering

CFD-DEM simulations of 3D fully periodic domains are performed over a wide range of different setups (see Table 1). Subsequently, these simulations are filtered (i.e., spatially averaged) with different filter sizes. The CFD part is realized within the framework of OpenFOAM® [16], and the DEM part is solved using LIGGGHTS® [17]. The coupling between these two tools is performed with CFDEM® [17].

1.1. Simulation setups

We focus on the effect of cohesion on drag correction for large filter sizes in the range of 40-70 particle diameters (d_p), since cohesive particles can be expected to form larger clusters and streamers than non-cohesive particles. Usually each side of the domain is about to be two times the the largest filter size of interest (or larger), to minimize the effect of periodic boundary conditions on the inhomogeneous flow structures. Subsequently the side of the domain must be about 140 d_p or larger. Simulations that track the motion of every primary particle in such large domains, are computationally too expensive. To overcome this problem, we perform coarse-grained CFD-DEM simulations where parcels of particles are simulated instead of primary particles. The coarse-graining ratio α is defined as the ratio of the parcel and primary particle diameters (simulations featuring primary particles are indicated by $\alpha = 1$). The transition from primary to coarse-grained parameters is done after Tausendschön et al. [18]. Simulations have been done in our study using $\alpha = 3$. In our simulations, the inter-particle cohesion was due to liquid bridges between the particles, which were modeled after Wu et al. [19]. A constant liquid loading level was used in all cohesive simulations.

Table 30: Overview of simulation setups.

	CG system, $\alpha = 3$
Particle / Parcel size $d_p / d_{p,p}$ (m)	150e-6 / 450e-6
Fluid grid size $\Delta_G = 9 d_p$ (m)	1.35e-3
Domain size 16 Δ_G x 16 Δ_G x 64 Δ_G (m)	0.0216 x 0.0216 x 0.0864
Solid volume frac. $\phi_{s,tot}$	0.10
Number of particles/parcels	285,147 / 10,561
Bond number	0-80
Liquid Loading Level	0.001
Capillary Number	0.01
Cohesion through	Liquid bridge
Filter size Δ_f	3 Δ_G ; 4 Δ_G ; 5 Δ_G

Unfortunately, the maximum level of cohesion in such simulations is limited by the system size, as discussed in [18] and [20]. We found that $Bo = 80$ was the upper limit for the simulations.

The calculated terminal settling velocity u_t for the primary particle is 0.8562 (m/s). The reference time is $t_{ref} = u_t/g = 0.0873$ (s). In our earlier study [18], we found that simulations needed 5 t_{ref} to reach a statistical steady-state. With this in mind, simulations were performed for nearly 30 t_{ref} in our present study. The time frame in which data were sampled ranged from 18 t_{ref} to 30 t_{ref} , with sampling performed every 0.25 t_{ref} .

1.2. Filtering procedure

Filtering operations are performed via the tool CPPPO [21]. The filtered solid volume fraction is:

$$\bar{\phi}_s(\mathbf{x}, t) = \iiint \phi_s(\mathbf{r}, t) G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{r} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the spatial position (any position in the grid), \mathbf{r} is the predefined spatial position. The box filter kernel or top-hat kernel $G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x})$ is normalized so that $\iiint G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{r} = 1$ and is defined by the fluid filter size Δ_f after:

$$G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Delta_f^3}, & \text{if } |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x}| \leq \frac{\Delta_f}{2} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The filtered gas and solid velocities and the filtered gas pressure are then:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_g(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{(1 - \bar{\phi}_s)} \iiint (1 - \phi_s(\mathbf{r}, t)) \mathbf{u}_g(\mathbf{r}, t) d\mathbf{r} \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\bar{\phi}_s} \iiint G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x}) \phi_s(\mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{u}_s(\mathbf{r}, t) d\mathbf{r} \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{p}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \iiint G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x}) p(\mathbf{r}, t) d\mathbf{r} \quad (8)$$

1.3. Closure for the interphase drag force

In our contribution we focus on the closure for the interphase drag and the mesoscale interphase force. The filtered Eulerian drag force is:

$$\bar{\Phi}_d = \overline{\beta^{Eul}(\mathbf{u}_g - \mathbf{u}_s)} \quad (9)$$

and needs to be closed in filtered simulations. One defines a quantity $\Phi_{d,sgs}$ as the difference between the filtered Eulerian drag force and the interphase drag force $\Phi_{d,sgs} = \bar{\Phi}_d - \Phi_d$. The interphase drag

force is $\beta^{Micro}(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_g - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s)$, where β^{Micro} is the drag coefficient evaluated based on filtered quantities using specific drag law, in our contribution Beetstra et al. [22]. Analogously as done in the work of Ozel et al. [15], the filtered Eulerian drag is approximated by:

$$\bar{\Phi}_{d,A} = \beta^{Micro}(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_g - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s + \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d) = \bar{\beta}^{Eul}(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_g - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s) \quad (10)$$

Here $\bar{\beta}^{Eul}$ is a filtered Eulerian drag coefficient. The sub-grid drift velocity $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d$ is defined by:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d = \frac{\overline{\phi_s \mathbf{u}_g}}{\bar{\phi}_s} - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_g \quad (11)$$

Rearranging Eqn. (10) yields following form of the approximated filtered Eulerian drag force $\bar{\Phi}_{d,A} = \tilde{\Phi}_d \mathbf{H}_d$. Where \mathbf{H}_d is the so-called drag correction function, defined as:

$$\mathbf{H}_d = \left(1 + \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d}{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_g - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s} \right) \quad (12)$$

2. Neural network-based drag correction

Deep neural networks (DNN) quickly found widespread application, thus only a brief overview is discussed here. The structure of the DNN is defined by: (i) the number of nodes in the input layer which equals the number of marker variables, (ii) the number of output nodes, defined by the single target variable, and (iii) the number of hidden layers and their respective number of nodes.

The number of hidden nodes in each hidden layer was searched by a randomized hyperparameter search. Each hidden layer was then followed by a Rectifying Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function [23], while no activation function was applied to the output layer [24]. Dropout was added as regularization added to each hidden layer [25]. The dropout rate was also part of the random hyperparameter search. To increase the overall efficiency of the training process, the mini-batch gradient descent method was used [26]. The mean absolute error (MAE) was selected as the cost function of the neural network optimization. As quality metric to evaluate the model prediction, the total coefficient of determination (R^2) was used.

2.1. Marker selection

Potential markers or input variables can only be used if they are present in or can be derived from filtered simulations. The input quantities of Jiang et al. [14] were (i) the particle Reynolds number, Re_p ; (ii) the scaled filter length, Δ_f^* ; (iii) the filtered solid volume fraction relative to maximum solid volume fraction, $\bar{\phi}_s/\phi_{s,max}$; (iv) the scaled gradient of the filtered pressure field in vertical direction, $\nabla_z \bar{p}^*$; and (v) the scaled slip velocity in the vertical direction, $\tilde{u}_{sl,z}/u_t$. In the present dataset only a single Re_p value is present, so this marker is not used. Instead, the Bond number Bo is included as new marker. Bo is calculated as the ratio of the cohesive and gravitational force on the particle, $Bo = 6 \sigma / (d_p^2 g \rho_p)$. The other markers are adopted from Jiang et al. [14]. The input markers are then, e.g., in vertical direction:

$$\psi_{z,5M} = \left(\frac{1}{\Delta_f^*}, \frac{\bar{\phi}_s}{\phi_{s,max}}, \frac{\tilde{u}_{sl,z}}{u_t}, \nabla_z \bar{p}^*, Bo \right) \quad (13)$$

In the horizontal plane, an analogous expression involving velocity components and pressure gradient in the lateral direction of interest is used. All input markers are dimensionless, nonetheless they are additionally normalized between -1 and +1. The routinely used normalization between 0 and 1 is adjusted to avoid a sign change of velocities and pressure gradients, which might be highly confusing. The respective minima and maxima values are searched in the

training dataset. When using a pre-trained model for prediction in a new system, the min- and max-values from the model development should be used.

2.2. Target and drag correction function

From Eqn.(12) a direct prediction of \mathbf{H}_d or $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d/\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{sl}$ looks appealing. However, areas or cells where $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{sl}$ is equal or very close to zero appear frequently, leading to numerical problems in the prediction or in the overall target data treatment. Therefore, Jiang et al. [13] used the product $\bar{\phi}_s \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d$ in their first contribution and adapted it to $\bar{\phi}_s \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d/(\phi_{s,max} u_t)$ in their later work [14].

In the present contribution we use the same target as Jiang et al. [14], since it comes with two significant advantages: (i) it is dimensionless, and (ii) no additional normalization needs to be applied for the usage as a target of a DNN. Therefore, the target (and hence what is the prediction of the DNN) is:

$$\mathbf{z}_{DNN} = \frac{\bar{\phi}_s \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_d}{\phi_{s,max} u_t} \quad (14)$$

Predicting the filtered drag force using the DNN can be done by:

$$\bar{\Phi}_{d,A,pred} = \beta^{Micro} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{sl} \mathbf{H}_{d,DNN} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{d,DNN}$ is built from:

$$\mathbf{H}_{d,DNN} = 1 + \begin{cases} \frac{\phi_{s,max} u_t}{\bar{\phi}_s \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{sl}} \mathbf{z}_{DNN}, & 0.01 \leq \bar{\phi}_s \leq 0.55 \\ 0, & else \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The drag correction is shown here as a vector quantity for the sake of completeness. However, in the performed approach, it was calculated separately in each direction.

2.3. Drag anisotropy

A key topic of the drag correction is to consider the anisotropy or not. To follow up on the discussion, we differentiate between the directions. In principle, there are three possible variants how to consider the anisotropy: (i) the prediction of the vector \mathbf{z}_{DNN} directly, (ii) using two separate neural networks differencing between gravitational and lateral directions, or (iii) the usage of three separate neural networks for each direction. All three possibilities faces the challenge of Galilean invariance [13], [27].

To ensure that the Galilean invariance is respected, we clearly specify our coordinate directions with respect to the gravity direction. However, the other two axes in the horizontal plane remain arbitrary. To separate the other axes effectively, statistics of the slip velocity or pressure gradient must manifest significant differences in the two lateral directions, which could happen in the vicinity of bounding walls. However, far away from such boundaries, one would not expect to see large differences in the statistics in the two lateral directions. Thus, we build the neural networks as shown in Figure 117, where the internal coordinate system is intuitive. Two DNNs can be used, one for the gravitational direction and the other for the two lateral directions.

Figure 117: Neural network scheme for anisotropy of the drag correction.

3. Results

The overall accuracy of a model is typically assessed by comparing the predicted and target values of suitable output variables. We show below the predicted and targeted filtered drag forces relative to the global-average volumetric gravitational force of the suspension in the domain, denoted as $\langle \Phi_{G,s} \rangle$. This reference volumetric force is defined by:

$$\langle \Phi_{G,s} \rangle = \|\mathbf{g}\| (\langle \bar{\phi}_s \rangle \rho_s + \langle \bar{\phi}_g \rangle \rho_g) \quad (17)$$

Here the angled brackets indicate a global (i.e., simulation-domain wide) average.

Figure 118 shows the parity force plots for the predictions in the 3D domain. As can be seen the high R^2 value indicates an accurate force prediction in gravitational direction.

Figure 118: Parity plot of the predicted filtered drag force and the target for the entire test dataset in gravitational direction.

Figure 119 displays the parity plot in lateral direction. One can see that accuracy is lower than in the gravitational direction by the difference in R^2 . Nonetheless, a reasonable accuracy was achieved.

Figure 119: Parity plot of the predicted filtered drag force and the target for the entire test dataset in lateral direction x .

Figure 120 shows the parity in the other lateral direction. As displayed no significant difference between the lateral directions x and y can be observed.

Figure 120: Parity plot of the predicted filtered drag force and the target for the entire test dataset in lateral direction y .

Figure 121 shows *a priori* created simulation snapshots for three different Bond numbers. A good agreement can readily be seen in most of the regions, with the model missing the target near the two extremes (in the range of drag correction values).

Figure 121: Comparison of drag correction snapshots in gravitational direction for dry, mid- and highly cohesive systems. Top row: target, bottom row: prediction.

4. Conclusion and outlook

We performed and then filtered Euler-Lagrange simulations of gas-fluidization of cohesive particles in fully periodic 3D domains to create datasets to develop of a drag correction model. In these simulations, we systematically varied the cohesion level and filter length.

We then developed a DNN-based drag correction model using the datasets. To ensure rotational invariance, separate drag correction models were formulated for the vertical and horizontal directions. *A priori* tests revealed that these models afford robust and accurate predictions of the drag correction and the actual drag force. The same model is employed for all horizontal directions. The DNN-based drag correction models can readily be implemented into commonly used simulation platforms.

Future studies should focus on *a posteriori* tests of the drag correction models in coarse-grid simulations. It has been noted in the literature [28]–[30] that improved models for the filtered particle phase stress could improve the accuracy of coarse-grid simulations even for non-cohesive systems; it seems reasonable to expect that the stress model would be even more important in cohesive systems.

References

- [1] F. Raganati, R. Chirone, and P. Ammendola, "Gas-solid fluidization of cohesive powders," *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.*, vol. 133, pp. 347–387, 2018.
- [2] K. A. Mehta, G. S. Rekhi, and D. M. Parikh, *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Granulation Technology*. 2016.
- [3] B. Cuq *et al.*, "Advances in Food Powder Agglomeration Engineering," vol. 69, J. B. T.-A. in F. and N. R. Henry, Ed. Academic Press, 2013, pp. 41–103.
- [4] C. M. Boyce, A. Ozel, J. Kolehmainen, and S. Sundaresan, "Analysis of the effect of small amounts of liquid on gas–solid fluidization using CFD-DEM simulations," *AIChE J.*, vol. 63, no. 12, pp. 5290–5302, 2017.
- [5] B. Buck, Y. Tang, N. G. Deen, H. Kuipers, and S. Heinrich, "Experimental investigation and force balance modelling of wet particle collisions," in *Particle Interactions 2018-Topical at the 8th World Congress on Particle Technology*, 2018, pp. 151–157.
- [6] B. Buck and S. Heinrich, "Collision dynamics of wet particles: Comparison of literature models to new experiments," *Adv. Powder Technol.*, vol. 30, no. 12, pp. 3241–3252, 2019.
- [7] M. Askarishahi, M. S. Salehi, and S. Radl, "Capability of the TFM Approach to Predict Fluidization of Cohesive Powders," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 61, no. 8, pp. 3186–3205, 2022.
- [8] P. Grohn, D. Weis, U. Bröckel, S. Heinrich, and S. Antonyuk, "Contact models and dem simulation of micrometer-sized particles and agglomerates at static loading based on experimental characterization," in *Particles in Contact*, Springer, 2019, pp. 115–163.
- [9] S. Radl and S. Sundaresan, "A drag model for filtered Euler–Lagrange simulations of clustered gas–particle suspensions," *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 117, pp. 416–425, 2014.
- [10] M. Girardi, S. Radl, and S. Sundaresan, "Simulating wet gas–solid fluidized beds using coarse-grid CFD-DEM," *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 144, pp. 224–238, 2016.
- [11] Y. Igci and S. Sundaresan, "Constitutive models for filtered two-fluid models of fluidized gas-particle flows," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 50, no. 23, pp. 13190–13201, 2011.
- [12] M. H. Zhang, K. W. Chu, F. Wei, and A. B. Yu, "A CFD-DEM study of the cluster behavior in riser and downer reactors," *Powder Technol.*, vol. 184, no. 2, pp. 151–165, 2008.
- [13] Y. Jiang, J. Kolehmainen, Y. Gu, Y. G. Kevrekidis, A. Ozel, and S. Sundaresan, "Neural-network-based filtered drag model for gas-particle flows," *Powder Technol.*, vol. 346, no. December, pp. 403–413, 2019.
- [14] Y. Jiang, X. Chen, J. Kolehmainen, I. G. Kevrekidis, A. Ozel, and S. Sundaresan, "Development of data-driven filtered drag model for industrial-scale fluidized beds," *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 230, p. 116235, 2021.
- [15] A. Ozel, Y. Gu, C. C. Milioli, J. Kolehmainen, and S. Sundaresan, "Towards filtered drag force model for non-cohesive and cohesive particle-gas flows," *Phys. Fluids*, vol. 29, no. 10, 2017.
- [16] H. G. Weller, G. Tabor, H. Jasak, and C. Fureby, "A tensorial approach to computational continuum mechanics using object-oriented techniques," *Comput. Phys.*, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 620, 1998.
- [17] C. Kloss, C. Goniva, A. Hager, S. Amberger, and S. Pirker, "Models, algorithms and validation for opensource DEM and CFD-DEM," *Prog. Comput. Fluid Dyn. An Int. J.*, vol. 12, no. 2/3, p. 140, 2012.
- [18] J. Tausendschön, J. Kolehmainen, S. Sundaresan, and S. Radl, "Coarse graining Euler-Lagrange simulations of cohesive particle fluidization," *Powder Technol.*, vol. 364, pp. 167–182, 2020.
- [19] M. Wu, J. G. Khinast, and S. Radl, "The Effect of Liquid Bridge Model Details on the Dynamics of Wet Fluidized Beds," *Am. Inst. Chem. Eng. J.*, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 1877–1897, 2016.
- [20] M. Girardi, S. Radl, and S. Sundaresan, "Simulating wet gas-solid fluidized beds using coarse-grid CFD-DEM," *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 144, pp. 224–238, 2016.
- [21] F. Municchi, C. Goniva, and S. Radl, "Highly efficient spatial data filtering in parallel using the opensource library CPPPO," *Comput. Phys. Commun.*, vol. 207, no. June, pp. 400–414, 2016.
- [22] R. Beetstra, M. A. van der Hoef, and J. A. M. Kuipers, "Drag Force of Intermediate Reynolds Number Flow Past Mono- and Bidisperse Arrays of Spheres," *AIChE J.*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 489–501, 2007.
- [23] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, and A. Courville, *Deep Learning*. The MIT Press, 2016.
- [24] J. Heaton, *Artificial Intelligence For Humans, Volume 3: Deep Learning and Neural Networks*. Heaton Research, Inc., 2015.
- [25] N. Srivastava, G. Hinton, A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and R. Salakhutdinov, "Dropout: A Simple Way to Prevent Neural Networks from Overfitting," *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 15, pp. 1929–1958, 2014.
- [26] M. Li, T. Zhang, and A. J. Chen, Yuqiang Smola, "Efficient mini-batch training for stochastic optimization," in *Proceedings of the 20th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, 2014, pp. 661–670.
- [27] J. Ling, A. Kurzawski, and J. Templeton, "Reynolds averaged turbulence modelling using deep neural networks with embedded invariance," *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 807, pp. 155–166, 2016.
- [28] S. Rauchenzauner and S. Schneiderbauer, "A dynamic multiphase turbulence model for coarse-grid simulations of fluidized gas-particle suspensions," *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 247, p. 117104, 2022.
- [29] Y. Zhang, M. Jiang, X. Chen, Y. Yu, and Q. Zhou, "Modeling of the filtered drag force in gas–solid flows via a deep learning approach," *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 225, p. 115835, 2020.
- [30] L. T. Zhu, J. X. Tang, and Z. H. Luo, "Machine learning to assist filtered two-fluid model development for dense gas–particle flows," *AIChE J.*, vol. 66, no. 6, 2020.